

**Final reports of 1st call
JRPs and evaluation
reports**

**WP3 Joint Research
Projects**

Responsible Partner: Sciensano

Contributing partners: ANSES

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Final JRP report on evaluation of finalized JRP, 1st round

1. Introduction

Eleven Joint Research Projects (JRP) have started at the beginning of the One Health EJP in January 2018. MAD-VIR has ended as foreseen in December 2019; IMPART, RADAR, METASTAVA, AIR-SAMPLE and MEDVETKLEBS received a one-year no-cost extension and have ended in December 2020. Finally, ARDIG, TOX-DETECT, NOVA, LIST-ADAPT and MOMIR-PPC have ended in June 2021, also after a no-cost extension period.

The projects have delivered many outputs that are all publically available according to the Open Access policy of the Horizon2020 framework programme. More than 240 deliverables and 70 publications are available through [Zenodo](#), which was chosen as the official repository of the One Health EJP. Very valuable outputs were achieved; to mention a few, the METASTVA project has delivered metagenomics guidelines that contribute to methods standardization; the NOVA project led to the development of disease and surveillance models and also improved data sharing between partners; the IMPART project has produced more than 50 000 MIC values and proposed new epidemiological cut-off-values for several bacteria of veterinary importance, including fastidious growing pathogens, MEDVETKLEBS has contributed significantly to the optimization and harmonization of *Klebsiella* culture protocols and the development of a molecular detection method of *K. pneumonia*, the AIR-SAMPLE project resulted in the development of a new cost-effective test for detecting *Campylobacter* in chickens; an essential outcome of the LIST-ADAPT project is the collection of 1575 *Listeria monocytogenes* strains and their genomes. All details can be found in the current document and in the One Health EJP [Outcome Inventory](#) on the website.

In the final months of the One Health EJP, the most interesting and promising of these outputs will be further disseminated across targeted stakeholders, i.e. relevant national and international authorities, research and clinical laboratories, risk assessors and risk managers. In addition to the publications and deliverables, the One Health EJP has created a unique network across public health, animal health and food institutes throughout Europe. The added value of this is extensively described in the “One Health Impact” sections of in the project final reports.

For each project, the project leader handed over a final report, which has been evaluated following the “*Guidelines for the evaluation of the Final Joint Research Projects (JRP) reports, based on D3.9*” (this guideline is available as an annex at the end of this report). Therefore, each final report has been evaluated by three different, independent evaluators:

- An external scientific expert that has already reviewed and evaluated the full proposal of this project.
- An additional external scientific expert.
- A member of the Programme Owner Committee of the One Health EJP (POC member).

Most evaluators have provided detailed comments for each of the evaluation criteria, with constructive suggestions. As requested in the guidelines, the evaluators have assessed the alignment of the project results with the initial objectives as described in the full proposal, the scientific excellence and the innovative approach of the projects, the quality and efficiency of the implementation, whether the research project has delivered integrative activities and One Health aspects, whether the results contain elements for sustainability, and finally what the expected impact of the project may be. Most of the comments are very valuable and, more than the scores, give an idea of the efforts done and the results obtained.

Although all evaluators have received detailed instructions with an extensive description of the criteria and a guidance for scoring, the figures should be interpreted with caution and should not be used to compare projects and their general performance. On average, all projects score well for all criteria mentioned above, with hardly no extreme low score. The total scores are what could be expected, with some projects that were evaluated higher or lower than the mean. In a few cases, the Programme Owner Committee members gave a remarkably lower score as compared to the other experts.

The anonymised evaluation reports were shared with the project leaders as a support for their further work. The One Health EJP Project Management Team will not take any particular initiative with respect to a project with a very high or very low score, but will focus on the deliverables obtained and their dissemination to the interested stakeholders.

2. Projects final reports and evaluations

In this document, every final report is followed by its evaluation. The names of the evaluators were removed from the report to guarantee the confidentiality of the process.

The sections relating to ethics and DMP from the original reports were not included in this document because they both refer only to information exchange (with the ethics advisors or with WG4 regarding DMP) and not to the scientific or technical results, and therefore have no influence on the evaluation of the project.

JRP01-IMPART

Final report

1 Consortium composition

Name of the Project Coordinator and of all applicants, with full affiliations

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Antonio Battisti	Senior researcher	IZSLT, IT	antonio.battisti@izslt.it

Short CV of each participating key scientist

Kees Veldman, PhD, is project leader of resistance monitoring in animals at Wageningen Bioveterinary Research. He is one of the key editors of the annual report on Monitoring of Antimicrobial Resistance and Antibiotic Usage in Animals in the Netherlands (MARAN) and in daily charge of the National Reference Laboratory on Antibiotic Resistance and has a wide experience in phenotypic testing. He has been involved in different research project concerning fluoroquinolone and colistin resistance as well as research projects involving ESBLs and MRSAs in livestock. He is member of the steering committee of VetCAST as data manager and member of the EUCAST subcommittee on MIC distributions and epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs).

Dr. Jean-Yves Madec, DVM, PhD, at the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health Safety (ANSES) is involved in National Surveillance Programmes of AMR in veterinary medicine in France and has recognized expertise in molecular genetics and epidemiology of resistance in Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria of animal origin (commensal, pathogenic, zoonotic) and issues regarding the animal-human transfer of AMR. He is member of several expert groups and committees on antimicrobial resistance and antimicrobial usage in animals and humans in France and Europe and is an active participant/leader in recent European scientific projects. He is also member of VetCAST.

Sophie Granier, PhD, joined ANSES (formerly known as AFSSA) in 2005 in order to take part in the national programme of antimicrobial resistance monitoring of bacteria isolated from animals and food. She is especially in charge of surveillance of resistance in non-human Salmonella, isolated from food, feed, animal health and the natural ecosystem. She is also involved in various research projects dealing with antimicrobial resistance in bacteria isolated from food, such as *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and ESBL. She is deputy head of the French reference Laboratory for antimicrobial resistance. She is appointed on regular basis as expert by ANSES, AFNOR, EFSA or FVO.

Agnès Perrin- Guyomard, is a scientist working on antimicrobial susceptibility testing. She is involved in the national programme of antimicrobial resistance monitoring of bacteria isolated from animals and food, especially on *E. coli*. She manages also research projects concerning microbiologic risk

assessment of xenobiotics, including antibiotics, on intestinal microbiota using a human flora associated (HFA) rodent model.

Dr. Muna Anjum and the APHA team have extensive expertise in characterization of AMR in Enterobacteriaceae isolated from food animals. The multidisciplinary team of molecular biologists and classical microbiologists work closely with veterinarians, and epidemiologists to conduct national surveillance, outbreak investigations as well as research activities to understand persistence and dissemination of AMR through the food chain. Muna Anjum is the Molecular Lead for Antimicrobial Resistance in Enteric pathogens and the Deputy Lead for the Antimicrobial Resistance Program at the APHA. She leads a team of post-doctoral scientists and PhD students. She holds an Honorary Associate Professorship at the University of Warwick and is a member of the Health Protection Research Unit at the University of Oxford, John Radcliffe Hospital, in partnership with Public Health England. She is also a member of the DEFRA Antimicrobial Resistance Coordination (DARC) Group, which reviews activities of the UK government on antimicrobials. She is an Academic Editor for PlosOne Scientific Journal and has authored more than 70 publications. Muna has led or is the APHA lead in a number of national (VMD/DEFRA, DoH, NERC), EU and commercial projects.

Dr. Mirjam Grobbel is senior scientist in the field of isolation and detection of antimicrobial resistant bacteria. She is coordinating the resistance testing of the National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistances at the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment. Mirjam Grobbel has a wide experience in isolation, characterization and resistance testing of bacteria, and she is involved in different research projects concerning detection and characterization of resistant bacteria (e.g. fluoroquinolones, colistin, ESBL, AmpC) in livestock and food.

Alexandra Irrgang, PhD is a researcher at the unit “Epidemiology, Zoonoses and Antimicrobial Resistances” at the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment. In the framework of the RESET project she is working on the isolation and characterization of colistin-resistant and/or carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* from various sources (especially livestock and food). Alexandra Irrgang has a wide experience in phenotypic and genotypic testing of antibiotic resistant bacteria. She is also involved in the bioinformatics analysis of whole genome sequencing data of bacterial isolates.

Dr. Sven Maurischat is a researcher at the unit “Bacterial Toxins, Food Service” at the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment. The main focus of his work is the development and validation of detection and typing methods for *Clostridium* spp. in food and animal samples. Currently, he is involved in the preparation of a monitoring programme for *C. difficile* in food. His main expertise is the methodology development and molecular characterization of zoonotic pathogens.

Jette S. Kjeldgaard has a PhD in zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance, and works as a postdoctoral researcher at DTU National Food Institute (DTU Food), Technical University of Denmark. Her focus is on international activities within the area of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and genomic epidemiology, as well as surveillance of foodborne disease outbreaks and antimicrobial resistance. Her qualifications include coordination of activities within the EU Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance (EURL-AR) such as organization of proficiency tests and training courses. In addition, she is organizing and facilitating national and international courses on the topics of antimicrobial susceptibility testing and genomic analyses and prediction of resistance using whole genome sequencing.

Jannice Schau Slettemeås is a researcher at the section for Research, Food Safety and Animal Health at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI). She is involved in the monitoring programme on antimicrobial resistance in the veterinary and food production sectors and is one of the co-authors of the annual NORM/NORM-VET report on Usage of Antimicrobial Agents and Occurrence of Antimicrobial Resistance in Norway in animals and humans. She has responsibility for the Norwegian Reference Laboratory on Antimicrobial resistance and has a wide experience on both phenotypic and genotypic testing. She has been involved in several research projects regarding resistance to fluoroquinolones, aminoglycosides and cephalosporins.

Dr. Marianne Sunde (DVM, PhD, Professor equivalent) is a senior researcher in veterinary microbiology at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute. Her main research activity has been on antimicrobial resistance. Dr. Sunde also holds a position at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health where the main research area is antimicrobial resistance in a “One Health” perspective. She has long-time experience in research on antimicrobial resistance and has been a key person in bacteriological diagnostics as well as monitoring of resistance in the veterinary sector in Norway. She has been project leader for national and Scandinavian research projects, has supervised Master and PhD students, has experience as a reviewer for scientific journals and is Assistant Editor for BMC Vet Res.

Anette M. Hammerum is a Senior Researcher at Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark. She has worked on antibiotic resistance more than 20 years. She has more than 110 published papers on resistance mechanisms, epidemiology and antimicrobial consumption. Dr. Hammerum has served for 10 years as an Editor of the Danish national resistance report, DANMAP. Dr. Hammerums research has both been in relation to antimicrobial resistance in humans and animals, including transfer of bacteria and resistance genes between animals and humans.

Stefan Börjesson is a senior researcher in microbiology and molecular biology. He is involved in the Swedish Veterinary Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring (Svarm) programme and is one of the co-authors of the annual Swedres/Svarm report. His research focus is on surveillance, molecular epidemiology, zoonotic aspects of antimicrobial drug resistance, and methodology development with special focus on Enterobacteriaceae with transferable antimicrobial resistance foremost ESBL, pAmpC and colistin. SB has participated as a partner in national and international collaboration projects including CoVetLab. He is a main partner in a Sino-Swedish project (IMPACT) investigating antibiotic resistance in China in a One Health perspective. In addition, he is the consortium coordinator on a proposal for the 3rd transnational research call within the JPIAMR involving six European institutes which qualified for a full proposal.

Märit Pringle is a veterinarian and associate professor at the national veterinary institute in Sweden (SVA). She is one of the editors of the annual report on consumption of antibiotics and occurrence of antibiotic resistance in Sweden (Swedres/Svarm) and is responsible for development of the broth microdilution system VetMIC, manufactured by SVA. Her research within the area of antimicrobial resistance has involved methods for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of fastidious bacteria (anaerobes, spirochetes) and molecular mechanisms of resistance. She has also been involved in several projects including molecular typing of bacteria, whole genome sequencing, resistance epidemiology, identification of virulence factors, diagnostics and treatment of bacterial infections in animals. She has 33 peer reviewed publications.

Dariusz Wasyl is a veterinarian, PhD and ScD in veterinary medicine. He works as associate professor at Department of Microbiology (PIWet), for more than 20 years being involved in research on Salmonella and antimicrobial resistance in Enterobacteriaceae. He is key researcher in NRL for Antimicrobial Resistance and salmonellosis. He has a great experience in traditional culture and molecular methods for identification and epidemiological characterisation of zoonotic bacteria. He currently leads PIWet teams participating in EU research projects: EFFORT (7FP) and ENGAGE (EFSA) focussed on antimicrobial resistance and foodborne pathogens. He is project leader for a national grant on invasive turtles as a source and vector of environmental and epidemiological threats (AMR included). He was a member of EFSA and Joint Programming Initiative working groups on antimicrobial resistance.

Cindy Dierikx (PhD, DVM) is a researcher working at the RIVM in the Netherlands. There she is working at the Department of zoonoses and environmental microbiology on antimicrobial resistance with focus on zoonotic bacteria in animals and humans. She is also secretary of the ESCMID Study Group for Veterinary Microbiology (ESGVM). Formerly she worked at the Central Veterinary Institute (now called Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (WBVR)) in the same group as Kees Veldman (project leader of this project), where she was involved in the yearly MARAN publication on the monitoring of antimicrobial resistance in animals in the Netherlands. She did her PhD on ESBLs in broilers and

obtained a lot of experience on antimicrobial resistance in general and specifically the detection and characterization of ESBL producing isolates.

Thijs Bosch (PhD) is a researcher at the RIVM in the Netherlands for the department of infectious diseases and perinatal screening. His research focuses on antimicrobial resistance in bacteria originating from humans and he is involved in the National surveillance of MRSA, CPE and CPPA in the Netherlands. He is also involved in the yearly Nethmap reports on the consumption of antimicrobial agents and antimicrobial resistance among medically important bacteria in the Netherlands. He did his PhD on the genotypic diversity and transmission of livestock-associated MRSA where he obtained a lot of experience on the characterization of bacterial isolates from both animals and humans and antimicrobial resistance in general.

Matthew Ellington (Dr.Phil) is a principal clinical scientist in Public Health England's world renowned Antimicrobial Resistance and Healthcare Associated Infections Reference Unit (AMRHAI). Dr Ellington has 12 year track record of phenotypic and molecular investigation of antibiotic resistance in and characterization of healthcare associated bacterial pathogens for epidemiological investigation purposes, with over 70 peer reviewed publications spanning these areas (4059 citations, h index = 31; i10 index = 50). Dr Ellington is an editor for the International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents has expertise in population biology, susceptibility testing methods, surveillance of resistance, molecular epidemiology and mechanisms of resistance with organism interests currently focussed on MDR gram negative bacteria that are carbapenem and colistin non-susceptible.

Prof Neil Woodford is head of PHE's Antimicrobial Resistance and Healthcare Associated Infections (AMRHAI) unit. He has worked on antibiotic resistance for over 25 years and is an internationally recognized authority on the molecular epidemiology of resistance with more than 250 published papers on resistance mechanisms and epidemiology. He has edited three books on the subject and is a Fellow of the Royal College of Pathologists on the basis of his published works. Prof Woodford has served for 10 years as an Editor of the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy, and is on the Editorial Board of Microbial Drug Resistance. Prof Woodford is a member of two Health Protection Units examining antimicrobial resistance, one with Imperial College and the other with the University of Oxford in partnership with APHA. As a committee member of several groups advising government on research and policy relating to antimicrobial resistance in humans and animals he has the insight and necessary understanding of the complex, multi-factorial problem of resistance epidemiology to advise on policy and research in relation to antimicrobial resistance in humans and animals.

Els Broens, DVM, PhD, is assistant professor at the Division Clinical Infectiology of the Department of Infectious Diseases and Immunology of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Utrecht University. There she is head of the Veterinary Microbiological Diagnostic Centre where routine diagnostics are performed on animal samples sent in from Dutch veterinary clinics. She has a wide experience in veterinary clinical microbiology and antimicrobial resistance testing. She is and has been involved in several research projects on monitoring prevalence and transmission of resistant and potential zoonotic, bacteria. She is member of the Dutch Working Party on Veterinary Antibiotic Policy (WVAB) and project leader of a project on Antibiotic Stewardship in Pets.

Alessia Franco at the Istituto Zooprofilattico del Lazio e della Toscana (IZSLT) is staff veterinarian and senior scientist at the NRL-AR Italy, led by Antonio Battisti DVM. She and the NRL-AR Italy group are well acknowledged in the field of epidemiology of AMR and in the phenotypic determination of antimicrobial resistance and in the characterization of both core genome and transferable elements such as plasmids in major AMR zoonotic and commensal bacteria (e. g. Salmonella, Klebsiella, E. coli, MRSA) in animals and food of animal origin. Based on population-based studies aimed at investigating the epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance, including zoonotic AMR, the NRL-AR Italy has been producing original research for more than ten years on the above cited antimicrobial resistant pathogens in both primary productions, foodstuffs and companion animals. Alessia Franco is author of several papers on the topics of infectious diseases and related AMR, published by international peer-reviewed journals.

Antonio Battisti at the Istituto Zooprofilattico del Lazio e della Toscana (IZSLT) leads the NRL-AR Italy and its research group. He and his group are well acknowledged in the field of epidemiology of AMR, phenotypic characterisation of resistance by AST and deep characterization of both core genome and transferable elements such as plasmids in major AMR zoonotic and commensal bacteria (e. g. Salmonella, Klebsiella, E. coli, MRSA) in animals and food of animal origin. Based on population-based studies aimed at investigating the epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance, including zoonotic AMR, the NRL-AR Italy has been producing for more than ten years original research on the above cited antimicrobial resistant pathogens in both primary productions, foodstuffs and companion animals. Antonio Battisti and his collaborators are Authors of several papers on the topics of infectious diseases and related AMR, published by international peer-reviewed Journals.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

For WP1 (Selective isolation, detection and characterization of colistin-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*), the final ring trial was organised in June 2019. All participants received a final report in November 2020 where a combined use of PCR step and selective commercial media were evaluated. As a result, PCR detection of *mcr*-genes showed 100% specificity and one out of three media tested shows a better sensitivity to selectively isolate colistin-resistant *mcr*-positive strains. Performance of the colistin-resistant screening process is greater for caecal than meat samples in the experimental conditions of this WP1. More trials are needed to test the effect of other matrixes, bacterial concentrations and a broader range of *mcr*-positive strains.

For WP2 (Selective isolation, detection and characterization of carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae*), the final ring trial was organised in September 2019. All participants received a report containing their own results compared to what was expected. Preliminary results of the WP2 ring trial were presented at the 2nd One Health EJP-ASM. In WP2, the final report was finalized in September 2020. The main outcome indicates that some of the commercially available selective agar media are not sensitive or selective enough to detect bacteria expressing low-level carbapenemase production. Further, there are no commercially available selective agars to detect carbapenem-resistant *Salmonella* spp., as they are non-chromogenic on most media. Some bacteria harbouring specific genes (*bla*_{VIM-1} *E. coli*) that circulate in the livestock population in Europe might be missed using the protocol currently set by the EU decision 2013/652/EU with a pre-enrichment in non-selective BPW-ISO. More studies are needed to test other selective enrichment broths, matrices and bacterial species.

Within WP3 (Establishing epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs)), the production and collection of MIC distributions was finished in May 2020. Uploading of the MIC distributions on the EUCAST website was completed in September 2020. The process of calculating epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) based on the uploaded MIC distributions was further delayed because of unexpected problems regarding the acceptance of MIC data by EUCAST due to differences in test method between EUCAST and the IMPART project for the more fastidious growing bacteria. To measure possible media effects, bridging studies have been conducted at WBVR at the end of 2020 and are currently evaluated. The discussion on the difference in test methods does not account for bacteria without supplements in the test media. For this reason the MIC distributions of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* are currently analysed and the first accepted ECOFFs for this bacterial species are expected in the beginning of 2021.

Within WP4 (Developing and optimizing a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile*), a *Clostridium difficile* strain collection comprising 527 strains was completely characterized regarding PCR-ribotypes, toxin gene and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) profiles (minimum inhibitory concentrations; MICs). An optimized disk diffusion protocol as alternative method for AMR testing was established and inhibition zone diameter (IZD) distributions determined for eight antimicrobials analyzing each strain of the collection. Evaluation of the MICs and IZDs for each strain to determine wild-type and non-wildtype phenotypes correlated well for most but not all antimicrobials. Preliminary results and cut-off values were presented at the 2nd One Health EJP ASM. The ring trial to finalize the validation of the proposed disk diffusion method was conducted in June

2020 with seven participating laboratories. Reports were sent out to the participants and uploaded to the One Health EJP group website. Overall, the optimized method description proved to be highly reproducible but critical steps could be identified.

Within WP5 (Coordination of the four work packages and knowledge dissemination both internally within and externally beyond the IMPART consortium), emails were sent out by the WP leaders to all consortium members containing general information on the progress of the different WP's. Furthermore, all WP leaders were in contact via Skype every two weeks discussing the organization of IMPART and the progress of the different WPs. Furthermore, three abstracts comprising results from WP2, WP3 and WP4 were presented as poster at the One Health EJP ASM online meeting in May 2020. The closing meeting was initially planned in June 2020, but postponed as teleconference to December and later to March 2021 because of COVID-19.

3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Selective isolation, detection and characterization of colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (M1-M36)

JRP1-WP1-T1: Describe existing methods to be evaluated in a ring trial (M1-M6)

A literature review had been performed to determine which media were used to isolate colistin-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*. This review had been complemented by exploring any other commercially available option on the market as off September 2018. We selected both ready-to-use commercial reagents available throughout Europe and in-house prepared reagents. The selected media for the pre-ring trial were: MacConkey Agar + 2mg/L colistin, COLISTIGRAM (SuperPolymyxin™), CHROMagar™ COL-APSE (CHROMagar), CHROMID® Colistin R (BioMerieux). Protocols using selective (1, 2 or 4mg/L of colistin) versus non-selective enrichment broth were also explored.

JRP1-WP1-T2: Preparation of the samples for the pre-ring trial (WP1 and WP2, M7-M8)

In order to avoid false positive detection, our samples to be artificially contaminated (later called “blank” samples) were mostly collected from slaughtered Specific Pathogen Free (SPF) animals from collaborating animal housing facilities (pig and turkey caecal content, turkey meat). Due to unavailability, pig meat had to be purchased at retail shop. Nevertheless, meat and caecal “blank” samples had been checked for absence of colistin resistant determinant by both multiplex PCR (Rebelo et al, 2018, Eurosurveillance) and plating on MacConkey + 2mg/l colistin agar. Non-contaminated sampled had been preserved frozen (-20°C).

Contamination of the “blank” samples of minced meat or caecal content was performed with characterized *mcr*-positive strains originated from animals.

Prior to spiking, a 0.5 McFarland ($\approx 10^8$ CFU/ml) target bacterial suspension in saline (0.9% NaCl) water using fresh colonies had been prepared and diluted to obtain the target concentrations in the pooled samples of minced meat or caecal content (10^2 CFU/g sample). The aliquots were stored at 4°C until shipping on Tuesday, December 11th.

Artificially contaminated aliquots were distributed at 4°C to the three participating labs (NVI, RIVM and WBVR). In order to avoid deviations due to different batches of reagents, ready-to-use media and powders for in-house media were distributed to the participants along with the samples.

JRP1-WP1-T3: Performance of the pre-ring trial and evaluation (M10-M11)

Performance of the pre-ring trial was evaluated all through the first semester 2019. An alternative protocol has been established to improve the detection of positive strains prior to the final ring-trial. The final report of the WP1 pre-ring trial was posted on the IMPART private group on 25 November 2019.

JRP1-WP1-T4: Preparation of samples for the final ring trial (WP1 and WP2, M12-M17)

The protocol for the final ring trial, along with a technical questionnaire, were sent out to the 11 participants at draft stage for consultation on 2 May 2019. The final version of the protocol and the result sheet were distributed to the participants by email on 3 June 2019. A panel of three meat samples and three caecal content samples was prepared at Anses-Fougères laboratory the 13 and 14 June 2019 and stored at 4°C until shipping. Panel of samples and commercially selective agar plates were shipped to the WP1 participants on Monday 17 June 2019.

JRP1-WP1-T5: Performing the final ring trial (M17)

The 11 participants received the parcel on Tuesday 18 June 2019. Ten participants started immediately the analysis, while one was advised to store the samples for a week at -80°C prior to analysis due to bank holiday.

Homogeneity and stability of the samples were assessed at Anses-Fougères laboratory the day of shipment and one day after reception and analysis of the samples by the participating laboratories.

JRP1-WP1-T6: Analysis of the results and reporting (M18-M19)

The analysis of results sheet has been accomplished from September 2019 to May 2020. A final report was draft and sent to the 11 participants for consultation in September 2020. The final report of the ring trial was uploaded to the IMPART EJP website the 4th of November 2020.

JRP1-WP1-T7: Publication in peer-reviewed journal (M25-M30)

This task is delayed and planned for the first half of 2021.

JRP1-WP1-T8: Plan joint implementation (M25-M30)

There will not be a joint implementation plan, because the method for isolation and detection of colistin resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* needs further development.

WP2: Selective isolation, detection and characterization of carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* (M1-M36)

JRP1-WP2-T1: Describe existing methods to be evaluated in a ring trial (M1-M6)

To establish the protocol for the WP2 pre-ring trial, a literature study was performed and a questionnaire was sent to the participants to share experiences between the participants. All information was gathered together with a summary of a questionnaire sent out by the European Union Reference Laboratory on Antimicrobial Resistance (EURL-AR) regarding selective media. Further, the following conditions was discussed: pre-enrichment (which media, selective/non-selective), choice of selective agar plates, incubation temperatures for pre-enrichment and selective agar plates, levels of contamination of the samples, which bacteria/gene-combination to spike with, and what kind of matrix to use (turkey, chicken, pig, cattle).

A list was made of selective agar plates used for detecting carbapenemase producers and the availability and possibility to produce the plates in-house was taken into consideration.

JRP1-WP2-T2: Preparation of the samples for the pre-ring trial (WP2, M7-M8)

All samples were prepared at Anses Fougères as described under **JRP1-WP1-T2: Preparation of the samples for the pre-ring trial (WP1 and WP2, M7-M8)**. Meat and caecal “blank” samples was checked for absence of carbapenem resistant determinant by using the EURL-AR method (https://www.eurl-ar.eu/CustomData/Files/Folders/21-protocols/530_esbl-ampc-cpeprotocol-version-caecal-v7-09-12-19.pdf, https://www.eurl-ar.eu/CustomData/Files/Folders/21-protocols/529_esbl-ampc-cpeprotocol-version-meat-v7-09-12-19.pdf). Non-contaminated sampled had been preserved frozen (-20°C). Contamination of the “blank” samples of minced meat or caecal content was performed with characterized CPE-positive strains originated from animals. The samples were distributed to the three

participating laboratories (RIVM, WBVR, and NVI) on Tuesday November 20th at 4°C and processed at arrival within 48 hours.

JRP1-WP2-T3: Performance of the pre-ring trial and evaluation (M10-M11)

The pre-ring trial focused on testing several conditions to detect carbapenemase-producing (CP) *Enterobacteriaceae* to narrow down different possibilities to test in the final ring trial. The focus was to:

1. Test all selective agar plates available in all European countries both in-house and ready-to-use.
2. Test two different temperatures for incubation of the selective agar plates:
 - a. Recommended by the different manufacturers: 35±2°C or 37°C.
 - b. An elevated temperature to try to eliminate unspecific growth: 44°C.
3. Preferably, test DNA extracts from the overnight pre-enrichment broth using a direct PCR protocol.

The performance of the pre-ring trial was evaluated through the first months of 2019 and the final report of the WP2 pre-ring trial was posted on the IMPART group private group in July 2019.

JRP1-WP2-T4: Preparation of samples for the final ring trial (WP1 and WP2, M12-M17)

The samples were prepared at Anses Fougères laboratory on Friday September 6th 2019. The samples were prepared using the same method as for the pre-ring trial (JRP1-WP2-T2).

JRP1-WP2-T5: Performing the final ring trial (M17)

The final ring trial was performed among eleven laboratories participating in IMPART. The samples (n=8) were prepared at Anses Fougères Laboratory on Friday September 6th 2019 and shipped to the eleven participants on Monday September 9th 2019. Analysis started immediately at arrival of the samples. The final protocol was sent as a draft to the participating laboratories for comments on July 5th 2019. Prior to the sample shipment, the ring trial protocol was distributed per email to each participant. The six selective agar plates to be tested, were shipped with the samples.

JRP1-WP2-T6: Analysis of the results and reporting (M18-M19)

Each participating lab received their own report containing what they reported and what was expected in the final ring trial, M27 March 2020. The analysis and drafting of the report from the entire ring trial was delayed due to the COVID-19 situation, but a draft was sent to the participants before the summer holidays (M30) and the report was finalized by M33, September 2020.

JRP1-WP2-T7: Publication in peer-reviewed journal (M25-M30)

The project received a last minute extension from M30 to M36 and due date was December 2020. This task is on-going, but has been delayed. A publication is planned for the first half of 2021. A draft manuscript was ready ultimo December 2020 and distributed to the laboratories participating in this work package.

JRP1-WP2-T8: Plan joint implementation (M25-M30)

There will not be a joint implementation plan, because this project did not result in a new method for isolation and detection of carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*, but ended up doing a multicentre study of an existing method with several selective agar plates, not giving a better harmonized method.

WP3. Establishing epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) (M1-M36)

JRP1-WP3-T1: Inventory, prioritizing and inclusion criteria (M1-M3)

This task was finalized in July 2018 but refined in May 2019. Soon after the physical meeting, an Excel sheet was prepared with a list of bacterial species to be tested. After consultation of the partners by email, it was boiled down to a short list consisting of 17 different bacterial species belonging to either

staphylococci, streptococci, *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Pasteurellae* or *Pseudomonas* spp. Based on this short list, a new Excel sheet was sent around by email to all partners on 20 July 2019 in which each partner was asked to fill in exactly which bacterial species they planned to test (or already had tested) including the number of isolates per panel. In this way, an overview was generated of the total number of isolates per bacterial species tested per panel per partner. For most bacterial species selected, at least 5 partners and > 100 strains were to be tested which should be sufficient for setting ECOFFs for these combinations according to EUCAST guidelines.

JRP1-WP3-T2: Production of MIC data (M4-M18)

Task was finalised in May 2020 (collection of MIC distributions completed).

JRP1-WP3-T3: Collection and quality control of MIC data (M4-M18)

Nine partner institutes performed antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of 2,831 bacterial isolates involving 19 different veterinary pathogenic bacteria including staphylococci (*Staphylococcus pseudintermedius*, *S. hyicus*), streptococci (*Streptococcus agalactiae*, *S. dysgalactiae*, *S. uberis*, *S. suis*, *S. canis*, *S. equi* subsp. *zooepidemicus*, *S. equi* subsp. *equi*, *S. equisimilis*), *Pasteurella multocida*, *Mannheimia haemolytica*, *Actinobacillus pleuropneumoniae*, *Bordetella bronchiseptica*, *Haemophilus parasuis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca* and *Klebsiella variicola*. This resulted in 1,310 MIC-distributions consisting 47,640 MIC-values of 34 different antimicrobials. The collection of MIC results was completed in May 2020. An additional request was sent out in June 2020 to collect raw MIC data. The correctness of the earlier received MIC distributions were reviewed using the raw MIC data files. In case MIC distributions were not in accordance with the raw data, the MIC distribution files were recalculated based on the raw MIC data files. Examples of frequently identified errors in the MIC distributions were incorrect translation of MIC-values at the edges of the test concentrations (\leq or $>$ values) and mistakes in the total number of isolates tested per antibiotic. Finally, all corrected MIC distributions were uploaded in the EUCAST database in September 2020.

JRP1-WP3-T4: Analysis of the data and publication of ECOFFs (M25-M36)

The process of calculating epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) based on the uploaded MIC distributions has been delayed and is currently still ongoing. The first ECOFFs are expected in the first quarter of 2021 for *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius*. On 24 September 2020 a teleconference was held with VetCAST and EUCAST to discuss the outcomes of IMPART WP3. During this meeting it was pointed out that EUCAST implemented a new SOP for determination of ECOFFs and as a result has become stricter on the acceptance of MIC-distributions with regard to the methods used for MIC-testing. The following is stated on the EUCAST website (www.eucast.org/mic_distributions_and_ecoffs/): "Using agreed criteria for the acceptance of MIC distributions, the database and ECOFFs are currently being critically evaluated. Official ECOFFs are determined by EUCAST, adhering to protocols generated by the "EUCAST Subcommittee on MIC distributions and the determination of ECOFFs" (SOP10.1) ". As a consequence, WBVR is currently performing bridging studies testing a selection of streptococci and *Pasteurella multocida* isolates to determine the possible effect of using CAMHB + LHB (according to CLSI) instead of MH-F broth (according to EUCAST). Depending on the outcome of these bridging studies MIC distributions of bacteria tested in CAMHB + LHB will or will not be accepted by EUCAST. Fortunately, this does not include bacterial species tested in CAMHB without supplements. Therefore, the analysis of MIC distributions of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* was given priority and the first accepted ECOFFs for this bacterial species is expected in the first quarter of 2021.

WP4: Developing and optimizing a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile* (M4-M36)

JRP1-WP4-T1: Establishment of a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *C. difficile* (M4-M14)

To establish a robust protocol for disk diffusion testing of *C. difficile*, we reviewed recent literature regarding this topic and identified critical parameters for reliability and repeatability of inhibition zone diameters (IZD) and growth of *C. difficile*. A first draft protocol was developed that is based on the EUCAST disk diffusion method (v 6.0) and includes recommendations from the literature. For optimization and standardization experiments, ten *C. difficile* strains were selected from the strain collection (see JRP1-WP4-T2) based on different resistance properties. Optimization experiments included the comparison of different media for inoculum preparation (BHI, TPGY, Brucella broth), different turbidity steps (McFarland 0.5 – 4.0) and different solid media (Brucella blood agar, Wilkins-Chalgren-agar, Columbia blood agar) for the disk diffusion itself. Furthermore, different procedures and conditions of anaerobic incubation and pre-treatment were analysed, to be able to propose guidelines later. While the different inoculum and solid media had no significant effect on IZD, the turbidity has to be amended from EUCAST recommendations to reach confluent growth for most of the strains. The biggest variance resulted from different anaerobic conditions and indicates that this factor is the most critical for standardization. The setup which resulted in reliable results and is applicable by most microbiological laboratories, was repeated several times to determine standard deviations and repeatability. Furthermore, the interlaboratory reproducibility will be tested in JRP1-WP4-T4.

Due to problems in recruiting the applied technician and problems in delivery of a gas mixture for working in an anaerobic workstation as well as the availability of culture media, this task including milestone M-JRP1-4 (M8) was delayed.

JRP1-WP4-T2: Assembly and characterization of *C. difficile* strain collection (M4-M12)

This task was finalized in December 2019 with a total number of 527 *C. difficile* strains of human, animal, environmental and food origin from ten partner institutes. All strains were completely characterized according to their PCR-ribotypes, toxin gene profiles and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) phenotypes (minimum inhibitory concentrations; MICs). The results and data will be provided on the One Health EJP website.

JRP1-WP4-T3: Performance of a ring trial study (M22-M32)

The ring trial was conducted in June 2020 with seven participating laboratories. The results were reported by 30th June 2020. Reports were sent out to the participants on 25th August 2020 and uploaded to the group on the One Health EJP website. The results indicate that the optimized disk diffusion protocol ensures comparable and reproducible results and reveals critical factors, e.g. the equipment for maintaining anaerobic conditions. Standard deviations were overall low but differed depending on the antimicrobial and equipment used.

JRP1-WP4-T4: Producing inhibition zone diameter distributions and proposing cut-off values for *C. difficile* (M17-M33)

Inhibition zone diameter distributions have been determined for eight antimicrobials (clindamycin, erythromycin, metronidazole, moxifloxacin, imipenem, rifampicin, tetracycline, vancomycin) analysing 527 strains of the *C. difficile* strain collection (see JRP1-WP4-T2). Preliminary results and cut-off values were presented at the 2nd One Health EJP-ASM and uploaded to the One Health EJP website. These results enable to compare IZDs and MICs for each strain in terms of classifying them to have a wildtype or non-wildtype phenotype. This task was finalized in September 2020 (M33).

WP5: Coordination of the four work packages and knowledge dissemination both internally within and externally beyond the IMPART consortium (M1-M36)

JRP1-WP5-T1: Organization of IMPART (M1-M36)

IMPART consists of five different WP's supervised by WP leaders. The first four WP's have defined scientific goals whereas WP5 is intended for the communication and dissemination of knowledge.

JRP1-WP5-T2: Communication within IMPART (M1-M36)

A kick-off meeting was held on 20th February 2018 at Schiphol airport for all consortium members. All partner institutes were represented by at least one person. During this one-day meeting, the IMPART project was introduced and the tasks and timelines of each work package was discussed with the participants.

During the second year, a physical meeting was held for all consortium members at the One Health EJP ASM meeting in Dublin. In addition, the WP leaders sent out emails to all consortium members containing general information on the progress of the different WP's. Furthermore, all WP leaders were in contact via Skype every two weeks discussing the organization of IMPART and the progress of the different WPs.

In the third and final year of IMPART, consortium members were informed by the WP leaders about activities and tasks via emails or teleconferences. In December 2020, a newsletter was sent to all consortium members by email with an update on the status of the different WP's. The closing meeting was initially planned in June 2020, but because of the COVID-19 crisis postponed to December 2020 and recently planned for March 2021 as a teleconference.

JRP1-WP5-T3: Communication beyond IMPART (M1-M36)

In the first year (2018) the IMPART project proposal was presented at the One Health EJP Kick-off meeting in Maisons-Alfort (France) on 30-31 January 2018. Project plans were presented and discussed in more detail during the IMPART kick-off meeting on 20 February 2018 at Schiphol airport. Furthermore, IMPART activities were presented at both Cogwheel meetings organised in 2018 with COMPARE (12 April) and EFFORT (26 October) and shared on the WBVR website as news item in December 2018.

Progress of IMPART research was presented through posters at the One Health EJP ASM meeting in Dublin in May 2019. The first results of IMPART was also presented during the annual workshop of the EURL for AMR, which gathers the European NRL for AMR on a yearly basis. The three presentations are available on: <https://www.eurl-ar.eu/presentations/workshop-kgs-lyngby-april-2019.aspx>.

In 2020, results of IMPART WP3 were presented during the kick-off meeting of COST action ENOVAT held on 25th of February in Tirana. Information about WP3 was shared in the VetCAST Newsletter 2020 and sent to all VetCAST members by email on 29th of April 2020. Results of WP2, WP3 and WP4 were presented as digital posters on 27th-29th of May 2020 at the online One Health EJP ASM meeting. Project outcomes and interactions with stakeholders were presented on 12th of October 2020 at the One Health EJP 6th Stakeholders Committee Meeting. A short summary of IMPART activities was presented on 4th of November 2020 at the ECDC food- and waterborne disease steering committee meeting. Finally, a first meeting was held with the Communication Team of the One Health EJP on 23th of October 2020. It was agreed to start working on the promotion of four deliverables from the IMPART project (one from each work package). The Communication Team will share a draft proposal with the IMPART management team in the beginning of 2021.

4 Project self-assessment

Objectives

Work package 1:

Selective isolation, detection and characterization of colistin-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*

The objectives of WP1 were to evaluate the feasibility and performance of different methods existing for isolation of colistin-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*. An initial protocol was established and evaluated in a pre-ring trial by few partners. This protocol aggregated the best performing commercially or in house methods where matrix (meat or caecal content), animal species (pig, cattle, poultry), bacterial contaminant (*E. coli*, *Klebsiella* or *Salmonella*) and resistance mechanism (*mcr* genes) to be detected were combined. The detection limit of the method was not evaluated because the number of combinations were too high at this stage of development. Evaluation of the pre-ring trial results led to a final amended protocol for which performance were evaluated in a ring trial with all the partners. All the tasks in WP1 have been met as was described in the initial proposal. Due to a huge combination of alternatives and complex flora in some matrices, it was not possible after evaluation of the final ring trial to propose a harmonized method suitable enough to monitor the current prevalence and spread of *mcr* variants in *Enterobacteriaceae*.

Work package 2:

Selective isolation, detection and characterization of carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*

The objectives for WP2 in this project was to find an optimal culture method for the detection of relevant carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* (CPE) in meat and caecal samples from animals. A pre-ring trial among three labs was performed to narrow down the different choices to be tested in the final ring trial among eleven labs. We ended up, after an extensive protocol tested in the pre-ring trial, to use pre-enrichment as outlined in the protocol amended in the EU Decision 2013/652/EU. After pre-enrichment, the broth was streaked onto different selective agar media that were commercially available. A new and better method was not validated through the project period. There is a challenge in developing a harmonized method covering several bacterial species harbouring different carbapenemase producing genes. The results from the ring trials in WP2 underline the need to find more optimal culturing methods to detect low-level carbapenemase producing *Enterobacteriaceae* and carbapenemase producing *Salmonella* spp., for which there is no commercially selective agar available that can detect them using a chromogen.

Work package 3:

Establishing epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs)

The main goal of WP3 was to establish epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) of antimicrobials for veterinary pathogens. The first step in this work package was to reach consensus on the bacterial species and antibiotics to be included. During the kick-off meeting in February 2018, a priority list with bacterial species (based on the results of a questionnaire) was agreed upon. Furthermore, the concept of designing three different antibiotic panels as Sensititre plates was accepted. The antibiotic panels were designed based on registration data of veterinary antibiotics and prescription guidelines. The design of the antibiotic panels took a bit more time than initially planned and Sensititre plates were ordered in August 2018. Unfortunately, there was a serious delay in the delivery of the plates. As a consequence, partner institutes received the Sensititre plates in February and March of 2019, but most partners started with the MIC testing soon afterwards. In the meanwhile, all consortium partners were consulted and the priority list of the bacterial species to be tested was refined and finalised in May 2019. Despite of the forced delay in testing, most partners managed to complete the production of the MIC data before the end of 2019. The MIC testing was fully completed in May 2020. The process of calculating ECOFFs based on the uploaded MIC distributions was further delayed because of unexpected problems regarding the acceptance of MIC distributions in the EUCAST database (as described in chapter 3, JRP1-WP3-T4) and is currently still ongoing. Finally, the analysis of MIC distributions of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* was given priority and the first accepted ECOFFs for this bacterial species are expected in the beginning of 2021. Depending on the outcome of the discussion with EUCAST, ECOFFs for other bacterial species like streptococci are expected to follow in 2021.

Work package 4:

Developing and optimizing a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile*

The aim of WP4 was to optimize a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of *Clostridium difficile*, to validate it by an international ring trial and evaluate this method in comparison with the gold standard, agar dilution, in order to distinguish wild-type from non-wild-type antimicrobial phenotypes. According to the proposal, a draft disk diffusion protocol was established based on the assessment of current literature and further optimized. Even though we could not recruit the entire number of 500 *C. difficile* strains directly from project partners, we were able to finally collect 527 *C. difficile* isolates addressing also external partners. Strains were characterized as planned (PCR-ribotype, toxin-gene profile and antimicrobial phenotype (MICs)) and used to establish IZD distributions for eight antimicrobials. Based on these distributions, we proposed cut-off values to distinguish wild type from non-wild type phenotypes except for vancomycin and imipenem due to a lack of non-wild type strains in the strain collection. Furthermore, phenotypic resistance testing against cefotaxime resulted in very high resistance rates which indicated the definition of cut-off values for this antimicrobial class to be not reasonable. So, we replaced cefotaxime by erythromycin for further analyses. For the final ring trial we had to involve external partners because most of the IMPART partners missed expertise/equipment in this special field or laboratory capacities due to the COVID-19 crisis. Though, the ring trial was overall successful and revealed important aspects for further method standardization but lacked participants for reliable statistics.

Work package 5:

Coordination of the four work packages and knowledge dissemination

The main goal of WP5 was to coordinate the knowledge dissemination within and beyond IMPART. In general, this was accomplished satisfactory. However, some of the planned activities (physical project meetings) were hindered by the COVID-19 crisis. Distribution of information within IMPART was well secured by the imbedded organisational structure of the project which included the role of a project leader (PL) responsible for the overall coordination of the project and work package leaders (WPL) responsible for the scientific quality and progress of each of the four scientific work packages. In addition, a separate work package (WP5) was defined to coordinate communication and dissemination activities. Within the consortium, information was shared through physical meetings (kick-off meeting and a project meeting in Dublin at the One Health EJP ASM conference), regular teleconferences between the PL and WPL, emails by the PL to WPL's and by the PL to the complete consortium and ad hoc communication of WPLs with WP participants depending on the planning of the different work packages. At the end of 2020 a newsletter with updated information about the different WPs was shared with the consortium and the EJP management. Communication outside IMPART was covered by active participation in workshops (EURL-AR), conferences (One Health EJP ASM), Cogwheel meetings and several contacts with stakeholders (EFSA, EURL-AR and EUCAST). The closing meeting of IMPART was initially planned in June 2020, but because of the budget neutral extension postponed to December 2020 still hoping to organise a physical meeting. Recently it was decided to plan the closing meeting for 2nd of March 2021 as a teleconference. Although this meeting is rescheduled after the official closing date of the project, it gives the IMPART management team (PL and WPLs) this final opportunity to present and discuss the completed results with the consortium members. Lastly, it was agreed that the Communication Team of the One Health EJP will work on the promotion of four deliverables from the IMPART project (one from each work package). The Communication Team will share a draft proposal with the IMPART management team in the beginning of 2021.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
01	D-JRP1-1.1	Protocol of methods ready to be used in the pre-ring trial	M6	M12		https://zenodo.org/record/3676410#.X3xKMHkzY2x	2, 9
01	D-JRP1-1.3	Evaluation of the pre-ring trial	M11	M13		https://zenodo.org/record/3676404#.X3xlvHkzY2w	9
01	D-JRP1-1.4	Protocol for the final ring trial	M15	M21		https://zenodo.org/record/3676425#.X3xMkXkzY2y	2, 9
01	D-JRP1-1.5	Notifications of shipment of the samples for the final ring trial	M16	M17		https://zenodo.org/record/3676431#.X3xLB3kzY2y	8
01	D-JRP1-1.6	Evaluation of the final ring trial	M21	M35		Full report confidential until paper is published (D-JRP1-1.7). Short evaluation uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4460952#.YA5amNhKg2w	9
01	D-JRP1-1.7	Publication in an open-access peer-reviewed journal	M30		M39	Public	8

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
01	D-JRP1-1.8	Proposal(s) for epidemiological study to monitor resistance to colistin	M30		No date	The design of an epidemiological study proposal will be very difficult based on this detection method, because the methods need further development.	1
01	D-JRP1-2.1	Protocol of methods ready to be used in the pre-ring trial	M6	M11		https://zenodo.org/record/3676433#.X3xLLnkzY2y	2, 9
01	D-JRP1-2.3	Evaluation of the pre-ring trial	M10	M19		https://zenodo.org/record/3676437#.X3xMtnkzY2y	9
01	D-JRP1-2.4	Protocol for the final ring trial	M15	M21		https://zenodo.org/record/3676439#.X3xLI3kzY2y	2, 9
01	D-JRP1-2.5	Notifications of shipment of the samples for the final ring trial	M16	M17		https://zenodo.org/record/3676431#.X3xLB3kzY2y	8
01	D-JRP1-2.6	Evaluation of the final ring trial	M26	M33		Full report confidential until paper is published (D-JRP1-2.7). Short evaluation uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4452580#.YAgxg9hKg2w	9
01	D-JRP1-2.7	Publication in an open-access peer-reviewed journal	M30		M39	Public	8
01	D-JRP1-2.8	Proposal(s) for epidemiological study to monitor resistance	M30		No date	The design of an epidemiological study proposal will be very difficult based on this detection method. Such a study should be conducted in close	1

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		to carbapenems				cooperation with EURL and EFSA.	
01	D-JRP1-3.1	Priority list	M3	M2		https://zenodo.org/record/4068251#.X3xshXkzY2w	2, 9
01	D-JRP1-3.2	Analysis of the data	M30		M39	All MIC distributions have been uploaded to the EUCAST database and have the status 'Created'. This database is only assessable by a select number of people from VetCAST and EUCAST (data curators). After acceptance of MIC distributions the data will be available for all visitors of the EUCAST website as diagrams with aggregated distributions: https://eucast.org/mic_distributions_and_ecoffs/	2, 9
01	D-JRP1-3.3	Publication of ECOFFs on EUCAST website	M30		M39	Public on EUCAST website; www.eucast.org	2, 9
01	D-JRP1-4.1	Collection of inhibition zone diameter distributions	M21	M36		Confidential until paper is published (D-JRP1-4.2)	9
01	D-JRP1-4.2	Publication in an open-access peer-reviewed journal	M30		M39	Public	8
01	D-JRP1-4.3	Performance of a ring trial study	M27	M33		Full report confidential until paper is published (D-JRP1-4.2). Short evaluation uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4457449#.YA5bHNhKg2w	2, 9

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
01	D-JRP1-5.1	Invitation to the kick-off meeting sent to participants	M1	M1		Public ; https://zenodo.org/record/3676441#.X3xJcXkzY2y	10
01	D-JRP1-5.2	Kick-off meeting notes sent to participants	M3	M2		https://zenodo.org/record/3678185#.X3xJ9HkzY2x	8
01	D-JRP1-5.3	IMPART News online on One Health EJP website	M30	M36		Public, uploaded to Zenodo : https://zenodo.org/record/4463049#.YBQTn-hKhM0	8
01	D-JRP1-5.4	Protocols and video tutorials online on One Health EJP website	M18	M21		Only protocols	8
01	D-JRP1-5.5	Invitation to the final meeting sent to participants	M21	M36		Date set on 2 nd of March 2021. Invitation uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4457438#.YA5cVthKg2w	8
01	D-JRP1-5.6	Final meeting notes sent to participants	M30		M39	Public	10

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); 9. This is supportive to an integrative activity; 10. This is not an integrative activity

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
01	M-JRP1-1	Kick-off meeting (notes of meeting)	2	Yes		
01	M-JRP1-2	Ordering of microtiter plates with antimicrobials (WP3)	4	Yes	6	Creating the layout of the microtiter plates was more complicated than expected.
01	M-JRP1-3	IMPART EXTRANET in place	6	No		OH-EJP platform opened in month 9, therefore it was decided not to build our own platform.
01	M-JRP1-4	Established disk diffusion method (WP4)	8	Yes	14	Advertised technician position could not be recruited on time. Delay in gas delivery by manufacturer.
01	M-JRP1-5	Completed strain collection (WP4)	10	Yes	12	
01	M-JRP1-6	Performing pre-ring trial (WP1 and WP2)	11	Yes	– 11 (WP2) 12 (WP1)	
01	M-JRP1-7	Mid-term video meeting to validate the protocol (WP1, WP2)	13	Yes		The protocols were presented by the WP leaders and discussed during the physical project meeting the One Health EJP ASM meeting in Dublin and at the EURL meeting in 2019.
01	M-JRP1-8	Performing final ring trial (WP1 and WP2)	17	WP1: Yes WP2: Yes	WP1: 18 WP2: 21	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
01	M-JRP1-9	MIC data collection complete (WP3)	M24	Yes		Achieved in M29
01	M-JRP1-10	Proposal of cut-off values based on inhibition zone diameter distributions (WP4)	M26	Yes	M35	
01	M-JRP1-11	Final meeting (notes of the meeting)	M30	No	M39	Due to the COVID-19 issues, the final meeting was postponed and is planned at 2 March 2021 as a teleconference.

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Spill-Over from Public Health? First Detection of an OXA-48-Producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> in a German Pig Farm, doi: 10.3390/microorganisms8060855 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4447289#.YAWijthKg2w	Yes		Yes, €1496,13
ChromID® CARBA Agar Fails to Detect Carbapenem-Resistant <i>Enterobacteriaceae</i> With Slightly Reduced Susceptibility to Carbapenems, doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2020.01678 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4447289#.YAfMEthKg2w	Yes		Yes €2629,35
First Detection of GES-5-Producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> from Livestock-An Increasing Diversity of Carbapenemases Recognized from German Pig Production, DOI: 10.3390/microorganisms8101593 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4451836#.YAfzdhKg2w	Yes		Yes, €1 389.79
Novel IncFII plasmid harbouring bla _{NDM-4} in a carbapenem-resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> of pig origin, Italy, doi:10.1093/jac/dkaa374 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4451840#.YAfPRNhKg2w	Yes		Yes, €3,603.60
Identification of a bla _{VIM-1} -Carrying IncA/C2 Multiresistance Plasmid in an <i>Escherichia coli</i> Isolate Recovered from the German Food Chain, doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010029 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4451858#.YAfqINhKg2w	Yes		Yes, €1180,27
Co-occurrence of the bla _{VIM-1} and bla _{SHV-12} genes on an IncHI2 plasmid of an <i>Escherichia coli</i> isolate recovered from German livestock, doi:10.1093/jac/dkaa436 Zenodo:	Yes		Yes, €1802,40

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
https://zenodo.org/record/4451874#.YAfs1NhKg2w			

Additional output

Poster presentations at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2019 (22-24 May 2019):

- WP5: COM IMPART: Poster summarizing 1st year of activities within IMPART, displayed during One Health EJP annual meeting in Dublin, May 2019
<https://zenodo.org/record/4066734#.X3xwdnkzY2w>
- WP4: susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile*, WP5: COM IMPART: Optimisation of a Disc Diffusion Method for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing of *Clostridium difficile* (confidential)

Poster presentation at 6th Joint Conference of the DGHM & VAAM 2020, Leipzig, Germany (8-11 March 2020):

- WP4: Optimization of a Disc Diffusion Method for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing of *Clostridioides difficile* (confidential)

Poster presentations at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2020 (27-29 May 2020):

- WP2: A multicentre study examining different culturing methods to detect carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae*
<https://zenodo.org/record/4066631#.X3xwsHkzY2w>
- WP3 : Susceptibility testing of veterinary pathogenic bacteria as a first step in setting new epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs)
<https://zenodo.org/record/4066667#.X3xw23kzY2w>
- WP4: *Clostridioides difficile* antimicrobial susceptibility testing using disc diffusion (confidential)

7 One Health impact

WP1: in collaboration with EFSA (Beatrice Guerra) and EURL-AR (Rene Hendriksen), we plan to review together the output of this work package to determine if a future surveillance programme is either feasible or relevant at a European level.

WP2: The draft of the protocol for the multicentre study was done in collaboration with the EURL-AR. In the Commission Implementing Decision 2020/1729, the detection of carbapenemase producing *E. coli* on caecal and meat samples will become mandatory from 2021. Both EURL-AR and EFSA would have great benefit of the outcome of the multicentre study to modify the protocol for the harmonized surveillance of carbapenemase producing *Enterobacteriaceae* at a European level, <https://www.eurl->

[ar.eu/CustomData/Files/Folders/21-protocols/530_esbl-ampc-cpeprotocol-version-caecal-v7-09-12-19.pdf](https://www.eurl-ar.eu/CustomData/Files/Folders/21-protocols/530_esbl-ampc-cpeprotocol-version-caecal-v7-09-12-19.pdf) and https://www.eurl-ar.eu/CustomData/Files/Folders/21-protocols/529_esbl-ampc-cpeprotocol-version-meat-v7-09-12-19.pdf. We refer to EFSA “Technical specifications on harmonised monitoring of antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from food producing animals and food” (DOI: 10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5709), where IMPART is specifically mentioned. Further, the EURL-AR will perform a survey to assess how widely used the pre-enrichment is for other parts of the monitoring of antimicrobial resistant bacteria (personal communication Rene Hendriksen; rshe@food.dtu.dk). This as a starting point to reassess the protocol for isolation of carbapenemase producing *Enterobacteriaceae*.

From the start, the activities defined in WP3 were clearly linked to EUCAST/VetCAST when it comes to setting new ECOFFs (PL is member of the steering committee of VetCAST). This has stimulated closer cooperation between VetCAST and EUCAST on a more technical level. Moreover, IMPART WP3 results have been used as starting point for the collection of more MIC distributions in order to set additional ECOFFs for veterinary antimicrobials within COST action ENOVAT (PL is also member of the management committee of ENOVAT). In other words, the efforts for setting new ECOFFs within IMPART will be continued within ENOVAT. It can be concluded that despite the recent problems with the acceptance of MIC distributions in the EUCAST database, IMPART has generated new opportunities for joint actions to further improve standardisation in veterinary diagnostic laboratories regarding methods for susceptibility testing of veterinary bacteria and setting of ECOFFs as will be supported by VetCAST and ENOVAT.

WP4: One Health EJP project FED-AMR aims to use the proposed protocol and cut-off values for the agar disk diffusion in IMPART to characterize and compare *C. difficile* strains with regard to their antimicrobial resistance.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	3	3	3
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	4	3	4
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	3	4	4
Integration	4	3	4
Sustainability	4	4	4
Impact of the project	3	2	3
TOTAL	21/30	19/30	22/30

AVERAGE: 21

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The work conducted aligns well with the objectives. Significant progress has been made against all objectives but they have not been met in full and further studies are still needed. The reasons for not meeting objectives are justifiable.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

All the tasks in WP1 have been met as was described in the initial proposal, however they did not consider initially the huge combination of alternatives and complex flora of some matrices and it was not possible to propose a harmonized method suitable enough to monitor the current prevalence and spread of mcr variants in Enterobacteriaceae. So, deliverable 1.8 was not achieved and deliverable 1.7 is delayed. Nevertheless, WP1 is one of the most successful results.

The objectives for WP2 was to find an optimal culture method for the detection of relevant carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae (CPE) in meat and caecal samples from animals. A new and better method was not validated, and also they make sure that is a challenge to develop a harmonized method covering several bacterial species harbouring different carbapenemase producing

genes. So, deliverable 2.8 was not achieved and deliverable 2.7 is delayed. Nevertheless, WP2 open a putative collaboration with EURL and EFSA for future development.

The main goal of WP3 was to establish epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) of antimicrobials for veterinary pathogens. Several problems arose during the development of the project, one is probably not related to the partners, as it was a serious delay in the delivery of the Sensititre plates, but the second one, should be considered in advance, as it was that EUCAST implemented a new SOP for determination of ECOFFs and as a result has become stricter on the acceptance of MIC-distributions with regard to the methods used for MIC-testing. Most probably the MIC distributions of bacteria tested in CAMHB + LHB will not be accepted by EUCAST. Consequently, deliverables 3.2 and 3.3 are delayed.

The aim of WP4 was to optimize and validate a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of *Clostridium difficile*. A start problem was to recruit 500 *C. difficile* strains, that was solved by collect of 527 *C. difficile* isolates addressing also external partners. They proposed cut-off values to distinguish wild type from non-wild type phenotypes for five antimicrobials, but difficulties arose with vancomycin, imipenem, and cefotaxime for different reasons. They had to involve external partners because most of the IMPART partners missed expertise or equipment for the final ring trial. The deliverables 4.1 and 4.3 were achieved and revealed an overall success, but further method standardization need more reliable statistics. Again, the deliverable 4.2 (publication in OA journal) is delayed.

The main goal of WP5 was to coordinate the knowledge dissemination within and beyond IMPART, and in general, this task has been accomplished satisfactory, but somehow hindered by the COVID-19 pandemia. Overall coordination of the project for the scientific quality and progress of each of the four scientific work packages was well achieved with fluent communication and dissemination activities, both inside and outside IMPART consortium. All deliverables have been got with small delays, except final meeting (deliverable 5.5) and final meeting notes (deliverable 5.6), due to COVID-19. A good initiative for the future is that the Communication Team of the One Health EJP will work on the promotion of four deliverables from the IMPART project (one from each work package).

Reviewer 3: POC member

The alignment is considered as very good as the actions under the project aimed at the best results possible in accordance with the report. Certain objectives were met, such as ECOFF values for *S. pseudointermedius* and successful ring trial and determining IZDs for *C. difficile*. However, there were some goals that could not be fulfilled, such as developing a harmonized method for monitoring mcr variants in Enterobacteriaceae.

Although, the Covid-19 pandemic has to be taken into account as a vis maior circumstance that hindered certain steps of the project.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project followed a rigorous and scientific approach using current best practise methodology, whereby each objective was thoroughly investigated. The work closely followed the plan laid out in the original proposal.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

These are some of the scientific result of the project, that are good but limited.

WP1.- PCR detection of mcr-genes showed 100% specificity and one out of three media tested shows a better sensitivity. Performance of the colistin-resistant screening process is greater for caecal than

meat samples. More trials are needed to test the effect of other matrixes, bacterial concentrations and a broader range of mcr-positive strains.

WP2.- Some of the commercially available selective agar media are not sensitive or selective enough to detect bacteria expressing low-level carbapenemase production. There are no commercially available selective agars to detect carbapenem-resistant *Salmonella* spp. Some bacteria harbouring specific genes (*bla*VIM-1 *E. coli*) that circulate in the livestock population in Europe might be missed using the protocol currently set by the EU decision 2013/652/EU. More studies are needed to test other selective enrichment broths, matrices and bacterial species.

WP3.- The process of calculating epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) due to differences in test method between EUCAST and the IMPART project for the more fastidious growing bacteria. The discussion on the difference in test methods does not account for bacteria without supplements in the test media. MIC distributions of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* and the first accepted ECOFFs for this bacterial species are expected in the beginning of 2021.

WP4.- An optimized disk diffusion protocol as alternative method for AMR testing was established and inhibition zone diameter (IZD) distributions determined for eight antimicrobials analyzing each strain of the collection. Evaluation of the MICs and IZDs for each strain to determine wild-type and non-wildtype phenotypes correlated well for most but not all antimicrobials, and preliminary results and cut-off values were presented. The optimized method description proved to be highly reproducible but critical steps could be identified.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Experts involved in the project proved scientific excellence and approach throughout the process and in each work package, also by taking into account all available scientific information to deliver sound and scientifically qualified results, following the proposal initially submitted.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

On the whole, the project appears to be well managed as tasks were largely completed according to the work plan and on time. Some scheduled management activities could not take place due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which is understandable. Conference dissemination has taken place but publication of peer reviewed journal articles is delayed, however, these are being drafted.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Overall coordination of the project for the scientific quality and progress of each of the four scientific work packages was well achieved with fluent communication and dissemination activities, both inside and outside IMPART consortium.

Reviewer 3: POC member

In accordance with the report, the project management was appropriate and made significant efforts on communication and organizing the different work phases (such as ring trials) among the participants of the project and also regarding coordination of the four work packages. WP5 itself was intended for the communication and it succeeded in disseminating of knowledge in different levels, also within the project and beyond IMPART. Therefore the quality and efficiency of implementation is considered as excellent.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Integration within the project was excellent. A broad range of partner organisations across Europe participated and included both veterinary and medical laboratories. The participants collaborated and worked using shared materials and Joint protocols for ring trials, aiming to establish harmonized protocols and guidelines.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Relevant integrative activities, as development of harmonising protocols and surveillance strategies have been done inside each WP and communicated to the One Health EJP. However, no final published results have been obtained for any WP and only members of the WP2 published individual papers.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Certain WPs were successful in achieving relevant integrative activities (i.e. development of harmonized protocols such as ECOFFs).

Attention was also definitely paid to the One Health aspect by addressing species of human health importance such as *Cl. Difficile* and different strains of Enterobacteriaceae resistant to critically important antimicrobials.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

WP2 and WP3 both outline a clear path forward for incorporating findings of the project within EURL-AR protocols and EUCAST guidelines, respectively. The path for sustainability of WP1 and WP4 is less clear but consortium members have plans to drive the work forward and involving new partners.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

This aspect is the best certificated because most of the limited achievements of the project will be maintained within the frame of the consortium, but if the final deliverables are attained at the predicted delayed time, other institutes would be able to take on board some results.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Other institutes will certainly be able to take on board (some of) the results of the project, such as MIC distributions uploaded in the EUCAST database, therefore sustainability is considered as excellent. Significant results were achieved even in case of objectives that were not fulfilled such as findings regarding selectivity and sensitivity of certain media in WP1 and 2.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project has strived to achieve harmonisation of methods used by veterinary laboratories across Europe to detect antimicrobial resistance in pathogens of veterinary and zoonotic relevance. While none of the methods they have explored are yet implemented they have made significant progress towards achieving this goal, which should be brought to fruition with appropriate follow up. Harmonised methods across European veterinary laboratories will improve standards and surveillance of AMR thus improving detection and control of AMR which will bring medical and economic benefits.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The impact of the project has only limited effect because the objectives were only partially achieved for most of the work packages, with some exception of WP1 and WP3. With the actual data is not expected secondary effects on the economy or the environment. Impact on One Health would depend on how EURL-AR and EFSA will use the partial achievements of WP1 and WP2 to modify the protocols for the harmonized surveillance in the future. The problems with the acceptance of MIC distribution in the EUCAST database have generate lower impact to the results of WP3, and again it would depend on future collaboration within COST action ENOVAT the setting of ECOFFs for veterinary bacteria supported by VetCAST.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The long term impact of the overall project is partly depending on further continuation of the work, especially in case of method for isolation and detection of colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae that needs further developments and of revealed aspects for further standardization for *Cl. difficile*.

For WP1 and 2, joint implementation plans could not be developed and more studies are needed.

JRP02-ARDIG

Final report

1 Consortium composition

Name of the Project Coordinator and of all applicants, with full affiliations

Project Coordinator	Position	Affiliation	email	Gender
Prof. Muna F. Anjum	Senior Scientist; Bacterial Characterisation Workgroup Leader	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA), United Kingdom	Muna.Anjum@apha.gsi.gov.uk	Female

Applicant	Position	Affiliation	email	Gender
Dr. Martina Velasova	Senior Scientist	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA), United Kingdom	Martina.Velasova@apha.gsi.gov.uk	Female
Dr. Francesca Martelli	Senior Scientist	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA), United Kingdom	Francesca.Martelli@apha.gsi.gov.uk	Female
Professor Roberto La Ragione	Professor of microbiology and pathology and Head of the Department of Pathology and Infectious Diseases	University of Surrey, School of Veterinary Medicine	r.laragione@surrey.ac.uk	Male
PD Dr. Bernd-Alois Tenhagen	Senior Scientist; AMR2-BfR Project leader	Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Germany	Bernd-Alois.Tenhagen@bfr.bund.de	Male
Dr. Jens A. Hammerl	Research Scientist, AMR2-BfR Project Deputy	Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Germany	Jens-Andre.Hammerl@bfr.bund.de	Female
Dr. Marianne Sunde	Senior researcher	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	marianne.sunde@vetinst.no	Female
Dr Philippe Glaser	Research Director; head of the EERA research Unit	Institut Pasteur, Paris, France	pglaser@pasteur.fr	Male
Prof. Bruno Gonzalez Zorn	Professor, Group Leader on AMR	Complutense University,	bgzorn@ucm.es	Male

Applicant	Position	Affiliation	email	Gender
	and Head of the Department of Animal Health	Veterinary School and VISAVET		
Jean-Yves Madec	Senior Scientist Head of the Antimicrobial Resistance Unit	ANSES, Lyon, FR	Jean-Yves.MADEC@anses.fr	Male
Marisa Haenni	Senior Scientist Deputy-Head of the Antimicrobial Resistance Unit	ANSES, Lyon, FR	Marisa.haenni@anses.fr	Female
Dr. Michael Brouwer	Postdoctoral researcher at the department of Bacteriology and Epidemiology	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research, formerly Central Veterinary Institute (CVI)	mike.brouwer@wur.nl	Male
Dr. Tim Eckmanns	Medical Epidemiologist	Robert Koch Institute, Germany	EckmannsT@rki.de	Male
Dr. Sebastian Haller	Medical Epidemiologist	Robert Koch Institute, Germany	HallerS@rki.de	Male
Prof. Neil Woodford	Head of AMRHAI	Public Health England, UK	Neil.Woodford@phe.gov.uk	Male
Dr. Matthew Ellington	Senior Scientist, AMRHAI	Public Health England, UK	Matthew.Ellington@phe.gov.uk	Male
Dr Sarah Gerver	Senior Epidemiologist	Public Health England, UK	berit.muller-pebody@phe.gov.uk	Female

Short CV of each participating key scientist (at least one per participating organization)

APHA: Muna Anjum

Prof. Muna Anjum and the APHA team have extensive expertise in characterization of AMR in Enterobacteriaceae isolated from food animals. The multidisciplinary team of molecular biologists, bioinformaticians, veterinarians, and epidemiologists conduct national surveillance, outbreak investigations as well as research activities to understand persistence and dissemination of AMR through the food chain. Muna Anjum is the Lead for Antimicrobial Resistance research and the Bacterial Characterisation Workgroup Leader in the Department of Bacteriology at the APHA. She leads a team of senior scientists, post-doctoral scientists and PhD students. She holds a visiting Professorship at the University of Surrey and is a member of the Health Protection Research Unit at the University of Oxford, John Radcliffe Hospital, in partnership with Public Health England. She is also a member of the DEFRA Antimicrobial Resistance Coordination (DARC) Group, which reviews activities of the UK government on antimicrobials. Muna has led or is the APHA lead in a number of national (VMD/DEFRA, DoH, NERC, BBSRC), EU and commercial projects.

APHA: Martina Velasova and Francesca Martelli

Two key members of the APHA team includes Dr. Martina Velasova, who is a senior epidemiologist and Dr. Francesca Martelli, who is a senior veterinarian. Some recent key publications are:

Abuoun M, 14 authors and Anjum MF. A genomic epidemiological study shows prevalence of antimicrobial resistance in Enterobacterales is associated with the livestock host, as well as antimicrobial use. *Microbial Genomics*, 2021.

Stubberfield, 4 authors and Anjum, MF. Use of whole genome sequencing of commensal *Escherichia coli* in pigs for antimicrobial resistance surveillance, United Kingdom, 2018. *Eurosurveillance*, 2019.

UoS: Roberto La Ragione

Prof. Roberto La Ragione, HoD for Pathology and Infectious Disease and Director of the Veterinary Pathology Centre at Veterinary School, UoS. In 2005 Roberto La Ragione was appointed head of pathogenesis and control at the AHVLA and in 2010 he was appointed Professor of Veterinary Microbiology and Pathology at the University of Surrey. Roberto gained the FRCPath in 2010 and in 2012 was appointed the Associate Dean for Veterinary Strategy in the new School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey. Roberto has published over 125 peer reviewed publications in the area of host-microbe interaction with a particular emphasis on foodborne pathogens. His current research interests focus on AMR and the pathogenesis of food-borne pathogens with a particular interest in the development of rapid diagnostics and intervention strategies including vaccination, pre and probiotics for the control of bacterial pathogens in animals. He has led a number of commercial, BBSRC, EPSRC, Defra and EU projects. Roberto is the current MedVet-Net Association president. Some important recent publications include:

Freire Martín I, Thomas CM, Laing E, AbuOun M, La Ragione RM, Woodward MJ. 2016. Curing vector for IncI1 plasmids and its use to provide evidence for a metabolic burden of IncI1 CTX-M-1 plasmid pIFM3791 on *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *J Med Microbiol*.

Freire Martín I, AbuOun M, Reichel R, La Ragione RM, Woodward MJ. 2014. Sequence analysis of a CTX-M-1 IncI1 plasmid found in *Salmonella* 4,5,12:i:-, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* on a UK pig farm. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 69(8):2098-101.

BfR: Bernd-Alois Tenhagen

PD Dr. Bernd-Alois Tenhagen is a veterinarian with a specialisation in food animal medicine and epidemiology. Since 2007 he is working at the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment in Berlin, Germany in the Department Biological Safety. He is head of the unit "Epidemiology, Zoonoses and Antimicrobial Resistance" that also houses the National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance. His works focus is on the epidemiology of resistant bacteria and resistance determinants in the food chain and the associated risks for public health. He has published more than 100 papers in peer reviewed journals and was involved in national and international research projects on AMR. He has been a member of several working groups of EFSA on topics related to the monitoring of AMR.

BfR: Jens A. Hammerl

Jens A. Hammerl obtained his Ph.D. from the Humboldt University of Berlin in 2012 working on the regulation of genetic switch in linear plasmid prophages. He works now in the National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance at the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment on microbiological and molecular tracing of food-borne pathogens in food chains to protect consumer's health. Further research interests are focused on the biology and genetics of antimicrobial resistances, mobile genetic elements and therapeutic applications of phages from environmental, food-borne and highly pathogenic bacteria.

Relevant papers from BfR include:

Irrgang A, N Roschanski, BA Tenhagen, M Grobbel, T Skladnikiewicz-Ziemer, K Thomas, U Roesler, and A Käsbohrer. 2016. Prevalence of mcr-1 in *E. coli* from Livestock and Food in Germany, 2010-2015. *PLoS One*. 25;11(7):e0159863.

Fromm S, Beißwanger E, Käsbohrer A, Tenhagen BA. Risk factors for MRSA in fattening pig herds - a meta-analysis using pooled data. *Prev Vet Med.* 2014 Nov 1;117(1):180-8. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2014.08.014. Epub 2014 Sep 2.

NVI: Marianne Sunde

Dr. Marianne Sunde is a senior researcher (DVM, PhD, Professor equivalent) in veterinary microbiology at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute. Her main research activity has been on antimicrobial resistance. Dr. Sunde also holds a position at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health where the main research area is antimicrobial resistance in a "One Health" perspective. She has long-time experience in research on antimicrobial resistance and has been a key person in bacteriological diagnostics as well as monitoring of resistance in the veterinary sector in Norway. She has been project leader for national and Scandinavian research projects, has supervised Master and PhD students, has experience as a reviewer for scientific journals and is Assistant Editor for *BMC Vet Res*. Recent publications are:

Grøntvedt CA/P Elstrøm, M Stegger, RL Skov, PS Andersen, KW Larssen, AM Urdahl, Ø Angen, J Larsen, S Åmdal, SM Løtvedt and M Sunde/JV Bjørnholt. 2016. MRSA CC398 in humans and pigs in Norway: A "One Health" perspective on introduction and transmission. *Clin Infect Dis*.

Mo SS, JS Slettebø, ES Berg, M Norström and M Sunde. 2016. Plasmid and Host Strain Characteristics of *Escherichia coli* Resistant to Extended-Spectrum Cephalosporins in the Norwegian Broiler Production. *PLoS One* 0154019

CVI: Michael Brouwer

In 2006 Michael graduated from the University of Amsterdam in Biomedical sciences, followed by a MSc degree in Immunology in 2008. His PhD research focussed on studying the mobile genetic elements of the nosocomial pathogen *Clostridium difficile* in the group of Prof. Peter Mullany at University College London. During his first postdoctoral appointment in the group of Dr. Adam Roberts in 2012, also at UCL, Michael started the study of resistance conferring plasmids in Gram-positive bacteria. In 2013 he switched to studying the plasmids of Gram-negative bacteria in the group of Prof. Dik Mevius at the Central Veterinary Institute. This research focusses on the molecular mechanisms employed by plasmids for conjugation, plasmid genomics and testing and development of novel strategies for the detection of plasmids and resistance genes. Some important publications include:

Veldman K, van Essen-Zandbergen A, Rapallini M, Wit B, Heymans R, van Pelt W, Mevius D. Location of colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* in Enterobacteriaceae from livestock and meat. *J Antimicrob Chemother.* 2016 May 30. pii: dkw181. PMID: 27246233

Brouwer MS, Tagg KA, Mevius DJ, Iredell JR, Bossers A, Smith HE, Partridge SR. Incl shufflons: Assembly issues in the next-generation sequencing era. *Plasmid.* 2015 Jul;80:111-7. doi: 10.1016/j.plasmid.2015.04.009. Epub 2015 May 4. PMID: 25952328

Institut Pasteur: Philippe Glaser

Philippe Glaser is co-director with Thierry Naas of the Ecology and Evolution of Antibiotic Resistance Unit, a joint unit between the Institut Pasteur and the Bicêtre hospital. It hosts the F-NRC laboratory for CPE. Philippe Glaser is an internationally recognized expert in bacterial genomics and evolution. He has a broad experience in analysing large sets of WGS data. He has recently shown by the analysis of 230 Group B Streptococcus (GBS) genomes that the massive use of tetracycline has been responsible for the emergence of neonatal infections in the 1960s. He also compared population structures of humans and bovine GBS. Thierry Naas director of the NRC is a pioneer in the field of carbapenemase genes and of their mobility. The Institut Pasteur Biomics group will provide all the equipment and the expertise in genomics. Some key publications are:

Glaser P, et al. Demography and Intercontinental Spread of the USA300 Community-Acquired Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* Lineage. *MBio.* 2016, 7(1).

Da Cunha V, 28 authors & Glaser P (2014) *Streptococcus agalactiae* clones infecting humans were selected and fixed through the extensive use of tetracycline. *Nature communications*, 2014, 5:4544.

UCM: Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn

Prof. Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn is Professor at the Complutense University in Madrid. He gained his DVM in 1996 and his European PhD in 2001. After his Postdoc at the Pasteur Institute in Paris he received a Ramon y Cajal tenure-track contract from the Spanish Ministry of Science to return to Spain. Currently he leads a group working on molecular microbiology and the ecology of antimicrobial resistance in Madrid. He is currently Head of the Animal Health Department. His research interests focus on the role and function of small plasmids in antimicrobial resistance, the bacterial SOS-response and the 16S rRNA methyltransferases in pathogenic bacteria. In 2011 he was awarded the biannual Jaime Ferran Award from the Spanish Society for Microbiology. He participates in several International Committees and Projects on AMR, including the SAB of the JPIAMR and EFFORT. Some key publications include:

San Millan A, Santos-Lopez A, Ortega-Huedo R, Bernabe-Balas C, Kennedy SP, Gonzalez-Zorn B. Small plasmid-mediated antibiotic resistance in *Haemophilus influenzae* is enhanced by increases in plasmid copy number and bacterial fitness. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 2015 Mar 30. Pii: AAC.00235-15.

Delgado-Blas JF, Ovejero CM, Abadia Patiño L, Gonzalez-Zorn B. Coexistence of *mcr-1* and *bla*NDM-1 in *Escherichia coli* from Venezuela. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother*. 2016 Oct (in press).

ANSES: Jean-Yves Madec

Dr. Jean-Yves Madec (ANSES)(DVM, PhD) at the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health Safety (Anses) is involved in National Surveillance Programs of AMR in veterinary medicine in France and has recognized expertise in molecular genetics and epidemiology of resistance in Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria of animal origin (commensal, pathogenic, zoonotic) and issues regarding the animal-human transfer of AMR. He is member of several expert groups and committees on antimicrobial resistance and antibiotics use in animals and humans in France and Europe and is an active participant/leader in recent European scientific projects. A key recent publication:

Haenni M. et al Madec JY (2016) Co-occurrence of Extended-Spectrum β Lactamase and MCR-1 encoding genes on plasmids. *Lancet Infectious Diseases*, January 7, 2016. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(16\)00007-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(16)00007-4)

RKI: Tim Eckmann and Sebastian Haller

Dr. Tim Eckmanns, Dr. Sebastian Haller are medical epidemiologists based at the German national public health institute with extensive research experience on AMR, conducting surveillance and analysing transmission of resistant bacteria from infections in humans as well as on antibiotic prescription at national level in Germany. Key recent publications are:

Haller S, Eller C, Hermes J, Kaase M, Steglich M, Radonić A, Dabrowski PW, Nitsche A, Pfeifer Y, Werner G, Wunderle W, Velasco E, Abu Sin M, Eckmanns T, Nübel U. What caused the outbreak of ESBL-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a neonatal intensive care unit, Germany 2009 to 2012? Reconstructing transmission with epidemiological analysis and whole-genome sequencing. *BMJ Open*. 2015; 5 (5).

Walter J, Haller S, Blank HP, Eckmanns T, Abu Sin M, Hermes J. Incidence of invasive methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections in Germany, 2010 to 2014. *Euro Surveill*. 2015;20(46).

PHE: Neil Woodford Prof Neil Woodford, is head of PHE's Antimicrobial Resistance and Healthcare Associated Infections (AMRHAI) unit. He has worked on antibiotic resistance for over 25 years and is an internationally recognized authority on the molecular epidemiology of resistance with more than 250 published papers on resistance mechanisms and epidemiology, he has edited three books on the subject and is a Fellow of the Royal College of Pathologists on the basis of his published works. Prof

Woodford has served for 10 years as an Editor of the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy, and is on the Editorial Board of Microbial Drug Resistance. Prof Woodford is a member of two Health Protection Units examining antimicrobial resistance, one with Imperial College and the other with the University of Oxford in partnership with APHA. As a committee member of several groups advising government on research and policy relating to antimicrobial resistance in humans and animals he has the insight and necessary understanding of the complex, multi-factorial problem of resistance epidemiology to advise on policy and research in relation to antimicrobial resistance in humans and animals.

PHE: Matthew Ellington and Berit Muller-Pebody

The PHE team will also include Dr. Matthew Ellington who is a senior scientist in AMRHAI and Dr. Sarah Gerver who is the lead epidemiologist and Head of Antimicrobial Resistance and Prescribing Section in the department of Healthcare associated infections at PHE and has been part of the team producing the reports on “English Surveillance Programme for Antimicrobial Utilisation and Resistance (ESPAUR)” from Public Health England and other agencies including the Veterinary Medicines Directorate (<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/english-surveillance-programme-antimicrobial-utilisation-and-resistance-espaur-report>)

Key recent publications are:

Day MJ, Doumith M, Abernethy J, Hope R, Reynolds R, Wain J, Livermore DM, Woodford N. Population structure of *Escherichia coli* causing bacteraemia in the UK and Ireland between 2001 and 2010. *J Antimicrob Chemother.* 2016 May 5. pii: dkw145. [Epub ahead of print] PubMed PMID: 27150395.

Doumith M, Godbole G, Ashton P, Larkin L, Dallman T, Day M, Day M, Muller-Pebody B, Ellington MJ, de Pinna E, Johnson AP, Hopkins KL, Woodford N. Detection of the plasmid-mediated *mcr-1* gene conferring colistin resistance in human and food isolates of *Salmonella enterica* and *Escherichia coli* in England and Wales. *J Antimicrob Chemother.* 2016 Apr 18. pii: dkw093.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The ARDIG project has continued to progress, and after 42 months there have been substantial achievements made by partners, including numerous peer-reviewed publication of papers from the ARDIG consortium. Several project-wide, as well as work package specific, meetings have also taken place by either meeting physically or by tele/videoconference, and there have been regular communication by email. Both oral and poster presentations made by ARDIG partners were well received at the OH-EJP Annual Scientific Meetings held during this project.

WP1 (Comparison of AMR and antibiotic sales/usage data collected through existing national surveillance and research programs and assessment of risk factors). The ARDIG project has identified that there is a lack of harmonisation on AMU and AMR in the livestock sector and on AMR in the human sector, although there is some overlap between national and international systems. A One-Health approach for AMU and AMR requires harmonisation in various aspects between systems in the human, animal and food sector; suggestions are provided within ARDIG to address this. Differences in AMR between clinical and non-clinical isolates were identified within and between countries for different animal populations. Higher resistance levels in clinical isolates than in non-clinical isolates were found for calves, while the opposite was found in isolates from broilers and turkeys. Decreasing resistance was found in animal isolates between 2014 and 2017. This suggests that measures carried out against AMR including the reduction in AMU in each country have effective results.

A workshop was held with experts in the field, including those from EFSA, EMA and ECDC and other European projects, to make recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance strategies.

WP2 (Longitudinal studies of AMR persistence). Both Med and Vet partners have been collecting *E. coli* isolates from retrospective as well as prospective longitudinal studies, including *E. coli* isolated from urinary tract infections from local hospitals, as well as livestock (cattle, pigs and poultry). Several

partners have also characterised *E. coli* isolated through EU harmonised surveillance for AMR. In addition, all partners who participated in a whole genome sequencing (WGS) AMR workshop have submitted ~50 WGS each (~450 in total) for analysis by five pipelines: APHA SeqFinder/Abricate, PHE GeneFinder, WBVR, Ariba, ResFinder/PointFinder. The AMR genotypes were compared with the corresponding MIC phenotypes for these isolates. WGS of >3000 isolates collected from longitudinal, as well as national surveillance by partners were also compared, and show human isolates generally to be more similar to each other than those from animals, and vice versa.

WP3 (AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates). All WP3 partners participated in the AMR pipeline comparison work to help harmonise *in silico* AMR gene prediction and to assess the impact of methodology on AMR gene prediction; a manuscript is currently being prepared for this work. In addition, all WP3 partners have continued AMR gene, plasmid and mobile genetic element characterization of isolates collected in WP2 by WGS (short and long reads), as well as other molecular techniques. Phylogenetic analysis and AMR profiling performed by partners on their dataset, as well as across ARDIG, have helped identify possible transmission events or epidemiological links between different compartments and countries. Also, plasmid characterisation between and across partners, has provided an overview of the types of AMR plasmids commonly circulating which belong to the following types: IncI, IncF and IncX.

3 Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Comparison of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic sales/usage (AMU) data collected through existing surveillance, monitoring and research programs and assessment of risk factors.

This WP was led by BfR, with major contributions from APHA, ANSES, NVI, RKI and PHE; other members of the consortium also contributed as and when appropriate. Details of the work performed in WP1 by the consortium is provided below.

WP1-T1 - Exploration and collection of data available on AMR, AMU and potential risk factors

Institut Pasteur

Monitoring of antibiotic consumption and of antibiotic resistance of bacteria responsible for infections has evolved at the start of the project in France with new actors. Monitoring is now under the responsibility of Santé Publique France (SPF) by the CPias nouvelle Aquitaine with a new tool called Consores for AMU, and by the CPias Pays de la Loire, with also a new tool called Medqual for AMR. In the past, AMR was monitored by ONERBA (Observatoire National de l'Epidémiologie de la Résistance Bactérienne aux Antibiotiques) which is a private association, collecting information on the voluntary basis. Given this situation, despite much efforts we have not been able to collect additional data on *E. coli* infections beyond what is transmitted by the French authorities to the ECDC (ESAC-net and EARS-net).

Data were collected from six countries represented in ARDIG (UK, NL, DE, FR, NO, ES) and collated in a database. This included data available in the respective institutions involved in ARDIG but also other National and regional systems in animal husbandry and the medical field. A detailed description of current (2019) surveillance and monitoring systems in the animal and the human sector was prepared, submitted as a deliverable and subsequently published in a peer reviewed paper (Mesa-Varona et al. 2020). A substantial diversity of systems and data types was encountered and comparability of data was largely hampered by this diversity. Metadata collected in the surveillance and monitoring systems were typically limited which further limited the scope of the analyses in task 2.

WP1-T2- Investigation of trends, associations and risk factors

The available data were first descriptively analysed (see deliverable 1.2) and subsequently a framework was developed to compare AMR in *E. coli* from different animal and human populations. A focus was

on the comparison of clinical and non-clinical isolates from animals that showed substantial differences which, however, were observed in both directions, depending on the animal population and the antimicrobial considered. One main obstacle to this analysis were differences in the substances included in AMR-testing between countries and populations (clinical vs. non-clinical) that limited the range of substances with comparable data. Another obstacle, the use of different laboratory methods could be partly overcome by the development of harmonized cut offs. The approach used the same methodology to determine the cut offs for different laboratory methods (i.e. broth microdilution vs. disk diffusion).

Analysis of clinical *E. coli* isolates was carried out to describe and compare trends in resistant *E. coli* isolates originating from clinical diagnostic submissions from three livestock species in three European countries. Associations between antimicrobial resistance and year of sampling, species and country were also investigated. The number of isolates tested increased over years 2014 to 2016 in all three countries and decreased in 2017. Similar patterns in resistance were observed between the countries, with cattle isolates having significantly higher odds of being resistant compared to both pigs and chicken isolates. The level of resistance decreased with age in cattle and chicken, younger animals had significantly higher resistance compared to older animals.

Similarly to the analysis of clinical vs. non-clinical isolates, also analysis of clinical isolates from different livestock species and countries faced the same challenges. Although each country monitors resistance levels of a large number of antimicrobials, only a small number of antimicrobials overlapped between different countries and livestock species, highlighting a need for a better harmonization between different countries and production systems. The use of different animal age categories by different countries also had a limiting impact on the scope of analysis. A further finding was that despite the short observation period (2014 -2017, i.e. four years) for several antimicrobials and animal populations a decrease in resistance was observed in the *E. coli* tested. This indicates that efforts taken by countries to control AMR mainly by reducing AMU did foster some progress, although – given the short time period – this was limited. First results have been published in two peer reviewed papers comparing clinical and non-clinical isolates of *E. coli* from three animal populations (broilers, turkeys and calves) (Mesa Varona et al. 2020b, 2021). Two further papers are in preparation that compare clinical isolates from animal populations between countries and isolates from different pig populations and humans in Germany.

WP1-T3- Develop recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance strategies

Based on the results of tasks 1 and 2 and experiences of other research groups, namely the Aacting consortium and the EU-JAMRAI project, recommendations were drafted and presented to experts in the field in a workshop on March 1 and 2 of 2021. The workshop included experts from the countries involved in ARDIG and the European Agencies (EFSA, ECDC, EMA). One day of the workshop was dedicated to reporting from the different projects (i.e. ARDIG, Aacting and EU-JAMRAI), from EMA and from Norway that has some experiences in presenting AMU and AMR data in a one health approach. The second day was devoted to three discussion groups working on pre-defined questions on surveillance of AMU (Group 1), AMR (Group 2) and the contribution of molecular methods to routine surveillance (Group 3). The workshop gave evidence of different attitudes to the questions that were partly driven by the different roles of the participants. In the AMU workshop the data collection systems currently developed under the new EU-veterinary medical legislation were extensively discussed and EMA clearly elaborated their needs based on the legislation, which are limited to certain tasks. This of course does not constrain the member states in setting up more ambitious collection systems provided that those systems are also fit to cover EMAs needs. While some participants, including members of the ARDIG consortium, underlined the usefulness of a harmonization process across the systems, others questioned this need with reference to the diversity of the underlying systems of animal production in the different countries.

A report on the workshop is currently in progress and is meant to be shared and discussed with the workshop participants. It will presumably be published after the consultation phase in early autumn 2021.

Main conclusions and recommendations from ARDIG WP1

On AMR

Collection systems on AMR often adopt specific standards and their corresponding evaluation criteria that do not cover all drug and bug combinations. Therefore, different standards and/or evaluation criteria are sometimes used for different drug and bug combinations in the same system. These systems show a lack of harmonisation within and between countries across the human and animal sectors.

Data collecting systems on AMR should collect data:

- applying the same standard (e.g. EUCAST and CLSI)
- using the same evaluation criteria (i.e. epidemiological vs. clinical approach)
- from both isolate types (i.e. clinical and non-clinical isolates)
- applying a similar antimicrobial panel
- from the same sample type
- addressing the same animal categories

These requirements in the same isolate type should be complied in order to compare, evaluate and analyse AMR. Otherwise, data comparisons could not be in most cases directly addressed.

The NRI approach is a statistical method that can be applied, to overcome the lack of harmonisation on laboratory methods and methodologies. These statistical methods require quantitative data across a substantial range of values for the interpretation of data. Therefore, reports on AMR should provide quantitative values rather than data on the SIR level.

Significant dissimilarities were found between data on clinical and non-clinical isolates within animal categories and countries. Higher resistance proportions were mainly encountered in non-clinical isolates of broilers and turkeys and in clinical isolates of calves. Results in calves confirmed previous descriptive data from other studies and were in line with expectations. However, results in poultry were surprising and require further targeted investigations. The results underline that AMR in clinical and non-clinical isolates needs to be evaluated separately and preferably both should be collected.

The lack of AMR harmonisation on further issues such as the lack of harmonisation on antimicrobial panels and animal categories remains. It is necessary to define a harmonised antimicrobial panel in clinical isolates and between clinical and non-clinical isolates.

Our analyses were applied in *E. coli* isolates of livestock between 2014 and 2017. However, this work could be extended in the future to include other bacteria and for longer periods.

On AMU

EU agreed units are not always provided in reports that show data from regional and national monitoring and surveillance systems on antimicrobial consumption in Europe. These units should be always applied.

ESVAC collected sales data in Europe using the agreed unit mg/PCU. However, this measurement only provides a general overview. Farm-level data are required for further analyses. However, there is no AMU usage agreed unit in the animal sector. To overcome this issue reusing the already collected data, two different approaches have been suggested:

- A harmonised AMU usage unit

- Numerator/denominator data to transform one unit into another:
 - a. The name of the active ingredient
 - b. The amount of active ingredient
 - c. The number of treated animals
 - d. The population at risk
 - e. The weight of treated animals
 - f. The time under treatment
 - g. The duration of the therapeutic effect of the active ingredient in the body

The implementation of the Regulation (EU) No. 6/2019 on veterinary products will greatly improve the comparability of AMU usage data in a large number of animal categories.

AMU data collection should be provided by drug, animal species (e.g. broilers and turkeys instead of poultry), type of production (e.g. broiler or laying hens instead of chicken), age categories when the animal production cycle is long (e.g. weaning or fattening pigs instead of pigs) and the mixture of age category and production (e.g. calves instead of cattle).

Reports on AMU should always report on the same drug and antimicrobial drug categories for the same animal category that should likewise be defined in a harmonised way.

It is significantly important to understand the data collection of the health care systems implemented in each country since the data collection procedure may vary. Therefore, data comparisons should be done with care.

On AMU and AMR

Availability of harmonised usage data for animals will allow enhancing the analyses on the association of use and resistance across countries.

In the field of non-clinical AMR, EFSA drove the harmonisation of EU data-collection. However, there is no incentive to harmonise AMU and AMR systems. In the absence of harmonisation, there is no requirement to report to the EU. A large number of AMU and AMR collecting systems were found per country and sector. Some overlap between monitoring and surveillance systems on AMU and AMR was encountered. This overlap may be convenient for system and data validation. However, a better use of the available sources could save resources.

Overlap between reports has been encountered as a logical consequence of the overlap presence between systems. AMU and AMR reports are published in different languages and time ranges. They should be provided annually in one international language to ease published data access.

Antimicrobial use was identified as an influencing factor on AMR. However, AMR prevalence might not necessarily decrease in some drugs addressing only the reduction of AMU due to phenomena such as co-resistance and multidrug resistance. AMR crisis must be addressed from all available angles (e.g. hygienic measures, vaccination, support of scientific studies and reduction of AMU) and as a collaborative action between countries.

During the funding period of ARDIG, the three agencies, EFSA, EMA and ECDC have jointly prepared the JIACRA report based on reported data from all EU-MS and some other EEA countries. As the WP leader of WP1 was member of the JIACRA working group on behalf of EFSA, he was able to consider the perspective of both projects in his work. The JIACRA report is solely based on non-clinical animal isolates as opposed to clinical animal isolates. The JIACRA report demonstrates that where there is a certain degree of harmonization, analysis can be run, keeping in mind the limitations to these analysis. For example the consumption data in animals in the JIACRA report are based on general sales data which limits the analytical potential. In ARDIG we tried to include population based data on AMU as

derived from the national systems, but as pointed out above, this was hampered by differences in the definition of populations and the units used in the description of use. Therefore, both, our work and the work in JIACRA underline the need for more harmonized data. Moreover, in ARDIG we focused on one bacterial species, including data on clinical and non clinical isolates. The differences we observed between clinical and non clinical isolates may indicate that analysis of clinical animal isolates might provide an additional perspective in one health analyses. ARDIG results show that, provided more harmonized data are available, additional analyses can be run. Currently, a lot of collected data have only limited use, as they are difficult to compare with data from other populations/compartments and countries.

WP2. Longitudinal studies of persistence ESBL/AmpC/carbapenem/mcr-1/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae on farms or hospitals

WP2-T1- Assessment and selection of longitudinal data from historical studies

UCM

Data from national surveillance projects carried out between 2014 and 2019 focused on antimicrobial resistance surveillance in different animal production sectors have been arranged to be added to the consortium common data for further analyses. From the EFFORT (Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission) project, up to 10 *E. coli* isolates were collected from faecal samples of 5 pig farms and 5 poultry farms located in different Spanish regions between 2014 and 2015, obtaining a total of 100 *E. coli* isolates. These isolates were not selected under antibiotic pressure and were further characterized by a standard panel of different antimicrobial compounds in order to assess Minimal Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs). All of them were sequenced by Illumina technology. Random-selected *E. coli* isolates (38 from pig samples and 35 from poultry samples) were included in further analyses for AMR detection pipeline comparisons and phylogenetic studies.

From the national surveillance program of antimicrobial resistance carried out by the VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre and the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA), a total of 200 *E. coli* isolates were collected from faecal samples: 100 isolates from swine production in 2017 and 100 isolates from poultry production in 2016 (50 isolates) and 2018 (50 isolates). These isolates were not selected under antibiotic pressure. All isolates were phenotypically characterized according to their antimicrobial resistance profiles to a standardized panel of antimicrobial compounds. Then, all of them were sequenced by Illumina technology and included in posterior analyses for AMR and plasmid characterization and phylogenetic studies. The results of these analyses are described in AMR characterization section.

Institut Pasteur.

In the course of the ARDIG project we have analyzed two set of data from historical studies.

- ESBL producing *E. coli* collected in the course of the i-bird project: The i-bird project coordinated by D. Guillemot (IP) was based on a 4-month study which took place in 2009 in a rehabilitation hospital. It combined weekly rectal swabs and human-human proximities recorded from wireless captors. 3500 rectal swabs have been collected from 329 patients. A total of 4882 bacterial isolates have been analyzed including 425 *E. coli*. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed for 30 antibiotics. 604 ESBL-Enterobacterales were isolated from 84 patients including 332 *E. coli* from 75 patients. One to 25 isolates were collected per patient, including patient colonized by ESBL isolates during the whole study. The main aim of the study was to analyze ESBL-bacteria transmission and plasmid acquisition. We selected 204 isolates for WGS (WP3). Selection was based on the patient to sequence at least one isolate per patient and on the week of sampling and taking into account negative samples (one isolate before and after each negative sample). By comparing over time within and between patient genomic diversity of ESBL-producing bacteria together with contact data, we

aim to infer transmission routes and the possibility of an environmental reservoir.

- Carbapenemase producing *E. coli* (CPEc) isolates collected by the French National Reference laboratory for carbapenemase producing enterobacteriaceae (Fr-CNR). CPEc represents a major public health threat for two main reasons. First only few therapeutic options remain to treat bacterial infections due to MDR CPEc and second given the ubiquitous nature of *E. coli*, these bacteria contribute to the dissemination of carbapenemase genes and of plasmids carrying those resistance genes. In Europe CPEc from animal origins are extremely rare and none isolates showing this resistance were isolated in the course of the project. However, we have shown that the acquisition of MDR and of carbapenemase genes is a multistep process. A still open question is the contribution of the animal sector in this process. We have focused our study on the four first years of activity of the Fr-NRC from 2012 (year of creation of the NRC) to 2015. During this period, a steady increase of the number of isolates received by the NRC was observed (44 in 2012, 94 in 2013, 250 in 2014 and 388 in 2015). It is likely a consequence of different factors: (i) an increased circulation of CPEc in France; the increased screening of potential carbapenemase carriers at their admission at hospital, as the number of disease associated isolates was found to increase more slowly than the number of samples from screening and (iii) to a raising awareness of hospital and private laboratories to send CPEc isolates to the Fr-NRC. In order to characterize the diversity of these isolates and of the carbapenemase gene, changes during the four years and their evolutionary trajectory related to the acquisition of the carbapenemase gene, we selected for WGS 713 isolates including 22 isolates received by the Bicêtre Hospital laboratory before 2012 (WP3)

NVI

Isolates from a previous study focusing on cephalosporin resistant Enterobacteriaceae have been characterized. All broiler flocks raised on ten broiler farms were sampled during the period from May to October in 2016 and a total of 43 positive isolates were obtained (one isolate per flock). These isolates have been sequenced with Illumina technology in order to study a possible on-farm persistence/transmission between batches of animals on the same farm or broiler house. In total, 11 different *E. coli* Sequence Types were identified. A possible clonal persistence of ESC-resistant *E. coli* at house level was shown for only a minor proportion of the included houses. Isolates from the same house belonging to the same ST could differ by a considerable number of SNPs, shown for ST38 isolates found in three different houses at one farm from several flocks throughout the sampling period. Similar plasmids were detected in different STs, suggesting possible horizontal transfer and/or persistence of plasmids. Seven ESC-resistant *E. coli* of different STs originating from two farms were selected for ONT sequencing and in-depth characterization of *bla*_{CMY-2}/*IncK2* plasmids. We performed hybrid assemblies and SNP analysis. On one farm, highly similar plasmids of approximately 85 kb size were present in three different STs. The plasmids differed by 17 SNPs. On the other farm, two plasmids of 116-117 kb, harboured additional resistance to sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline and aminoglycosides. When compared using Snippy, 0 SNPs were present between these plasmids. The results indicate that highly similar/identical plasmids can exist in *E. coli* of different STs, and possibly persist on broiler farms. Our data show variation at both gene, plasmid and ST level when ESC resistant *E. coli* from consecutive flocks were characterized. It is not possible to determine whether different *E. coli* variants and/or ESC resistance genotypes were present simultaneously in a flock, as only a single isolate was characterized per sample. A manuscript is in preparation and will be submitted later this year.

PHE

PHE collected carbapenemase producing Enterobacteriales, including *E. coli*, isolated from colonisation and infections by hospital laboratories and referred to the PHE reference national reference lab. The isolates were received by the PHE National Reference laboratory in 2014 and 2016 and have been analysed for their genomic and resistance gene diversity (collaborative manuscript with Katie Hopkins submitted).

ANSES

Extended-Spectrum-Cephalosporins (ESC)-resistant Enterobacteriaceae have been isolated from veal calves in France have been included to be studied within ARDIG. Two studies were set up to investigate the trends in ESBL/AmpC prevalence and antimicrobial usages (AMU) in veal calves during the fattening process.

In a first study, ten fattening farms were selected and visited twice. A total of 50 animals per farm were sampled for ESC-R carriage and other AMR phenotypes upon arrival and 5-6 months later before slaughter.

A second study was then set up to get further insights into the dynamic of ESBL/AmpC spread over the fattening period. Three farms out of the ten from the first study were visited 11 or 12 times at regular intervals of 15 days. A total of 15 calves per farm were sampled and processed as for the first study. In the two studies, the number and types of treatments during fattening were collected.

WP2-T2- Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae on farms

UoS

Task completed. See second annual report, 2019.

UCM

A total of 110 *E. coli* isolates recovered from urinary tract infections were collected from March 2019 to November 2020 in collaboration with a reference hospital located in Madrid. Out of the 110 isolates, 77 were collected from GP patients (community-related infections) and 33 were obtained from inpatient samples (hospital-related infections). We performed the phenotypic characterization according to the antimicrobial resistance profile of all isolates following standard surveillance antimicrobial panels. We sequenced all collected isolates by Illumina technology to carry out the genomic characterization. Illumina data were applied for subsequent AMR, plasmid and phylogenetic analyses.

WBVR

In 2019 and 2020, a group of approximately 700 veal calves in the Netherlands was individually followed from birth to slaughter on 5 to 6 sampling moments. The animals were born on 13 dairy farms spread throughout the country and transported between 14 and 28 days of age to 8 veal farms for fattening. Rectal swabs were taken at each sampling moment for selective culturing on cefotaxime containing media to determine the prevalence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*. At the dairy farms the prevalence of *E. coli* ranged from 0-86% (average 26.4%). At all veal farms the prevalence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* amongst the animals went up to >50% at least one sampling moment. In 6 farms, prevalence significantly decreased over time.

Extensive records were recorded on farm management, hygiene, antimicrobial usage and health parameters of the animals and analysed using a linear mixed and multivariate regression model to determine risk factors associated with ESBL/AmpC carriage. No association between age of transportation, sex, breed, and presence of ESC-R *E. coli* at the dairy farm was found. At the veal farm, different management practices for veal calves destined for fattening or replacement heifers, as well as the presence of pets (cats and dogs) and other livestock (horses, sheep and goats) were positively associated with presence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*. The presence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* at the veal farm was positively associated with presence of these bacteria at consecutive time points. Antibiotic batch treatment of the animals is positively associated with presence of ESBL/AmpC *E. coli* while individual treatment was not. A manuscript describing these results has been prepared and is currently awaiting approval by collaborators before submission.

Short-read WGS data has been generated of > 300 isolates and confirms extensive clonal spread of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*, both on dairy farms through the year and on veal farms during a single

production cycle. Nonetheless, multiple variants are spread through each farm and animals are colonised by different *E. coli* variants over time. In order to determine the role plasmid spread in the transmission of ESBLs within the farms, ~70 isolates were selected for long-read using Oxford Nanopore Technologies in collaboration with the OH-EJP Full-Force project which is currently under way.

ANSES

In the two studies, ESBL-producing *E. coli* were collected from MacConkey agar for the culture of the dominant flora and onto selective ChromID ESBL agar (bioMérieux) for the specific selection of ESC-resistant isolates from the subdominant flora. After incubation at 37°C for 24 h, one presumptive *E. coli* colony was arbitrarily selected from each plate and isolates were identified using MALDI-TOF.

In the first study, ESBL-producing *E. coli* rates have significantly decreased in all 10 farms (arrival: 67.7%; departure: 20.4%)(Gay et al, *Frontiers in Microbiology* 2019). Feeding milk containing antimicrobial residues to veal calves is hypothesized to explain the high ESBL loads in animals at the entrance on farms. In the dominant flora, proportions of resistances to amoxicillin, tetracyclines, streptomycin and sulfonamides were very high (>60%) at arrival of animals in the farm and had significantly increased at departure. Proportions of resistances to other beta-lactams than amoxicillin were overall low and significantly decreased during the fattening process. Resistance to quinolones also significantly decreased from arrival to departure. A total of 11 isolates were resistant to colistin (MICs ranging between 6 and 16 mg/L) of which 9 were detected in animals upon arrival (originating from 7 different farms), and 2 in animals at departure (both originating from the same farm). The proportion of multi-resistant isolates significantly increased from 60.2% upon arrival to 67.2% at departure of animals. The proportion of isolates susceptible to the seven selected antibiotics was 23.3% upon arrival and 7.3% at departure. Only two isolates displayed co-resistances to all seven antibiotics.

The second study was performed in three veal farms (A, B and C) located in the region of Brittany, France (Massot *et al*, manuscript submitted). Rectal swabs from 15 calves per farm were collected every 15 days until departure to slaughterhouse and screened for intestinal carriage of ESBL-producing *E. coli*. A decrease in ESBL prevalence in calves was observed over the fattening period, although each farm displayed a specific dynamic. In conclusion, we showed that the diffusion of ESBL-encoding genes in calves is a combination of two scenarios encompassing bacterial clone and/or plasmid spread, which highly rely on local features and contexts, including the types and number of antibiotic treatments per farm.

In this second study, we also took the opportunity of the same sampling to characterize the dynamics of the calves' microbiota subjected to antimicrobial pressure (Massot et al., *Animal Microbiome*, 2020). This observational study showed early convergence of the developing microbiota between veal calves and demonstrated associations between the dose of milk powder and composition of the microbiota. It suggested that group treatments of antibiotics resulted in a reduction of microbial diversity and size of the *E. coli* population in the gut and highlighted the need for additional work to fully understand the impact of antibiotherapy in the veal industry.

Finally, we used the three veal calf fattening farms of the second study as a model to investigate and compare the effectiveness of possible interventions to reduce the AMR burden in this sector (Bastardet al, *One Health* 2021). Longitudinal data of ESBL-EC carriage and antimicrobial use (AMU) were used to develop agent-based mechanistic models to assess different hypotheses regarding the main drivers of ESBL-EC dynamics in calves. The models were independently fitted to the longitudinal data using Markov Chain Monte Carlo and the best model was selected. Within-farm transmission between individuals and sporadic events of contamination were found to drive ESBL-EC dynamics on farms. In the absence of AMU, the median carriage duration of ESBL-EC was estimated to be 19.6 days (95% credible interval: [12.7; 33.3]). In the best model, AMU was found to influence ESBL-EC dynamics, by affecting ESBL-EC clearance rather than acquisition. This effect of AMU was estimated to decrease

gradually after the end of exposure and to disappear after 62.5 days [50.0; 76.9]. Moreover, using a simulation study, we quantified the efficacy of ESBL-EC mitigation strategies. Decreasing ESBL-EC prevalence by 50% on arrival at the fattening farm reduced prevalence at slaughter age by 33.3%. Completely eliminating the use of selective antibiotics on arrival had a strong effect on average ESBL-EC prevalence (relative reduction of 77.0%), but the effect was mild if this use was only decreased by 50% compared to baseline (relative reduction of 3.3%).

APHA

We have completed the collection of samples for a longitudinal study which focused on two sites of the same UK pig farm which are separated geographically; a non-clinical farm site that houses five age classes of healthy pigs and has ceased group antimicrobial treatments for at least five years, and a clinical farm site that is comprised of three age classes of pigs sent from healthy sites following disease, that have subsequently undergone group and individual antimicrobial treatment. Faecal samples were obtained from both sites from pigs at four time-points at 6 month intervals over 18 months, alongside seagull faecal samples from two time points. Representative *E. coli* were purified from all time points from non-selective and antibiotic selective agar plates (cefotaxime and ciprofloxacin), followed by Illumina whole-genome sequencing (WGS). The WGS data was analysed by reconstructing phylogeny of the *E. coli* isolates, determining presence of AMR genes, plasmid replicon types, in silico Multilocus Sequence Type and mobile genetic elements (WP3).

MIC determination for the isolates collected during visits 4 and 5 has also been completed. An overall analysis of the MIC data across 5 visits has been carried out. Temporal trends were evaluated, as well as a comparison between antibiotic treated and non-antibiotic treated groups of pigs was carried out. A draft publication is in preparation to report these results.

WP2-T3-Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae in hospitals and care facilities

UoS

Task completed. See third annual report, 2020.

Institut Pasteur

The ARDIG project focused on *E. coli*. Following within the consortium discussion, it was decided to focus on *E. coli* isolates responsible for Urinary Tract Infections (UTI) as those isolates are representative of extra intestinal pathogenic *E. coli* and are collected in different countries in a similar way. In addition, it was decided in this prospective study to collect both isolates of community or hospital origins. Community isolates were either from city microbiology laboratories or from outpatients (emergency) in the hospital. Hospital isolates were from hospital clinical microbiology laboratories. As the objective of the study was to analyze the diversity of the isolates, no data on patient were collected. Several studies have been published on isolate collections following selection for either resistance to third generation cephalosporin (3CG) or producing ESBL and we expected, following such selection to retrieve a majority of ST131 isolates, we decided to have a more agnostic approach and not to select for a specific antimicrobial resistance phenotype. In total, we analyzed 1067 isolates collected in 2019 by five partners:

Institut Pasteur together with the team of Thierry Naas at the Bicêtre hospital collected a total of 251 isolates, including 123 from emergencies (community) and 128 from the hospital wards. These 251 isolates were submitted to WGS (WP3)

NVI

E. coli isolates from humans with UTI in a large centrally located hospital in Norway, and from GP in the same area were collected (the 20 first isolates of each category, from each month in 2019). The isolates have been sequenced (Illumina short read) at NVI and MIC determination have been carried out. The dominating sequence types were ST131, ST73 and ST69. Resistance genes were uncommonly present in ST73 isolates, in contrast to ST131 isolates that usually were resistant to several

antimicrobial agents. No particular ST dominated among hospitalized patients. WGS data are included in analyses in WP3.

PHE

PHE have collaborated with UoS (Rob LaRagione, Maria Getino) to short-read WGS sequence a collection of *E. coli* isolated from human urinary tract infections occurring in the community and a hospital setting. Quality checked sequences have been shared for collaborative analysis at IP.

WP2-T4- Data analysis of collected resistant Enterobacteriaceae on national levels

UCM

Within the framework of the ARDIG project, we have characterized and studied the dissemination dynamics of multi-resistant bacterial clonal groups and the genetic determinants that they carry in different settings, including animal production and hospital environments. The isolates were sequenced by Illumina technology and the resulting data were analyzed for AMR and plasmid characterization and phylogenetic studies. The epidemiological metadata and phenotypic resistance profiles of the isolates were integrated with the genotypic data. Thanks to the studies developed during the project, we have identified risky *E. coli* STs that are disseminated in different production types and environments, such as ST1196 and ST10, as well as genes of resistance against antibiotics of clinical importance, such as *mcr* genes and determinants of resistance to cephalosporins, in both pig and poultry farms. Some of them were selected and sequenced by Nanopore technology, based on Illumina genomic analysis and genotypic resistance profiles, in order to study particular antimicrobial resistance gene dynamics. We are working on the manuscript to public the results obtained at national level, but also, we have collaborated with other partners of the project that have similar results in order to analyse international trends and epidemiological dynamics of specific resistance genes and/or STs.

BfR

On request, the BfR had provided sequencing data on *mcr-1*- and *qnr*-carrying isolates for comparative analysis.

APHA

Whole genome sequencing of ESBL/AmpC *E. coli* that have been collected by APHA from national surveillance of livestock (pig and poultry) since 2013 have been analysed for their AMR gene content as well as plasmid diversity. A paper has been published in Science Reports on AMR analysis in *E. coli* from pigs collected between 2013-2017.

WP2-T5: Comparative analysis of collected isolates on a Europe-wide level (M30-M36)

APHA, ANSES, BfR, IP, NVI, PHE, UCM, UoS, WBVR

ARDIG partners have submitted WGS of up to 50 *Escherichia coli* isolates per institute to a repository and five partners (APHA, WBVR, PHE, UCM, and NVI), representing the diversity of pipelines (APHA SeqFinder/Abricate, PHE GeneFinder, WBVR, Ariba, ResFinder/PointFinder), have analysed ~450 WGS data through the pipelines. All partners have performed MICs on the EFSA panel of antimicrobials on their isolates from this panel of 450 isolates, so phenotypic data could be obtained for comparison with the AMR genotypes resulting from each of the 5 bioinformatic pipelines.

UoS

The UoS has carried out a comparative analysis of swine *E. coli* isolates collected from four different European countries. A total of 1223 WGS assemblies, including 916 from the APHA (UK), 117 from the UoS (UK), 122 from the UCM (Spain), 50 from the BfR (Germany) and 18 from the WBVR (Netherlands) were included in the analysis. Phylogroups and sequence types were determined using ClermonTyping and MLST bioinformatic tools, respectively. Half of the isolates belonged to phylogroup A, 25% to B1

and 13% to C, whereas the common human phylogroup B2 only represented 1% of the swine isolates, reflecting a low degree of transmission between these hosts. At sequence type level, the most common MLST groups found among swine isolates were ST10 (11%), ST744 (11%) and ST88 (7%).

ResFinder and PlasmidFinder databases were used to characterise the acquired AMR genes and plasmid replicons harboured by the isolates. While the most common plasmid types were IncFIB (48%) and IncI1 (36%), the most abundant AMR genes were tetA (41%), aph(6)-Id (35%), blaTEM-1B (34%), sul2 (30%) and blaCTX-M1 (30%). In addition, point mutations were determined using PointFinder, phylogenetic trees were produced with ParSNP, genes were annotated with Prokka and a pangenome analysis was produced with Roary. Out of a total 33797 genes included in the pangenome analysis, 3006 were core genes with an identity between 99 and 100%. An initial representation of the swine collection of isolates based on core genome phylogeny, gene content and country of isolation, showed no specific pattern, possibly due to the bias of the collection towards UK isolates. However, a complete analysis of over 3,000 *E. coli* isolates from humans and different animal species that is being performed by the different ARDIG partners may provide additional insights into host- and country-specific determinants that may be important for AMR transmission.

UCM

We provided the phenotypic resistance data and genomic sequencing data of 50 *E. coli* isolates from poultry and swine farms in order to compare and analyse our results from AMR detection to those obtained by other partners with different pipelines and AMR databases. We performed the AMR genetic detection over the total 450 *E. coli* isolates collected from all partners using the ARIBA (*Antimicrobial Resistance Identification By Assembly*) pipeline and applying the ResFinder database. Regarding the comparative study of certain clonal groups of epidemiological importance, as well as genetic determinants of resistance and plasmid types involved in their dissemination, our group participated with different partners. We provided sequencing data and metadata of *E. coli* isolates belonging to specific STs requested by partners for in depth studies (ST744 and ST38, among others). Likewise, we have focused on the epidemiological study of ST1196 *E. coli* in diverse environments from different countries, for which other partners provided metadata and sequencing data from their project databases. We have integrated these data to perform epidemiological analysis of clonal dissemination at European level. We cooperated with other partners in the study of the epidemiological dynamics of *mcr* genes across Europe, focusing on the mobile genetic elements involved in their dissemination, by providing Illumina-Nanopore hybrid assemblies of *E. coli* isolates carrying these resistance genes from national surveillance studies. The same way, we have facilitated hybrid assemblies and metadata of multiple *E. coli* isolates harbouring resistance plasmids belonging to specific incompatibility groups (IncFII, IncI1 and IncX) to partners of the project that are developing AI tools focused on the rapid prediction and accurate identification of these AMR genetic platforms.

PHE

PHE has shared short read data with partners for *E. coli* belonging to the ST744 and ST1196 lineages in addition to any *E. coli* harbouring CTX-M-1 and IncI1 sequences in order to facilitate the comparisons of isolates across countries and One Health compartments.

APHA

APHA has collected WGS from *E. coli* ST744 isolates from partners in the consortium for further characterisation. Work is progressing to compare the WGS data by reconstructing phylogeny of the *E. coli* isolates, determine presence of AMR genes and mobile genetic elements present in the isolates.

WBVR

Colistin resistance due to *mcr*-encoding *E. coli* have been described in many countries but most reports concern limited numbers of isolates due to the relatively low prevalence in most countries compared to ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*. WBVR have collected *mcr*-encoding *E. coli* from livestock, meat and humans from the Netherlands between 2010 and 2020 and sequenced these using Illumina short read

sequencing and a selection of isolates also with Long-read sequencing to complete plasmid sequences. Furthermore, partners from the UK, Germany and Spain have submitted WGS data of mcr-encoding *E. coli* from livestock in their collections in order to perform a Europe-wide analysis of > 250 isolates. Analysis of this dataset is currently still ongoing.

WP3. AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates.

WP3-T1 - Detailed molecular characterisation of AMR genes present in human, animal, food and environment isolates from WP1 and WP2.

Five partners (APHA/PHE/WVBR/NVI/UCM) have run WGS data from 450 *E. coli* isolates submitted by ARDIG partners (APHA, ANSES, BfR, IP, NVI, PHE, UCM, UoS, WBVR) through their pipelines (APHA SeqFinder/Abriicate, PHE GeneFinder, WBVR, Ariba, ResFinder/PointFinder) to assess the impact of similarities and differences in methodologies commonly used for AMR genotyping within European Institutes on AMR gene predictions. Results from the pipelines analysis have been shared with the consortium, and partners have compared the AMR genotype prediction for each isolate with the corresponding antimicrobial tested by MIC (EFSA panel), using the database/gene catalogue available to them through their Institute. The results of the genotype/ phenotype comparison have been compiled by APHA and analysed further to identify agreements and discrepancies between each approach, as well as the sensitivity and specificity values to aim for between genotype and phenotype correlations. A manuscript of this work is in its final stages and will include recommendations for future use of WGS for surveillance activities. Such comparisons are of extreme importance to EFSA and ECDC as they are moving to reporting of AMR data by genotyping, and we expect our study to make a valuable contribution to harmonisation of current approaches between animal and human sectors in this context of One Health.

UoS

A total of 730 *E. coli* isolated from four different host species have been characterised by whole genome sequencing. Out of 9 sets of isolates, 4 were collected during longitudinal studies over 12-month periods, including 255 from human urinary tract infections, 108 from human bloodstream infections, 85 from healthy poultry faeces and 117 healthy swine faeces. The other 5 collections of isolates are composed of 94 ESBL-harboring *E. coli* from human urinary infections, 15 *E. coli* from healthy human faeces, 16 collected from the caeca of healthy poultry, 26 from avian colibacillosis samples and 14 from healthy cattle faeces.

The genome assemblies, available metadata and molecular characterization results (including assembly quality, MSLT, phylogroups, AMR genes, AMR point mutations and plasmid replicons detected in these isolates) have been uploaded to the ARDIG shared folder for further analysis.

PHE

Analysis of Enterobacterales producing carbapenemase enzymes revealed that, in addition to isolates producing the OXA-48 carbapenemase associated with a pandemic of self-transferable IncL/M incompatibility group plasmids, other plasmids belonging to this incompatibility grouping have emerged with the NDM carbapenemase. Analysis revealed the NDM gene had been acquired by IncL/M plasmids on multiple occasions occurring in geographically widespread isolates (manuscript submitted to the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy). To undertake a risk assessment for the threat posed by these emergent NDM encoding plasmids, examples of the most notable 'type' have been shared for fitness comparisons vs. the pandemic OXA-48 plasmid, at the UoS.

APHA

The farm isolates were characterised further by analysis of the WGS data. Levels of AMR genes present within indicator *E. coli* from non-selective media varied significantly between sites, with 84% identified as multi-drug resistant (3 or more AMR genes) on the clinical site in comparison to 4% on the non-

clinical, with a corresponding difference in Sequence Types (ST) identified. In contrast, *E. coli* isolated on both sites from antibiotic selective media were mostly identical STs, with ST744 being the dominant *E. coli* isolated from ciprofloxacin containing media and ST88 the dominant from cefotaxime media. Persistence of ST744 clones with <10 SNP differences were identified across time-points, age classes of pigs and seagull samples in both sites. Both STs have previously been reported from animals and humans globally.

The presence of *E. coli* of the same ST with few SNP differences across time points, pigs and gulls indicates persistence and transmission of *E. coli* subtypes on and between sites. Further work is planned to identify factors that may be selecting these clones on site and maintaining AMR in the absence/low use of antimicrobials. A manuscript of this work is currently under review.

BfR

Within the work package 3 of the ARDIG project, we characterized *Escherichia (E.) coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food, provided by the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) for Antimicrobial Resistance (AR) in depth. Selection of isolates for detailed molecular characterization was based on the prevailing phenotypic characteristics (esp. MIC values, resistance profiles) of the (fluoro)quinolone-resistant *E. coli*. By focusing on nalidixic acid (NAL) and ciprofloxacin (CIP)-resistant *E. coli*, all isolates with a MIC of ≥ 8 mg/L for NAL and/or a MIC of ≥ 0.25 mg/L for CIP were further characterized. In total, 452 *E. coli* from the NRL-AR collection of 2017 fulfill the requirements for further investigation. These isolates were screened for six different *qnr*-variants, namely: *qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrC*, *qnrD*, *qnrS* and *qnrVC*. The most frequent *qnr*-variant was *qnrS* with 16.1 % among all investigated isolates. Despite of *qnrS*, the occurrence of other *qnr* genes in the isolate collection was rather low. For screening of genomic relation of *qnr*-positive *E. coli*, we conducted XbaI macrorestriction analysis (XbaI-PFGE). The resulting phylogenetic tree revealed certain relations between a few isolates, but overall a broad diversity of XbaI-patterns was observed. For plasmid prediction, the isolates were subjected to S1-nuclease PFGE. This investigation in combination with DNA-DNA hybridization against *qnr*-genes allowed us to derive plasmidal associations with *qnr*-determinants. One-hundred and three *E. coli* were further subjected to Illumina NextSeq sequencing and were analyzed in detail for their genetic types (i.e. cgMLST, MLST, serotype etc.) and specific features (i.e. AMR, virulence, biocides etc.). The sequencing data were further used for predicting associations between the occurrence of *qnr* and isolate- or plasmid-specific features.

UCM

A total of 383 *E. coli* isolates collected and selected in the WP2 of the project were sequenced using Illumina technology, comprising samples from diverse sources: human hospital settings (110 isolates) and swine and poultry production farms (138 and 135 isolates, respectively). All isolates were obtained from non-supplemented culture media, in order to have an extensive and representative *E. coli* population according to AMR profiles. Phenotypic resistance profiles to different antibiotic groups by MIC evaluations were performed, showing a general high prevalence of fluoroquinolone and tetracycline resistance among all collected isolates from animal production sources. With Illumina data we studied the resistance gene content to all antibiotic families, comparing our results to those obtained by other partners with different AMR detection pipelines over the same isolates. This allowed us to identify the similarities and discrepancies between different bioinformatic tools and databases, which will be extremely useful for implementation of national and global AMR surveillance programs. We assembled the reads obtained by Illumina sequencing to perform the detection of antimicrobial resistance genes following different approaches and to identify the different *E. coli* sequence types involved in the dissemination of specific resistance genes at national and international levels. From 100 analyzed isolates from swine and poultry farms, a total of 45 different STs were identified, highlighting a high clonal diversity in the animal production area. However, one of this STs, ST10, was comprised by 23 isolates from both production types, representing the 23% of the isolates, which shows the broad distribution of this clonal group. Other ST, ST1196, also showed a high dissemination

in different sources (including human, animal and environmental samples), not only in Spain, but in other several countries around the world. Thus, our group is focused on the epidemiological study of this clonal complex and other ARDIG partners provided sequencing data and metadata of isolates belonging to ST1196, so we are finishing phylogenetic analysis to put in context the epidemiological links of all multi-drug resistant isolates found. We are working on the publication of these results. In addition, one of our main goals was the study of the dissemination dynamics of *mcr* colistin resistance genes on different mobile genetic elements and *E. coli* clones, such as ST1196 and plasmids belonging to IncI and IncX types. We have collaborated with other partners to combine our *mcr*-carrying isolates and we have performed Nanopore WGS to resolve the genomic structure of these isolates and the plasmids involved in the dissemination of these clinically relevant resistance genes. We provided to the project the assemblies and analyses of Illumina data from all human, swine and poultry *E. coli* isolates in order to establish their clonal relationship and common genetic and plasmid contents.

ANSES

In the first study, the ESBL phenotype was largely due to the presence of CTX-M group 1 enzymes, which were identified in 71.5% of the animals upon arrival, and in 61.2% upon departure to the slaughterhouse (Gay et al, *Frontiers in Microbiology* 2019). Of the 241 *bla*_{CTX-M-group1}-carrying *E. coli* upon arrival, 200 harbored *bla*_{CTX-M-1} (200/241, 83.0%), 23 *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (23/241, 9.5%), 12 *bla*_{CTX-M-32} (12/241, 5.0%); 4 *bla*_{CTX-M-55} (4/241, 1.7%) and 2 *bla*_{CTX-M-3} (2/241, 0.8%). PFGE profiles performed on a subset of 10 ESBL-producing isolates per farm upon arrival showed a wide variability without any clustering. At departure, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} was also the most frequently identified gene (51/60, 85%) followed by *bla*_{CTX-M-55} (4/60, 6.7%), *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (3/60, 5.0%), and *bla*_{CTX-M-3} (2/60, 3.3 %). At departure, the PFGE profiles were much more similar than upon arrival so that a high degree of clonality was observed inside each farm. As an example, the PFGE distribution in farm E at departure, where three distinct PFGE profiles were observed, highlights the epidemiological success of certain ESBL *E. coli* clones more than others during the fattening process. Nonetheless, since different CTX-M enzymes were also produced by the same clone, not only a clonal but also a plasmid dissemination has likely occurred, which illustrates the complexity of ESBL spread at farm level. Similarly, the emergence of CTX-M-2 enzymes before slaughter was most likely due to the dissemination of a single clone within farm C since all but one CTX-M-2 enzymes were identified in this farm. Altogether, depending on the farm presenting ESBL-positive isolates, from 1 (farm H, 1 ESBL producing *E. coli* isolate) to 7 (farm B, 26 ESBL-producing *E. coli* isolates), distinct PFGE profiles were observed at the end of the fattening process. Of note, none of the successful clones identified at departure for the slaughterhouse was shared between farms, proving a specific and local evolution. *E. coli* belonged to phylogroups A (n = 134, 39.8%), B1 (n = 78, 23.1%), B2 (n = 9, 2.7%), and D (n = 116, 34.4%) upon arrival, and to phylogroups A (n = 50, 51.0%), B1 (n = 15, 15.3%), B2 (n = 1, 1.0%), and D (n = 32, 32.7%) at departure to slaughterhouse. The *mcr-1* gene was identified in 18 isolates, while one isolate carried both the *mcr-1* and *mcr-3* genes. At departure for slaughterhouse, only 4 animals from 2 different farms still carried a colistin-resistant *E. coli* (MICs ranging between 2 and 4 mg/L). The *mcr-3* gene was detected in all four isolates and was co-harbored with the *bla*_{CTX-M-55} gene.

In the second study, one colony was isolated from the 173 positive samples for further characterization (Massot et al, manuscript submitted). The ESBL-producing *E. coli* isolates carried either *bla*_{CTX-M-1} (112/173 isolates, 64.7%), *bla*_{CTX-M-14} (58/173, 33.5%) or *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (3/173, 1.8%). All of them were resistant to at least two antimicrobials other than β -lactams, the most common resistances being against tetracyclines, sulfonamides, trimethoprim and aminoglycosides. The median number of co-resistances was four.

Institut Pasteur

Study 1. Analysis of CPEc isolates received by the Fr-NRC. We have sequenced 713 isolates received by the Fr-NRC until 2015 by using the Illumina technology. As ST38 represented the most frequent ST among those isolates, we sequenced to completion by using the PacBio technology 10 CPEc ST38 isolates. Furthermore, in order to quantify the fitness cost of plasmids carrying carbapenemase genes we similarly fully sequenced six isolates from ST38, ST410 and ST131 closely related to CPEc isolates, but devoid of any carbapenemase genes. We performed whole genome phylogeny of the 713 CPEc isolates together with reference *E. coli* isolates. For each isolate, we determined the ARG content and the presence of mutations known to contribute to decrease susceptibility in *gyrA*, *parC* and *parE* QRDR regions (fluoroquinolones), in the porin genes *ompC* and *ompF* and in the penicillin binding proteins 3 (PBP3) gene *ftsI* (β -lactams). The most frequent carbapenemase genes were *bla*_{OXA-48}, (65%), *bla*_{OXA-181} (15%), *bla*_{NDM-5} (7%) and *bla*_{NDM-1} (6%). We observed a great diversity of CPEc as the 713 isolates belong

to 166 STs from all phylogroups. Nevertheless 57% of the isolates belong to 14 STs with at least 10 isolates. In particular we identified 3 dominant lineages: clonal complex (CC) 10 (including ST10, ST167 and ST617), CC23 including ST410 and ST38 which together gather 50% of the isolates (Figure X). In terms of relation with animal isolates, two CC23 lineages need to retain further attention: ST410 for which closely related ESBL producing bovine isolates have been characterized and ST88 (15 isolates), which was the most frequent lineages among

Figure X Phylogeny of 713 CPEc isolates received by the FrNRC. Genome annotation are indicated in outside circles as indicated in the figure key on the left

540 3GC-R *E. coli* isolates from diarrheic veal in Belgium we have analyzed.

Phylogenetic analysis (Figure X) revealed a combination of disperse isolates and of lineages enriched in CPEc isolates. We first focused our analysis on an ST410 clade broadly disseminated and producing OXA181. *bla*_{OXA-181} is carried by a *incX3* plasmid. Analysis of mutations in the branch leading to the ST410 OXA-410 clade revealed candidate loci which might have contributed to the dissemination of this clone. Among those mutations, we focused our analysis on mutation in *ompC*, *ompF* and *ftsI* which lead to to decrease susceptibility to some β -lactams including ertapenem. We first extended this analysis to the whole species by retrieving CPEc genome from the NCBI and Enterobase web sites. We combined phylogeny and association study to define three evolutionary trajectories: (i) broadly disseminated MDR lineages mutated in these three genes before the acquisition of the carbapenemase gene and contributing to the “success” of these clones, (ii) ST38 which shows specific properties including an intrinsic reduced susceptibility to certain β -lactams, and (iii) diverse isolates which have likely recently acquired a carbapenemase gene with no sign of dissemination. This last class included isolated from the pandemic lineage ST131 (Patino Navarrete et al. 2020).

We next analyzed data on Fr-NRC isolates considering these observations (Rosinski-Chupin et al. in preparation). Similarly, to what was observed on worldwide collection of isolates, Fr-NRC isolates belong to the same three categories. Sporadic cases were mainly associated with *bla*_{OXA-48}. It could be due to the high conjugation efficiency of the *IncI* pOXA-48 plasmid and its high prevalence in

K. pneumoniae isolates in France. We also identified and confirmed three clusters of isolates corresponding to hospital outbreaks which all belong to MDR lineages.

Finally, we focused our analysis on ST38 isolates by characterizing the disseminated lineages. Strikingly, the vast majority of isolates belong to three disseminated lineages. In these three lineages, all ARG were inserted into the chromosome and were generally devoid of any plasmid. Combined analysis with publicly available ST38 genomes showed that two of these clades were broadly disseminated, whereas one clade was mostly restricted to France with few isolates from the Netherlands. In order to better characterize the insertion and their dynamic, we fully sequenced 10 isolates belonging to these lineages. In addition to the OXA-48 producing clades, we identified a small cluster of seven isolates carrying *bla*_{VIM-4}. In this case, the carbapenemase gene was not inserted into the chromosome but carried by a new plasmid we characterized. The *bla*_{VIM-4} gene is carried by an integron. Strikingly, it is virtually identical to the non-conjugative plasmid pROUEN1, a plasmid identified in an MDR *Pseudomonas putida* clinical isolate (Eleni Liapis et al. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 2019). pROUEN1 carries a similar integron with five resistance genes including the *bla*_{IMP-63}. Therefore, the only difference between the two plasmids is the gene content of the integron. This observation raised the issue of the evolution from one plasmid to the other one. Our hypothesis is that pVIM-4 derived from pROUEN1 by integration (including *bla*_{VIM-4}) and loss of cassettes (including *bla*_{IMP-63}). It raised also the issue of the acquisition of this plasmid. Analysis of *E. coli* sequences from Enterobase did not reveal any related isolates carrying *bla*_{IMP-63} and BLAST search at the NCBI no similar plasmid. This plasmid does not seem to have disseminated.

Study 2: Analysis of the i-bird collection. The 205 isolates belong to 32 different STs revealing a broad diversity of ESBL-*Ec* carried by the patients. However, 100 belong to ST131, almost 50%. They are carriage isolates recovered from systematic screening and not clinical isolates, showing that, in this environment, ST131 is dominant even among colonizing ESBL isolates. In-depth phylogenetic analysis of the 205 isolates revealed cases of transmission or of a common source only for ST131 isolates (Fig. 1). ST131 isolates clustered in four groups (Figure 1) with exchanges between patients, as exemplified for group 3 (in blue) identified in seven patients. Furthermore, we observed a within host diversity. A representative isolate of each lineage was fully sequenced by combining long read (PacBio) and short read (Illumina) sequencing to characterize the within- and between host diversity and to infer transmission and directionality. The genomic data will be confronted with temporal and contact data collected during the i-bird project. Therefore, the prolonged carriage of ST131 ESBL-P isolates and their capacity to be transmitted from patient to patient have likely contributed to their predominance among ESBL-P *E. coli*. We also identified three cases of plasmid transmission from *K. pneumoniae* to *E. coli* but no cases of transmission from *E. coli* to *K. pneumoniae*, suggesting that in this context, *E. coli* act mainly as a receiver more than a donor of antibiotic resistance plasmids.

Figure X Phylogenetic tree of 100 ST131 isolates from the i-bird project. The majority of isolates clusters in four different clades that have disseminated in the hospital.

Analysis of UTI isolates from ARDIG

The 250 isolates from UTI collected by ARDIG partners (IP, UCM, NVI, UoS) have been sequenced by the Illumina technology. The isolates belong to 81 different ST revealing a broad diversity (Fig. X). The four most frequent STs are also frequently reported in other studies as responsible for UTI (ST73, 31 isolates; ST131, 20 isolates; ST69, 19 isolates and ST95, 18 isolates). Susceptibility to β -lactams has been determined by disc diffusion assays for the first 120 isolates. MICs of 25 isolates for 14 antibiotics were determined by serial microdilution by ANSES for benchmarking pipelines for ARG identification and for genotype phenotype correlation. Antibiotic resistance genes have been detected using Resfinder and candidate mutations have been investigated by using point finder. 21% of the isolates share a mutation in the FQRD region of *gyrA* and/or *parC* and were predicted to show a reduce susceptibility to fluoroquinolons, whereas 11% express a ESBL of the CTX-M family. Only one isolate, of ST410, carries a carbapenemase gene (*bla*_{OXA181}). These genome sequences are combined to other ARDIG *E. coli* sequences for a global analysis.

NVI

NVI was responsible for phylogenetic analysis of *E. coli* isolates of human and animal origin collected by from partner countries (UCM, IP, NVI, UoS, WBVR, APHA, BfR). A phylogenetic reconstruction of all

E. coli isolates from longitudinal studies and national surveillance (n = 3812) was carried out to investigate possible cross-country zoonotic transfer. Briefly, all genomes were quality controlled and checked for contamination using QUASt and Kraken2, respectively. In total, 33 genomes were removed due to low quality or contamination. Additionally, isolates from ducks, roe deer, and clinical isolates of animal origin were removed from the dataset, leaving 3745 genomes. Panaroo pangenome was used to calculate the pangenome and generate the core gene alignment. The core gene alignment was used for reconstructing the phylogeny with IQ-Tree. The program snp-dists was used to calculate the SNP

Figure X. ST distribution among the 250 UTI isolates

distances between the genomes. After inspecting the phylogenetic tree, subclades were selected for further analysis. The selection of clades was based on the following: To show a possible transmission between food producing animals and humans (demonstrate shared strains between humans/animals), and to demonstrate closely related strains from the same animal species, but originating from different countries (which again can indicate AMR transfer via international animal trade). Each subclade was subjected to another phylogenetic pipeline, using the ALPPACA pipeline (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4452122). Briefly, ParSNP was used to predict the core genome, and Gubbins was used to identify recombinant areas in the alignment. Then, maskrc-svg was used to mask these regions in the alignment, and IQ-Tree reconstructed the phylogeny from that alignment.

WBVR

WBVR have been responsible for determining the AMR gene content of the 3812 *E. coli* isolates of human and animal origin collected by from partner countries (UCM, IP, NVI, UoS, WBVR, APHA, BfR). These isolates were run through the ResFinder pipeline, which performs similar to other pipelines used by consortium members, to determine the isolate AMR genotypes. Differences between host species, geography and management systems that may impact on AMR content and distribution is currently being assessed.

WP3-T2- Characterisation of prevalent circulating plasmids and their transfer in vitro

UoS

The UoS has quantified the transfer of a representative set of broad host range plasmids carrying NDM-1 and OXA-48 carbapenemase genes. Original host species (*E. coli*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca* and *Citrobacter*) were used as donors in conjugation experiments performed for 1h on LB-agar. A broad range of frequencies was observed when original hosts were used as donors (from no detected transconjugants to high conjugation rates), while more homogeneous results were obtained when the obtained transconjugants (*E. coli* MG1655) were used as donors, reflecting the high sequence similarity between plasmids.

As a general rule, IncL OXA-48 plasmids conjugated at a higher rate than IncM NDM-1 plasmids, likely due to the inactivation of the fertility inhibition gene *tir* in IncL plasmids, and possibly causing the more extensive global spread of OXA-48 plasmids.

UCM

We determined the plasmid content of *E. coli* isolates from WP2, identifying all different plasmid incompatibility groups according to plasmidic replication structures using short-read sequencing data. We focused on the study of dissemination dynamics of *mcr* genes, among others. Out of 35 *mcr-1*-carrying *E. coli* isolates identified in both swine and poultry production farms, we selected 20 belonging to diverse clonal complexes and sources to perform WGS using Nanopore technology. We generated Illumina-Nanopore hybrid assemblies of the *E. coli* genomes, which allowed the in-depth study of plasmids and mobile genetic elements involved in the dissemination and mobilization of *mcr* genes among these bacteria at farm, regional and national levels, as well as the association of these genes with other genetic resistance mechanisms in the same plasmidic platform. The results showed two different epidemiological routes of *mcr-1* dissemination in animal farms in Spain: i) dissemination via specific bacterial clones, which are present in different farms, even in different animal production types; ii) dissemination via specific plasmid types highly associated with *mcr* genes, which are spread and present in multiple bacterial clones. Among these plasmids, those belonging to the IncI1 type were the most prevalent ones. We are finishing conjugation experiments to assess the capacity of these plasmids to be transferred and maintained at intra and interspecies level. We are currently preparing a manuscript with the aforementioned results. Furthermore, we provided the metadata and Illumina-Nanopore sequencing data of all these *mcr-1*-positive *E. coli* isolates to other partners of the project in order to study the dissemination dynamics of *mcr* colistin resistance genes and their carrying mobile genetic elements and *E. coli* clones at the European level.

BfR

For determination of plasmid-types carrying *qnr*, we focused on *in-silico*-based finishing of the plasmid genomes. For this, the refSNPer tool was used, which elects the closest reference, by mapping the input sample to a chosen reference set and identifies the coverage by using bedtools. With this, we were able to assign several *qnr*-carrying plasmids to reference plasmids and track putative plasmid paths. Moreover, we discovered plasmids, which are yet not described to be associated with *qnr*. In this manner, we detected the most frequently detected plasmid to cluster for the groups of IncY (n=19) and IncX (n=27). It has been emphasized before, that there is a correlation between this IncX plasmids, harboring *bla*_{TEM} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} genes next to *qnrS*, resulting in ESBL-producing *E. coli*. We could confirm this observation through annotation of our sequences. IncX plasmids are regularly described as a group inhabiting the *qnrS1* gene. Therefore, we decided to determine this plasmid group in detail. We wanted to find out more about the *E. coli*, prone to inhabit this plasmid type and we wanted to describe a proper plasmid backbone. Moreover, our aim was to derive a core genome for the individual *qnr* plasmid types. With this, we wanted to understand their potential in disseminating *qnrS1* and other potential resistance genes. However, the *E. coli* inheriting the IncX-plasmid carrying the *qnrS1* were highly heterogenic. We found diverse ST-types of *E. coli* as well as different matrices, which did hold the respective IncX plasmids. From the XbaI-macrorestriction profile, we confirmed a high diversity of *E. coli*, possibly transmitting this plasmid. Thus, one can conclude that this plasmid, carrying the *qnrS1* gene, is spreading over different *E. coli* types within multiple sources. Further, we screened for their

conjugal behavior. First, we determined the conjugal behavior *in silico* with the mob-suit tool. Thus, we found most of the *qnrS* carrying IncX plasmids to hold the respective relaxase and oriT region on the plasmid, suggesting possible transfer. This observation was then validated by laboratory experiments. However, the *in vitro* and *in silico* results for evaluation of the transmissibility of the plasmids mostly showed divergent results.

Next to the *in-silico* detection of plasmid references, we analyzed plasmid structures with long-read sequencing methods. Thus, we were able to generate scaffolds for the most prevalent *qnr*-carrying plasmid types. These basis structures assisted when reconstructing of other *qnr*-plasmid was aimed for characterization of the most prevalent plasmids.

Next to *qnrS* we set our focus on *qnrB*-carrying plasmids in ESBL producing *E. coli*. Therewith, we found some prevailing plasmid types as IncH and Col440I. Further characterization of these plasmids indicates that especially *qnrB19* did mainly exist on small, non-conjugative plasmids. Thus, the spread of these small plasmids remain a mystery. Furthermore, we detected *qnrB2* on IncH plasmid, known for spreading multi-resistance across different matrices. The presence of these *qnrB* resistance determinants in ESBL-producing *E. coli* do pose a particular risk, as it may confer resistance against a “Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials” for human medicine next to the already present genes leading to ESBL producing *E. coli*.

Altogether, with those comprehensive investigations of *qnr*-positiv *E.coli* isolates a thorough and complex picture will be generated for the mobile genetic elements and their dissemination as well as their commonalities in commensal *E. coli*.

NVI

Analysis of circulating ESBL plasmids/strains from broilers in Norway have been performed by using both short and long-read sequencing (isolates with blaCTX-M-1 located on IncI1-ly plasmids). Our data showed that dissemination of blaCTX-M-1 in Norwegian broiler production is due to both clonal expansion and horizontal transfer of plasmids carrying blaCTX-M-1. The genetic diversity at both strain and plasmid level indicates multiple introductions to Norwegian broiler production. The study was published in Frontiers in Microbiology.

Comparison studies showed that blaCTX-M-1 plasmids circulating in Norwegian broiler production are highly similar to plasmids previously described from broiler production in other countries. Reconstruction of blaCTX-M-1/ IncI1-ly plasmids from broilers in Norway showed that a plasmids from ST57 isolates harboured IncI1-ly/IncFIB hybrid plasmids with blaCTX-M-1. Conjugation experiments showed that a non-hybrid IncI1-ly blaCTX-M-1 plasmid (sequence similar to the IncI1-ly part on the co-integrated IncI1-ly/IncFIB plasmid) was transferred into more recipient strains, indicating that that the non-hybrid plasmid exhibited a greater promiscuity in terms of acceptance and maintenance by various *E. coli* strains.

ANSES

The bla_{CTX-M-1} gene was carried by five plasmid types disseminated in 16 clones (encompassing 112/173 isolates, 64.7%), while the bla_{CTX-M-14} gene was carried by five plasmid types disseminated by 15 clones (encompassing 58/173 isolates, 33.5%) (Massot *et al*, manuscript submitted). The bla_{CTX-M-1} and bla_{CTX-M-14} genes were carried by distinct plasmids and clones. Of note, the bla_{CTX-M-15} gene was detected on the chromosome of the same clone in farms B and C. Four ESBL plasmids were identified in several farms: IncI1/ST312 in farms A and B, IncK in farms A and C, IncF/F2:A-B- in all three farms, and IncF/F2:A-B42 in farms A and C. IncF/F2:A-B42 plasmid was spread by the same *E. coli* clone in different farms, and the others by distinct *E. coli* clones in the different farms. While present in two farms, IncK and IncF/F2:A-B42 plasmids were detected only in one clone per farm, suggesting a limited spread. On the opposite, IncI1/ST312 and IncF/F2:A-B- have spread in several clones in each farm.

APHA

To characterize prevalent plasmids and their dissemination between different systems (D-3.3 and D-3.4), including different host types and geography, APHA has been evaluating a machine learning approach where by presence of some of the most common AMR plasmid types such as those harbouring Inc-I1, Inc-F and Inc-X can be determined. Validation of a test set of isolates harbouring these Inc-types from various partners (APHA, NVI, UCM, and WBVR) with long and short read WGS available, has indicated clearly that the machine learning approach can identify isolates from each Inc-type, as well as separate AMR from non-AMR harbouring plasmids. As part of the next step we are testing all 3812 *E. coli* isolates of human and animal origin collected by partner countries (UCM, IP, NVI, UoS, WBVR, APHA, BfR) to determine what plasmids may be common and disseminating across these regions and host-types.

WP3-T3- Fitness cost of AMR and stability of plasmids in different host strain background

UoS

The UoS has performed *in vitro* growth curves in different media to determine the fitness cost of IncL/M plasmids carrying NDM-1 and OXA-48 genes in *E. coli* MG1655 and other Enterobacterial hosts. In most cases, the tested plasmids had an associated fitness cost to the bacterial host when compared to the growth rate of the same bacteria with no plasmid. In addition, the fitness cost associated with OXA-48 plasmids in *E. coli* MG1655 was slightly lower than the corresponding cost of NDM-1 plasmids, which could also contribute to the increased success of OXA-48 plasmids.

UCM

Fitness and stability experiments of most prevalent *mcr-1*-carrying plasmids from swine and poultry Spanish farms are programmed after completing conjugation assays. Experiments are scheduled to be performed with a broad range of bacterial hosts, including diverse *Enterobacterales* species.

BfR

In this task, selected plasmid types (n=12) were further chosen for fitness and stability tests. Therefore, the *qnr*-carrying isolates were introduced into *E. coli* J53 by transformation or conjugation. The growth performance of the *E. coli* with and without the different *qnr*-plasmid types showed no significant differences. We had also not observed a significant difference in the stability of the plasmids in *E. coli* J53 under selective and non-selective conditions over a time of >150 bacteria generation. Thus, we suppose that the selected *qnr*-carrying plasmids probably had not an influence on the growth of the *E. coli* and will persist without any significant loss over time within its host bacterium. However, up to now we cannot predict any potential influence of the different plasmid types on the fitness and their stability in other Enterobacteriaceae. Based on the results of the conjugation, the majority of the plasmids could be also successfully transferred, but with lower efficacy to other Enterobacteriaceae (i.e. *Klebsiella*, *Morganella*). Further fitness and stability tests need to be done to develop reliable data on this issue.

NVI

Fitness cost and competitive growth of IncI plasmids with ESBL/pAmpC genes from Norwegian broiler production have been performed. We have also investigated the rearrangement of IncI1 shufflons which segment B was interrupted by the transposition unit ISEcp1-blaCTX-M-1-orf477. The study included two IncI1 plasmids (pMLST CC3) harbouring shufflon interrupted by the transposition unit, and a plasmid harbouring uninterrupted, complete shufflon. Plasmids with interrupted shufflons were present in their original hosts and conjugated into an *E. coli* ST162 strain. Liquid single-strain cultures were sampled at four time points during bacterial growth and the shufflon region was PCR amplified and amplicons were subjected ONT sequencing. The interrupted shufflons generated a lower number of shufflon variants in comparison to the uninterrupted shufflon. Segment-loss frequency of the interrupted shufflons was distinctive in different plasmid hosts. In both uninterrupted and interrupted

shufflons, segment A was more favoured to complete partial *pilV* ORF. The study was published in Plasmid.

WP3-T4- Measuring AMR plasmid dissemination in vivo in mouse and Galleria, and chicken and pig in-vitro gut models

UoS

Representative examples of OXA-48 and NDM-1 IncL/M plasmids transferred to *E. coli* MG1655 were used as donors in *Galleria mellonella* conjugation experiments. These studies were performed over a 4h period following injection of 10^7 CFU of donors and recipients into the *Galleria*, separately. Although the differences in transfer rates between both plasmids were not statistically significant due to high variability rates, the frequencies of the OXA-48 plasmid were slightly higher, reinforcing previous findings *in vitro*. Interestingly, in each case, both transfer rates *in vitro* (1 h in LB-agar) and *in vivo* (4h in *Galleria*) were very similar.

Figure X. *In vivo* conjugation frequency of IncL/M plasmids harbouring NDM-1 (PSAP1756) and OXA-48 (POXA48-1). 10^7 CFU of donors (*E. coli* K12 carrying the plasmid) and 10^7 CFU of recipients (*E. coli* K12) were injected into *Galleria mellonella* larvae. Inoculated larvae were incubated for 4 h at 37 °C, euthanised and homogenised. Donor, recipient and transconjugant CFU/ml were selected in plates containing the corresponding antibiotic combinations. Transfer frequency was calculated as the logarithm of transconjugants per recipient.

The *in vivo* mouse work and *in-vitro* gut models could not be performed due to continued restrictions from Covid19 severely impacting the amount of laboratory activities that could be undertaken for this workpackage; therefore Milestone M-AMR2.ARDIG.16 could not be delivered. The WGS pipeline comparison and analysis of isolates collected from both national and longitudinal farm studies by phylogenetics were additional *in silico*, and the laboratory component (i.e. isolation of *E. coli* and WGS) had already been delivered.

WP4. Project coordination and management.

WP4-T1- Steering committee quarterly meeting

Regular tele- and video-conference meetings, and updates by email, have been made to all members in the steering committee within ARDIG.

WP4-T2- Consortium members annual meeting

Due to COVID19 posing restrictions on travel the ARDIG consortium was unable to meet physically for an annual ARDIG meeting in both 2020 and in 2021, where at least one member from each partner organization was expecting to attend. However, an online meeting via Zoom or MS Teams, was successfully held between partners. It provided an opportunity for partners from all WPs to interact and discuss the work being performed in ARDIG.

Previous to 2020, the ARDIG consortium met physically during the OH-EJP ASMs to discuss and review the project, its objectives and deliverables.

ARDIG partners have used telecommunications and video conferencing facilities, to remain in touch. Regular meetings have been held over the past 42 months of this project to ensure the project is progressing well, and to capture any delay which may have resulted, especially due to the impact of COVID19.

WP4-T3- Reporting and communication

Several work package associated subgroup meetings have been held online to provide time for more in-depth discussion between partners.

All ARDIG 9M and 12M reports were submitted in full and in a timely manner. There have been a number of publications, presentations (both oral and poster) from ARDIG partners which has included work performed within ARDIG.

4 Project self-assessment

The ARDIG project has been highly successful; it has been extremely collaborative, completed all major Milestones and Objectives, and partners have delivered a large number of publications, with several still in preparation or under review, despite the setbacks of COVID19. Assessment of each WP individually is given below.

WP1: Most objectives of ARDIG WP1 were achieved. However, we had hoped to collect and analyse a larger range of variables regarding AMR and AMU. Analysis was substantially hampered by a lack of harmonization across systems and within systems across regions and countries. Based on the collection efforts we are now able to better characterize the shortcomings of the current systems from a one health and transnational perspective. This may inform future efforts for more harmonization and support current efforts such as the EARS-Vet proposal.

WP2: The large number of isolates with WGS data available from both retrospective and prospective studies from partner collections has made it possible to perform AMR trend analysis both within and between countries and compartments. This was a key deliverable for ARDIG and such comparisons will help understand how mobile genetic elements may be disseminating. A possible short fall was that not all “vet” partners were able to access the same livestock farm-type or visit farms at the same frequency, which has made it somewhat challenging to compare across the ARDIG dataset. This shortfall was mainly due to budget constraints which meant partners had to incorporate ARDIG Objectives within existing national and/or research studies, in addition to leveraging national co-funding. Nevertheless, comparison of WGS data collected from both human clinical and veterinary settings, has been performed and analysed, as described in Section 2.

WP3: In general, the main objectives of the WP3 were achieved. The performed analyses had also supported the development of routine sequencing in the NRL-AR and bioinformatics analysis for assessment of AMR dynamics in commensal *E. coli*. However, sequence comparisons with different interpretation pipelines showed that further harmonization would be necessary to obtain comparable results at the EU level. Furthermore, the interpretation of *in silico* data without any additional phenotypic or genotypic data can also lead to misinterpretation. In general, the analyses confirmed the suitability of WGS for resistance prediction, but further efforts are necessary to improve interpretation of the observed genes and the genomic association (plasmid vs. chromosome). Studies on the dynamics of plasmids will need further efforts in the future, because of the broad diversity of transmissible plasmid types, which sometimes also differ from region to region and from country to country. Due to the remit of ARDIG being so broad, long read was performed on only a small proportion of isolates with short read data available, so most plasmid genomes remained unresolved. We have therefore developed a machine learning approach to utilise the short read data for plasmid characterisation, which requires further testing in future.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
02	D-1.1	A report of AMR and AMU data (and data collection activities) in livestock and humans in the seven participating countries, and with indication to its quality, comparability and purpose.	M12			Available on One Health EJP Zenodo:Uploaded A publication resulting from this work is available and has already been uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0	
02	D-1.2	Description of the specified AMR prevalence/frequency and AMU at population/country/regional level.	24	25		Available on One Health EJP Zenodo: Uploaded https://zenodo.org/record/5336876#.YURcObgza70	Report; 9
02	D-1.3	A list of the regions identified for in-depth analysis, and a report including the assessments of parallel trends and estimates of potential	24	25		Available on One Health EJP Zenodo: Uploaded Two publications resulting from this work is available and has already been uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0 https://zenodo.org/record/4704208#.YKS6KKgzbY0	Report; 9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		associations between AMR and AMU.					
02	D-1.4	A report of the assessment of risk factors for AMR and AMU	42	42		Available on One Health EJP Zenodo: Uploaded https://zenodo.org/record/5336902#.YURcfLgza70	
02	D-1.5	Recommendations and target zones for improved "One Health" surveillance	42	42		Available on One Health EJP Zenodo: Uploaded https://zenodo.org/record/5416606#.YURcqLgza70	
02	D-JRP2-2.1	Assessment of criteria for inclusion of retrospective and prospective longitudinal studies.	36	42		<p>A questionnaire has been completed by all partners to assess the criteria for inclusion.</p> <p>For both the animal and human isolates that were used from retrospective and prospective studies the criteria was discussed and finalized so comparisons can be made across all datasets available.</p> <p>For the prospective studies for the human isolates the criteria is that the first 20 E. coli isolated from urine from each hospital at each month over a year will be included.</p> <p>There are no criteria for the animal isolates as different livestock and management systems have</p>	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
						been sampled. However, we are evaluating differences and similarities in AMR <i>E. coli</i> given the diverse sample types. One Health EJP: available Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5236699#.YSPSruIUmM9	
02	D-2.2	Assessment of retrospective longitudinal studies and collection of necessary data.				One Health EJP: available https://zenodo.org/record/5236764#.YSPU1eIUmM8	
02	D-2.3	A project isolates database accessible to all member of the consortium	24			As part of WP2 and WP3, a hub has been created at WBVR for depositing WGS data for analysis across partners, which will also be a database of isolates. The full data set of 3812 <i>E. coli</i> will become accessible on publication, but WGS of many isolates are already available through the publications listed in D-2.4 (below).	
02	D-2.4	Data analysis of all collected isolates on a national level.	42	42		Various national studies have been performed. These have been published in various manuscripts and are available also through Zenodo (see links below).	

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						They are: https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70 https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAqc_uhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAqkH-hKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4981248 https://zenodo.org/record/4981351	
02	D-2.5	Comparative analysis of results from the various national studies.	42	42		A manuscript is currently being prepared which compares the individual/country level WGS of isolates from the national studies (D-2.4), as detailed in WP3 T1 and T2. Confidential	
02	D-2.6	Comparative analysis of strains persistence in farms and hospital through longitudinal studies	42	42		This task has been completed and phylogenetic analysis has been performed for comparison across partners or geography, and different compartments (humans/livestock) to detect possible clonal transmission. Details of the work performed by partners for D-2.6 is given in WP2, and in WP3-T1 and T2. Confidential	

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02	D-3.1	Prevalent AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria from humans, animals, food and environment.	20	42		<p>All partners have assessed and are reporting on the AMR gene content of their isolates, especially those already collected in prospective studies and from historical collections. Following a workshop in 2019 to harmonise AMR gene analysis within ARDIG, we have used the ResFinder pipeline to look at AMR content across sectors, although partners have reported used their preferred pipeline on collections from their own dataset.</p> <p>The publications have been uploaded to Zenodo and include those already given for D-2.4: https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70 https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAqc_uhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAqkH-hKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4981248 https://zenodo.org/record/4981351</p>	
02	D-3.2.	Circulating plasmids in humans, animals, food and environment	24	42		<p>Partners have assessed plasmids and mobile elements harbouring AMR genes, including their fitness, as detailed in WP3-T2 and T3.</p> <p>This has resulted in a number of publications, which have already been uploaded to Zenodo. These are:</p>	

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						https://zenodo.org/record/3730621#.Xn3MyYhKi70 https://zenodo.org/record/4475507#.YBKNvOhKhM0 https://zenodo.org/record/3701226#.YAqeSehKjcc	
02	D 3.3.	Predictive modelling of plasmid spread	42	42		Presence and transmission of AMR plasmids are being considered across different compartments. https://zenodo.org/record/4964345 https://zenodo.org/record/4244116#.X6KBDjiWxM0 https://zenodo.org/record/5506463#.YUBKk50zaUk	
02	D-3.4	Validation of plasmid AMR threats in animal models	42	42		Presence of AMR plasmids harbouring OXA-48 and NDM-1 could increase the “threat” of AMR. This theory was tested using a <i>Galleria mellonella</i> model and details are provided in WP3-T4. A study was also performed to look at the association of gut microbiome in calves with antibiotic treatments. https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc	

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02	D-4.2	Annual communication to stakeholders	24	42		The stakeholder is aware of the work being performed and will receive a copy of the final report.	
02	D-4.3	Annual communication to stakeholders	42	42		The stakeholder is aware of the work being performed and will receive a copy of the final report.	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
02	M-JRP2-1	Two datasets on (1) AMR and (2) AB usage of the six participating countries.	12	Yes		
02	M-JRP2-2	Assessment of retrospective longitudinal studies and collection of necessary data.	12	Yes		
02	M-JRP2-3	Preliminary molecular characterization of AMR genes from isolates collected in WP1 and WP2.	12	Yes		
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.4	Identification of MDR isolates circulating in humans, animals, food and environment	24	Yes		<p>An assessment has been made by partners of common MDR isolates circulating within the different regions/countries. Based on this assessment partners have agreed to look in more details at the WGS of different E. coli STs collected from partner institutes.</p> <p>In addition, the profiles of >3000 AMR isolates, is being analysed to identify common factors associated with MDR.</p>
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.5	Assessment of AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria collected from humans, animals, food and environment.	24	Yes		<p>With WP1 AMR phenotypes have been correlated with AMU at regional or country level. Details are provided in D-JRP2-1.2 and 1.3.</p>

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.6	Assessment of AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria collected from humans, animals, food and environment.	18	Yes		All partners have started molecular characterisation of isolates. WP3 provides details of the work. An ARDIG workshop was undertaken and differences between AMR gene analysis identified. The five pipelines used by partners will be compared to each other using WGS data from the same set of 500 isolates.
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.7	Identification of circulating plasmids in humans, animals, food and environment	24	Yes		An assessment has been made by partners of some of the most common circulating plasmids within the different regions/countries. Based on this assessment partners have agreed to look in more details at the genomes of a number of different E. coli ST plasmids collected from partner institutes.
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.8	Assessment of ecological and management factors associated with AMR and Antimicrobial usage (from WP1)	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see Task 1).
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.9	Recommendation for improved One Health surveillance	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP1)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.10	Collecting of samples and veterinary data, phenotypical testing of	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see Task 1).

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		resistant isolates from farms and slaughterhouses.				
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.11	Collecting of samples and clinical data, phenotypical testing of resistant isolates from hospitals and care homes.	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP2)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.12	Data analysis of all collected isolates on a national level.	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP2 and 3)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.13	Comparative analysis of results from the various national studies (WP2).	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP2)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.14	Identification of plasmid and host chromosome factors that determine plasmid stability, spread, and adaptation to new bacterial hosts and conditions.	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP3)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.15	Identification the host factors that influence plasmid-host adaptation and conjugation rates using animal models	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP3)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.16	Identification of plasmid-modifications and effects on the resident microbiota through WGS.	42	No		This work was to be completed in WP3 T5 but as laboratory experiments were severely impacted by COVID19 in 2020 and 2021, when this work was planned.

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries. 10.2147/IDR.S237038 https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0	Yes	Gold	2590 €
Stepwise evolution and convergent recombination underlie the global dissemination of carbapenemase-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> . https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-019-0699-6 https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70	Yes	Gold	2656 €
Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization via Multicopy Plasmid Encapsidation mediated by temperate phages. https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa311 https://zenodo.org/record/4244116#.X6KBDjiWxM0	Yes	Gold	2590 €
The shuffling of IncI1 plasmids is rearranged constantly during different growth conditions 10.1016/j.plasmid.2019.03.003 https://zenodo.org/record/3730621#.Xn3MyYhKi70	Yes	Gold	2590 €
The importance of using whole genome sequencing and extended spectrum beta-lactamase selective media when monitoring antimicrobial resistance. https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-020-76877-7 https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAcqH-hKjcc	Yes	Gold	1844 €
Antimicrobial Usages and Antimicrobial Resistance in Commensal <i>Escherichia coli</i> From Veal Calves in France: Evolution During the Fattening Process https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00792 https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAcq_uhKjcc	Yes	Gold	2590 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Temporal dynamics of the fecal microbiota in veal calves in a 6-month field trial https://doi.org/10.1186/s42523-020-00052-6 https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAcfnuhKjcc	Yes	Gold	1390 €
Mobile colistin resistance gene mcr-1 detected on an IncI1 plasmid in Escherichia coli from meat https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2020.08.018 https://zenodo.org/record/4475507#.YBKNvOhKhM0	Yes	Gold	1660 €
blaCTX-M-1/IncI1-ly Plasmids Circulating in Escherichia coli From Norwegian Broiler Production Are Related, but Distinguishable https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.00333 https://zenodo.org/record/3701226#.YAcSehKjcc	Yes	Gold	2400 €
Phenotypical antimicrobial resistance data of clinical and non-clinical Escherichia coli from poultry in Germany between 2014 and 2017 https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243772 https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0	Yes	Gold	1695 €
Comparison of Phenotypical Antimicrobial Resistance between Clinical and Non-Clinical E. coli Isolates from Broilers, Turkeys and Calves in Four European Countries 10.3390/microorganisms9040678 https://zenodo.org/record/4704208#.YKS6KKgzbY0	Yes	Gold	1446 €
Clinically Relevant Escherichia coli Isolates from Process Waters and Wastewater of Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses in Germany.	Yes	Gold	2000 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040698 https://zenodo.org/record/4981248			
Outcome of Different Sequencing and Assembly Approaches on the Detection of Plasmids and Localization of Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in Commensal <i>Escherichia coli</i> https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9030598 https://zenodo.org/record/4964345	Yes	Gold	2000 €
Colistin-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae Isolated From Process Waters and Wastewater From German Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.575391 https://zenodo.org/record/4981351	Yes	Gold	2400 €
Phenotypic and Genotypic Properties of Fluoroquinolone-Resistant, <i>qnr</i> -Carrying <i>Escherichia coli</i> Isolated from the German Food Chain in 2017 https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9061308 https://zenodo.org/record/5501918	Yes	Gold	2000 €
Horsing around: <i>Escherichia coli</i> ST1250 of equine origin harbouring epidemic IncHI1/ST9 plasmid with bla CTX-M-1 and an operon for short-chain fructooligosaccharides metabolism DOI: https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.02556-20 https://zenodo.org/record/5506463#.YUBKk50zaUk	Yes	Gold	2396 €

Additional output

2018

Posters

- Juraschek, Katharina; Malorny, Burkhard; Kaesbohrer, Annemarie; Hammerl, Jens A (2018). Influence of mobile genetic elements on the dissemination of important resistance determinants in commensal *Escherichia coli*. In: Doktorandensymposium der FU Berlin. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956225>
- Juraschek, Katharina; Shamoun, Dina; Schmogger, Silvia; Irrgang, Alexandra; Grobbel, Mirja; Käsbohrer, Annemarie, Tenhagen, Bernd-Alois; Hammerl, Jens A (2018). A predominant ColE-

plasmid prototype is associated with dissemination of the *mcr-4* resistance gene in German *E. coli* isolates from food and livestock. National Symposium on Zoonoses Research. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956247>

Oral presentations

- K. Juraschek, B. Malorny, A. Käsbohrer und J. A. Hammerl (2018). Influence of mobile genetic elements on the dissemination of important resistance determinants in commensal *Escherichia coli*. In: Pre-Doc Symposium des BfR. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956287>

2019

Posters

- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Surveillance and monitoring systems for antimicrobial usage in livestock animals in six European countries. In: Quantification, Benchmarking and Stewardship of Veterinary Antimicrobial Usage (AACTING) 2nd International Conference, Bern, Switzerland. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4785050>
- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Evidences of overlapping between antimicrobial resistance and drug usage surveillance and monitoring systems in the Human, Animal and Food Sectors in European countries. In: Zoonosen symposium, Berlin, Germany. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4785061>
- K. Juraschek, M. Borowiak, D. Shamoun, S. Schmoger, A. Irrgang, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B. Malorny und J.A. Hammerl (2019). Isolation and characterization of a novel *mcr-5* carrying *Escherichia coli* plasmid from chicken feces in Germany. In: 29th European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Disease (ECCMID). Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956484>
- K. Juraschek, C. Jäckel, C. Banyai, K. Nöckler, J. Beutlich, A. Käsbohrer und J.A. Hammerl (2019). Characterization of *qnr*-plasmids from *M. morganii* isolates of various sources. In: 29th European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Disease (ECCMID). Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956584>
- K. Juraschek, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B.-A. Tenhagen und J.A. Hammerl. Occurrence and commonalities of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food in Germany. In: 29th European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Disease (ECCMID). Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956370>

Oral presentations

- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Reviewing antimicrobial resistance and drug usage surveillance and monitoring systems in the Human, Animal and Food Sector in European countries. In: The 1st One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (Dublin, Ireland). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4786827>
- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Reviewing antimicrobial resistance and drug usage surveillance and monitoring systems in the Human, Animal and Food Sector in European countries. In: The Predoc symposium (Berlin, Germany). Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4944270>
- K. Juraschek, S. Krekow, N. Pauly, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer und J.A. Hammerl (2019). Comparison of Plasmid-Mediated Quinolone Resistance in *Escherichia coli* Isolates from Bovine and Swine Origin Recovered from Livestock and Food in Germany. In: 1st Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Food-Borne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956663>
- K. Juraschek, B. Malorny, D. Meemken, S. Schwarz, A. Kaesbohrer, J.A. Hammerl (2019). Influence of mobile genetic elements on the dissemination of important resistance

determinants in commensale *Escherichia coli*. In: Junior Scientist Zoonose Meeting Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956734>

- K. Juraschek, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B.-A. Tenhagen, J.A. Hammerl (2019). Occurrence and commonalities of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food in Germany. In: DRS Doktorandensymposium. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956773>
- K. Juraschek, C. Jäckel, C. Banyai, S. Schmogger, T. Skladnikiewicz-Ziemer, B. Lesniewsky, K. Nöckler, J. Beutlich, A. Käsbohrer and J.A. Hammerl (2019). Dissection of a New *qnrD2 M. morganii* Plasmid Isolated from Systematically Diseased Cold-Blooded Amphibians. In: The International Symposium on Zoonoses Research. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956847>
- Katharina Juraschek (2019). WGS mit der PB SMRT Technologie. In: Abteilungskolloquium. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956855>
- K. Juraschek, S. Krekow, N. Pauly, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, J.A. Hammerl (2019). Comparison of Plasmid-Mediated Quinolone Resistance in *Escherichia coli* Isolates from Livestock and Food in Germany. In: BfR-PreDoc Symposium. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956899>

2020

Posters

Oral presentations

- Mesa-Varona O., Mader, R. Jarrige N., Granier S-A., Perrin A., Jouy E., Chauvin C., Kaspar H., Anjum M., Grobbel M., Velasova M. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Phenotypic antimicrobial resistance in *Escherichia coli* strains on clinical and non-clinical isolates from broilers in Germany, France and United Kingdom. In: The 2nd One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (Prague, Czech Republic). Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/deposit/4787487>
- Velasova M., Smith R., Chaintarli K., Mesa-Varona O., Tenhagen B-A., Kaspar H., Mader R., Amat J-P., Madec J-Y. and Anjum M-A (2020): Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* isolates originating from diagnostic submissions from veterinary scanning surveillance in UK, Germany and France from 2014 to 2017. In: The 2nd One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (Prague, Czech Republic). Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4786343>
- Mesa-Varona O., Mader, R. Granier S-A., Perrin A., Jouy E., Madec J-Y., Kaspar H., Anjum M., Grobbel M., Velasova M. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Comparison of antibiotic resistance in *Escherichia coli* from clinical diagnostic submissions and isolates of healthy broilers, turkeys and calves from surveillance and monitoring systems in Germany and France. In: the Tenth International Conference on Antimicrobial Agents in Veterinary Medicine (AAVM), Israel. Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4787383>
- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Main outputs of the work package 1 from ARDIG (Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics: the influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment) project. In: The workshop on surveillance/monitoring of AMR and AMU in animals and humans, Berlin. Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4944311>
- K. Juraschek, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B.-A. Tenhagen, J.A. Hammerl (2020). High heterogeneity of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food in Germany. In: 6th Joint Conference of the DGHM & VAAM. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956927>

2021

Poster

- Mesa-Varona O, Tenhagen B-A. Comparison of antimicrobial use and resistance data on clinical and non-clinical isolates from livestock in four countries. In: Junior Scientist Zoonoses Meeting 2021. Virtual. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4905583#.YL3gqvkbY0>
- Mesa-Varona O, Kaspar H, Grobbel M, Tenhagen B-A. The influence of the antimicrobial use in the resistance data on clinical and non-clinical isolates from broilers and turkeys in Germany. In: the 5th International Conference on Responsible Use of Antibiotics in Animals. Virtual. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4916495>

Oral presentation

- Mesa-Varona O., Mader, R. Jarrige N., Granier S-A., Perrin A., Jouy E., Chauvin C., Kaspar H., Anjum M., Grobbel M., Velasova M. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Comparison of antibiotic resistance in Escherichia coli from clinical diagnostic submissions and isolates of healthy broilers, turkeys and calves from surveillance and monitoring systems in Germany and France. In: The Predoc symposium (Berlin, Germany). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4944150>
- Katharina Juraschek, Carlus Deneke, Silvia Schmoeger, Mirjam Grobbel, Burkhard Malorny, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Stefan Schwarz, Diana Meemken and Jens Andre Hammerl (2021). HIGH DIVERSITY OF PLASMIDS CARRYING QNR RESISTANCE GENES IN FLUOROQUINOLONE RESISTANT ESCHERICHIA COLI ISOLATED IN GERMANY IN 2017. In: One Health EJP ASM. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4957003>
- Katharina Juraschek, Maria Borowiak, Simon H. Tausch, Burkhard Malorny, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Saria Otani, Stefan Schwarz, Diana Meemken, Carlus Deneke and Jens Andre Hammerl (2021). DIFFERENT SEQUENCING AND ASSEMBLY APPROACHES INFLUENCING THE DETECTION OF PLASMIDS AND ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE GENES IN COMMENSAL ESCHERICHIA COLI. In: One Health EJP ASM. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4957118>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

It has been evidenced a lack of harmonisation on AMU and AMR across countries, within animals and, therefore, between humans and animal ([10.2147/IDR.S237038](https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S237038)). Higher resistance levels were found in clinical isolates of calves as compared to non-clinical isolates. The opposite was shown in isolates of broilers and turkeys (<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243772>; <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040678>). It is required incentives to harmonise AMU and AMR systems as EFSA had driving the harmonisation of EU data-collection in non-clinical isolates. Otherwise, the One Health approach is not straightforwardly achievable.

If sequencing technologies are used for AMR surveillance, it will provide added value by use of AMR gene mechanisms, transmission of clones and the plasmids that contain the AMR genes. Markers of AMR genes can also be looked at and compared to review prevalence over time, effectively following in the footsteps of Enterobase but expanding upon this. Methods harmonisation of AMR predictions should be considered, as ARDIG has shown some of the common AMR WGS pipelines can vary in their outcomes. Any recommendations made on WGS pipelines should be assessed through the use of EURL.

When performing WGS, ideally all commensal as well as those *E coli* from antibiotic selective plates should be sequenced. However due to the expenses of this work, realistically there needs to be more selective approach which could be that all isolates from antibiotic plates and a subset of commensals are sequenced.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Sales data are collected in Europe providing a general overview on AMU. However, farm-level data are required for further analyses. Some projects, namely ARDIG and AACTING, have provided some suggestions to overcome this issue.

The implementation of the Regulation (EU) No. 6/2019 on veterinary products will allow collecting usage data in a large number of animal categories. This will greatly improve the comparability of data and populations.

Data on non-clinical isolates from livestock is harmonised by the decision 2020/1729/EU. However, except for zoonotic bacteria, there is no harmonisation on clinical isolates. Therefore, there is a lack of harmonisation between clinical and non-clinical isolates from livestock in different aspects. The EU JAMRAI project has proposed to create a European harmonised system on AMR in clinical isolates of animals called EARS-Vet. This project and authors have also suggested antimicrobials panels in clinical isolates.

The outcomes of ARDIG were presented at a workshop (1 and 2 of March 2021) that included experts in the field from EFSA, EMA, ECDC and national governments. Particularly the debate on the data collection systems for antimicrobial use in animals has been supported by the work done in ARDIG.

Bernd-Alois Tenhagen was involved in the preparation of the “3rd Joint Interagency Antimicrobial Consumption and Resistance Analysis (JIACRA) Report” by EFSA, EMA and ECDC and included the findings from ARDIG in his contributions to the report which materialized in ARDIG papers being cited in the report.

Findings were also considered when advising the German Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) on changes in the antibiotics minimization strategy for Germany and when commenting on the foreseen changes in the EU-legislation with respect to the collection of AMU-data in the European Union.

7 One Health impact

The outcomes of ARDIG were presented at a workshop (1 and 2 of March 2021) that included experts in the field from EFSA, EMA, ECDC and national governments. Particularly the debate on the data collection systems for antimicrobial use in animals has been supported by the work done in ARDIG.

A member of the consortium was involved in the preparation of the “3rd Joint Interagency Antimicrobial Consumption and Resistance Analysis (JIACRA) Report” by EFSA, EMA and ECDC to be published in 2021 and included the findings from ARDIG in his contributions to the report which materialized in ARDIG papers being cited in the report.

Collaboration between the animal and medical sector in the field of AMR and AMU was fostered including interaction with other projects such as the German One Health Initiative (GOHI) involving BfR and RKI that worked in related areas. Likewise collaboration between different institutions working on AMR in animals in Germany (BfR and BVL) was further strengthened by the exchange of data and the collaborative analysis of the data.

Recommendations on surveillance of antimicrobial use are also fed into the current German national debate on the further development of the antimicrobial minimization concept.

ARDIG has strengthened the collaboration between institutes involved in the consortium and the mutual understanding of the challenges each institute is facing. Further, an important collaboration has been set up between ARDIG and EU-JAMRAI in discussions on the EARS-Vet project and was also manifested in a collaborative paper (Mesa-Varona et al 2021).

The project forces the development and optimization of WGS techniques in the NRL-AR for routine, which will be further used for *in silico*-based evaluation of the status of isolates from the ESBL-

monitoring. Furthermore, the NRL-AR had successfully established in house pipelines, which are focussed on the evaluation of the resistances and the prediction of their genetic localization. Some of the results were further included in an EJP project of the second round, which is focussing on plasmid finishing and assessment of evolution of mobile genetic elements. The provided sequencing data will be used as a reference for a WGS-based ring trial for harmonization of long read sequencing.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	4	4	4
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	3	4	4
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	4	5	4
Integration	5	3	3
Sustainability	4	4	4
Impact of the project	3	5	3
TOTAL	23/30	25/30	22/30

AVERAGE: 23

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

I agree with the partner's project self-assessment that the ARDIG project has been highly successful; it has been extremely collaborative, completed all major Milestones and Objectives, and partners have delivered a large number of publications, with several still in preparation or under review, despite the setbacks of COVID19. Only one milestone: "Identification of plasmid-modifications and effects on the resident microbiota through WGS" could not be finished. The in vivo mouse work and in-vitro gut models could not be performed, but the WGS pipeline comparison and analysis of isolates collected from both national and longitudinal farm studies by phylogenetics were analysed in silico.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The obtained results seem to be in line with the project objectives as set out. Some objectives were not achieved due to (i) lack of harmonized data (WP1) and (ii) Covid19 (WP3), which I believe is reasonable. As far I could see, the title of the project is not given at all in the final report, only the project the acronym has been given. It could have been good to include it, on the title page for example. Furthermore, the project objectives were not well presented in the final report. I had to extract them from the individual work package evaluations.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The results are well aligned with the project objectives. Substantial achievements have been made by the project partners each in their own (especially animal or human) compartment. Great efforts have been done to characterize AMR genes in human, animal, food and environment isolates and to characterize circulating plasmids and study their transmission dynamics. Comparing data was not easy due to lack of harmonization between isolates of livestock.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project delivered sound and scientifically qualified results with progress beyond the state-of-the-art, although many of them are still under analysis to get a final conclusion. i.e. the interpretation of in silico WGS data without any additional phenotypic or genotypic data can lead to misinterpretation, but the analyses confirmed the suitability of WGS for resistance prediction, however further efforts would be necessary to improve interpretation of the observed genes and the genomic association. Also, many problems have arisen during the project, and a main problem was a lack of harmonization across systems and within systems across regions and countries, but this allowed the consortium to define a number of criteria for future analysis, as for example: AMR in clinical and non-clinical isolates needs to be evaluated separately and preferably both should be collected, and it is necessary to define a harmonised antimicrobial panels.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project delivered results as initially proposed in the project submitted. The whole project benefited from the multi-disciplinary approach of the partners, linking experimental work with the in silico approach for AMR gene prediction.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The results of the project are of excellent scientific quality and state-of-the-art techniques have been used or even further developed and implemented.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The outcomes of ARDIG has been presented at a workshop (March 2021) that included experts in the field from EFSA, EMA, ECDC and national governments, and the debate on the data collection systems for antimicrobial use in animals has been supported. Collaboration between the animal and medical sector in the field of AMR and AMU was fostered including interaction with other projects such as the German One Health Initiative (GOHI). ARDIG has strengthened the collaboration between institutes involved in the consortium and the mutual understanding of the challenges each institute is facing. Further, an important collaboration has been set up between ARDIG and EU-JAMRAI in discussions on the EARS-Vet project.

Recommendations on surveillance of antimicrobial use were also fed into the current German national debate on the further development of the antimicrobial minimization concept.

The project forces the development and optimization of WGS techniques in the NRL-AR for routine, and established in house pipelines focussed on the evaluation of the resistances and the prediction of their genetic localization, which will be further used for in silico-based evaluation of the status of isolates from the ESBL-monitoring.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The progress of the project has been monitored and the project has been managed with physical meetings until 2020 then with online meeting after the pandemic. Package associated subgroup meetings has enabled in-depth discussion between partners. As for dissemination activities, in addition to scientific publications in prestigious journals, oral and poster presentation have been performed. The presentation of the outcomes of ARDIG and the drafted recommendations resulting from ARDIG in the workshop with the participation of experts from EFSA, EMA, ECDC and national governments is an important step for the improvement of “One Health” surveillance strategies.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The management was appropriate. Almost all milestones and objectives have been achieved. Results have been disseminated effectively via several ways: workshops, posters, oral presentations, peer-reviewed scientific publications and through discussion fora with stakeholders. Partners have delivered an impressive number of publications with high scientific impact.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project was completely successful in achieving relevant integrative activities, involving several implementation and discussions (most of them through digital media) for development of harmonised protocols, joint databases, and harmonised surveillance strategies.

A hub has been created at WBVR for depositing WGS data for analysis across partners, which will also be a database of isolates.

The consortium has made big effort to define criteria for both the animal and human isolates that were used from retrospective and prospective studies. The criteria were discussed and finalized so comparisons can be made across all datasets available. For the prospective studies for the human isolates the criteria were that the first 20 E. coli isolated from urine from each hospital at each month over a year will be included, and there were no criteria for the animal isolates as different livestock and management systems. However, they were evaluating differences and similarities in AMR E. coli given the diverse sample types.

All partners have assessed and are reporting on the AMR gene content of their isolates, especially those already collected in prospective studies and from historical collections. Following a workshop in 2019 to harmonise AMR gene analysis within ARDIG, they have used the ResFinder pipeline to look at AMR content across sectors, although partners have reported used their preferred pipeline on collections from their own dataset.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has displayed the importance of harmonization of AMR and AMU data collection, AMR prediction methods and analysis of the data. However, integrative activities could not go much beyond recommendations. The interaction with other project such as the German One Health Initiative (GOHI) involving BfR and RKI has been a positive move towards to establishing collaboration between the animal and medical sector in the field of AMR and AMU.

Reviewer 3: POC member

From the report it is difficult to assess the amount of integration between partners. Most of the work has been done within the compartments (animal, human). Integrative work has been mostly done in WP3 (AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates. Phylogenetic analysis and AMR profiling by partners have helped to identify possible transmission events or epidemiological links between different compartments and countries. Plasmid characterisation

between and across partners, has provided an overview of the types of AMR plasmids commonly circulating.

A lack of harmonisation on AMR was identified within and between countries across the human and animal sectors. Significant dissimilarities were found between data on clinical and non-clinical isolates within animal categories and countries. It was argued that a harmonised antimicrobial panel in clinical isolates and between clinical and non-clinical isolates should be defined. AMU data collection needs further elaboration. It was shown that data comparisons on AMU in health care systems should be done with care due to lack of harmonisation.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Some of the developments achieved by the project will be maintained within the organisations of the consortium. The NRL-AR had successfully established in house pipelines, which are focussed on the evaluation of the resistances and the prediction of their genetic localization. Some of the results were further included in an EJP project of the second round, which is focussing on plasmid finishing and assessment of evolution of mobile genetic elements. The provided sequencing data will be used as a reference for a WGS-based ring trial for harmonization of long read sequencing

As mentioned before, ARDIG has strengthened the collaboration between institutes involved in the consortium and the mutual understanding of the challenges each institute is facing.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

There is no specific statement regarding the maintenance on the developments achieved in the project but I understand that the obtained sources will be maintained and the partners will continue the work with the obtained sources to resolve the genomes of the plasmids that remained unresolved. Thus, they will try to continue the work on the dynamics of the plasmids. The feeding of the recommendations on surveillance of antimicrobial use into the current German national database is also an indication for the endeavor of long-term sustainability.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Based on the experience gained in the project, partners are now able to better characterize the shortcomings of the current AMU and AMR systems from a one health and transnational perspective. This may help establishing future efforts for more harmonization and support current efforts such as the EARS-Vet proposal.

The experience partners gained by their collaborative work in this project will be very useful for further work on AMU and AMR: establishing proper surveillance methods, comparing datasets, trend analysis, understanding dissemination of mobile genetic elements, developing routine sequencing in NRL-AR and bioinformatics analysis.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The impact of the project is it likely to generate a limited effect, and putative secondary effects such as a positive impact on the economy or the environment are very limited.

However, conclusion of the project allowed for a number of results and recommendations that will be useful for future development of the One Health concept:

Decreasing resistance was found in animal isolates between 2014 and 2017. This suggests that measures carried out against AMR including the reduction in AMU in each country have effective results.

WGS of >3000 isolates collected from longitudinal, as well as national surveillance by partners were also compared, and show human isolates generally to be more similar to each other than those from animals, and vice versa.

Phylogenetic analysis and AMR profiling performed by partners on their dataset, as well as across ARDIG, have helped identify possible transmission events or epidemiological links between different compartments and countries.

If sequencing technologies are used for AMR surveillance, it will provide added value by use of AMR gene mechanisms, transmission of clones and the plasmids that contain the AMR genes. Markers of AMR genes can also be looked at and compared to review prevalence over time, effectively following in the footsteps of Enterobase but expanding upon this. Methods harmonisation of AMR predictions should be considered, as ARDIG has shown some of the common AMR WGS pipelines can vary in their outcomes. Any recommendations made on WGS pipelines should be assessed through the use of EURL.

Due to the remit of ARDIG being so broad, long read was performed on only a small proportion of isolates with short read data available, so most plasmid genomes remained unresolved. They have therefore developed a machine learning approach to utilise the short read data for plasmid characterisation, which require further testing in future.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project should have a long-term impact. It underlines the essentiality of harmonization of data collection, of methods used and of analysis to understand spread of AMR in different populations in different settings and to regulate AMUage. It will definitely affect and shape related regulations to prevent spread of AMR.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The outcomes of the project were presented at a workshop including experts from EFSA, EMA, ECDC and national governments. Recommendations were made for improved 'One Health' surveillance strategies.

Some members of the consortium were involved in the preparation of the 3rd Joint Interagency Antimicrobial Consumption and Resistance Analysis report by EFSA, EMA and ECDC.

Collaboration between different institutions working on AMR in animals in Germany was strengthened.

The project has strengthened the collaboration between institutes involved in the consortium.

An important collaboration has been set up between the project and EU-JAMRAI in discussions on EARS-Vet project.

JRP03-RADAR

Final report

1 Consortium composition

Coordinator:

RIVM; Dr. Eelco Franz, Head of Department Epidemiology and Surveillance of Gastroenteritis and Zoonoses, Centre for Infectious Disease Control, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). P.O. Box 1, 3720 BA Bilthoven, the Netherlands, Email: eelco.franz@rivm.nl, Tel.: +31 30 2747063 / +31 6 15502479

Deputy Coordinator:

DTU; Prof. dr. Tine Hald, Research Leader of Epidemiology and Risk Modeling, National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Technical University of Denmark, Søtofts Plads, Building 221, room 163, 2800 Kgs. Lyngby. Email: tiha@food.dtu.dk

Other Applicants:

Netherlands

WBVR (former CVI): Thomas Hagens

NCOH (UMCU): Martin Bootsma

Germany

BfR-33: Thomas Sellhorst,

BfR-43: Annemarie Kaesbohrer

Italy:

ISS: Luca Busani, Annalisa Pantosti

United Kingdom:

APHA: Robin Simons, Emma Snary

Norway:

NVI: Madelaine Norstrom, Camilla Sekse

France:

ANSES : Pierre-Emmanuel Douarre

CVs of each participating key scientists

Coordination Team

The project will be coordinated in cooperation between Dr. Eelco Franz (RIVM) and Dr. Tine Hald (DTU). Both coordinators and their respective institutes have a background in risk modelling, disease burden studies, AMR, and involvement international collaborative research.

RIVM - Coordinator

Dr. E. (Eelco) Franz (male). Studied Biology at University Utrecht (Utrecht, The Netherlands) (2002, specialization population biology) and conducted PhD (2007) at Wageningen University (Wageningen,

The Netherlands) in microbial risk assessment. From 2007-2010 he worked as junior researcher at the RIKILT – Institute for Food Safety (Wageningen, The Netherlands). From 2010 he worked at the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM, Bilthoven, The Netherlands). First at the department of Food Safety (part of the Centre for Zoonoses and Environmental Microbiology). Per September 2016 he is head of the department “Epidemiology and Surveillance of Gastroenteritis and Zoonoses” (part of the Centre for Surveillance and Epidemiology of Infectious Diseases). His responsibility is to maintain and further improve the surveillance and outbreak control of gastrointestinal pathogens and to conduct relevant epidemiological research on gastroenteritis and zoonotic diseases.

DTU - Deputy Coordinator

Prof. Tine Hald (female) is a trained quantitative epidemiologist holding a PhD degree in veterinary epidemiology. In 2016, Tine took on a professorship in translational epidemiology.

Work is focused on research and development of mathematical models for explaining the transmission and assessing the burden of zoonoses and foodborne diseases, including methods for identifying and prioritizing interventions. Tine has been pioneering the international development and application of methods for source attribution of foodborne diseases. Tine is currently involved in two EU research projects, COMPARE (H2020 GA no. 643476) and EFFORT (FP7 GA no. 613754) and a core member of the World Health Organisations’ (WHO) Foodborne disease Epidemiology Reference Group (FERG). From 2009-2015, Tine was a member of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) expert panel on biological hazards (BIOHAZ). A main responsibility is to give scientifically-based advice to veterinary and food authorities, farmers’ and consumers organisations, and international organisations e.g. EFSA and WHO.

Project Consortium

The project consortium is a diverse group of international experts in A multidisciplinary team of researchers combining expertise in animal science, epidemiology, food and environmental microbiology, molecular biology, bioinformatics and risk assessment modelling from 7 European countries and 9 institutes.

Netherlands

WBVR (former CVI)

Thomas Hagenaars. Thomas Hagenaars obtained a PhD in theoretical physics at Utrecht University in 1995. During subsequent postdoctoral periods at Oxford University and Imperial College London he turned into an infectious-disease epidemiologist specialized in mathematical modelling. Since 2003 he is a senior researcher at Wageningen Bioveterinary Research in Lelystad, where he applies modern quantitative methods to address questions about disease transmission and control relevant to veterinary policy making and public health.

NCOH-UMCU

Martin Bootsma. He obtained his master in theoretical physics (cum laude) and mathematics from Utrecht University. He obtained his PhD on the thesis ‘mathematical studies of the dynamics of antibiotic resistance’ in 2005. Afterwards he worked at the department of infectious disease epidemiology of Imperial College London for 1 year. Since then he is employed by the mathematics department of Utrecht University and the *Julius Center* for Health Sciences and *Primary Care* of the University Medical Center Utrecht. His research interest are mathematical and statistical models to obtain insight in the dynamics of antimicrobial resistance.

Germany

BfR

Thomas Selhorst (male) studied agriculture with specialization in animal science. He has an PhD in agriculture with specialization in plant pest epidemiology and biological control (1989). In 1997 he received the *venia legendi* for Theoretical Ecology. The habilitation thesis was awarded the *Oce van*

der Grinten award for exceptional research in environmental sciences. His research focused on Epidemiological Modelling and the development of efficient strategies for a) Rabies control in Germany (until rabies free status in 2006), for risk analysis focussing on BSE, avian influenza and bovine virus diarrhoea. In the last year he focused on epidemic spread on trade networks and the

Annemarie Käsbohrer (female) is veterinarian with specialisation in microbiology and epidemiology. Since 2006, she is Head of Unit for Epidemiology, Zoonoses and Antimicrobial resistance at the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment. In addition, since April 2016 she is professor and head of institute for Veterinary Public Health at the Veterinary University in Vienna. She has very much expertise in the areas monitoring and surveillance of zoonotic pathogens in the food chain; collection and analysis of data related to antimicrobial consumption in livestock; the epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance and the impact of risk factors on the spread of resistance determinants; development and validation of epidemiological models; exposure assessment of zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance. She is head of the National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance in Germany.

Robert Opitz studied biophysics at the Humboldt University of Berlin, and in 2012 completed his PhD in drug design at the Leibniz Institute for Molecular Pharmacology and the Free University of Berlin, where he also worked as a postdoc. Throughout this time, he was able to gain a wide range of experience in the field of modelling and statistical analysis, which eventually led him to machine learning. After a brief interlude at EMBL, in Heidelberg, he has been working at the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment in Berlin since 2018.

United Kingdom

APHA

Dr. Robin Simons (male) is a senior risk analyst at APHA, primarily responsible for planning, design and leadership of research projects, developing qualitative and quantitative risk assessment models and production and dissemination of reports and scientific publications. Robin has been at the APHA since 2006 and worked on a range of pathogens, most recently working on interdisciplinary projects involving ESBL E. coli in the dairy industry, developing models examining the risk of feeding waste milk to dairy calves and the risk of human exposure to ESBL E. coli via raw milk consumption. Robin has been involved in a number of previous EU projects; he was responsible for developing the Transport & Lairage model for an EFSA project to develop a generic farm-to-consumption risk assessment for Salmonella in pigs, more recently he was responsible for the delivery of the APHA risk assessment work in WP13 of the ANTIGONE project and is currently a workpackage lead for the aniwah funded project SPARE. Robin has also led a number of national projects, including a project for FSA Scotland to develop a qualitative risk assessment for the microbiological risks to consumers from the consumption of small game birds for which he wrote the proposal. Prior to starting at the APHA, Robin completed his PhD at the University of Surrey, UK, which involved modelling the phenomenon of blowfly strikes using delay differential equations.

Norway

NVI

Madelaine Norström (female) (DVM, PhD) is a senior researcher in epidemiology at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute. She has a large experience in design and sampling strategies and is a key person in data management at the dep. of epidemiology. She is working with surveillance and in particular the Norwegian monitoring program of antimicrobial resistance in feed, food and animals (NORM-VET). Her key areas of research are antimicrobial resistance, infectious diseases, spatial analyses and modelling of transmission. She has supervised Master and PhD students and been reviewer for several scientific journals.

Camilla Sekse (female), PhD, Cand.Scient, is a senior scientist in bacteriology at NVI. She has worked for 13 years with bacteriology, in particular pathogenic *E. coli* (STEC, aEPEC) with characterization,

molecular typing and recently high throughput sequencing. She has been involved in several research projects including the ongoing EU-project; DECATHLON in FP7 and national research projects focusing on pathogenic and antibiotic resistant *E. coli*. Her current leading roles include WP and task leader in the national project “Quinolone resistant *E. coli* in Norwegian poultry and their impact on humans” in the WP focusing on comparison of human and poultry isolates. She is task leader for two tasks;” WGS and sequence assembly” and “Comparative genome analyses of a subset of isolates”. Camilla is partly responsible for the National Reference Laboratory of pathogenic *E. coli* and has been involved in surveillance programs for pathogenic *E. coli* in sheep and cattle. She has 18 publications according to WoS with an *h*-index of 9.

France

ANSES

Dr Michel-Yves Mistou (male) (M, 54 y/o, PhD Biochemistry, HDR), initial research experiences in France (Ecole Polytechnique, Palaiseau) and Germany (Max Planck Institute, Heidelberg) were in the enzymology and structural biology field. Hired by the French national institute for agronomical research (INRA, Jouy-en-Josas), he developed research projects in bacterial genetics applied to food science. He then moved for 5 years at the Pasteur Institute studying virulence factors of streptococci by combined genetic and mass-spectrometry approaches. In 2009, he co-founded with M.P Chapot-Chartier a research group in the MICALIS (Microbiology Applied to Human health) Institute (INRA) dedicated to genetic and biochemistry of the cell wall of Gram-positive bacteria. In 2014, he is hired by ANSES, the French public agency that undertakes research and reference missions in human, animal and plant health fields. He is the head of the Microbiology department where he drives a change management strategy toward the development of NGS technologies.

Pierre-Emmanuel Douarre: Pierre-Emmanuel (PE) is a microbiologist that specialized in bacterial genomics. PE obtained his PhD in Ireland in 2010 based on his research on the characterization of the pathogen *Mycobacterium paratuberculosis*. He then performed a 3 years postdoctoral project in the Institut Pasteur analysing the evolution and the ATB resistance genotypes of group B streptococcus (GBS). PE continued working on GBS for two years in a microfluidic-based start-up, on the development of an ultrafast multiplex PCR. He joined the Food Safety Laboratory in ANSES in 2018 to work on the EJP project "RADAR" which aimed to identify and characterize the plasmidome of bacterial species and more specifically *Salmonella enterica*. During his career, PE developed a strong set of skills in microbiology, molecular biology & bioinformatics and his research activities now focus on microbial genomics. He just integrated the research team of the *Salmonella & Listeria* Unit to perform genomic analysis to better characterize these two pathogens.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Antimicrobial resistance threatens the effective prevention and treatment of an ever increasing range of infections. It is an increasingly serious threat to global public health that requires action across all government sectors and society. Assessment of the importance of different transmission routes and quantifying public health effects (i.e. disease burden) associated with AMR represent major knowledge gaps. The RADAR project contributed significantly to filling these data gaps by producing and harmonizing modelling methodology and frameworks specifically for AMR related problems. A diverse group of international experts in epidemiology, molecular biology, transmission modelling, risk modelling, and disease burden modelling was brought together in the RADAR consortium.

This project achieved its goals in a multi-disciplinary and One Health approach with partners of different expertise (microbiology, epidemiology, risk assessment) and from different domains (public health, veterinary health, food safety). RADAR delivered some interesting and potential useful tools and insights.

1. We delivered a large-scale curated database of (AMR) plasmids from a range of different bacterial species and sources (“COMPASS”, Douarre 2020 *Frontiers in Microbiology*). This

novel resource will help researchers understand the genetic plasticity and transmission routes of plasmids, which are crucial in the fight against the spread of antimicrobial resistant pathogens.. The database is available at <https://github.com/itsmeludo/COMPASS>

2. We provided an infrastructure for exchanging and annotating risk assessment models in an exchangeable and reproducible file format called FSK and key or desirable features that facilitate access and usability of the inventory (<https://ejp-radar.eu/>).
3. We produced state-of-the-art AMR risk assessment models for different food chains in a generic framework. These generic methods may be more crude, but will allow for combining the risks in the different (sub-)categories and may thus help to create a more complete picture of the AMR problems throughout.
4. We produced a framework for the use of machine-learning methods in AMR risk assessment in order to identify risk factors from high-dimensional data with more variables than data points and/or categorical features with many classes.
5. We designed a new burden of disease (BoD) approach suitable for estimating the excess BoD associated with AMR bacterial infection. By 'excess BoD' we mean mortality and morbidity (computed as DALY) associated with resistance, over and above the mortality and morbidity associated with the same – but antimicrobial-susceptible – bacterial infection.
6. We produced a One-Health source attribution model that estimates the relative contribution of reservoirs and transmission routes to AMR (ESBL E. coli) carriership in the population. We adopted established source attribution methods for zoonotic pathogens for specific use for AMR (mainly by introducing humans not only as an endpoint but also as a source).
7. We studied a new paradigm for AMR surveillance based on metagenomics where we showed that metagenomic surveillance is a suitable methodology for population based surveillance of AMR and observed that AMU and AMR are in general correlated both at phenotypic and genotypic levels, but also that other factors play a role in the abundances of AMR.
8. Finally, we developed and applied a Bayesian Evidence Synthesis (BES) approach to integrate all available data and information by combining all relevant data with a priori knowledge and thereby eventually infer estimates on prevalence/incidence of AMR infections / carriership.

3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WPO. Coordination and communication (M1-M30)

JRP3-WP0-T1: Coordination and project management (M1-M30)

Regular meetings with WP leaders were organized throughout the duration of the project. During this meetings the list of milestones and deliverables (incl. the timelines) were systematically discussed.

JRP3-WP0-T2: Consortium meetings (M1-M30)

The project has seen three physical meetings: the kick-off meeting (Schiphol airport), a half-way meeting (Schiphol airport), and a meeting towards the end of the project (BfR Berlin). During the extension period from Jan to Dec 2020 no physical meetings were organized due to the COVID19 crisis. Regular phonecalls between the project management and WP leaders took place.

JRP3-WP0-T2-ST1: Kick-off meeting

January 2018 Schiphol Airport, The Netherlands. Important first alignments and directions were consolidated.

JRP3-WP0-T2-ST2: Mid-term meeting (M10-M12)

Held January 18th Schiphol Airport, The Netherlands. Scientific progress was presented and discussed. Good agreements for WP alignments were made.

JRP3-WP0-T2-ST3 Final meeting (M30-M30)

Due to the corona crisis it no final meeting took place. Discussions are still ongoing to organize an OH EJP AMR workshop in summer 2021 in combination with other AMR projects.

JRP3-WP0-T3: Annual reports (M1-M30)

JRP3-WP0-T3-ST1: First annual report (M10-M12)

Completed.

JRP3-WP0-T3-ST2 Second annual report (M22-M24)

Completed.

JRP3-WP0-T3-ST3 Third annual report (M28-M30)

This is the final report presented here.

WP1. New genomic information to feed AMR transmission models (M1-M30)

JRP3-WP1-T1: Build collections of high throughput sequencing (HTS) data needed for project- specific milestones and deliverables (M1-M15)

Sub-Task 1.1.1: Plasmids are the keystone of horizontal gene transfer in bacteria and are of major clinical interest due to their contribution to the dissemination of antibiotic resistance genes. As the number of plasmid sequences in public databases is growing exponentially, the creation of a comprehensive and curated complete plasmid database is critical to capitalize on the available data and provide an exhaustive library for the scientist community.

Here, we have compiled and curated a dataset of complete plasmid sequences with associated metadata sourced from the NCBI database. The resultant database contains 12084 plasmid records that have been analysed and summarized using R and online tools such as Gunmap 2 and Krona. Resistance genes acquisitions were identified by BLASTn search against the ResFinder database.

The plasmid database encloses 1564 distinct species, 443 genera, 189 families, 93 orders, 38 classes and 21 phyla. Proteobacteria (66%) and Firmicutes (21%) are the most represented phyla and 38% of the bacterial species belong to the Enterobacteriaceae family. The vast majority of the plasmids (94.5%) are circular and with sizes ranging from 744 bp to 2 555 069 bp. Plasmids were isolated in 126 different countries from 1884 to 2018. In total, 13812 resistance genes were detected among the 12 084 plasmids and they included 503 different resistance variants. From our dataset, we found that 3438 plasmids (28%) carry at least one resistant gene and resistance to beta-lactams, aminoglycosides and sulphonamides are the most frequent. Among these resistant plasmids, 41% are multi-resistant of which 80% were isolated from Enterobacteria.

This curated plasmid database can be easily integrated, as a reference, into pipelines aiming at identifying new plasmids, thus enabling the exploration of the metadata of all complete plasmids in the NCBI database, in light of their predicted antibiotic resistance. This novel resource will help researchers and clinicians understand the genetic plasticity and transmission routes of plasmids, which are crucial in the fight against the spread of antimicrobial resistant pathogens.

This curated plasmid database was integrated, as a reference, into our new developed pipelines (**JRP3-WP1-T2**) aiming at identifying plasmids from sequencing data. This novel resource will help researchers

and clinicians understand the genetic plasticity and transmission routes of plasmids, which are crucial in the fight against the spread of antimicrobial resistant pathogens.

The database was named “Compass” and was published in **Frontiers in Microbiology (Dourarre 2020, *Frontier in Microb.* 24 march 2020)**. See fig.1. for a visual description of the database. The database is available at <https://github.com/itsmeludo/COMPASS>.

Sub-Task 1.1.2: New environmental genomic datasets relevant to various AMR challenges have also been collected and organized in a database for future study. These datasets include: 1) Salmonella surveillance network (2000-2016) from all food, animal and environmental sectors, a total of **2839 isolates**. This dataset have a particular focus on fluoroquinolone resistance and the plasmidome, 2) Quinolone resistant E. coli (QREC) from animals (poultry, pigs, wild birds, foxes) in Norway, 3) Cephalosporin resistant E.coli (containing blaCMY-2) from poultry in Norway, 4) the pig faecal metagenomics data collection obtained in the frame of the EFFORT H2020 project (<https://academic.oup.com/jac/article/74/4/865/5289505> ; ENA: PRJEB22062), 5) The metagenomics dataset of urban sewages under the H2020 COMPARE project (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08853-3>).

Fig. 1. Description of the COMPASS database. (A) Violin plot displaying plasmid size distribution (log10) among the main phyla (n=12 084). The phylum entitled “Other” is composed of 57 plasmids from 12 minority phyla (n<25) and 129 plasmids missing taxonomy data. (B) Krona plot showing the compositions of taxa and taxonomic ranks (n=12 084).

JRP3-WP1-T2: Develop an innovative automated bioinformatic pipeline integrating de novo plasmid reconstruction and identification (M1-M18)

Identifying and tracking circulating plasmids is heavily relying on the ability to accurately assemble their whole genome sequences and differentiate chromosomal from plasmid contigs. Even though several bioinformatics tools can be applied to reconstruct plasmid sequences from short reads, a contiguous assembly is still difficult to obtain. Plasmid *de novo* assembly based from the coverage and the assembly graph was first perform by SPAdes. In order to assess the performance of different

plasmid detection tools, we built a “test dataset” composed of 56 known genomes of *Salmonella enterica* (Chromosome and plasmids) and tested against MOBrecon, PlaScope, Plasflow and HyAsP programs. Our COMPASS database was integrated in the detection tools as a reference database to help discerning the plasmids contigs from the chromosomal sequences and to identify the closest plasmid neighbour present in COMPASS. Core plasmid genes necessary for replication (replicon) and mobilization (Relaxase, MPF and *oriT*) were annotated by the MOBtyper program from the MOBsuite package and the plasmid resistome was characterized in silico by detecting resistance genes of the Resfinder database. Finally, we developed an automated plasmid identification pipeline by integrating plasmid assembly (SPADES) and detection programs (PlaScope), annotation tools (MOBtyper and Resfinder) and reference-based identification (Mash program against the COMPASS database) (Fig. 2).

The outputs of the pipeline (plasmid contigs / genes and resistance genes) were designed for handling by microbiologists and modelers to facilitate biological interpretation and integration into transmission models. Following the validation of our pipeline on the “test dataset”, our novel plasmid tool was used to detect and identify plasmids from the new environmental datasets collected in (T1 subtask 1.2).

Fig. 2. Scheme of the automated plasmid identification pipeline (described below) by integrating plasmid assembly (SPADES) and detection programs (PlaScope), annotation tools (MOBtyper and Resfinder) and reference-based identification (Mash program against reference database).

JRP3-WP1-T3: Plasmidome: biological annotation and risk assessment (M12-M24)

We used the pipeline we developed in JRP3-WP1-T2 to characterize the plasmidome of 3109 genomes of *Salmonella enterica* strains isolated from all food, animal and environmental sectors (ANSES collection). We successfully identified and reconstructed 2776 plasmids, which were categorized into 242 clusters. Replicon and MOB types identified a diverse population of plasmids. The resistome and the virulome were characterized in all the plasmids and compared within different serovars. Our results suggest that resistant plasmids are shared among different serovars while virulent plasmid (like the pSLT) were restricted to few serovars.

JRP3-WP1-T4: Methods to identify genetic traits associated to AMR (M12-M24)

Genome Wide Association Studies (GWAS) are hypothesis-free methods for identifying genetic variations associated with particular phenotypic traits within a population. Microbial genome-wide association studies (mGWAS) are a new and exciting research field that is adapting human GWAS methods to understand how variations in microbial genomes affect host or pathogen phenotypes.

Given the availability of large panels of bacterial genomes combined with phenotypic data in public databases, GWAS have shown promising results for genetic marker discovery and as emerged as a fundamental task in bacterial genomics. To determine best practices for microbial GWAS, it is essential to compare current GWAS methods in terms of their performance across a range of realistic effect sizes, recombination rates and sample sizes. With the growing number of different GWAS softwares available, the choice of tool, methods or workflows presents a major challenge to biologists. Here we present in Table 1 a summary of bioinformatics tools and pipelines available for microbial GWAS and highlight their advantages and limitations. We made an overview of different mGWAS methods (see deliverable 1.4.1 and 1.4.2, combined).

WP2. Pharmacodynamics and transmission models (M1-M24)

JRP3-WP2-T1: On-farm transmission models (M1-M24)

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST1: PK/PD model to assess relationship between animal exposure and change in antimicrobial resistance (M1-M20)

The goal of this work was to refine and develop a “within-host PKPD model” (hereafter simplified as PKPD model) to assess and predict the impact of an AMD treatment (as an input of the model) on the emergence/selection of resistant bacteria within guts and excretion towards faeces (output of the model) for pig, at the individual level and population level (taking into account the inter-individual variability). The PKPD models initially developed for colistin (with a “simple” intestinal Pharmacokinetic) allowed us to identify key points for the development of a PKPD model for amoxicillin and ESBL *E. coli* (**Fig. 3**).

This work highlighted the different tools and methods that exist but also the numerous gaps to develop a mechanistic PKPD model of antimicrobial resistance within guts. Our work outlined the relative importance of the inherent variability of each PK and PD sub-levels for the understanding of the evolution of bacterial populations toward resistance development/selection after a perturbation due to an AMD. The influence of specific bacterial parameters on the plasmid dynamism and its influence on the selection, maintenance or disappearance of resistance could be independent of the initial exposition.

This work outlined that the mechanistic modelling of the digestive tract is still challenging and should be improved but will probably need additional data. Some very mechanistic models of digestion and food transit have already been published but are sometimes theoretical with parameters values not based on experimental measures. The complexity of such model will definitively need inter-disciplinary approach combining mathematicians and pharmacologist/biologists.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram for the proposed Pharmacodynamic model.

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST2: Assess relative importance of AMU and clonal dissemination for resistance occurrence (M1-M20).

Simulations were carried-out to study the influence of bacteriological and pharmacodynamic parameters describing 2 bacterial population from a same clone with and without a plasmid coding for a reduced susceptibility. Pattern analysis and clustering have also been performed and will help to identify key influential parameters. For the PD model, our simulations focused only on one bacterial specie, *E. coli*, and the different case scenario outlined the need to get a better understanding of the bacterial interactions within species. Indeed, these interactions/competitions between strains are likely a major key that affects the dynamics of resistance evolution. However, the inter-species transmission of AMR should also be considered and the development of more complex model including the whole microbiota is currently an ongoing research topic and it will probably be possible within the next years to include ecological models inside the PKPD models.

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST3: Development of on-farm transmission model (M1-M20)

The transmission of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) between animals, their environment, food and humans is a complex issue and more evidence is needed to strengthen current understanding. Models of disease transmission within commercial farm environments can provide further insight to the on-farm transmission dynamics of AMR between animals and their environment, as well as predict the effect of various on-farm interventions. Previous generic models indicate that ESBL resistant bacterial populations may be self-sustaining through horizontal and vertical gene transfer, even in the absence of antimicrobial pressure. However, models focusing purely on the biochemical aspects fail to incorporate the complicated host population dynamics which occur within a farm environment. Here, we present a model framework for incorporating pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic (PKPD) models; exploring the complex host/gut bacteria interplay, with on-farm models of disease transmission in order to predict the infection dynamics on pig farms. The model is designed to be adaptable for the simultaneous transmission of multiple bacteria and resistant strains. In addition, the model

incorporates the faecal excretion (and subsequent ingestion) of antimicrobial residues from pigs that have been treated with antibiotics. The model is an individual based, stochastic, susceptible-infected-susceptible (SIS) model of the colonisation of pigs with resistant bacteria within commercial pig farms. It is based on a previous model of *Salmonella* transmission on commercial pig farms in the European Union. The model consists of two main components: a pig management component and a bacterial transmission component (Figure 4). The management component simulates the movement of individual pigs throughout their time on the farm. It incorporates different management practices of commercial pig farms, such as when cleaning of the pens occurs, and the simultaneous movement of groups of different aged pigs.

The model output is the average prevalence and concentration of resistant bacteria in the faeces of pigs sent to the abattoir. The model was run with 500 iterations, each iteration representing production from one farm over a 365-day period. The timestep of the model was one day. To account for different farm types, the model subdivides farms into one of three pig production systems: breeder-finisher (where a pig stays on the same farm from birth until it goes to the abattoir), breeder-weaner (where pigs stay on one farm from birth to the weaner stage and then moves to a finisher-only unit) or finisher-only (pigs arrive on the farm after weaning and stay until they leave to go to the abattoir). Farms may run an all-in-all-out (AIAO) production system where batches of pigs are kept in rooms without direct contact between batches, or a continuous production system. AIAO systems were not applicable for the farrowing stage. Farms may also use either an indoor or outdoor production system in the farrowing stage and may use either solid or slatted floor in the pig pens. Different production systems are randomly selected for each iteration.

The model predicted that after introduction of ESBL *E. coli* onto a pig farm, the disease is likely to persist on the farm for more than a year leading to a high level of carriage (13.7%, 5th and 95th percentiles: 0-53.1) and faecal shedding in slaughter-age pigs. The average individual pig prevalence over all iterations in the baseline scenario was 13.7% (5th and 95th percentile: 0%-53.1%). However, the average batch prevalence, i.e. proportion of batches sent to slaughter with at least one positive pig, was 34.6% (5th and 95th percentile: 0%-97.9%) and the average pig prevalence in these batches was 39.6% (5th and 95th percentile: 5.6-56.3).

Figure 4: Overview of model framework simulating the colonisation and transmission of resistant bacteria in pigs within a commercial farm environment. The model has both management and transmission components.

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST4: Scenario analysis to assess hypothetical on-farm intervention measures (M6 M20)

Three farm-based interventions were modelled to investigate possible options for reduction of ESBL transmission between pigs. Firstly, sick pigs were simulated to move to a quarantined sick pen during the duration of their antibiotic treatment course. It was hypothesised that this could isolate the pigs which are most likely to be shedding the highest levels of resistant bacteria (due to the antibiotic use), and therefore reduce pen contamination levels. A further intervention was modelled to understand the effect of an enhanced cleaning and disinfection (C&D) protocol.

Isolation of pigs in sick pens for the duration of their antibiotic treatment reduced the number of positive batches whereas an enhanced cleaning and disinfectant (C&D) protocol reduced the within herd prevalence. Both interventions were able to reduce the number of pigs shedding more than $2\log_{10}$ ESBL *E. coli* from 8.5% (5th and 95th percentiles: 0-29.2) in the baseline scenario, to 0.07% (5th

and 95th percentiles: 0-0.3) when sick pens were used and 3.4% (5th and 95th percentiles: 0-16.5) when an enhanced C&D protocol was applied. A combination of the two interventions was most effective at reducing overall prevalence (5.6%, 5th and 95th percentiles: 0-40.6). The results suggest that actions targeted towards preventing or removing the colonisation of AMR bacteria within the microbiome of pigs are more likely to be effective than steps to remove contamination levels within the pen environment.

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST5: Communication of results (M18-M24)

A first draft of the on-farm model report is currently in internal review, but COVID-19 is delaying progress.

JRP3-WP2-T2: Models for transmission between livestock and human populations

JRP3-WP2-T2-ST1: Development of mathematical models for source-attribution (M1-M22)

A systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted in order to assess relevance of transmission routes of antibiotic resistant bacteria calculated using different methodologies and the relevance of routes per pathogen. This is being transformed in to a scientific paper. PubMed and EMBASE were searched, resulting in 6054 articles published up until January 1st, 2019. Full text screening was performed on 525 articles and 277 are included. This review took considerably more time than anticipated given the huge number of papers that had to be screened. The main conclusion of the review is that, on the one hand, there is a plethora of estimates and studies on risk factors and transmission routes of ABR bacteria, while on the other hand, the relevance of routes on a population scale is missing. As the frequency at which all kind of risk factors and exposure occurs, the relevance of transmission routes on a population level are lacking. For a specific pathogen, i.e., *Escherichia coli* containing β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes, we importance could be obtained 2), but even this study could pinpoint (with some uncertainty) how important different reservoirs are for the acquisition by humans of *Escherichia coli* containing β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes, but could not pinpoint the mechanisms behind the transmission routes. Given the almost complete absence of estimates of the importance of AMR transmission pathways, a mathematical model to calculate reproduction numbers would be highly speculative and any assessment of the effectiveness of intervention measures would lead to high-levels of uncertainty.

JRP3-WP2-T2-ST2: Assessment of intervention measures (M13-M22)

This work was merged with *JRP3-WP2-T2-ST1*

JRP3-WP2-T2-ST3: Communication of results (M18-M24)

Ongoing. A poster was presented at the Epidemics Conference in December 2019 (P1.069) . D2.3 I being transformed into a scientific paper.

WP3. Transmission through the food chain (M1-M30)

This WP focuses on risk assessment models that calculate risks of exposure/infection with ESBL *E. coli* from different sources and through different food chains..

JRP3-WP3-T1: Inventory of available exposure assessment models and related data and transfer to FSK Standard (M1-M24)

JRP3-WP3-T1-ST1: Inventory of available exposure assessment models (M1-M12)

We have completed the development and implementation of the RADAR model inventory. This includes the provision of a proper infrastructure for exchanging and annotating models in an exchangeable and reproducible file format called FSK and key or desirable features that facilitate access and usability of the inventory. The features were defined in the annual report 2018. However, the inventory currently runs on a firebase server hosted by Google (<http://ejp-radar.eu>). It is planned

to migrate the web application to a stand-alone BfR server as soon as possible. We have uploaded three models to the inventory, two showcase models and the primary production model from JRP3-WP3-T1-ST2.

JRP3-WP3-T1-ST2: Transfer of available exposure assessment models developed in R (or Matlab) to FSK Standard for at least one type of AMR bacteria and at least one animal (chicken, pig or mussels) (M10-M24)

We have uploaded three models to the inventory, two showcase models and the primary production model from JRP3-WP3-T1-ST2.

JRP3-WP3-T2: Exposure assessment models for different production chains (M1-M24)

JRP3-WP3-T2-ST1: Exposure assessment model for the chicken production chain (M1-M24)

During the project an exposure assessment model for the broiler production chain was developed. This model is a combination of two preexisting models which have been connected with each other (Fig. 4). One of the two preexisting models looks at the primary production and calculates how far ESBL *E. coli* spread within flocks and among flocks. This primary production model is then linked to a model describing how bacterial colonization on the surface of carcasses change over the course of a chicken processing line. The work in this deliverable then focused on the development of a generic model framework and for that the second part, the processing line model, was chosen to create a concrete implementation of how such a generic model might look like. The result is a R package *genpromodel* developed in this project that can help the user to build and customize its own processing model which might not be limited to chicken.

Fig. 4. The Exposure assessment model for the chicken production chain model considers following processes: Bacteria can go from the slaughter equipment to the carcass and the other way around. Bacteria on the carcass and on the slaughter equipment can be inactivated (symbolized by the arrows that lead out of the slaughter stage, indicating that the bacteria which become inactivated no longer take part in the model calculations). And finally bacteria that are in leaked faeces can either go onto the carcass or onto the slaughter equipment. The letters at the arrows describe the proportion of bacteria which transfer from the start point of the arrow to its end point.

JRP3-WP3-T2-ST2: Exposure assessment model for the pork production chain (M13-M24)

The pig processing model is developed in WP2 (primary production) and WP 3.2 (the slaughter process, consumption phase). It is developed to closely link to WP6, where an evidence synthesis approach for combining QMRA and epidemiology in the context of ESBL in the pork chain is developed. The model chain is parametrized for the Netherlands.

With approval of the RaDAR project lead, the dissemination mode of the current deliverable has been changed from scientific report to scientific article, thereby increasing dissemination value. Hence, full coverage of the model development for the slaughter phase, consumer phase, and dose-response will be discussed in detail in a forthcoming publication (Swart et al., in preparation). The exposition below should be considered a brief summary, highlighting the most prominent features.

The full QMRA model consists of a farm model, a slaughter model, a consumption model, and a dose-response model.

JRP3-WP3-T2-ST3: Exposure assessment model for the mussel production chain (M13-M24)

The potential for blue mussels to be a significant source of ESBL-producing *E. coli* to humans is unknown. Blue mussels typically undergo heat treatment before consumption, and commercial produced blue mussels have a food safety regulation limit of 230 *E. coli*/100g for direct human consumption (854/2004/EC, 2004), demanding that shellfish with higher *E. coli* concentrations be moved to cleaner water until the concentration falls below this level. As *E. coli* is an indicator of faecal contamination makes it useful as an indicator of pathogens which spreads this way, but this limit might not be enough to avoid ESBL-producing *E. coli* being transferred to humans from mussels/ shellfish. In addition, consumption of wild-harvested mussels occurs in many coastal areas, particular during vacation times.

The heat treatment performed by the consumer is traditionally kept to a minimum (until the shell opens), so there is a need for public knowledge of the potential for survival of both *E. coli* and ESBL-producing *E. coli* in such a food matrix. There exists little knowledge about the persistence of viable ESBL producing *E. coli* in different food matrixes where only light heat treatment are performed before consumption, but both the maximum obtained temperature within the mussel as well as the duration of certain temperatures will likely have an impact on bacterial survival, determining the amount of remaining viable from the original contamination.

The model for the mussel production chain described here (Fig. 5), is focused on the preparation step which is critical for exposure and disease risk. It addresses the question of how much ESBL *E. coli* bacteria consumers are exposed to when they prepare a batch of blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) or similar food item through the common practice of steaming raw shellfish before immediate consumption. Thus, the output of the model is the number of colony forming units of ESBL *E. coli* in a mussel meal depending on the duration and temperature of heat treatment, mussel size and initial contamination levels.

The model for the mussel production chain incorporates two sets of experiments, integrating them through a supervised learning algorithm for a robust output. The first set of experiments involves inoculating live mussels with non-ESBL *E. coli* by allowing them to naturally filter contaminated water in an aquarium, and then batches were steamed in a procedure mimicking common kitchen practices for different time intervals. Samples were taken of raw mussels as well as those subjected to different heat treatments, individual mussels were recorded, and colony-forming units per gram mussel meat (CFU/g) assessed by culturing. This experiment could, however, not utilize ESBL strains due to biohazard procedures, and the steaming does not allow incremental adjustment of temperature. Thus, a second set of experiments addressed this by homogenizing a mix of mussel meat and either non-ESBL or ESBL-producing *E. coli* in a series of in small, heat-resistant plastic bags, and subjecting them to water baths of different temperatures and durations before culturing. Lastly, these approaches were integrated through a simple learning algorithm for a more robust model by linking heat stress captured by “button-type” temperature loggers used in both experiment sets.

Additional work carried out in WP3 concerns a risk assessment for ESBL *E. coli* via sea-food consumption. Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase (ESBL) producing *Escherichia coli* (EEC) are a significant public health concern. Although previous studies have calculated the exposure through meat consumption, the risk from seafood has not been quantified. A Quantitative Microbiological Risk

Assessment (QMRA) model for meat was adapted to incorporate the complexities along the seafood chain. Total exposure of the Dutch population (EEC / year) was highest for raw salmon (48.1%) and smoked eel (43.9%). The top five seafood products (raw salmon, smoked eel, caviar / cod roe, smoked salmon and anchovies) all had a higher annual exposure estimate than any meat product. The high exposure by raw salmon is due partly to the current EU legislation which permits farmed salmon to be sold without prior freezing. With current antimicrobial usage remaining high in aquaculture industries, the results question whether the current legislation is adequate to mitigate against emerging microbiological hazards such as antimicrobial resistance.

Figure 5. Summary of the production/handling chain from growth and harvest to end consumer for blue mussels. In the growth stage they concentrate any contaminants in their surroundings through filter feeding, and are then kept alive through a more or less unbroken cold chain until they are exposed to a short heat treatment at the point of consumption.

JRP3-WP3-T3: Generic comparative exposure assessment model (M13-M24).

This task focussed on the potential for deriving or creating generic methods for exposure assessments for different production types, different bacteria, different processing etc.. These generic methods may be more crude, but will allow for combining the risks in the different (sub-)categories and may thus help to create a more complete picture of the AMR problems throughout.

In order to study how one could go about developing a generic modelling approach for assessing exposure while taking into account different exposure pathways the following was done. Four in this project independently developed models for three different food chains were compared in a synoptic way identifying conceptual communalities which were then considered central parts of a possible generic exposure modelling approach. The three different food chains were the chicken, pork and seafood chain. Within the seafood chain, there are two models: a comparative exposure assessment model for various types of seafood (fish) and an exposure model focussed on steamed mussels. The models for each food chain have of course their own idiosyncrasies given the different concrete

question they try to answer. However, there are still many conceptual communalities, which are useful to highlight in order to identify the generic elements of current state of the art exposure assessment models.

WP4: Machine learning methods for quantification of risk and health effects (M1-M30)

Assessing risk factors from data needs statistical modelling of that data. Here, mostly generalized linear models are applied, including logistic regression, and Poisson regression. The used framework struggles when the data set at hand is not a low-dimensional problem (i.e. only consists of only a few features), the data generating model is unknown and should a bit more ambitious than just a very simple linear one. Very often, we have data sets with almost as many, or even more variables than data points, and categorical features with many classes increase this problem for linear models even more (i.e. by inflating the design matrix with dummy variables). The classical framework fails here completely, as it has very high requirements on the data in order to successfully do a data analysis. And if the data generation model is unknown and we have to somehow guess a good model, it only gets worse. Here, we investigated the vast possibilities of Machine Learning (also known as statistical Learning, predictive modelling, and algorithmic modelling). On the field of machine learning, we often encounter data sets that are difficult to handle when using the classical statistical framework.

JRP3-WP4-T1: Add state of the art ML models for risk profiling to an inventory of exposure risk assessment models (M1-M2)

JRP3-WP4-T1-ST1, ST2, ST3:

There is a wide variety of different ML algorithm families, and many different packages available in R. Unfortunately, the quality and user guidance of the various packages is very diverse, partly because the writers of the packages are not qualified programmers and there is no peer or code review of R packages. The validation of used packages, especially if they are new, is the responsibility of the user.

Unfortunately, new and interesting packages can be so plagued by programming errors that they become unusable. The same applies to the partially erratic user guidance of the model functions, although a factual standard exists for this in R (see the function *lm*, *nls* and *glm*). Unfortunately, this is not binding, as a peer and code review would then have to be carried out, which is currently practically impossible, as the necessary structures do not exist. Many packages are the result of academic research, and with the end of this research the maintenance and responsibility for the package may cease. Thus these packages disappear again, even if they offer interesting approaches. Or programming errors remain unresolved. This can undermine your own analyses if they are based on the existence of these packages. (Since the underlying code may work, but is often unmaintainable, taking over the old, no longer hosted code would be a task of de-facto rewriting the code. We usually do not have the time or manpower to do this.).

Meta-packages such as *caret* (short for *_C_lassification _A_nd _RE_gression _T_raining*) try to clear up this chaos, and we strongly recommend the newcomer to familiarise himself with this or similar packages. Unfortunately, fixed approaches such as *caret* are only good in machine learning as long as the path is not deviated from. Therefore “only” standard evaluations are possible. But we had to do that here. Furthermore, even *caret* is also not immune to programming errors and poor performance. The R package ‘*caret*’ offers a treatment of supervised machine learning problems from a single source. At the same time it also contains a repository for a very large number of different machine learning models and their variations. The available models in *caret* can be viewed at: <http://topepo.github.io/caret/available-models.html>

We hope that packages such as *caret* will be further developed and maintained so that R remains competitive in the area of machine learning. We have avoided using meta-packages as much as possible.

There are other meta-packages in R for Machine Learning, namely `mlr`, and `mlr3`. But these two packages have the following problems: first of all, they want to do everything very differently from how it is normally done in R. The user guidance reminds more of Python than of R, which is not an advantage. The learning curve is very steep, so that `mlr` and `mlr3` are not worth it for most, relatively simple problems. It is then much more time-saving and efficient to use the underlying ML packages directly, and to program the possibly missing functionalities yourself in R, if these problems exist at all. It also saves the time-consuming research for how to access certain functionalities -- which are easily accessible in the underlying packages -- using `mlr` or `mlr3`. The second problem is that the development of `mlr` was abandoned in favour of `mlr3`. Unfortunately, some special, very advanced possibilities (e.g. multi-label classification) of `mlr`, are currently not available in `mlr3`.

JRP3-WP4-T1-ST4: Repository setup including setup of a Github repository(M7-M12).

Building a separate repository may be deemed superfluous given the existence of the Caret methods library on Github (<http://topepo.github.io/caret/index.html>) for which model evaluation manuals are readily available and a paper evaluating model performance on AMR risk models

JRP3-WP4-T2: Methods for testing model -validity, -sensitivity and -robustness (M13-M21)

In ML, models are developed differently from how we know it from classical statistical modelling. In ML, models with high predictive power are to be created, whereby the concrete form of the model is of little interest. This is called function estimation or approximation, in contrast to the parameter estimations of the assumed (hopefully correct) model in classical statistical modelling.

JRP3-WP4-T2-ST1: Selection of test data set(s) to be used (M13-M14)

For testing of different ML methods we searched for suitable pilot datasets from the AMR research field. We selected suitable ML benchmark data sets, simulated data sets (in silico data sets) with known effect size, variability and interdependence (correlation), and AMR data sets provided by partners within RaDAR and other EJP projects. Some of these data AMR data sets will be provided in the future. Data sets were selected according to our needs: one well behaved data set, one misbehaved data set that exceeds the possibilities of current fitting routines. Both data sets are already analysed and published.

- Fromm et al., *Prev. Vet. Med.*, 117, 2014 (fattening pig herds and MRSA)
- Hille et al., *Pred. Vet. Med.*, (pig herds and ESBL)

JRP3-WP4-T2-ST2: Defining a work bench for assessing model (M15-M17)

Here we present a framework for building an ML model (fig. 6). This consist of different steps.

1. Splitting data into training and test data.
In ML we have to somehow test or validate the predictive power of our created model. If we had a constant flow of new data at hand, the task would be easy to accomplish. Unfortunately, collecting data is usually complex and expensive, so we generate our own test data from the existing data set. To do this, we retain part of the data set for test purposes and create the model with the remaining data (training data).
2. Calculating performance measures .
Unlike in the classical stat. modeling, we are not interested in how good the model fits the data. We are interested, how good the model **predicts** the data, especially new unseen data. That is why, we need measures that are able to grasp this information somehow. Most often, the accuracy, and the misclassification rate are used for that.
3. Hyperparameter optimization.
Many machine learning models have parameters that have to be set before the model is created. These parameters are also called hyperparameter. For example, in the case of random forest models, hyperparameters include the number of trees formed and the number of

randomly selected features with which each individual tree is formed. In the elastic net regularisation, the continuous hyperparameters are available for setting the effect strength of the regularisation. These hyperparameters can have a very strong influence on the performance of the model and must therefore be optimised.

Fig. 6. General flow chart for creating and testing of a machine learning model. Here, only the scheme for one training/test split is shown, but to improve the assessment of the performance many (unique, non-repeated) splits are performed. E.g. for small data sets a leave-one-out cross-validation (or jackknife) is performed, where a single data point is separated from the data set for testing, and the rest of the data is used for training. Then, the training data is pre-processed, if necessary. The pre-processing for training is then used to pre-process the test data. With the pre-processed training data the trained model is build. Many machine learning models for classification do not produce a hard classification, but instead produce a probability, or a probability-like response. With the introduction of a threshold (often 0.5) a hard classification is performed. But it is sometimes an advantage to optimize the threshold, especially if the overall performance of the model is rather weak. Finally, with the model (and the optimized threshold) and the test data the performance measures a computed, and evaluated.

JRP3-WP4-T2-ST3: Model Analysis (M18-M21)

We compared the methods using real data sets (see above) that have already been evaluated by classical means in order to better explore the possibilities of machine learning for our purposes. Both datasets have a very different structure and in the corresponding papers various problems have been encountered during data analysis, which we would like to address with the methods we have chosen.

We concluded that regularized parametric algorithms would satisfy our needs. For the regularization we realized that the elastic net is the most appropriate approach. Three algorithms were selected: logistic regression with elastic net, linear discriminant analysis using the elastic net, and sparse distance weighted discrimination. The last two models need additionally a final probability calibration.

Ongoing: Model analysis has been completed but sensitivity and testing of model robustness ongoing
JRP3-WP4-T3: Literature review of methodologies and compilation of the selected methods (M22-M24)

Combined with T1.

JRP3-WP4-T4: ML and causality. Does it fit together? (M28-M36).

Not finished within the time-span of the RADAR project.

WP5: The burden of disease caused by AMR exposure (M1-M30)

We have modified these goals to take into consideration available personnel resources for WP5 and recent developments in the field. Instead of producing actual, EU-wide, estimates for the disease burden of infection with resistant forms of two bacteria, this task will now concentrate on developing a suitable methodological framework for computing resistance-attributable disease burden, and comparing this methodology against other approaches. We also included source attribution into this WP (redesigned T2).

JRP3-WP5-T1: Methodological framework for AMR burden (previously “Identify data gaps and define target questions for SEJ (Structured Expert Judgment)”)(M1-M12)

We designed a new burden of disease (BoD) approach suitable for estimating the *excess* BoD associated with AMR bacterial infection. By ‘excess BoD’ we mean mortality and morbidity (computed as DALY) associated with resistance, over and above the mortality and morbidity associated with the same – but antimicrobial-susceptible – bacterial infection (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. The concept of the excess burden approach to AMR.

We illustrate this approach for a single infection site (urinary tract) and a single bacterial agent (*E. coli*; extended spectrum beta-lactamase [EBSL]-producing compared with non-EBSL producing *E. coli*). We designed a methodology approach for estimating the BoD of urinary tract infection caused by antibiotic-susceptible and resistant *E. coli*. We modify an existing outcome tree (OT) describing the clinical progression pathway for UTI, and describe the separate transition parameters, disability durations, and disability weights that are needed to fully quantify the health consequences of infection with both susceptible and resistant versions of the same bacterial agent (Fig. 8). We have chosen the DALY as composite measure of departure from ideal health, and adopt the ‘incidence-based’ approach rather than a ‘prevalence-based’ approach to DALY computation. To arrive at a valid estimate of the excess BoD of UTI attributable to AMR, we propose to use a counterfactual approach. This involves simply subtracting the total BoD that is expected for antibiotic-susceptible UTI (using the ‘susceptible’ version of the OT), for the same number of incident cases, from the BoD computed using the ‘resistant’ version of the OT. A basic assumption of this approach is that the resistant form of UTI

will lead to greater BoD, which may be driven by greater mortality risk, longer disability durations, and higher risks of developing long-term sequelae. Note that an eventual further step is required, for the purposes of RaDAR, to distribute/attribute the estimated excess BoD to various transmission routes, including the food chain.

Fig. 8. Proposed outcome trees(s) for UTI, for antimicrobial-susceptible (upper panel) and antimicrobial-resistant (lower panel) infection. Transition probabilities (P) stratified by type of infection ($[S]$ usceptible or $[R]$ esistant) are indicated for several transitions, as are disability durations (DD).

JRP3-WP5-T2: Comparison of AMR burden methods (previously “Defining the seed questions”) (M1-M12)

We compared the proposed method for estimating AMR-attributable BoD with the ‘ECDC method’ (Cassini 2018) in terms of data needs, assumptions required, and limitations/points of concern. The principal difference between methodologies concerns the type of ‘input’ data. The proposed approach requires directly measured incidence; in contrast the ECDC method applies the Rhame-Sudderth formula to convert point prevalence and information on days spent in hospital to incidence. The second main difference between the two approaches concerns the pre-calculation of AMR attributable mortality and duration (i.e., LOS).

For valid estimation of BoD *attributable* to AMR, it seems clear that the relevant steps of the BoD methodology must correctly attribute morbidity and mortality to resistant infection only. Control groups on which the calculation of attributable risk/effect sizes (progression and mortality probabilities, disability durations) depends must represent only patients with susceptible infection, and not uninfected patients. A fundamental limitation of the ECDC method is that incidence is not measured directly; instead the Rhame-Sudderth formula is applied to convert point-prevalence to incidence. This formula can lead to over- or under-estimation of true incidence, and although frequently used, its non-established validity raises questions about conclusions drawn regarding absolute incidence (as opposed to trend analyses or comparisons across countries, for which the formula’s approximation to incidence appears more suitable). All methods suffer from confounding

bias in the estimation of AMR-attributable burden, as patient characteristics (e.g., age, presence of comorbidities, frailty, immunosenescence) can differ between those persons who acquire resistant form of bacterial infection and those who do not, and even if statistical adjustment could be straightforwardly integrated within the DALY computation, it would still be insufficient to correct for such differences due to unmeasured factors. Finally, when calculating attributable risks from longitudinal study data (for transition probabilities between health outcomes) or attributable mortality, it is vital to consider the impact of competing risks, such as discharge from hospital, death, or development of a complication that precludes observation of the health outcome of interest. The potential for erroneous transition probability calculations (usually over-estimated) is particularly high for patient populations at high risk of such competing events. It is not clear whether the reviewed studies used as basis for the ECDC transitions take competing risks into account, but the proposed BoD approach will apply appropriate methods when inferring the transition probabilities.

JRP3-WP5-T3: Application of AMR disease burden framework to urinary tract infections (previously “Identifying, enrolling and interviewing the experts”) (M4-M30)

We illustrated the approach described above for a single infection site (urinary tract) and a single bacterial agent (*E. coli*; extended spectrum beta-lactamase [ESBL]-producing compared with non-ESBL producing *E. coli*). This has not yet been done for the Netherlands using national-level data and country-specific parameter values. To achieve the goal of producing the most accurate estimate possible, we use systematic review to determine parameter values whenever possible and obtain data on incidence from a nationwide AMR surveillance system.

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are among the most frequent infections occurring in the community, hospital outpatient and inpatient settings. UTI is a common cause of sepsis in infants and accounts for up to 20–30% of all cases of sepsis, which is a life-threatening complication with a high mortality rate. As UTIs are frequently caused by AMR bacterial agents, a pressing research question is whether or not AMR urinary tract infections are associated with a higher BoD than AMS UTIs.

We performed a systematic literature search to locate parameter values for the risk of progression to bacteraemia, risk of progression to health states following bacteraemia, length of stay, other indicators of duration of illness and mortality risk. a second search was undertaken to locate relevant studies specifically informing the model parameters involving bacteraemia (i.e., $P(\text{Bact}|\text{UTI})$, $DD(\text{Bact})$, $P(\text{Death}|\text{Bact})$). A third systematic literature search was conducted to attempt to find relevant studies specifically to inform $P(\text{Bact}|\text{UTI})$, with restriction to studies of resistant *E. coli* UTIs.

We found an excess burden of 860 DALY, of which 98% was due to premature mortality. The sensitivity analysis, which indicated a 46% higher BoD when the mortality risk parameter was assumed to be age-independent, illustrates that for accurate BoD estimation stratified parameter values are vital. Parameter values obtained from a study population with a certain characteristic (e.g., older age) are not necessarily generalisable to strata of the population that do not match the study participants' profile. We were only able to crudely account for age-dependent mortality risk, and due to lack of suitable data, necessarily had to estimate the reduced risk for younger age-groups from a single, relatively small, national study of mortality due to bacteraemia caused by a different organism (*S. aureus*). The estimated 60 excess deaths in the sensitivity analysis do not appear realistic as an estimate for the annual AMR attributable-mortality among all patients with UTIs caused by ESBL-producing *E. coli* in the Netherlands, and are not consistent with other estimates of annual deaths due to resistant *E. coli* BSIs.

Our estimate of BoD among patients with resistant UTIs computed using the ECDC parameters is not comparable to the BoD for resistant UTIs as reported in Cassini et al. because of the very different approach of attributing BoD due to UTI and infections in other sites that progress to bacteraemia/sepsis to the BoD due to BSI. Namely, the BoD for the health outcome *symptomatic UTI* only was reported at 4.14 DALY (95% UI: 3.22-5.17)[1]. However, by making the assumption that the

parameter value for $P(\text{Bact}|\text{UTI})$ for AMS UTIs from the literature source can also be applied to AMR UTIs, we could then calculate the resistant BoD by incorporating this parameter into the rest of the ECDC parameters, which then allows a more direct comparison to our estimates to be made. We found that this approach estimated an 3.3-fold greater BoD among patients with resistant *E. coli* infection compared with the Netherlands-specific model.

JRP3-WP5-T4: Source attribution of AMR for attribution of disease burden to sources (previously Analysing the data to obtain aggregated responses to the target questions”) (M0-M30)

Although complex dynamics are involved in ESBL-EC and pAmpC-EC transmission, our results provide quantitative links between specific ESBL-EC and pAmpC-EC genes in the open community and their probable human and non-human sources of direct transmission. Approximately two-thirds of community-acquired ESBL-EC and pAmpC-EC carriers are attributable to human-to-human transmission, with the considered non-human sources accounting for the other third (Fig. 9). We also attributed the different ESBL genotypes to reservoirs (Fig. 10). While anthroponotic sources prevail, our findings underpin the need for longitudinal studies and warrant continuous monitoring in both human and non-human populations, because intracommunity ESBL-EC and pAmpC-EC spread alone seems unlikely to be self-maintaining without transmission to and from non-human sources. Transmission routes of antibiotic resistance are complex, with numerous interconnected cycles and subcycles involving different hosts and environments. Because resistant bacteria might pass into humans from animals and food, and via environment-mediated and human-to-human transmission, a One Health approach is needed that values interdisciplinarity and stresses the connections between public, animal, and environmental health, and provides an integrated framework for improving our understanding of the global threat of antimicrobial resistance.

This work was published in **Lancet Planetary Health (Mughini-Gras et al. 2019 3:357-369)**.

Fig. 9. Summary results of ESBL source-attribution

Fig. 10. Attribution of different ESBL genotypes to reservoirs.

EXTRA: JRP3-WP5-T5: A new paradigm for AMR surveillance based on metagenomics (M18-M30)

In this study we recovered and shotgun-sequenced caecal samples collected from pigs under the Danish monitoring of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) over two time periods (1999-2004 and 2015-2018), and compared this to gathered phenotypic results and antimicrobial use (AMU) data for the same time periods. The aim was to compare findings obtained with the present methods employed in AMR surveillance (phenotypic testing of indicator- and pathogenic-bacteria), with a new surveillance paradigm - a metagenomics-based surveillance of AMR determinants. We showed that metagenomic surveillance is a suitable methodology for population based surveillance of AMR and observed that AMU and AMR are in general correlated both at phenotypic and genotypic levels, but also that other factors play a role in the abundances of AMR.

WP6: Integration of information by Bayesian evidence synthesis (M1-M30)

We applied the Bayesian Evidence Synthesis (BES) approach to estimate human carriage of ESBL-producing *E. coli* (ESBL *E. coli*) in the Netherlands that is attributable to pork. BES is a statistical modelling approach that can make use of all available information, by combining all relevant data with a priori knowledge regarding model parameters, and is suitable for estimation of parameters such as prevalence or incidence for which no direct measurements exist, but which may be indirectly informed by other data sources. This approach importantly recognises all sources of uncertainty in the data sources contributing to the uncertainty of parameters of interest. As in meta-analysis, multiple sources of data informing the same parameter are naturally weighted by their accuracy; as a corollary, all data sources contributing information to a given parameter are also essentially weighted by precision. The ultimate aim of implementing a full BES network would be to eventually integrate information from all exposure pathways and all health effects and in multiple countries, but under the lights of the pilot project that RaDAR conforms, to make the initial problem tractable we focused only on ESBL *E. coli* in humans attributable to pork consumption in the Netherlands.

JRP3-WP6-T1: Collect current status data (M1-M6)

We made a descriptive overview of available Dutch data relevant for risk assessment and epidemiological calculations. For risk assessment, this will comprise of ESBL *E. coli* prevalence data but also data that describe the human exposure intensity to ESBL *E. coli*. For epidemiology, data relate to the distribution of ESBL genes of plasmids in the human population and in the respective reservoirs. Also, risk factors and epidemiological metadata are described.

JRP3-WP6-T2: Build evidence synthesis network for current status database (M1-M12)

The full QMRA pig processing model consists of a primary production farm model (WP2), and a slaughter process model, a consumption phase model, and a dose-response model (WP3), which are described more in detail in their corresponding work package reports. In here we will briefly explain how they are interlaced in the network and then joined together with the EPI model. The purpose from this report is to highlight the most prominent findings after successfully managed to implement the full BSE network. A manuscript describing this study in detail is currently being written (Bonacic Marinovic et al., in preparation) and will be submitted for publication during 2021, together with a manuscript resulting from the task from WP3.2, where the slaughter model and the consumer behaviour model, both part of the QMRA submodel, are also described in detail. We built up a prototype evidence synthesis network for the pork chain as a multi-level bayesian model, where parameters have initial prior distributions whose parameters in turn have prior distributions. This allows to manage the level of desired uncertainty and also to find the most representative values for some priors, e.g., uncertainty in the estimated average values on top of the spread around that estimated value. The code for carrying out the calculations is being written in R for JAGS. As first step we constructed a network inspired on the analysis carried out by Evers & Bouwknegt (2016) and using data there in found. By means of the QMRA analysis there and Markov chain Montecarlo simulations, we calculate posterior distributions for doses to which the population is exposed yearly. Information on the distributions is given as averages and for our code we introduced poisson and normal spreads as first attempt to deal with point estimates. We used a dose-response relation model based on a Beta-Poisson function, where the function parameters are loosely constrained and informed by data from challenge studies. From the Epidemiology side we employed information on duration of carriage (distributions from Teunis et al., 2018) and ESBL carriage attribution to pork (expert opinion) to estimate distributions of incidence per year and prevalence. We joined the two approaches by using the so called zero-crossing method, where the estimated incidence of carriage from both QMRA and Epidemiology approaches is forced to be the same within a given standard deviation. So far, we identified ESBL carriage attribution to pork and the dose-response relation as the culprits of a difference of three orders of magnitude between the posterior distributions for yearly ESBL carriage as calculated independently by the Epidemiology approach and by the QMRA approach.

JRP3-WP6-T3: Update evidence network for information developed in the other work packages (M12-M18)

The results from JRP3-WP3-T2-ST2 were implemented in the evidence synthesis network. The other exposure assessments from WP3 will undoubtedly be valuable for future work. The evidence synthesis framework links with JRP3-WP2-T1-ST3 (development of an on-farm transmission model for ESBL *E. coli* in pigs) and JRP3-WP3-T2-ST2 (development of a model for the pig production chain and consumption phase). Here, the farm models of WP2 was coupled to the pig processing model and consumer phase model is nearly completed, with some final improvements being implemented. Epidemiological inputs to the model were finalized.

JRP3-WP6-T4: Define endpoint for the current project and report results for the evidence synthesis model in its endpoint state (M18-24)

The result of the final model is depicted in Fig. 11, where now the predicted incidences for *ESBL E. coli* for the QMRA and EPI model are very close together. Also, the combined model has a smaller credible interval than both submodels, meaning that precision of the prediction was improved due to the evidence synthesis of the submodels. The final prediction is 5249 (credible interval: 983-24852) *ESBL E. coli* cases due to consumption of pork per year.

Fig. 11. Predicted number of ESBL E. coli carriers, for the EPI submodel (green), the QMRA submodel (blue) and the coupled model (red).

We presented models for carriage of ESBL producing *E. coli* in humans. On the one side we have an epidemiological submodel, based on cross-sectional and longitudinal studies. On the other side we have a risk-assessment model, based on a farm-to-fork QMRA approach. Both models are supposed to estimate the same quantity: human carriage. We applied a Bayesian evidence synthesis approach to combine the submodel, integration all data sources in one overarching model.

One major advantage of this approach is that variability and uncertainty are separated, meaning that we get insight in where additional data collection is warranted.

Furthermore, we have shown that it is possible to assess consistency of data sources. In particular, we identified one data source in the cross-sectional data which was inconsistent with the others. Upon closer inspection, this data pertained to farmers, an occupational group for which higher *ESBL* carriage prevalence is not unexpected as compared to the general population.

Another benefit of the approach is detection of parameters that need a great change to accommodate the joining of the submodels. In other words: the prior (i.e. our knowledge of the parameter value before the model is applied) is very different from the posterior (i.e. our updated estimate of the parameter). We made this explicit by running two scenarios. The first scenario was to deliberately use an incorrect dose-response relation for illness instead of carriage. The second scenario consisted of the correct dose response for carriage only. In the incorrect scenario, we observed that the dose-

response parameters shifted far from their initial value to accommodate the model joining. In the second scenario, parameters were hardly affected, and joining of the epidemiological and QMRA models resulted in a more precise consensus estimate than either of the individual models.

So, not only did we obtain more reliable estimates of incidence of carriage, but we also unlocked a toolbox for assessing model and data reliability. A paper detailing the approach is currently being written for submission to a scientific journal.

4 Project self-assessment

Antimicrobial resistance threatens the effective prevention and treatment of an ever-increasing range of infections. It is an increasingly serious threat to global public health that

requires action across all government sectors and society. Assessment of the importance of different transmission routes and quantifying public health effects (i.e. disease burden) associated with AMR represent major knowledge gaps. The current knowledge on public health risks and burden of AMR is limited due to the complex nature of the system (humans/food/animal/environment, relation between antimicrobial use and development of resistance, complex multi-directional transmission routes, and diverse effects on human health).

The key objective of RADAR was (copied from the project proposal) to systematically integrate top-down epidemiological and bottom-up risk assessment information from diverse modalities to obtain best estimates for attribution, risk factors and health effects as information is collected.

More specifically to objective were:

1. To develop bioinformatics tools to analyse (meta-)genomic data and retrieve
2. information relevant for AMR and its transmission
3. To produce models regarding AMR development, transmission
4. To develop machine learning approaches for risk assessment
5. To fill data gaps by structured expert judgement
6. To produce a Bayesian evidence synthesis of all available data and information in
7. order to come to consensus estimates on source attribution, risks of exposure and health effects.

To that end a diverse group of international experts in epidemiology, molecular biology, transmission modelling, risk modelling, and disease burden modelling was brought together in the RADAR consortium. This was very much a success since corporation went very natural and all members were highly motivated. Little pressure by the project management had to be carried out.

The RADAR project deviated from the original plan regarding WP5 (burden of disease). Originally we aimed at applying an established method using expert elicitation for burden estimates. This was redesigned to the development of new method where we estimated the excess burden of resistant infection and applied this to urinary tract infections. In addition we added a new method for AMR source attribution (applied to ESVL E. coli) where we included humans as a possible source (which is not done in source attributions of zoonotic pathogens). Finally we added a pilot study into the use of metagenomics for AMR surveillance. See fig.12 for an overview of the redesign of WP5.

WP5 old	WP5 new
T-5.1. Identify data gaps and define target questions for SEJ	T5.1 methodological framework for AMR burden
T-5.2. Defining the seed questions	T5.2 Comparison of AMR burden methods
T-5.3. Identifying, enrolling and interviewing the experts	T5.3 Application of burden framework to UTIs
T-5.4. Analysing the data to obtain aggregated responses to the target questions	T5.4 Source attribution of AMR for attribution of disease burden to sources
	T-5.5. Propose and assess a new paradigm for AMR surveillance in pigs.

Fig. 12. Overview of the redesign of WP5 tasks.

The RADAR project delivered beyond the state-of-the-art by:

- producing a new curated database of (AMR) plasmids
- development and coupling of models for on-farm development and spread of AMR
- producing new risk assessment models for AMR in different food chains
- defining and testing frameworks for machine learning methods for AMR risk assessment
- developing a new method for specific AMR burden of disease
- developing and applying a new source attribution approach for AMR
- investigating the usefulness of metagenomics for AMR surveillance
- developing and applying methodology to integrate various sources of AMR data in order to come to consensus estimates on exposure and risks of carriage.

In addition the RADAR project published in respected journals like The Lancet Global Health and Frontiers in Microbiology. At least 7 other publications are in preparation.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
03	D-JRP3-0.1	First annual report	M12	18			
03	D-JRP3-0.2	Second annual report	M24	36			
03	D-JRP3-0.3	Third annual report	M30	36			9
03	D-JRP3-1.1	Establishment of a database of synthetic, reference and genomic data	M12	20		https://zenodo.org/record/4476359#.YBLXYfZFw2w	
03	D-JRP3-1.2	Establishment of a database of field (meta-)genomic data	M15	18		https://zenodo.org/record/4476374#.YBLYzvZFw2w	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
03	D-JRP3-1.3	Automated assembly pipeline integrating de novo plasmid reconstruction	M12	24		https://zenodo.org/record/4476381#.YBLZuvZFw2w	
03	D-JRP3-1.4 (AWP2020)	Test and parameterization of the assembly pipeline for metagenomics data	M24	24		https://zenodo.org/record/4476406#.YBLai_ZFw2w	
03	D-JRP3-1.5 (AWP2020)	Biological annotations of plasmid identified in the pipeline	M24	24		https://zenodo.org/record/4476436#.YBLbc_ZFw2w	
03	D-JRP3-1.6 (AWP 2020)	WGAS-based method for genomic data analysis	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476483#.YBLcQ_ZFw2w	2
03	D-JRP3-1.7 (AWP 2020)	Development of regression model for genomic data analysis	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476483#.YBLcQ_ZFw2w	9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
03	D-JRP3-1.4.3 (AWP2020)	Integration of genetic traits associated to AMR and plasmid content information into models (WP6)	M30		M36	Cancelled (COVID and lack of capacity)	9
03	D-JRP3-2.1	Report on Pharmacodynamics and transmission models	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4478642#.YBPwkvZFW2w	8
03	D-JRP3-2.2	Report - A risk assessment to predict the sustainability of ESBL-producing E.Coli carriage within commercial pig farms	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4478651#.YBPxH_ZFW2w	8

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
03	D-JRP3-2.3	Report - The relevance of transmission routes of antibiotic resistant bacteria calculated using different methodologies and the relevance of routes	M30	27		https://zenodo.org/record/4476487#.YBLizfZfw2w	8
03	D-JRP3-2.4	Report -Report on intervention strategies	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4478291#.YBPDMfZfw2w	8
03	D-JRP3-3.1	Inventory with models and related data in FSK standard	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476609#.YBLoOvZfw2w	3
03	D-JRP3-3.2	Scientific report on a generic model for the chicken production chain	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476623#.YBLpl_Zfw2w	8 or 9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
03	D-JRP3-3.3	Scientific report on an adapted model for the pork production chain developed	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476637#.YBLrD_ZFw2w	8 or 9
03	D-JRP3-3.4	Scientific report on an model for the exposure assessment of AMR through mussels	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476661#.YBLsz_ZFw2w	8 or 9
03	D-JRP3-3.5	Scientific report on a generic comparative exposure assessment model	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476674#.YBLuTfZFw2w	8 or 9
03	D-JRP3-3.6	Comparative Exposure Assessment of ESBL-Producing Escherichia coli Through Seafood Consumption	NEW	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476684#.YBLvYPZFw2w	8 or 9
03	D-JRP3-4.1	Model repository of state of the art ML methods for	M12	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476722#.YBLxoPZFw2w	8 or 9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		risk profiling available					
03	D-JRP3-4.2	Recommended methods for risk profiling in investigations on antibiotic resistance available	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476722#.YBLxoPZFw2w	8 or 9
03	D-JRP3-5.1	The 'excess burden' approach for computing the burden of disease attributable to AMR: Application to urinary tract infection	M30	27		https://zenodo.org/record/4476732#.YBLyrPZFw2w	9
03	D-JRP3-5.2 (NEW)	A proposal for a new paradigm for AMR surveillance (NEW)	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476751#.YBLzY_ZFw2w	9
03	D-JRP3-5.3	Attributable sources of community-acquired	M36	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476761#.YBL1ffZFw2w	9

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
	(NEW)	carriage of Escherichia coli containing β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes					
03	D-JRP3-5.4	Report on structured expert judgement				Cancelled (redesigned WP5; see D D-JRP3-5.1)	
03	D-JRP3-6.1	Publication on final evidence network	M30	36		https://zenodo.org/record/4476793#.YBL3QvZFw2w	8
03	D-JRP3-6.2	Policy-targeted report	M30		TBC	COVID delay – will be completed first half 2021	9

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M-JRP3-1	Kick-off meeting and report	M1	yes		
03	M-5 .1	Identification data gaps and SEJ (Structured Expert Judgment) target questions	M3	yes		
03	M5.2	Defined seed questions	M6	Yes		
03	M-JRP3-3.1 (See FP)	Complete literature reviews of previous PK/PD and on-farm models (ANSES, APHA)	M5	yes		
03	M AMR3.11 (See FP)	Complete literature reviews of AMR transmission modelling (CVI, NCOH, RIVM)	M5	Yes		
03	M-JRP3-6	Database of available data	M6	yes		
03	M AMR3.2 (See FP)	Develop model frameworks for PK/PD and on-farm model (ANSES, APHA)	M8	yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M-JRP3-8	Mid-term meeting and report	M12	yes		
03	M-3.1	Structure for inventory of models and related data developed	M12	Yes		
03	M 4.1	Repository filled with models on Github	M12	Yes		
03	M6.1	Database of available data	M6	yes		
03	M6.2	Functional consensus evidence network	M12	yes		
03	M-AMR3-1.2.1 (see AWP2020)	Test and validation of assembly pipeline on synthetic and reference genomic data	M24	Yes		
03	M-AMR3-1.2.2	Analysis of HTS field data with assembly pipeline	M24	yes		
03	M-AMR3-1.4.1	Analysis of field genomic data with WGAS-based method	M30	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M-AMR3-1.4.2	Analysis of field genomic data with regression model	M30	Yes		
03	M AMR3.2	Develop model frameworks for PK/PD and on-farm model (ANSES, APHA)	M8	yes		
03	M AMR3.3	Produce case study (collected datasets) baseline results for PK/PD (ANSES)	M15	yes		
03	M AMR3.4	Establish connection between the PK/PD model and the on-farm-model (ANSES, APHA)	M24	yes		
03	M AMR3.5	Establish connection between the PK/PD model and the on-farm-model (ANSES, APHA)	28	YES		
03	M AMR3.6	Simulations of the PK/PD model for green AMDs (ANSES)	M28	YES		
03	M AMR3.7	Produce case study baseline model results for on-farm model (APHA)	M28	yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M AMR3.8	Structural adaptations of the PK/PD model according to AMR mechanisms (ANSES)	28	YES		
03	M AMR3.9	Assess hypothetical intervention measures using on-farm model (APHA)	M30	Yes		
03	M JRP3.10	Data gaps in PK/PD modelling and propositions of experimental studies with a defined methodology (ANSES)	M30	YES		
03	M-AMR3.12	Formulate CM/NGM (CVI, NCOH) and SD (RIVM) transmission models	M24	Yes		
03	M-AMR3.13	Calibrate models using data library (CVI)	M24	Yes		
03	M-AMR3.14	Formulate/investigate interventions (RIVM, NCOH, CVI, BfR43)	28	Yes		COVID delay and granted extension
03	M-AMR3.15	Assimilate project-generated data (NCOH)	28	Yes		COVID delay and granted extension

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M-AMR3.16	Make recommendations to fill data gaps (RIVM, NCOH, CVI)	M30	Yes		COVID delay and granted extension
03	M-JRP3-34	Final meeting and report	M30	Final report: Yes Final meeting: TBC		COVID delay and granted extension
03	M-3.2 (See AWP2020)	Concept for an improved model for the chicken production chain developed	M24	Yes		
03	M-3.3	Concept for an adapted model for the pork production chain developed	M24	Yes		
03	M-3.4	Concept for an model for the exposure assessment of AMR through mussels	M24	Yes		
03	M-3.5	Concept on a generic comparative exposure assessment model	M27	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M4.2	Model development and model assessment completed	M21	yes		
03	M 0.2.2	Final meeting	M30	NO	M36	COVID delay and granted extension

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Analysis of COMPASS, a New Comprehensive Plasmid Database Revealed Prevalence of Multireplicon and Extensive Diversity of IncF Plasmids https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.00483 https://zenodo.org/record/3968418#.XyQSQTgUIM2	YES		
Attributable Sources of Community-Acquired Carriage of Escherichia Coli Containing β -Lactam Antibiotic Resistance Genes: A Population-Based Modelling Study https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(19)30130-5 https://zenodo.org/record/3621285#.Xjl8UGhKhPY	YES		

The following manuscripts are in preparation:

- “Benchmarking of plasmid prediction tools to explore the plasmidome of *Salmonella enterica*” (ANSES)
- “A risk assessment to predict the likelihood of ESBL-producing *E.coli* carriage in slaughter-aged pigs following bacterial introduction onto commercial pig farms: an interdisciplinary approach combining a within-host and a farm model” (APHA/ANSES)
- “The relevance of transmission routes of antibiotic resistant bacteria calculated using different methodologies and the relevance of routes per pathogen: a systematic review and meta-analysis” (NCOH)
- “Machine learning methods for qualification of AMR related risk factors and health effects” (BfR)
- “Defining a methodological framework for estimating AMR related excess disease burden” (RIVM/NCOH)
- “Integration of risk assessment and epidemiology by Bayesian evidence synthesis: a case for ESBL-E. coli attributable to pork” (RIVM)
- “When the heat is on enough: modelling the persistence of ESBL-producing *E. coli* in blue mussels under meal preparation” (NVI)

Additional output

Due to the corona-crisis little scientific dissemination activities were undertaken. Congresses were cancelled and sparse time available was dedicated to the progress of the project.

7 One Health impact

This project achieved its goals in a multi-disciplinary and One Health approach with partners of different expertise (microbiology, epidemiology, risk assessment) and from different domains (public health, veterinary health, food safety). RADAR delivered some interesting and potential useful tools and insights.

- We delivered a large-scale curated database of (AMR) plasmids from a range of different bacterial species and sources (“COMPASS”, Dourarre 2020 *Frontiers in Microbiology*), This novel resource will help researchers understand the genetic plasticity and transmission routes of plasmids, which are crucial in the fight against the spread of antimicrobial resistant pathogens. **Moreover this will be potentially of use in future AMR risk assessment model that may integrate genetic data.** The database is available at <https://github.com/itsmeludo/COMPASS>
- We provided an infrastructure for exchanging and annotating risk assessment models in an exchangeable and reproducible file format called FSK and key or desirable features that facilitate access and usability of the inventory (<https://ejp-radar.eu/>). **This will be helpful to the risk assessment community since it makes risk assessment models more transparent and re-useable (with parametrisation based on the local situation/data).**
- We produced state-of-the-art AMR risk assessment models for different food chains in a generic framework. These generic methods may be more crude, but will allow for combining the risks in the different (sub-)categories and may thus help to create a more complete picture of the AMR problems throughout. **This may be helpful to national and supra-national institutes to rank food related AMR (and pathogen) related risks.**
- We produced a framework for the use machine-learning methods in AMR risk assessment in order to identify risk factors from high-dimensional data with more variables than data points and/or categorical features with many classes. **This may be very useful for future risk assessment that will likely integrate more and more diverse data.**
- We designed a new burden of disease (BoD) approach suitable for estimating the excess BoD associated with AMR bacterial infection. By ‘excess BoD’ we mean mortality and morbidity (computed as DALY) associated with resistance, over and above the mortality and morbidity associated with the same – but antimicrobial-susceptible – bacterial infection. **The method will help to add the burden of AMR to a larger set of infectious disease burden estimates used by policy makers to set priorities.**
- We produced a One-Health source attribution model that estimates the relative contribution of reservoirs and transmission routes to AMR (ESBL E. coli) casrriership in the population. We adopted established source attribution methods for zoonotic pathogens for specific use for AMR (mainly by introducing humans not only as an endpoint but also as a source). **This method can be used to help policy makers in ranking and setting priorities regarding intervention strategies.**
- We studied a new paradigm for AMR surveillance based on metagenomics where we showed that metagenomic surveillance is a suitable methodology for population based surveillance of AMR and observed that AMU and AMR are in general correlated both at phenotypic and genotypic levels, but also that other factors play a role in the abundances of AMR. **This will be**

of interest to public health and veterinary institutes looking for all-in-one surveillance methods.

- Finally, we developed and applied a Bayesian Evidence Synthesis (BES) approach to integrate all available data and information by combining all relevant data with a priori knowledge and thereby eventually infer estimates on prevalence/incidence of AMR infections / carriership. **This approach will be very helpful in providing policy makers with consensus estimates based on all available data.**

Now that the scientific work of RADAR is completed we aim at having a **supranational stakeholder (EFSA, ECDC) meeting** early 2021 in order to disseminate our results and scout the possibilities for further use of our work. In addition, several consortium partners have been in interaction with their **local governments** regarding the use of the developed methods and gained knowledge. An example is the interests of the Dutch Ministry of Health in applying the AMR burden methodology more broadly to AMR infections in order to include them in the national burden comparisons aiming at setting intervention priorities.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	5	4	4
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	5	5	5
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	5	3	4
Integration	5	5	4
Sustainability	5	5	4
Impact of the project	5	3	5
TOTAL	30/30	25/30	26/30

AVERAGE:27

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

All objectives as set in the full proposal were achieved. Slight changes in WP 5 did not make deviation from the main goals of the project and provide more value to scientific excellence of this research project.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

RADAR met the majority of the objectives. This judgement is based on the reports on the Zenodo platform and on information provided in the final project report. One of the WP (N°5) was redefined and the tasks modified accordingly; reasons for these modifications are justified in the final report. The project is very ambitious with a high degree of complexity (a large number of tasks and subtasks). The first impression was that the various tasks and subtasks were quite dispersed, but after a more thorough reading, it was obvious how the tasks and subtasks connected and addressed the stated objectives of the project.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The key objective of RADAR was to systematically integrate epidemiological and risk assessment information from diverse modalities to obtain best estimates for attribution, risk factors and health effects of AMR. It also aimed at producing models regarding AMR development, transmission and developing bioinformatics tools to analyse (meta)genomic data and retrieve information relevant for AMR and its transmission.

The project definitely brought important and various results that help to understand transmission of resistance in animals and in their environment by developing different biomathematical models and databases.

WP5 deviated from the original plan, but resulted in important findings, together with the pilot study on metagenomics.

The alignment of the results with the project objectives should be accordingly considered as excellent.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Project scientific data is beyond state of the art following initially submitted proposal. A new plasmid data basis, state of the art risk assessment models in different food chain, designed a new burden of disease (BoD) approach for estimating AMR associated infection, developing and applying methodology to integrate various sources of AMR data in order to come to consensus estimates on exposure and risks of carriage and other project achievements show great multidisciplinary integration between microbiologist, epidemiologist, risk assessment and veterinary specialists.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The research group is highly skilled and high quality results are produced from the project. As of the time of final reporting, two publications have been published and it is mentioned that at least seven publications are in progress. The research groups have, among many things, developed harmonized methodologies and frameworks to assess transmission routes and quantify disease burden associated with AMR and important knowledge gaps were thereby addressed. The group has also developed toolbox for assessing models, data reliability and exposure results. The scientific quality of the outputs produced is high and also highly relevant.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project delivered scientifically qualified results with progress beyond the state-of-the art, with excellent innovative approach, by developing several models, methods and databases, such as the Compass database, the “within-host PK/PD model” and on-farm transmission model.

Therefore the scientific excellence is considered as outstanding.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Scientific achievements showed well organised project management, especially keeping in mind participants from 7 countries and multidisciplinary approach to this project. Scientific results were published in respected journals like The Lancet Global Health and Frontiers in Microbiology, and at least 7 other publications are in preparation.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Research data is well managed through the various platforms developed and results from the project are/will be available in various scientific journals. It is less clear from the final report how well the research group disseminated the project and communicated results in other scientific fora, for example at congresses, and if the project was disseminated to relevant stakeholders outside academia. Since not all activities have been completely finalized it might also be that further dissemination activities are to be initiated.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The management was effective to coordinate seven WPs.

Several reports were issued on the outcome and certain results were already published in respected journals, besides, further manuscripts are in preparation.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Project is successful in achieving relevant integrative activities. All topics results (data bases, learning methods, designed new bioburden of diseases and produced a One-Health source attribution model that estimates the relative contribution of reservoirs and transmission routes to AMR (ESBL E. coli) casrriership in the population helps policy makers in ranking and setting priorities regarding intervention strategies and help to add the burden of AMR to a larger set of infectious disease burden estimates used by policy makers to set priorities.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has highly successful in achieving integrative activities, which can be exemplified by the development of new and harmonized methodologies, development of new frameworks, transmission-exposure-source attribution models and development of databases. These outputs will be of importance both for future research and for advising policy and decision-makers about prioritization and developing tools to mitigate AMR. A One Health approach was used and the project integrated AMR in food producing animals, in humans and transmission through the food chain.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project consortium itself implemented integration by its diverse constitution of international experts in amultidisciplinary team of researchers of different fields such as animal science, epidemiology, food and environmental microbiology, molecular biology, bioinformatics and risk assessment modelling.

Integration was excellently fulfilled by several WPs of the project and One Health aspect was also highlighted especially in WP3 on risk assessment models that calculate risks of exposure/infection with ESBL E. Coli from different sources and through different food chains (chicken, pork and mussel). Also special additional work was carried out in WP3 regarding risk assessment for EEC via seafood consumption.

JRP3-WP5-T4 on source attribution of AMR for attribution of disease burden also highlighted zoonotic importance by highlighting different sources in fig. 9 and 10 of the report. Besides, WP6 aimed at estimating human ESBL E. Coli carriage attributable to pigs and presented models for carriership.

The project also achieved integrated activities such as searching AMR datasets provided by other EJP projects.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Created data bases and project results are available for other scientist and institutions.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The various outputs from the project will likely be well maintained within the project consortium and constitute a platform for future research and further harmonization. The project has developed improved methodologies that also can be used by other researchers and agencies. There is great potential for project outputs to reach outcome and impact.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The results achieved by the project are expected to be highly useful for other institutions as well, such as databases on genomic data.

The AMR risk assessment models for different food chains may be helpful to national and international institutes to rank food related AMR (and pathogen) related risks.

The models developed in WP2 further highlights the importance of pig farms in transmitting resistant microorganisms to the environment and their zoonotic significance and also provides intervention measures for reducing ESBL transmission due to antibiotic use that can be utilized by other stakeholders as well.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Project results will have impact over a long period of time due to new approach to resolving tasks in the project. Also results have very good secondary effect on learning, understanding of AMR (ESBL also) spreading through the different food chains. This also impact food quality and resistant bacteria spreading among food chains and society.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project contributes to improved knowledge about models, methodologies to assess burden of AMR, which might contribute to better-informed support and decision systems. There is thus potential for a long lasting impact of the project given the outputs are further refined by the consortium with the intention to have them incorporated within national and EU strategies. The results obtained will also be used as basis for future research, which also makes long-term impact possible.

The project contributes to the ambition of the One Health EJP.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The outcome of the project is expected to be outstanding.

The database "Compass" developed under WP1 will contribute to researchers and clinicians to understand the genetic plasticity and transmission routes of plasmids, which are crucial in the fight against the spread of resistant pathogens. It could also contribute to future risk assessment models. New environmental genomic datasets relevant to various AMR challenges have also been collected and organized in a database for future study.

The FSK will be helpful for future risk assessments.

The results in WP3 on seafood risk assessment can also lead to consideration if current legislation is adequate to mitigate microbiological hazards in aquaculture animals for human consumption.

The burden of disease caused by AMR exposure can also be better understood through the results of WP5 and could contribute to prevent resistant urinary tract infections.

The One-Health source attribution model that estimates the relative contribution of reservoirs and transmission routes to AMR (ESBL E. coli) carriage in the population can be used to help policy makers in ranking and setting priorities regarding intervention strategies.

As an extra result, JRP3-WP5-T5 “a proposal for a new paradigm for AMR surveillance” showed that metagenomics surveillance is a suitable methodology for population based surveillance of AMR and observed that AMU and AMR are in general correlated both at phenotypic and genotypic levels, besides other factors.

JRP04-MAD-VIR

Final report

1 Consortium composition

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2 Summary of the work carried out in the JRP

The aim of the MAD-Vir Project was to further develop and validate a metagenomics PanVirus microarray for fast detection of viral FBZ agents and emerging threats. The PanVirus microarray provides a rapid, simultaneous and unbiased detection of all known virus species and identification of novel virus types or strains belonging to currently known virus families (viral genomes present in Genbank). This metagenomics PanVirus microarray is very fast, easy and cheap (compared to NGS), does not require any bioinformatics skills or super computers and can eliminate the need for a specific clinical hypothesis regarding the disease causing viral pathogen.

The PanVirus microarray technology has been implemented in four EU reference laboratories and a standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P has been harmonized between three of the four laboratories. Ring-test trials and molecular EQAs have ensured the specificity and sensitivity of the method in all four laboratories. Several other European reference laboratories have expressed an interest in implementing the PanVirus microarray technology and it is expected that at least five additional Institutes will implement the technology in 2020, beyond the end of the MAD-VIR project.

In the MAD-VIR project, 1210 samples of human and animal origin have been analysed with the PanVirus microarray. Of these samples, 432 samples contained a known virus content previously identified by either qPCR/RT-qPCR, sequencing, negative EM staining, serology (ELISA) or other microarrays. The remaining samples contained an unknown virus content that either had not previously been analysed or was tested negative using standard diagnostic methods.

The PanVirus microarray detected 94% of all PCR confirmed positive samples with a known viral content. A 100% detection was observed for cell culture isolates, gastrointestinal samples, respiratory samples, serum samples, plasma samples and external materials such as skin swaps, biopsies etc. For urine samples and sample belonging to the central nervous system and internal organs the detection was 91%, 95% and 98%, respectively. The lowest detection was observed in samples from water-living animals such as fish (40%) and whole blood-samples (53%). A key element in the PanVirus microarray S.O.P is whole genome amplification (WGA) of DNA virus and whole transcriptome amplification (WTA) of RNA virus. Analysis of the WTA/WGA showed that the amplification was inhibited/lowered in fish and whole blood samples, for unidentified reasons. These results show that almost all sample materials from all species can be analysed by the PanVirus microarray.

The metagenomics PanVirus microarray also detected additional unknown co-infections in 48% of the samples with a known virus content. Co-infections were predominantly identified in domestic farm animals (70%) and in samples from the gastrointestinal system (76%) with up to 10 different viruses belonging to different virus genus and species. In the samples with unknown etiology, the PanVirus microarray identified virus in 38% of these samples with a viral content of up to 10 different viruses. In samples from insects and domestic farm animals, 64% and 58% respectively, were virus-positive. These findings are currently being investigated further by the interested MAD-VIR partners and will continue beyond the end of the MAD-VIR project.

In summary, the MAD-VIR project showed that the dispersed, implemented and harmonized PanVirus microarray method/technology has a clinical sensitivity comparable to diagnostic RT-qPCR/qPCR assays in all sample materials tested except fish and whole blood. These results show that the metagenomics PanVirus microarray is a fast, easy, and inexpensive alternative to NGS for detection of all unknown viral FBZ agents, multiple viruses and novel emerging threats, might aid in an early identification of zoonotic pathogens, and will aid in sustained European outbreak preparedness and response.

3 Work carried out, the main results

WP1. Coordination and management

The Project management and coordination of the project has proceeded according to the plan. At the One Health EJP website (<https://onehealthejp.eu/>) in the MAD-VIR group (<https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/mad-vir/>) all documents such as reports, deliverables, publications, newsletters, metadata and results have been uploaded.

All raw microarray data files and a metadata spreadsheet will be unloaded to the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/info/submission.html>) in connections with submission the MAD-VIR manuscript to a peer-reviewed scientific journal (see section regarding publications and patents).

WP2. Sample collection

Each partner in the project selected different samples of interest from their biobanks to be tested with the PanVirus microarray in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th round. A common standardized sample pre-treatment/inactivation protocol was followed when possible.

In total 1210 samples were collected and tested by the PanVirus microarray at SSI, INIA, PIWET and APHA (Table 1).

Table 1: The total number of samples analyzed by PanVirus microarray

Institute	No. of samples							
	SSI 1 st round	SSI 2 nd round	SSI 3 rd round	SSI 4 th round	PIWET	INIA	APHA	Total
PIWET	14	25	30		26			95
INIA	5	20	25	25		6		81
IZSAM	10	20	25			16		71
NPHC (OIK)	16	20	30	31				97
ANSES	8	37	14					59
VRI	3	20	25	19				67
IZSLER	12	46	25	26				109
UoS		20	13	34				67
APHA		17	18	33			13	80
SSI	58	80	196	47	34	34	34	483
Total	126	305	401	215	60	56	47	1210

The samples were from wild-life (rabbit, wild boar, duck, pheasant, stork, tortoise, hare, wolf, pigeon, springbook, deer, buffalo, crow, pteropus vampyrus, partridge, eagle, owl, hedgehog and mouse etc), Domestic farm animals (cat, goat, cow, chicken, horse, turkey, pig, sheep etc), ZOO animals (elephant, lemur, bee-eaters etc), Insects (*aedes*, ticks, midglets, sandflies etc.), water living animals (dolphin, fish, tadploes etc.) and human samples.

WP3. Diagnostic and surveillance

JRP4-WP3-T1: Technology transfer (M0-M20)

SSI has made special arrangements with Agilent Technologies so that INIA, APHA and PIWET can directly order the non-commercial custom made SSI PanVirus microarray v2, v3.1 and v3.2 designs, even beyond the end of the MAD-VIR project.

All standard operating procedures (S.O.Ps), microarray files for scanning and data analysis have been standardized and distributed to INIA, APHA and PIWET.

SSI (MWR) has visited the three reference Institutes and implemented the PanVirus microarray technology (INIA; 15th - 25th of April 2018, PIWET; 10th - 20th of June 2018, APHA; 25th - 26th of June 2018). Training in sample preparation, microarray technology and data-analysis have been performed at each Institute. The visit at APHA was shorter because APHA was already using another in-house pan viral pathogen microarray and was familiar with the microarray technology.

APHA has not been using the standardized S.O.P for the PanVirus microarray but instead used an in-house protocol. The first ring-test showed that the APHA in-house protocol was not as sensitive as the PanVirus microarray standardized S.O.P and could not detect DNA-virus (Table 4 in the “QA-validation section”). Instead of using the standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P, APHA decided to optimize their own in-house protocol. They replaced a random PCR amplification step with a WGA/WTA amplification step (a key element in the standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P) (Erlandsson et al., 2011, Rosenstjerne et al., 2014), in order to increase the detection of DNA virus (Table 2). The assessment performed at APHA is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Assessment of the efficiency of the REPLI-g Cell WGA & WTA kit in amplifying DNA and RNA viruses

VIRUSES	SAMPLE TYPE	EXTRACTS (60µL) CT VALUES	AMPLICONS CT VALUES/ADJUSTED ^A	MICROARR AY
PORCINE CIRCOVIRUS-3 (PCV-3)	Tissue	18.9	14.6/6.0	PCV-3
PORCINE PARVOVIRUS (PPV)	Tissue	14.0	10.8/2.2	PPV
SCHMALLEMBERG VIRUS (SBV)	Tissue	15	9.6/1.0	SBV
ATYPICAL PORCINE PESTIVIRUS (APPV)	Cell culture	29.6	25.1/16.5	APPV
BOVINE VIRAL DIARRHOEA VIRUS (BVDV)	Tissue	25.2	14.3/5.7	BVDV
BORDER DISEASE VIRUS (BDV)	Cell culture	32.0	23.1/14.5	BDV
TALFAN VIRUS	Cell culture	24.4	17.5/8.9	Talfan virus
CLASSICAL SWINE FEVER VIRUS (CSFV)	Cell culture	23.5	19.2/10.6	CSFV

a: Ct values were adjusted for the dilutions introduced during REPLI-g Cell WGA & WTA kit amplification (1 in 7) and also 100-fold dilution of amplicons before qPCR.

APHA showed that the REPLI-g Cell WGA & WTA kit resulted in at least 10⁴ fold increase in starting DNA, which is similar to previous published results (Erlandsson et al., 2011, Rosenstjerne et al., 2014).

APHA has also adopted a different labelling protocol to that used by the standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P. APHA uses amino allyl dUTP in the WTA/WGA amplification step to simplify the process of labelling DNA amplicons (Table 3).

Table 3: Assessing the effect of amino allyl dUTP on REPLI-g Cell WGA & WTA kit amplification efficiency.

VIRUS	AMINO ALLYL DUTP	AMPLICONS CT VALUES/ADJUSTED ^A	AMPLICONS CLEAN-UP	MICROARRAY RESULTS	MICROARRAY SIGNAL AVERAGES (LOG ₂)
PCV-3	Yes	13.5/4.9	MinElute PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen)	PCV-3	4.2
PCV-3	Yes	15.0/6.4	QIAamp spin columns & AL buffer (Qiagen recommendation)	PCV-3	4.1
PCV-3	No	13.0/4.4	Not applicable		
BVDV	Yes	18/9.4	MinElute PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen)	BVDV	7.1
BVDV	Yes	16.0/7.4	QIAamp spin columns & AL buffer (Qiagen recommendation)	BVDV	6.8
BVDV	No	16.0/7.4	Not applicable		

The preliminary findings of this alternative labelling method indicate that the amino allyl dUTP has no or negligible adverse effect on REPLI-g Cell WGA & WTA kit amplification efficiency (Table 3). The microarray outcome also indicates that the two procedures/kits used to clean the amino allyl dUTP labelled amplicons are equally adequate for the purpose.

The significant difference between the two microarray S.O.Ps is that the APHA S.O.P uses an amino allyl dUTP labelling during the WGA/WTA amplification whereas the PanVirus microarray S.O.P have separate labelling steps using Cy3 and/or Cy5 dUTPs. The APHA protocol reduces some of the handlings steps and reagents; however, the use of amino allyl dUTP labelling during the amplification eliminates

multiplexing and therefore increases the use of microarray slides. Both protocols can be performed within 1½ day.

APHA has expressed that they will not use the standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P due to the cost of reagents and analysis time. Because of this, the standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P has not been harmonized among all partners in the MAD-VIR project. The PanVirus microarray has been harmonized among INIA, PIWET and SSI and in 2020, the standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P is going to be implemented at IZSAM (another MAD-VIR partner). After the EVD-LabNet meeting in November 2019 (see section about dissemination and additional output) several other European Laboratories have expressed an interest in setting up the PanVirus microarray and collaborations has been initiated with four other Institutes.

JRP4-WP3-T2: QA-validation (M0-M20)

SSI has sent virus positive samples (purified or non-purified inactivated samples) to INIA, PIWET and APHA for ring testing in 2018 and 2019 (Table 4, 5 and 6). All the samples were Quality Control EQA samples for Molecular diagnostics (QCMD) from different test panels in 2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019.

In the 1st ring-test INIA detected 12/12 samples, PIWET 11/12 samples and APHA 6/12 samples¹ and 11/12 samples² (Table 4 and supplementary Table 1-4).

Table 4: Ring-test no. 1 - selected samples from different QCMD test panels

Sample no.	Virus content	Virus type	SSI	PIWET	INIA	APHA ¹	APHA ²
1	Zika virus	RNA	+	+	+	+	+
2	Chikungunya virus	RNA	+	+	+	+	+
3	Dengue virus type 2, West Nile virus, Yellow fever virus	RNA	+,+,+	+,+,+	+,+,+	+,+,+	+,+,+
4	Measels virus	RNA	+	+	+	+	+
5	Varicella Zoster virus	DNA	+	-	+	-	+
6	Cytomegalovirus	DNA	+	+	+	-	+
7	Adenovirus type 1	DNA	+	+	+	-	+
8	Human herpes virus type 1	DNA	+	+	+	-	+
9	Parechovirus type 1	RNA	+	+	+	+	+
10	Mumps	RNA	+	+	+	+	+
11	Epstein–Barr virus	DNA	+	+	+	-	-
12	Human herpes virus type 2	DNA	+	+	+	-	+

¹APHA in-house protocol no.1 (original S.O.P using random PCR amplification), ²APHA in-house protocol no. 2 (adapted S.O.P using WTA/WGA amplification)

In the 2nd ring-test INIA detected 8/12 samples, PIWET 9/12 samples and APHA 6/12 samples (Table 5 and supplementary Table 1-4).

Table 5: Ring-test no. 2 - selected samples from different QCMD test panels

Sample no.	Virus content	Virus type	SSI	PIWET	INIA	APHA ²
1	Human coronavirus OC43 (Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 2, Bovine polyomavirus 1, Bovine parvovirus 2, Border disease virus C413)*	RNA	+	(+)	-	-
2	Human parainfluenza virus 2 (Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 2, Bovine parvovirus 2, Border disease virus C413)*	RNA	+	+	+	+

3	Enterovirus (Pestivirus type 1, Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 2, Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 1, Border disease virus C413)*	RNA	+	+	-	+
4	Human parvovirus B19	DNA	+	-	+	-
5	Human Herpesvirus type 5	DNA	+	+	+	-
6	Human Herpesvirus type 1	DNA	+	+	+	+
7	Zika Virus (French Polynesian)(Pestivirus type 1, Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 1)*	RNA	+	-	-	-
8	Human Metapneumovirus A	RNA	+	-	+	-
9	Human adenovirus type 4	DNA	+	+	n.a	+
10	HHV6 type A, HHV6 type B	RNA	+	+	+	-
11	Human rhinovirus A90 (Pestivirus type 1, Bovine viral diarrhoea virus, Border disease virus C413)*	RNA	+	+	+	+
12	Enterovirus 68 (Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 2, Border disease virus C413)*	RNA	+	+	+	+

²APHA in-house protocol no. 2 (adapted S.O.P using WTA/WGA amplification). *many of the samples also contain Bovine Pestivirus, Bovine Parvovirus, Bovine polyomavirus that are contaminants from cell culture cultivations. n.a; not analyzed

These results indicated that the integrity of the 2nd ring-test may have been compromised during shipment, which was confirmed by PCR analysis of the samples at INIA (Supplementary Table 2). Therefore, a 3rd ring-test was shipped to INIA, PIWET and APHA in September 2019 (Table 6 and supplementary Table 1-4).

Table 6: Ring-test no. 3 - selected samples from different QCMD test panels

Sample no.	Virus content	Virus type	SSI	PIWET	INIA	APHA ²
1	Human parainfluenza virus 4a , Pestivirus type 1, Bovine viral diarrhoea virus, Border disease virus*	RNA	+	+	+	+
2	Human respiratory syncytial virus, Human orthopneumovirus , Bovine viral diarrhoea virus, Border disease virus C413, Pestivirus type 1*	RNA	+	+	+	+
3	Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus	RNA	+	+	+	+
4	Dengue virus 4 , Border disease virus C413, Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 2, Pestivirus type 1*	RNA	+	+	+	+
5	Human adenovirus type 7	DNA	+	+	+	+
6	Human adenovirus type 31	DNA	+	+	+	+
7	Human parvovirus B19 ,	DNA	+	+	+	+
8	Human herpesvirus 4	DNA	+	+	+	+
9	Human herpesvirus 2 , Bovine polyomavirus 1, Bovine parvovirus 2*	DNA	+	+	+	+
10	Human herpesvirus 5 , Torque teno virus (TTV) 16	DNA	+	+	+	-

²APHA in-house protocol no. 2 (adapted S.O.P using WTA/WGA amplification). *many of the samples also contain Bovine Pestivirus, Bovine Parvovirus, Bovine polyomavirus which are contaminants from cell culture cultivations. n.a; not analyzed

In the 3rd ring-test INIA detected 10/10, PIWET 10/10 and APHA 9/10 samples (Table 6 and supplementary Table 1-4). APHA is using the slightly different in-house protocol, which may contribute to the negative outcome for the gamma herpesvirus samples used in the ring trials.

As an additional quality control the molecular EQA on yellow fever virus (YFV) organized by EVD-LabNet EVD-LabNet was tested at SSI using the PanVirus microarray v2 (Table 7).

TABLE 7: TESTING OF THE MOLECULAR EQA ON YELLOW FEVER VIRUS (YFV)

QCMD-SAMPLE	Material	Virus content	Copies/vial	Detection by RT-qPCR	Detection by PanVirus array v2
YFV 1	plasma	YF strain 17D	5,4x10 ³	+	+
YFV 2	Plasma	YF strain American	3,5x10 ⁴	+	+
YFV 3	Plasma	YF strain American	3,4x10 ³	+	-
YFV 4	Plasma	Zika, WNV, DENV	unknown	+,+,+	+,+,+, +PIV-5
YFV 5	Urine	YF strain American	3,5x10 ⁵	-	-
YFV 6	Plasma	YF strain American	4,7x10 ⁶	+	+
YFV 7	plasma	Neg. ctrl		-	-
YFV 8	Plasma	YF strain American	2,8x10 ⁶	+	+
YFV 9	Plasma	YF strain American	2,8x10 ⁵	+	+
YFV 10	Urine	Neg ctrl		-	-
YFV 11	Urine	YF strain Africa	2,3x10 ³	-	-
YFV 12	Plasma	YF strain Africa	4,8x10 ⁵	+	+
YFV 13	Plasma	YF strain Africa	3,7x10 ³	+	+
YFV 14	Plasma	YF strain 17D	6,5x10 ⁴	+	+
YFV 15	Plasma	YF strain Africa	4,9x10 ⁴	+	+

The PanVirus microarray v2 performed similar to the in-house YFV RT-qPCR assay and the correct viruses were detected in all samples except the urine samples (Table 7). The urine samples were negative in both assays, which could indicate that the integrity of these samples have been compromised during storage in the freezer. The PanVirus microarray also detected Parainfluenza 5 virus (PIV-5) in the Zika, WNV, and Dengue virus (DENV) positive sample (Supplementary Table 1).

Two additional Molecular EQAs; the Neurotropic disease viruses (2018) and the Orthopox viruses (2019) organized by EVD-LabNet were tested at SSI using the PanVirus microarray v3.1 (Table 8 and Table 9).

TABLE 8: TESTING OF THE MOLECULAR EQA FOR NEUROTROPIC DISEASE VIRUSES (2018)

QCMD-SAMPLE	Material	Virus content	Copies/vial	Detection by RT-qPCR	Detection by PanVirus array v3.1
1	plasma	Toscana lineage A	3,50x10 ⁵	+	+, +Chikungunya
2	Plasma	Toscana lineage B	2,48x10 ⁵	+	+
3	Plasma	TBE	1,01x10 ⁵	+	+
4	Plasma	WNV lineage 1	1,44x10 ⁵	+	+
5	Plasma	WNV lineage 2	9,92x10 ⁵	+	+
6	Plasma	Usutu	1,27x10 ⁴	+	+
7	plasma	Neg ctrl.		-	-
8	Plasma	Neg ctrl.		-	-
9	Plasma	Neg ctrl.		-	-
10	Plasma	Neg ctrl.		-	-

TABLE 9: TESTING OF THE MOLECULAR EQA FOR ORTHOPOX VIRUSES (2019)

QCMD-SAMPLE	Material	Virus content	Copies/vial	Detection by Orthopox qPCR	Detection by PanVirus array v3.1
1	plasma	Monkey pox	25.7	+	+
2	Plasma	Monkey pox	29.2	+	+
3	Plasma	Monkey pox	29.6	+	+
4	Plasma	Neg ctrl.	-	-	-
5	Plasma	Monkey pox	28.2	+	+
6	Plasma	Monkey pox	34.9	+	+
7	plasma	Monkey pox	36.3	+	+
8	Plasma	Neg ctrl. (ORF)	29.5	-	+
9	Plasma	Cowpox	29.8	+	+
10	Plasma	Cowpox	28.0	+	+
11	Plasma	Neg ctrl. (HSV-1)	29.9	-	+
12	Plasma	VACV	28.2	+	+
13	Plasma	Neg ctrl. (VZV)	32.8	-	+

The PanVirus array v3.1 performed similar to the different neurotropic virus RT-qPCR assays and the Orthopox virus qPCR assay and the correct viruses were detected in all samples (Table 8 and table 9). The PanVirus microarray also detected Chikungunya virus in a Toscana positive sample, which was confirmed by a specific Chikungunya virus RT-qPCR assay (Supplementary Table 1). The Orthopox virus negative controls containing ORF, HSV-1 and VZV were also detected by the PanVirus microarray and confirmed by specific qPCR assays (Supplementary Table 1).

In conclusion, the PanVirus microarray as a clinical sensitivity comparable the diagnostic RT-qPCR/qPCR assays when tested on molecular EQA panel samples.

JRP4-WP3-T3: Analysis of samples (M0-M20)

In total 1210 samples were collected and tested by the PanVirus microarray (Table 1 and Supplementary Tables 1-4). Of these samples, 1040 samples were analysed at SSI (supplementary table 1) and of these 432 samples contained a known virus. The remaining 608 samples contained an unknown virus content that either had not previously been analysed or was tested negative using standard diagnostic methods (Supplementary Table 1).

The content of this chapter describing the results will be disclosed after publication in peer reviewed journals

In summary, the MAD-VIR project showed that the PanVirus microarray has a clinical sensitivity comparable to diagnostic RT-qPCR/qPCR assays when tested on molecular EQA panel samples, cell culture isolates, gastrointestinal samples, respiratory samples, serum samples, plasma samples and skin swaps, skin biopsies, urine, samples from the central nervous system and internal organs. The method can be used on all sample materials from all species; however, caution should be made when analysing fish samples, insect samples and whole blood samples.

Many new virus findings were identified in the unknown samples (supplementary Table 1-4) and these are currently being investigated further by the MAD-VIR partners and will therefore not be described in this report.

However, to briefly show the usefulness of the PanVirus microarray as a metagenomics screenings tool for virus detection a few results are described below:

1. SSI identified for the first time Uukuniemi virus and a new Phlebovirus in danish *Ixodes ricinus* ticks (Petersen A et al., Ticks Tick Borne Dis. 2019 Aug;10(5):1028-1032). To obtain the Phlebovirus genome sequence, NGS was performed and sequence analysis revealed the presence of several novel Phleboviruses (Manuscript in preparation).
2. APHA investigated two syndromic disease outbreaks in animals. **I)** The first disease outbreak was a self-limiting disease involving multisystemic inflammation in stillborn and pre-weaned pigs with nervous disease. Widespread multisystemic inflammation, mainly lymphoplasmacytic, reflecting likely in utero viral infection was detected in tissues from seven stillborn piglets, four with arthrogryposis, and three 18-day-old piglets with postnatal tremor and paresis. One herd was affected in 2014 (retrospective analysis), the other in 2018. Stillborn and arthrogryptic piglets were in litters from sows of any parity, and in the 2018 incident, occasional piglets developed tremors and paresis post-natal. Virus microarray and next generation sequencing detected PCV-3 in all piglets with multisystemic inflammation. RT-PCR confirmed PCV-3 in all tissues with low Ct values and PCV-3 was demonstrated in association with histological lesions by ISH in two stillborn piglets with arthrogryposis from each of the two herds, and in two piglets with nervous disease. Tissues with low or no PCV-3 viral loads from pigs without multisystemic inflammation did not show PCV-3 genome by ISH (Manuscript in preparation). **II)** The second disease outbreak involved two juvenile male grey squirrels weighing 80 and 116 grams respectively that were being fostered at a UK wildlife hospital. The animals developed diarrhoea and died in 2010. On post mortem examinations, the animals were very thin and dehydrated with no abdominal fat. Stomach was distended with clotted milk with smooth cream mucosal surfaces. Small intestines was filled with creamy fluid content with yellow/green tinged distally and pale pink mucosal surfaces. Fluid yellow/green content was also present from caecum to rectum. Microarray analysis indicated the presence of an Aichivirus-like virus. To confirm the microarray outcome and obtain the virus genome sequence, NGS was performed and analysis of the sequence data revealed presence of a novel Kobuvirus (Manuscript in preparation).

In conclusion, the metagenomics PanVirus microarray is a very fast and very useful non-NGS-based metagenomics method for detection of unknown virus in human and animal samples (except fish and whole blood samples).

WP4. Data Sharing

The common EJP website (<https://onehealthejp.eu>) is used for the MAD-VIR project. A private MAD-VIR group has been generated and all microarray results have been uploaded to this group as metadata and shared between the MAD-VIR partners. Other documents such as minutes, newsletters, summary reports, deliverables etc. are also present in the MAD-VIR group. All MAD-VIR partners has joined the EJP website.

4 Achievements of the JRP

Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-1.1a	Kick-off meeting	6	6		Deliverable available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website.
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-1.1b	First annual meeting for the participating Institutes	24	17		The first annual meeting (2 nd meeting in total) was held at the 1 st ASM One Health EJP in Dublin in May. Deliverable available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website.
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-2.1	Collection of samples (maximum 1500 samples in total from year 2017 to 2019)	18	18		Deliverable available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website.
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-3.1	Implementation of MAD-VIR to INIA and APHA	6	6		Deliverable available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website.
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-3.2	QA-validation of MAD-VIR to INIA and APHA	12	10		Deliverable available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website.
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-3.3	MAD-VIR microarray analysis of minimum 500 samples	12	12		Deliverable available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website.
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-3.4	MAD-VIR microarray analysis of all collected samples (max. 1500)	24	24		A total of 1210 samples have been analyzed in the MAD-VIR project. Deliverable available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website.
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-4.1	Functional Website	12	12		The common EJP website (https://onehealthjep.eu) is used for the MAD-VIR project. All documents, reports, newsletters, metadata and results are available on MAD-VIR

<i>JRP name</i>	<i>Project deliverable number</i>	<i>Deliverable name</i>	<i>Delivery date from AWP</i>	<i>Actual delivery date</i>	<i>If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date</i>	<i>Comments</i>
						group of the One Health EJP website (https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/mad-vir/). All partners joined the website
MAD-VIR	D-JRP4-4.2	Fully updated Website	24	24		All documents, reports, newsletters, metadata and results are available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website (https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/mad-vir/).

Milestones

<i>JRP name</i>	<i>Milestone number</i>	<i>Milestone name</i>	<i>Delivery date from AWP</i>	<i>Achieved (Yes / No)</i>	<i>If not achieved: Forecast achievement date</i>	<i>Comments</i>
MAD-VIR	M-JRP4-1	Collection of samples (minimum 750 samples)	12	yes		The final sample collection is described in the final metadata file, the D-JRP4-3.4 and the final report available on MAD-VIR group of the One Health EJP website (https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/mad-vir/).

5. Publications and patents

Field samplings of Ixodes ricinus ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus micro-focus in Northern Zealand, Denmark. Petersen A, Rosenstjerne MW, Rasmussen M, Fuursted K, Nielsen HV, O'Brien Andersen L, Bødker R, Fomsgaard A. Ticks Tick Borne Dis. 2019 Aug;10(5):1028-1032. doi: 10.1016/j.ttbdis.2019.05.005. Epub 2019 May 19.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877959X18304205?via%3Dihub>

The metagenomics Panvirus microarray as a diagnostic tool for unknown emerging virus in a one-health perspective (working title). Rosenstjerne MW, Lecollinet S, Gonzalez G, Bigarré L, Moutailler S, Niczyporuk JS, Rzeżutka A, Kozyra I, Steinbach F, Dastjerdi A, Takács M, Nagy A, Ruzek D, Horton DL, Royall E, La Ragione R, Lavazza A, Savini G, Jiménez-Clavero MÁ, Fernandez-Pinero J, Llorente F, Fomsgaard A. Manuscript in preparation.

Additional output

The most relevant dissemination are highlighted here, although also reported under point 6.

Rosenstjerne MW, MAD-VIR consortium collaborates, Fomsgaard A. **Metagenomic Array Detection of emerging Virus in EU (MAD-VIR)**. Meeting: 16th Smögen Summer Symposium on Virology, Smögen, Sweden, 21-24/08/2019

Rosenstjerne MW, MAD-VIR consortium collaborates, Fomsgaard A. **Metagenomic Array Detection of emerging Virus in EU (MAD-VIR)**. Meeting: 4th EVD LabNet annual meeting, Thessaloniki, Greece, 4-6/11/2019

Rosenstjerne MW, MAD-VIR consortium collaborates, Fomsgaard A. **Metagenomic Array Detection of emerging Virus in EU (MAD-VIR)**. Meeting: SVA research day, Uppsala, Sweden, 12/11/2019

Rosenstjerne MW, Lecollinet S, Bigarré L, Moutailler S, Gonzalez G, Niczyporuk JS, Rzeżutka A, Kozyra I, Steinbach F, Dastjerdi A, Takács M, Nagy A, Ruzek D, Horton DL, La Ragione R, Lavazza A, Savini G, Jiménez-Clavero, MA, Fernandez-Pinero J, Llorente F, Fomsgaard A. **Metagenomic Array Detection of emerging Virus in EU (MAD-VIR)**. Poster at 1st One Health EJP ASM, Dublin, Ireland, 2019

Jiménez Clavero, M.A.; Llorente, F.; Fernández Pinero, J.; Fernández-Pacheco, P.; Cano-Gano-, C; Gallardo-Frontaura, C.; Pérez Ramírez, E.; Fomsgaard, A. and Rosenstjerne, M.W. **Testing of Pan-virus Metagenomic Array Detection assay (MAD-VIR) using panels of samples from animals experimentally infected with known viruses.** Meeting: 13th EPIZONE Annual Meeting, Berlin, Germany, 26-28/08/2019.

Dastjerdi A. **Detection of porcine circovirus-3 (pcv-3) in stillborn piglets with multi-systemic inflammation.** Poster at Epizone, Berlin, Germany, 26-28/08/2019.

6 One Health impact

The metagenomics PanVirus microarray was developed at SSI and is a very fast and simple non-NGS-based metagenomic method for detection of unknown virus in human and animal samples. The major advantages of the method are;

- Analysis time (1½ day from sample to result)
- A simple excel based data analysis method (does not require any bioinformatics skills or super computers)

- Simple basic laboratory equipment (Hybridization oven and Array scanner for glass slides containing a 532 nm laser (Cy3) and a 633/647 nm laser (Cy5))
- Simultaneous and unbiased detection of different virus species and identification of novel virus types or strains belonging to currently known virus families (viral genomes present in Genbank)

The simplicity of the method is a huge benefit when used as a screenings tool for detection of unknown viral FBZ agents, emerging threats and identification of new (zoonotic) human and animal pathogens.

The MAD-VIR project has validated the metagenomics PanVirus microarray, using a whole range of samples materials from different animal and human species. This has not only brought MED-VET partners closer together but also resulted in the identification of new virus types and viral pathogens in many different animal species. The many new results are currently being investigated in collaborations between the MED-VET partners, which will continue beyond the end of the MAD-VIR project.

The MAD-VIR project has also resulted in capacity building, training and implementation of a harmonized metagenomics technology in 3/4 MED-VET Institutes. The simplicity and robustness of the PanVirus microarray method have resulted in an easy implementation in the different laboratories, and the analysis of ring trials and molecular EQAs have, and will in the future ensure a specific and sensitive method. One disadvantage of the method is that viruses mutate which may influence the detection of new virus strains; however, the microarray can easily be updated with new probes for specific virus strains. All new future updated PanVirus microarray versions will be available for laboratories using the technology (free of charge).

The dissemination of the MAD-VIR project at International meetings have resulted in an enormous interest in the technology and several other European MED-VET Institutes and laboratories have expressed an interest in implementing the method. It is expected that at least five additional Institutes will implement the technology in 2020 (IZSAM, Italy; CSMM, Cyprus; HOH, Finland; DNPFI, Netherlands; IRBA, France). Hence, the implementation of the metagenomics PanVirus microarray as a virus detection method will continue beyond the end of the MAD-VIR project, which will lead to sustainability of the PanVirus microarray as a diagnostic assay.

The MAD-VIR project has so far resulted in an enormous interest within the scientific MED-VET community. It is expected that the publication of the manuscript describing the MAD-VIR project (and all the following manuscripts) will result in even more interest in the PanVirus microarray as a screening tool for detection of viral FBZ agents, emerging threats, multiple infections and identification of new (zoonotic) pathogens.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer1 (new evaluator)	Reviewer1 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	5	3	3
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	4	4	2
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	4	3	2
Integration	5	4	2
Sustainability	5	4	2
Impact of the project	1	4	3
TOTAL	24/30	22/30	14/30

AVERAGE: 20

Additional comment from the POC member

Note : I'd like to briefly criticize the evaluation criteria themselves:

- The scale seems to be biased to the 'good' side.
- From the 6 points (taking also 0 as a point), only 0 and 1 can be considered as insufficient or negative (weak and poor). The second (2) point in the scale is already Good. A total score of 12 over 30 (not even the midpoint) would mean GOOD.
- Good appears defined as: results are rather average of what could have been expected. I wouldn't calify a 'rather average' as 'good'. In classical reviews, good is better than average. Average is mediocre.
- There is not an intermediate point (say average). An intermediate point here could be set at 2.5 and would fall between good and very good, it wouldn't be average...

As evaluator, on the one hand, it is difficult not to give at least a good according to this scale and criteria description. On the other hand, if I think a project is 'good' but I don't think it reaches a 'very good', the final score will be low (12) in comparison with the standard evaluations we are used to.

Regarding the report template, I don't see the rationale for presenting the dissemination activities in complex and long tables, providing only a couple of characteristics of the seminar/meeting/publication but occupying much space.

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

This was an excellent proposal, aiming construction of the platform, based on the microarray system, for detection of all known viruses in various materials. The constructed PanVirus microarray allows for rapid, sensitive and cheap detection of the presence of viruses in majority of biological materials (fish and whole blood samples are exceptions). Therefore, the constructed system may be an outstanding tool for detection and identification of viruses in many laboratories.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The aim of the project "to develop and validate a metagenomics PanVirus microarray for fast detection of viral FBZ agents and emerging threats" was met properly. The MAD-VIR project validated the metagenomics PanVirus microarray, using a whole range of samples materials from different animal and human species. This project is well justified, it is pertinent and will contribute for the knowledge of viral FBZ agents and emerging threats. Some analyses are still in process, so the results have not been included in the final report.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Execution of the work plan and results are fully in alignment with the objectives outlined in the full proposal, although there are some deviations regarding the number of samples and the distribution among partners.

The proposal was to analyse 1500 samples in three labs, with a similar share, with a total cost of 1.3 ME and a request of 582k€.

As far as I understand, a total of 1210 analyses (around 80% of the objective) were performed of a smaller number of samples (some were repetitions or comparisons), this is not mentioned and difficult to deduct from the tables.

The project execution seems unbalanced among partners. Most samples (87%) were analysed by one lab SSI. Other two INIA, PIWET were trained in the technique and APHA introduced modifications to their own protocol. All three analysed 13% of the samples for comparison.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The obtained product is highly innovative. Its advantages over the known methods of detection of viruses are rapidity, low cost, and possibility to identify any known viruses in the tested sample. The only unsolved problem is poor efficiency in the case of samples from fish and whole blood samples. Unfortunately, the consortium failed to overcome this problem.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has delivered sound and scientifically qualified results, following the proposal initially submitted. The methodology used and the validation of the results was properly addressed. The multi-disciplinary, complementary approach between the consortium partners was delivered successfully and allowed to standardize the developed methodology. The viruses assessed are of animal and public health concern. Furthermore, the project permitted to identify new viruses.

Reviewer 3: POC member

This is a very focused, not very ambitious project with the main aim of validating one methodology of virus identification. Also, a comparison with other techniques (such as PCR) was foreseen.

In my view it is not exactly a research project, but a comparative study among European labs to validate an analytical technique. In the end, most partners provide the samples (from their own collections, not new samples) and one main lab analysed them. Three other labs implement the technique and analyse a low amount of samples as a way to test the quality of their performance.

There is not sufficient results analysis in the final report to judge the excellence and I have no access to deliverables nor publications. Results are mainly not given by the reason that publications are being prepared.

According to the proposal, the objective was to share and compare samples in these three labs. I understand that this was done only in the 13% of the samples.

It is not clear how many of the control analyses (other than microarray) were performed by all 10 partners. Most samples have not been checked with other techniques as control, as from the annex tables 1 to 4.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The realization of the project was effective and number of tested samples is impressive. Obtained results indicated that the proposed PanVirus microarray gives results comparable to their methods, while being more rapid, cheaper and allowing detection of any known viruses.

The only unsolved problem remaining is poor results with samples from fish and whole blood.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The management and the number of samples analysed were appropriate. The clinical sensibility value of the PanVirus microarray technology obtained from positive samples with a known viral content was high (94%). The results obtained indicate that this non-NGS-based metagenomics method could be used for detection of both known and unknown viruses in human and animal samples (except fish and whole blood samples). List of dissemination and communication activities included in the final report is high. However, taking into account the duration of the project, the effectiveness of the measures taken to exploit and disseminate the project results is still limited as only one manuscript has been published and other is in preparation.

Reviewer 3: POC member

To me, the personnel costs are underestimated in comparison with the other costs (or vice versa).

I cannot properly judge this part from the data provided in the report. The unbalance may be pointing to some kind of inefficiency of the coordination or to a lack of interest by partners, since in the end, only a few partners did the job (in fact most of the work was carried out by one partner) and other just provided the samples and two learned the technique.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

During realization of the project, close cooperation between members of the consortium was evident and very effective. Communication was excellent, and vast majority of results came from collaborative works.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The MAD-VIR project has a One Health approach and was successful in achieving relevant integrative activities that will allow partner organisations to further improve harmonization or alignment in order to better support their prevent-detect-response tasks.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Good interaction and capacity building from SSI to the other three labs with an active role in the array assays.

Harmonization was the main objective. Two labs were trained in this technique, harmonization was achieved between 3 labs SSI, INIA and PIWET. APHA used its own approach, even though it was improved to reach a higher sensitivity. The standardized PanVirus microarray S.O.P has not been harmonized among all partners in the MAD-VIR project, authors say. Only INIA, PIWET and SSI harmonized the methodology.

Again, most of the samples were analysed by only one lab SSI. Apparently, the role of some partners has been providing the samples.

The coordinator reports one publication signed by Danish partners, presumable not as a result of this project. *Field samplings of Ixodes ricinus ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus micro-focus in Northern.*

Nevertheless, I cannot access the details of this publication such as acknowledgements, which could be relevant to the funding source.

Other articles, presumably joint papers, are in preparation.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The realization of the project was sustainable and various aspects of the research and the implementation were considered.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Developments achieved by the project will be maintained within the organisations of the consortium and have been implemented and standardized in three EU reference laboratories. Moreover, other European reference laboratories have expressed an interest in implementing the PanVirus microarray technology.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The cost per analysis is 281 Euro. 1,5 days to perform... It seems expensive in comparison with PCR. Share of collections is a positive aspect.

All the samples for the ring analyses were Quality Control EQA samples for Molecular diagnostics (QCMD) from different test panels in 2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019. No comparison with real samples?

A good result reported is that many new virus findings were identified in the unknown samples (supplementary Table 1-4) and these are currently being investigated further by the MAD-VIR partners, which will continue beyond the end of the MAD-VIR project.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The impact of the project is the major problem identified in the final report. Although the results of the project were presented at several conferences, and are available at web pages related to the project, the major weakness is almost complete lack of publications. According to the report, only one research article has been published as a result of realization of this project. Moreover, this paper concerns a side effect of the project, rather than description of the major results. The lack of publication of the main results (which are in fact excellent) makes the dissemination effects poor, and should be improved by preparing papers describing the PanVirus microarray and its use in detection of viruses.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

This project will certainly have an important social impact. The standardization of the metagenomics PanVirus microarray can be a useful, fast and economic tool to detect known virus species and identification of novel virus types or strains belonging to currently known virus families. The implementation of this methodology may have an impact over a long period of time and the results of the project likely will have positive impact on the economy as well as on the animal and public health.

Reviewer 3: POC member

No financial report available. No cost/benefit analysis. The cost per analysis seems high for a routine approach. This technique can be interesting for research purposes.

Some other labs seem interested in the implementation of the microarray detection, although those were not the MAD-VIR project partners (only IZSAM). The additional Institutes interested in the technology in 2020 (CSMM, Cyprus; HOH, Finland; DNPFI, Netherlands; IRBA, France).

New virus findings are currently being investigated further by the MAD-VIR partners, which will continue beyond the end of the MAD-VIR project.

In view of the latest crisis, some of the objectives of this project may have an application to the identification of COV-SARS-2, although PCR appears to be the first choice.

JRP05-TOX-DETECT

Final report

1 Consortium composition

This is the consortium composition as presented in the project proposal. Please correct if any changes occurred to the consortium during the project life-span.

Project coordinator:

Dr Jacques-Antoine HENNEKINNE (deputy: Dr Yacine NIA). P1 (Anses).

Applicants:

- **P1:** Anses, Laboratory for Food Safety (Dr J.-A. Hennekinne, Dr Y. Nia); Laboratory for Hydrology, MALDI-ToF -based technological identification platform (Dr B. Gassilloud); Laboratory of Fougères, High content cellular analysis platform (Dr V. Fessard, Dr K HOGEVEEN).
- **P4:** Sciensano (before WIP-ISP - Scientific Institute of Public Health) Organic Contaminants and Additives, unit toxins (Dr J. Masquelier, Dr M. Andjelkovic until 01-09-2018); Foodborne Pathogens- unit toxin producers and toxins (Dr T. Van Nieuwenhuysen, Dr S. Denayer until 31-12-2020)
- **P9:** BfR (German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment) (Dr S. Marino, Dr H. Frentzel).
- **P18:** INRAe (National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment), MICALIS Institute, PIMs group (Dr N. Rama Rao) and GME group (Dr M. Gohar) ; Microbiology research unit UR454 and Plate-Forme d'Exploration du Métabolisme composante protéomique [PFEMcp] (Dr M. Hébraud).
- **P19:** IP (Institut Pasteur), Structural Mass Spectrometry and Proteomics Unit (Dr J. Chamot-Rooke); Collection of Institut Pasteur (Dr D. Clermont); French National reference center for anaerobic bacteria and botulism (Dr C. Mazuet).
- **P33:** NVI (Norwegian Veterinary Institute) (Dr T. Skjerdal)

Short CV of each participating key scientist (at least one per participating organization)

P1: Anses

Jacques-Antoine HENNEKINNE (male, 45 years-old) has a PhD degree in life sciences (AgroParis Tech, Paris). At Anses since 2000, he manages the staphylococci, bacillus, clostridia and milk unit. This unit is in charge of both national and European mandates for staphylococci and milk. He conducts research activities in the field of toxigenic bacteria. He was work package leader of the FP7 EQUATox program (www.equatox.eu) dedicated to potential misuse of bacterial toxins from 2012 to 2014. He participated in the development of certified reference material containing staphylococcal enterotoxin A in close collaboration with the JRC-IRMM. He currently leads the TAG12 of the CEN Mandate M/381 dedicated to standardization of analytical methods to screen SEs content in food matrices. He authored 27 publications and 4 book chapters.

Yacine NIA (male, 42 years-old) obtained his PhD in 2011 (Aix-en-Provence University) dealing with contamination and metals' speciation in the environment. He is deputy head of unit staphylococci, bacillus and clostridia, and responsible of National Reference Laboratory for Coagulase Positive Staphylococci. In the frame of the reference activities, he was coordinator of European Inter Laboratory Proficiency Tests. His research activities are in the field of SEs detection in food matrices by ELISA and Mass spectrometry methods.

Valérie FESSARD (female, 48 years-old) is a toxicologist who graduated in 1996 as a PhD at the University of Paris 7 and then worked for one year at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory (UK) (European Science Foundation post-doctoral fellow). Since 1997, she has been working at the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (Anses). She has now nearly 20 years' experience in food toxicology, dealing in particular with the detection and hazard characterization of toxins contaminating food and drinking water such as phycotoxins and cyanotoxins. As the head of the unit "Toxicology of contaminants", she has a long experience in genotoxicity with in vitro and in vivo assays. She is also involved in the development of detection methods for unknown toxins using effect-directed analysis, as well as in the improvement of the methods used for predicting human toxicity through new cell models and high throughput investigation.

Kevin HOGVEEN (male, 47 years old) is a toxicologist in the Contaminant Toxicology Department at ANSES, Fougères. Kevin obtained his PhD in Pharmacology and Toxicology in 2003 from the University of Western Ontario (Canada). Since 2009, he has been working at the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES). With over 12 years of experience in food toxicology, Kevin has significant expertise in in vitro toxicology and High Content Analysis-based approaches. Other areas of scientific interest include the hazard characterization of toxins and nanomaterials, as well as the development of new cellular models and high throughput assays for predictive toxicology.

Benoit GASSILLOUD (male, 42 years-old) is a water microbiologist who graduated in 2003 as a PhD at the University of Henry Poincaré in Nancy in the field of environmental viruses, and then worked for 1 year in the Laboratory of Environmental Chemistry, Physics and Microbiology (LCPME-CNRS-UMR7564) on the development of a concentration process for viral detection in bottled mineral water. 2004. Since 2005, he has been working at the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (Anses) as the head of the water microbiology department, Nancy Laboratory for Hydrology. He has now more than 11 years' experience in water microbiology, dealing in particular with the detection and characterization of water-borne pathogens (bacteria, viruses and parasites). In 2013, he took the head of the MALDI-ToF Platform which is a structure that could be use by all the laboratories of the agency for identification or typing bacteria and fungi strains using this technology.

P4: Sciensano (ex-WIV-ISP)

Julien Masquelier (male) is a senior pharmacist holding a PhD in biomedical and pharmaceutical sciences with a focus on the analyses of different compounds with LC-MS/MS. He is head of the toxins unit in the service Organic Contaminants and Additives of Sciensano. He conducts research on the myco-, phyco-, phyto- and bacterial toxins quantification in food, human and environmental matrices. He also has more than 10 years of experience with LC-MS method development and is involved in both European and Belgian research projects dealing with toxins and food safety.

Tom Van Nieuwenhuysen (male) holds a PhD in biochemistry and biotechnology and is part of the service foodborne pathogens since 2017. He heads the unit toxins and toxin producers and is responsible for the NRL for botulism, the NRL for Coagulase Positive Staphylococci and the NRC for *C. botulinum*, *C. perfringens* and *C. tetani*. He is involved in several national and international projects dealing with bacterial toxins.

P9: BfR

Stephen F. Marino (male): is a protein biochemist with more than 20 years of experience in basic research. He holds M.Phil. and Ph.D. degrees in Molecular Biophysics and Biochemistry from Yale University. Before coming to the BfR, he conducted independent research in multiple Institutes in Switzerland and Germany, including the Max Planck Institutes for Biophysics and Brain Research, the Max Delbrück Centrum for Molecular Medicine of the Helmholtz Gemeinschaft and the Charité Universitätsmedizin in Berlin. His expertise includes the characterization of membrane receptors and ion channels, recombinant protein production, protein structure determination by X ray crystallography and cryo-electron microscopy and the development and characterization of

therapeutic antibodies. He supports the German National Reference Laboratory for coagulase positive *Staphylococcus* in developing and optimizing toxin detection assays and the production of reference material.

Hendrik Frentzel (male) is head of the Laboratory for sporeformers within the “Unit Bacterial Toxins, Food Service” in the Department Biological Safety. He studied Biology with a focus on microbiology and molecular biology at the universities of Greifswald and Potsdam and received his doctoral degree from the Freie Universität Berlin in 2017. After working experience at the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research and a private microbiological diagnostic laboratory he works as a scientist in the Department Biological Safety at the BfR, since 2010. His scientific work focusses on the detection of pathogenic microorganisms (especially members of the *Bacillus cereus*-group) in food and the characterization of these organisms by phenotypic and genotypic methods. This work includes taxonomic and phylogenetic analyses as well as the detection of genetic virulence determinants and produced virulence factors.

P18: INRAE

Nalini RAMA RAO (female) is the head of the PIMs (Pathogens, Immunity and Microbiota) team. She is a cell biologist/microbiologist specialized in host-pathogen interactions. She has a double education as a Biotechnology Engineer (International biotechnology engineering) and as a researcher (PhD, Max Planck Institute, Germany). She has been working on the interaction between *B. cereus* and host cells for the last 18 years and is now a recognized expert on *B. cereus* virulence factors and host-pathogen interaction. She has published significant papers dealing with host-pathogen interaction, and specifically with the mechanism of bacterial defence against the host immune cells. She studied the role and the expression of several virulent determinants and developed models to search for markers that could differentiate pathogenic from non-pathogenic *B. cereus* strains.

Michel GOHAR (male) worked in the research departments of pharmaceutical and crop protection companies for 16 years before joining INRA in 2003 as a senior scientist. He authors 45 articles, one book chapter and 3 patents, and his H-index is 20 (Web of Science, September 2015). His scientific expertise includes the molecular mechanisms involved in *B. cereus* pathogenesis and biofilm formation. He is a member of the GME (microbial genetic and environment) team included in MICALIS, an INRA/AgroParistech Research Institute of 300 people located on the INRA campus at Jouy-en-Josas. GME is a leader, at the international level, regarding the molecular mechanisms involved in the virulence of *B. cereus* and closely related bacteria. The other GME members involved in the project are the scientists Didier Lereclus (which leads the team), Leyla Slamti (expert in virulence factors regulation), and Alexei Sorokine (expert in comparative genomics).

Michel HEBRAUD (male) is a Research Director recruited within INRA in 1989. He works in the Research Unit of Microbiology (UR454) at the INRA Centre of Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, site of Theix. He is the scientific responsible of the proteomic component of the "platform of metabolism exploration (PFEM)". This proteomic component is dedicated to the identification and characterization of proteins and peptides by mass spectrometry. His research activities have focused on the adaptation of *Listeria monocytogenes* to food processing plants. In this context, his work concerned the molecular determinants involved in biofilm formation, the physiology of bacteria in biofilms, their resistance to cleaning disinfection treatments and the mechanisms by which some of them face to technological stresses. He has also worked on the biodiversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains by proteomics approaches.

P19: IP

Dominique CLERMONT (female) received a diploma of dental surgeon from University Lyon I in 1983, then a Ph.D. in Odontology, from University Paris VII in 1993. Following post-doctoral position at the Pasteur Institut (Laboratory of Streptococci and Enterococci) focusing on antibiotic resistance on *Streptococcus anginosus*, she joined the Collection de l'Institut Pasteur (CIP) as research engineer in 1997. Since this date, her research focuses on bacterial preservation, taxonomy and phylogenetic

studies as well as bacterial strain typing. She is also involved in the bacterial collection management of the CIP. At the national level, she participates in the French infrastructure BIOANQUES and is member of scientific committee of two biological resource centers (ICAReB Biobank and the International Centre of microbial resources (INRA-CIRM). She is in the steering committee of the Rapid project ANVBIS3 funded by Direction Générale de l'Armement (DGA) (2012-2016), co-coordinator in the transversal research project between Anses and Pasteur (IdBc) (2015-2017), and work package leader in the project pathoTOP (2015-2019) funded by the French National Agency for Research. At the European level, she participates in the European Infrastructure "MIRRI" (Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure) and she is scientific officer of the European Culture Collection Organization (ECCO).

Julia CHAMOT-ROOKE (female, 46 years old) is a CNRS senior scientist and head of the "Structural Mass Spectrometry and Proteomics" Lab at the Institut Pasteur in Paris, which gathers a research group and the Pasteur proteomics platform. Her research focuses on the development of new mass-spectrometry based methodologies for the analysis of proteins involved in infectious diseases. In last years, Julia Chamot-Rooke gained an international expertise in the development of top-down proteomics approaches applied to bacterial protein analysis. She published 70 papers in total in peer-reviewed journals (h-index: 21) and has been invited in 25 international conferences in the last three years. Julia Chamot-Rooke has been the coordinator of multidisciplinary projects funded by the French National Agency in 2009 and 2015. She is a past president [2008-09] of the French Society of Mass Spectrometry (SFSM) and the French representative of the International Mass Spectrometry Foundation. She is also a founding member of the International Consortium for Top-Down Proteomics. Her lab is equipped with the most recent high-resolution mass spectrometers (including 5 Orbitrap systems) and highly trained staff (15 people).

Christelle MAZUET (female, 46 years-old) is a biochemist who graduated in 1997 as a PhD at the University of Paris 11 and then worked for six years at the Pasteur Institute as a study director of the center "Allergy and Environment/Texcell". Since 2004, she has been working in the research unit "Anaerobic bacteria and toxins" headed by Michel-Robert Popoff at the Pasteur Institute. She has now 12 years' experience in anaerobic bacteria and bacterial toxins in particular with the development of new detection and characterization methods of botulinum toxins. As deputy director of the National Reference Center (NRC) "Anaerobic bacteria and Botulism" since 2008, she is also in charge of the technical and scientific activities of the team including animal and human botulism diagnosis and investigation of *Clostridium perfringens* and *Clostridium botulinum* outbreaks.

P33: NVI

Taran SKJERDAL (female) has more than twenty-year experience of research from research institutes and companies within the areas food quality, food safety, risk assessment and multidisciplinary decision support. The last 10 years she has worked at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute with food safety and bacteriology with focus on growth, survival, pathogenicity and adaptation of *Listeria* and *Staphylococcus* during food processing. The work includes research activities and support to food authorities. She has coordinated two EU funded projects DESCOD (FP4) and STARTEC (FP7) and been strongly involved in SEAFOODplus and BASELINE (FP6 and 7). Besides, she has been the supervisor for three PhD studies, one of them about incidence, toxin profiles, antibiotic resistance and genetic relatedness of *Staphylococcus* in Ethiopian milk and milk products. In addition, she has led several multidisciplinary research and innovation projects. The project has often been initiated by challenges for the food authorities and food trade and led to new tools, legislation or analytical methods. She was responsible for the national reference functions for coagulase positive *Staphylococci* (CPS) until July 2016. She was a guest researcher at the European reference laboratory (ANSES) in 2016.

Currently, she is also a member of the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety. She has more than thirty peer reviewed papers and book chapters in addition to two patents.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Bacterial toxins produced by *Staphylococcus* spp., *Bacillus* spp. and *Clostridium* spp. are responsible for a large number of food-poisoning outbreaks (FPOs) in the European Union. The true incidence of FPOs caused by these toxigenic bacteria is underestimated due to a lack of relevant detection tools and to a common symptomatology that makes outbreak investigation challenging. The One Health EJP TOX-Detect project uses three different non-NGS approaches for a better detection of *Staphylococcus* spp., *Bacillus* spp. and *Clostridium* spp and characterization of some of their toxins, including emerging threats that remain currently undetectable.

First, collections including strains from various sources (animal, environment, food and human) and different geographical locations in the EU were established under specific criteria selected by the consortium. Strains issued from this “strains collection” were used to analyze the RNAseq, PCR and cytotoxicity data and to study potential correlations between gene presence or expression with strain toxicity and virulence. The growth conditions of the strains, the cytotoxicity assays, the RNA extraction procedures and development of RNAseq assays were defined and optimized. The data were analyzed to allow gene expression and strain toxicity measurement. PCR and RNAseq methods were developed for both *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*. The analysis allowed to propose known as well as new biomarkers to characterize the strains.

A panel of three non-NGS based methods allowing characterization of the three studied pathogens and some of their toxins were developed: (i) MALDI-ToF , (ii) LC-MS¹ and (iii) ELISA methods.

For MALDI-ToF , a new library based on the selected strains collection was developed. Therefore, 152 reference spectra (MSP) from 76 strains were selected after the spectra-processing step. Comparisons and request access with the commercialized database showed high reliable scores that allow to differentiate these three species. The difficulty to differentiate species within the *B. cereus* group was highlighted. Transfer of this database was realized to the European Union Reference network through the organization of an inter-laboratory test.

Staphylococcus enterotoxins types SEM, SEN and SEO and *B. cereus* enterotoxin CytK2, hemolysin HlyII and Sphingomyelinase were selected for methods development, as there is a lack in commercially available methods to detect these toxins. In the absence of toxins standards, procedures for recombinant toxins production and purification were optimized. Stability studies showed that standards produced for Staphylococcal enterotoxins SEO and CytK2 are unstable and, consequently, cannot be transferred between partners for method development. Thus, standards for SEN, hemolysin HlyII and Sphingomyelinase have been produced and transferred to partners in charge of LC-MS methods development. For *Bacillus* enterotoxins, ELISA and LC-MS methods were developed, optimized and transferred to TOX-DETECT partners in order to evaluate their transferability. For Staphylococcal enterotoxins, LC-MS to target type SEN was developed and transferred to partners for inter-laboratory test.

Results obtained in the TOX-DETECT project allowed to enhance acknowledgment on strains producing toxins. Methods developed could be used by reference laboratories (NRLs and EURL) for further development and foodborne outbreak investigation, especially when it comes to non-classical toxins. Selected reference strains for *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* have been included in One Health EJP CARE project.

¹ Liquid Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry

3 Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP0. Coordination, management and communication

WP0-T1- Coordination, management and communication

The overall purpose of the management structure is to ensure the timely implementation of the tasks and the smooth running of the project as a whole. Its primary goal is to identify arising opportunities and detect the occurrence of obstacles as early as possible, hence maximise the outcome of the project while preventing delays in its implementation. In total, 57 meetings, web conferences and telephone conferences were organised by the coordination team over the 42 months of the project. Objectives were to manage the progress of different tasks and to discuss with partners on technical issues. Discussion and procedure of transfer of the collection of strains between TOX-DETECT partners and between TOX-DETECT and CARE projects were managed by coordination team. Finally, impact of Covid 19 crisis on TOX-DETECT project was also managed by the coordination.

WP0-T2 to T5: Organisation of four face-to-face meetings with all partners

The TOX-DETECT kick-off meeting held in Maisons-Alfort (France) from 28th of February to the 1st of March 2018 (M3). 16 participants representing all TOX-DETECT partners were present during the kick-off meeting.

The aims were:

- I. to introduce all project members;
- II. to get information on administrative and financial issues by representatives of EJP coordination team;
- III. to give an overview of the aims of the project and provide detailed information on all work packages;
- IV. to discuss open questions on the selection of the reference strains that should be used in this project

1st meeting was organized on 20 and 21 March 2019 at Anses (France). 15 participants representing all TOX-DETECT partners were present during this meeting. General discussion dealing with EJP projects took place after the presentation of Fanny Baudoin from One Health EJP general coordination. Briefly, she presented guidelines, specific rules, budget, communication tools and spoke about the possible 6-month extension. Special discussion sessions were dedicated to the coordination between WP3 and WP4 in order to transfer the produced enterotoxins in WP4 to WP3 for LC-MS development and protein characterisation.

2nd meeting was organized on 15 and 16 January 2020 at Anses (France). 23 participants representing all TOX-DETECT partners were present. C. Cordevant and A. Callegari were invited by the coordination of TOX-DETECT Project as SSB member and general coordination, respectively. All participants presented their activities and involvement in the TOX-DETECT project. A specific discussion was dedicated to the organization of inter-laboratory tests for each technique developed in WP1, WP3 and WP4.

3rd meeting was organized as web-meeting on 25 of June 2021. All partners were present. The aim was to discuss on the final report, and to present the restitution of WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4. Remaining tasks of WP5 (MALDI-ToF and ELISA inter-laboratory tests) were also developed.

WP0-T6: mandatory reports on network activities: interim activity report, final report

The coordination drafted and uploaded on One Health EJP website the interim and mandatory reports:

Report	Submission period
9 Month report for year 1	September 2018
9 Month report for year 2	September 2019
9 Month report for year 3	September 2020
12 Months report dispatched on	February 2019
Intermediate report (36M)	January 2021
24 Months report	February 2020
36 Months report	December 2020

WP1. Constitution of a reference strain collection for *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*

Criteria for selecting the strains have been defined in connection with the needs of other work-packages in order to select the most appropriate strains to be used for the development and harmonization of methods and databases. An inventory of available resources has been done and a list of reference strains with their associated data established with all partners. This collection includes strains from various sources (animal, environment, food and human samples) and different geographical locations.

WP1-T1- Constitution of *S. aureus* strains collection

80 *S. aureus* strains have been proposed by TOX-DETECT partners, representing human and food categories. The major part was issued from food poisoning outbreaks. The aim was to develop Ab against SEN and SEO toxins. Therefore, 21 strains encoding for SEN and SEO and a negative control (CIP 53.154) have been selected. Some of these strains have been exchanged between partners under a Material Transfer Agreement.

WP1-T2- Constitution of *B. cereus* strains collection

90 *Bacillus* (Bc) strains have been proposed by TOX-DETECT partners, representing human and food categories. The collection includes a total of 21 *B. cereus* strains. Some of these strains have been exchanged between partners under a Material Transfer Agreement.

WP1-T3- Constitution of *C. perfringens* strains collection

As in CPS and BC 54 *C. perfringens* (Cp) strains have been proposed by TOX-DETECT partners, representing human and food categories. The collection includes a total of 34 *C. perfringens* strains. Some of these strains have been exchanged between partners under a Material Transfer Agreement.

WP1-T4- Transfer of libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra

The MALDI-ToF reference spectra library has been developed using all strains referenced in tasks WP1-T1, T2 and T3. Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) was drafted and uploaded on EJP site. It will be accessible to the scientific community after the publication of this new database.

MALDI-ToF mass spectrometry was performed for bacterial species identification and for verification of purity of stock cultures as well as to establish a library of reference MALDI-ToF spectra. Protocol for protein extraction has been discussed, defined and shared among partners. For each strain, reference spectra (MSP) were generated using 26-32 spectra from total protein extracts spotted onto a target plate in eight replicates, and each spot was analysed four times. Acquisition of raw spectra was done with a laser frequency of 60 Hz, an acceleration voltage of 20 KV and extraction delay of 120 ns. All raw spectra were analysed according to the established MSP protocol of the MALDI Biotyper® V1.1 to remove suboptimal spectra. 152 MSP from 76 strains were selected after the spectra-processing step. 2 MSP have been created for each strain. Comparisons with the commercialized Bruker Daltonic

Database: Version 9.0.0 containing 9997 MSP (including 7 MSP for *B. cereus*, 14 MSP for *Staphylococcus* and 10 MSP for *C. perfringens*) were access. The request access with the commercialized Bruker Daltonic database shown high reliable scores that allow to differentiate these three species. A misinterpretation was obtained only for one strain for which a contamination was detected. The difficulty to differentiate species within the *B. cereus* group *sensu lato* was also highlighted. Technical and data processing transfer procedure has been established with partners before organization of a dedicated PT trial (cf WP5). This database was transferred to European Union Reference Laboratory network (11 National reference Laboratories) in June 2021. Technical assistance was provided by WP1 over the inter-laboratory period.

WP2. Characterization of toxins/virulence factors

WP2-T1- Characterization of candidate toxin and/or virulence genes using toxicity tests

This task was launched on M4. The 21 *B. cereus* strains selected in WP1 were tested for cytotoxicity using classical cytotoxicity tests. Among the 40 *C. perfringens* strains selected in WP1, a subset was tested using classical cytotoxicity tests. For those strains, the growth conditions of the strains (vegetative and sporulating) as well as the cytotoxicity assays were defined and optimized.

Following obtention of the strain supernatant of *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*, a suitable analytical method was developed for the determination of the cytotoxic potential of the strains. Potential effects of the supernatants on the pro-inflammatory response in Caco-2 cells (IL-8 secretion) was also investigated. Cellular imaging-based High Content Analysis approaches were developed and used to characterize the mechanisms of toxicity. A subset of strains were chosen based on results from classical cytotoxicity tests, and further evaluated for markers of apoptosis (active-Caspase-3), genotoxicity (γ H2AX, phospho-ATM), pro-inflammatory response (nuclear translocation of NF- κ B), mitochondrial membrane potential (TMRE) and cytotoxicity (Nuclear DAPI staining). The cytotoxic potential varies amongst strains, providing further insight into the complex mechanisms of *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* pathogenicity.

Figure 1: Cytotoxicity of bacterial culture supernatants from vegetative and sporulating cultures of *C. perfringens* (left) or *B. cereus* (right) in human intestinal Caco-2 cells.

WP2-T2- Assessment of virulence and toxin gene expression using RT-PCR and transcriptomic assays

This task was launched on M5. The aim of this task was to select genes over- or highly expressed in various strains within a panel of candidate genes suspected to play a role during *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* pathogenesis. In addition, a whole transcriptomic assay was performed (RNAseq technology) in various growth conditions.

WP2-T2-ST1- Optimization of growth conditions to be used for gene expression analysis

For *C. perfringens* different protocols were used: vegetative and sporulating as well as co-incubation with human intestinal Caco-2 cells. Changes were made to the *C. perfringens* sporulation protocol to optimize the production of virulence factors, including CPE. For *B. cereus*, the conditions were chosen based on two parameters, the oxygen level and the pH.

WP2-T2-ST2- Development of RT-PCR assays and transcriptomic analysis

For both organisms, the protocols of bacterial growth, RNA extraction and qRT-PCR were developed and optimized. RNAs were extracted and checked for purity and integrity. The RNA samples were then subjected to RNAseq analysis. Analytical methods were then developed to ensure a proper analysis of the data. These analytical pipelines were then successfully used to provide heat maps and PCA analysis, generating information on up and down regulated genes for each bacterial strain.

For *B. cereus*, 15 strains grown in microaerophilia at pH 7 were sent in triplicate for RNAseq analysis. 9-15 million reads per samples were obtained, with 90% correctly paired. The biological triplicates clustered well together and showed no major differences in the profile of their transcriptomes. 3276 genes were identified in the core transcriptome, which represents approximately 65% of the genes in each strain. 264 genes were found to be differentially expressed (up or down regulated), with p-values less than 0.01.

For *C. perfringens*, 5 strains grown in vegetative and sporulation conditions were selected for the RNAseq analysis. Comparing growth conditions (vegetative vs sporulation), a mean of 677 ± 290 were significantly differentially expressed, of which an average of 444 ± 123 were upregulated and 232 ± 169 genes were downregulated. The majority of differently expressed genes (60 % to 76 %) showed significantly upregulation in all vegetative growth condition compared to sporulation condition.

In conclusion, methods were developed as expected during this task, to 1) optimize growth conditions (subtask 2.1) and 2) develop qRT-PCR and transcriptomic analytical pipelines to successfully analyze and select genes (subtask 2.2).

This allowed to propose a panel of candidate genes to be further characterized during the task 2.3.

WP2-T3- Correlation of specific toxicity profiles with expression patterns of bacterial toxins/virulence factors

The objective of this task was to analyze the RNAseq, PCR and cytotoxicity data and study potential correlations between gene presence or expression with strain toxicity and virulence.

The growth conditions of the strains, the cytotoxicity assays, the RNA extraction procedures as well as the development of RNAseq assays were defined and optimized. The data were analyzed to allow gene expression/presence and strain toxicity and pathogenicity comparison.

First, the *B. cereus* strains were characterized by detecting by PCR the presence of ten genes involved in virulence. According to the presence/absence of the genes, the strains were assigned a genetic signature (GS). The assignment of strains according to their GS shows the genetic diversity of *B. cereus* strains.

Among the strains tested for cytotoxicity, a strong correlation could be identified between *hlyII* presence and high cytotoxicity. Similarly, a strong correlation could be measured between Nhe production and high cytotoxicity.

Figure 2: correlation between cytotoxicity and toxins

As such, it could be concluded that Nhe and HlyII were strong candidates for the development of further detection methods (WP3 and WP4).

For *B. cereus*, the RNAseq data were further analysed to provide correlation with strain pathogenicity. The strains were grouped according to the pathogenicity they induced (non-pathogen vs FBO or clinical strains). We used a penalized conditional logistic regression with the lasso method to select relevant genes for the prediction of pathogenic potential. By applying the prediction model to the 11,179 genes with the selected penalty constant of 0.01, 7 genes were selected as markers to differentiate the strains according to their pathogenicity.

Using this combination of genes, the best results obtained to compare non-pathogenic with FBO strains was an AUC of 0.768, the sensitivity 0.69 and the specificity 0.773.

Remarkably, regarding the clinical strains, the best results were achieved with an AUC of 0.955, sensitivity of 0.9 and specificity of 0.86. Therefore, the analysis concludes that an accurate differentiation between clinical and non-pathogenic strains can be obtained by using these biomarkers.

Figure 3: Best performing biomarker combination for non-pathogenic and clinical strains

Finally, the correlation of the gene expression/presence/absence with the toxicity profiles of the strains have been performed. Thus far, no correlation could be observed between the presence or the expression of the newly identified biomarkers and the cytotoxic potential of the strains.

Further analyses need to be performed to identify other biomarkers, which expression could correlate with cytotoxicity and/or HCA data.

Conclusions

The objective of this task was to analyze the RNAseq, PCR and cytotoxicity data and study potential correlations between gene presence or expression with strain toxicity and virulence.

The growth conditions of the strains, the cytotoxicity assays, the RNA extraction procedures as well as the development of RNAseq assays were defined and optimized. The data were analyzed to allow gene expression and strain toxicity measurement. PCR and RNAseq methods were developed for both *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*. The analysis allowed to propose known as well as new biomarkers to characterize the strains. We thus successfully implemented methods to answer the initial questions, we provided accurate SOP and the deliverables were obtained.

8 SOPs were drafted in this WP2 were uploaded on the OH EJP website.

WP3. Development of Mass Spectrometry-based proteomics procedures for detection of bacterial toxins and virulence factors

WP3-T1- Development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of new enterotoxins (eg SEG, SEH, SEI) from *S. aureus*

In this task, focus is laid on the development of an innovative analytical method for the quantification of three non-classical SEs (SEM, SEN and SEO) suspected to play a role in the notorious pathogenicity of *S. aureus*, specifically in food poisoning outbreaks. To this end, recombinant protein standards expressed in *E. coli* as part of WP 4 were subjected to a quality control, a sample preparation technique based on-filter digestion was developed with SEB pure well characterized standard (obtained from H2020 EuroBioTox project, <https://eurobiotox.eu/>) as a model protein and finally a targeted LC-MS² method with the on-filter digestion sample preparation was developed and validated for the quantification of SEN in cultures of *S. aureus*. To assess the quality of the recombinant SEM, SEN and SEO standards, both electrophoresis tools and mass spectrometry were used to verify the purity and amino acid sequence of each standard. The on-filter digestion sample preparation consisted of four major stages namely the filtration of the culture supernatant, the protein denaturation process, enzymatic protein digestion step and finally the elution of the obtained tryptic peptides. Each of the four steps was optimized with *S. aureus* enterotoxin B as a model protein while a standard culture of a *seb* and *sen* negative strain of *S. aureus* was used as blank matrix. Thereafter, the optimized sample preparation was applied and tested with the recombinant SEN standard for quantification by means of an UHPLC system coupled to a Orbitrap mass spectrometer. Separation of the different peptides was performed with a classical C18 column while their subsequent quantification was performed in parallel reaction monitoring mode. Subsequent validation of the obtained method was performed according to FDA guidelines for bioanalytical analyses. Thorough analysis of the three recombinant SE standards demonstrated that only SEN could be seen as a quantitative standard. Hence, only the rSEN standard was used for the development of a targeted LC-MS² method as proof of principle. Ensuing experiments showed that SEN was efficiently retained by the filter and sufficiently digested with the developed on-filter digestion technique. Due to the low expression of SEN, the method was validated in a range of 1 to 7.5 ng/mL, with 1 ng/mL as demonstrated limit of quantification (LOQ). The average recoveries calculated for the concentrations 1, 2.5, 5 and 7.5 ng/mL were respectively 114, 104, 102 and 99%. Calculated coefficients of variance for both repeatability and reproducibility were below 8%, while the calculated measurement uncertainty was below 20% for all nominal concentrations and below 30% for the established LOQ (1 ng/mL).

WP3-T2- Development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *B. cereus*

Characterizing foodborne toxigenic bacteria and detecting bacterial toxins is a key goal of the project. Here we focused our work on the development of a targeted LC-MS/MS method for the identification of two foodborne *Bacillus* bacteria virulence factors: Sphingomyelinase and Hemolysin-II (HLY-II). These toxins are part of a large number of other toxins that are secreted by the bacterium and responsible for foodborne infections. They were chosen among several other ones because they are present, even if in low amount, in many described strains.

The methods we developed are based on liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and more specifically on targeted methods.

The first step was the selection of the strain of *Bacillus cereus*. We then first decided to set-up a Top-down proteomics approach to identify toxins from bacterial supernatant. Top-down proteomics, in contrast to the usual bottom-up approach based on protein digestion, relies on the analysis of intact proteins. It allows uniquely addressing the different forms of a protein (proteoforms) present in a sample. However, the first top-down proteomics experiments indicated a very low sensitivity of the approach since no intact toxin could be identified in the bacterial supernatant. This was due to the

very low amount of toxins produced by *Bacillus cereus* strains in medium. We should note that this information was not available in the literature. It thus quickly appeared that we had to resort to the more usual bottom-up approach to set up our analysis. To maximize the sensitivity and thus the chance to identify our toxins of interest, we decided to develop a targeted bottom-up method called PRM (Parallel Reaction Monitoring) on a Q-Exactive mass spectrometer. Even with this sensitive targeted approach, the low amount of endogenous toxins in our samples led us to spike our samples with purified toxins (obtained from WP4, INRAe partner) for both method development and sample preparation. These spiked samples were used to set-up both LC conditions and MS parameters. We used the Pinpoint 1.1 software to achieve the selection of proteotypic peptides.

The full validation of the method was therefore implemented by using a nano-HPLC easy-1200 (ThermoFisher) system coupled to Q-Exactive plus mass spectrometer (ThermoFisher). A SOP has been prepared (see document in annex) in order to allow the transfer of the method to the project partners involved in the inter-laboratories tests.

WP3-T3- Development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *C. perfringens*

A nanoLC-PRM/MS method has been developed for the detection of *C. perfringens* enterotoxin CPE. Mass spectrometry allows the characterization of protein sequence and direct measurement of the toxin, leading to unambiguous identification and unequivocal evidence of its presence, with a sequence coverage up to 86% and at least 20 peptides identified. In parallel, sixteen other virulence factors as well as numerous proteins involved in the sporulation of the bacterium were present in the supernatant, confirming that the presence of CPE is dependent on sporulation. We have developed a method, focused on the detection of CPE, which is based on 6 peptides generated by its tryptic digestion, achieving a sequence coverage of 19.7%. As a protein standard is not commercially available in Europe, a strain from the TOX-DETECT collection was selected for its high CPE production under culture conditions developed by ANSES to serve as reference. A homogeneity test was performed on pooled supernatants of this reference strain and 4 out of 6 peptides were found homogenous with a CV of less than 20% and the carryover in the matrix blank was estimated to be less than 0.05%. Serial dilution experiment was performed by diluting the digested reference sample in the digested matrix blank and CPE was detected for dilutions up to 128th. The full validation of the method has been implemented by using nano-HPLC (column Acclaim Pepmap 100 C18, 3 μm 75 μm x 250 mm, ThermoFischer) system coupled to Q-Exactive HF-X mass spectrometer (ThermoFischer). A SOP has been drafted (see document in annex) in order to allow the transfer of the method to the project partners involved in the Inter-Laboratories Comparison tests.

WP3-T4- Transfer of LC-MS/MS methods

The three LC-MS/MS methods, developed in the T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 and focusing on the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*, respectively, were also implemented in laboratories of several other participants.

First, the new LC-MS/MS methods were developed and in-house validated, when quantitative standard was available (e.g. SEN). Then, for each analytical method, a detailed analytical protocol (and validation report, if done) was written and these protocols were drafted as SOP (see SOPs uploaded on the OH EJP site) before the transfer to the partners for implementation. These methods were transferred to the partners of the WP3 in order to test applicability of the methods before further implementation in WP5. Some adaptations were necessary, given the differences between the instruments used by the partners involved in WP3: Liquid chromatography systems (UHPLC vs nano LC) but also mass spectrometers (ThermoScientific - Q Exactive Focus vs ThermoScientific - Q Exactive HF-X) used for development and implementation were not always the same. Finally, with some modifications, results of the transfer were quite good, with acceptable qualitative results for all the three methods (See WP5). Inter-laboratory comparison tests and the obtained results by participants will be presented in deliverable D5.2 "Final report including results from the eight inter-lab tests".

WP4. Development of new immuno-enzymatic assays for detection of *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence determinants

WP4-T1- Development of quantitative immunoassays for five known *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence factors

WP4-T1-ST1- Selection of 5 target genes and construction of genetic tools for proteins overexpression

At the beginning of the project Staphylococcal Enterotoxins (SEs) G, H and I had been chosen as targets for the effort. These choices were changed in month 9 on the wish of the Coordinators to minimize overlap with contemporary projects and maximize the resources allotted to the TOX-DETECT Consortium. As of October 2018, the official targets were SEN and SEO. As genetic tool for overexpression of SEs in *E. coli*, the SEN and SEO genes have been cloned in an IPTG (isopropylthiogalactoside) inducible expression vector, with additional N-terminal tags for affinity purification (His6) and protease cleavage (FLAG/Enterokinase recognition site) in place of the wt secretion signal sequences.

WP4-T1-ST2- Proteins production

The necessary SE cloning and production work at the BfR required gaining official approval from the responsible Authority for work with genetically modified organisms; this approval was granted in December 2018, subject to the fulfilling of strict safety requirements. In order to meet these requirements, the SE production procedures and the laboratory organization had to be adjusted, including the purchase of necessary equipment. Due to the need to overcome these problems, the successful production of purified recombinant SEs for both WP3 and WP4 was only possible from March 2020. Although production was successful, the enzymatic removal of the affinity tag after purification (required in order to produce a wildtype N-terminus) was surprisingly ineffective, leading to a further delay in delivering the final protein preparations. Toxin samples for the Partners in WP3 were first delivered in May 2020.

WP4-T1-ST3- Development of specific Ab (poly/monoclonal)

Due to the problems and delays outlined in the above sections, final, purified SE preparations of sufficient quality and quantity were available in June of 2020. Because the production of monoclonal antibodies requires at least 5 – 6 months, there was not sufficient time to allow for the delivery of the hybridoma cultures and characterization of the binders (all of which was necessary for the development of the immunoassays) before the end of 2020 – the original, official end of the TOX-DETECT project. The Coordinators therefore requested the contracting of polyclonal sera and the antigens were delivered to the firm Covalab for the production of rabbit immune sera in June of 2020. The polyclonal sera for both SEN and SEO were delivered to the BfR in September 2020.

WP4-T1-ST4- Design of immunoenzymatic assays

The assay development for SEN and SEO began immediately upon delivery of the respective antisera and purified IgGs. While both purified IgG pools effectively and reproducibly recognized their antigens in a simple ELISA (immobilized antigens, respective pAbs and then an anti-rabbit-HRP detection antibody), only the assay for SEO was robust and reproducible in a sandwich format with toxins diluted in BHI culture medium. However, when testing culture supernatants from *S. aureus* strains having no SE genes, it became clear that the pAbs were cross-reactive against other, unknown *S. aureus* components. Although these pAbs against SEN and SEO are not alone suitable for the development of the envisioned immunoenzymatic assays, they will find application in SE affinity enrichment procedures to support other (for example, MS-based) detection methods. In June 2021, these developed Ab were transferred to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Coagulase Positive Staphylococci for development of an LC-MS based Immuno capture extraction method for detection of enterotoxins in food matrices. Results on this application are expected by end of 2021.

WP4-T2- Development of a quantitative immunoassay on a new *B. cereus* toxin or virulence factor

WP4-T2-ST1- Selection of 3 target genes and construction of a genetic tool for protein overexpression

Because WP2 could not deliver data on new *B. cereus* factors possibly involved in the diarrheal strains virulence, this task could not be implemented.

The development of immunoassays against *B. cereus* enterotoxins Nhe and Hbl was discarded because assays (although not quantitative) are already available against these toxins. The BCET-RPLA kit from Oxoid detects HblL2, the BDE-VIA assay from 3M-Tecra detects NheA and NheB, and the DuoPath assay from Merck detects NheB and HblL2. Therefore, in accordance with the coordinators, it was decided to develop assays against the enterotoxin CytK2, the hemolysin HlyII and the Sphingomyelinase.

WP4-T2-ST2- Protein production

For *B. cereus*, the first step was to select, for the three toxins, conserved sequences between reference diarrheal strains. Because these strains were not available at the project start, they were recovered from external laboratories and the toxins were sequenced using Micalis sequencing facilities and funds outside One Health EJP TOX-DETECT. Due to this preliminary task, cloning of the toxins genes started, after the sequences alignment, with a 6-months delay. The recombinant, His-tagged toxins were successfully produced in an almost pure form and could be delivered to WP3 and used for antibodies production. However, CytK2 was found to be quite unstable (half-life below 20 min.), and the design of an assay against this toxin was dropped.

WP4-T2-ST3- Development of specific Ab (poly/monoclonal)

Polyclonal rabbit antibodies against *B. cereus* toxins were also produced by the subcontractant company Covalab. Western blots with the purified toxin showed that the antibodies had a good affinity, since the serum could be used with dilutions up to 1/30000. Antibodies were purified on Protein A columns. Only the targeted toxins were recognized by the antibodies, meaning that they were quite specific.

WP4-T2-ST4- Design of the immunoenzymatic assay

Because of its ease of use, the development of a lateral flow assay (LFA) similar to the Merck DuoPath, allowing for the simultaneous detection of *B. cereus* Smase and HlyII, was initiated at first. However, despite good results, it appeared that the full design of this assay was not compatible with the project deadlines. Therefore, ST4 of WP4-T2 moved to the design of a simple sandwich ELISA, in which the capture antibody and the detection antibodies are identical. The detection antibody was HRP-tagged. The detection limit was 0.5 ng/ml for Smase and 1 ng/ml for HlyII, and the range of quantification was 0.5 ng/ml to 15 ng/ml for Smase and 1ng/ml to 40 ng/ml for HlyII. Toxins in culture supernatants could be readily quantified and spike-recover assays with these culture supernatants gave good results. SOPs are currently being written and material is being prepared for the interlaboratory trials.

WP5. Inter-laboratory ring trial scheme

The inter-lab tests were organized in order to evaluate the transferability of MALDI-ToF , LC-MS and ELISA methods developed in WP1, WP3, and WP4, respectively. These inter-lab tests have been prepared according to the regulation ISO/IEC 17043. Procedure allowing designing and implementing Inter-lab test was drafted and validated by the consortium. This document presents the objectives and a detailed plan for each ILC (Inter-lab comparison test) organization, see deliverable D5.1.

Training session dedicated to the implementation of ILC according to regulation ISO/IEC 17043, presentation of quality documents, samples preparation and establishment of inter-laboratory tests planning was organized by WP5 leader on 1st of December.

WP5-T1- Inter-lab test on MALDI-ToF for species identification

MALDI-ToF Library developed in the frame of WP1 by partner 1 was successfully transferred and implemented in the laboratory of partner 33 for the three pathogens: *Staphylococcus*, *Bacillus* and *Clostridia*.

EJP TOX-DETECT and European Reference Laboratory network were invited to participate to MALDI-ToF ILC. In total 12 participants agreed and received the method for implementation. Samples used in This MALDI-ToF PT were issued from reference collection implemented in the frame of WP1 (Constitution of a reference strain collection). On 1st of June, each participant received 10 codified samples for each pathogen (30 samples in total). Results from participants were expected by end of June 2021.

WP5-T2- Inter-lab test on LC-MS/MS

Three LC-MS based methods have been developed in the WP3. SOP's were drafted and transferred to different EJP TOX-DETECT partners in order to test the transferability of these developed methods.

- For *Bacillus* LC-MS method, 3 participants implemented the method, and took part to the Inter-lab exercise. In March 2021, each laboratory received standards, and 2 unknown samples. Results obtained by participants were 100% satisfactory.
- For *Clostridium* LC-MS method, 4 participants implemented the method, and participated to the Inter-lab exercise. Each laboratory received standards and several known samples for implementation of the method. In April 2021, each participant received 2 unknown samples (codified). Participants obtained 7/8 satisfactory results. The ILC report was dispatched to participants on 17th of June 2021.
- For Staphylococcal enterotoxin 'type N' LC-MS method, 3 participants implemented the method, and participated to the Inter-lab exercise. In March 2021, each laboratory received standards and several known samples for implementation of the method. In April 2021, 5 unknown samples (codified) were sent to the three participants. 2/3 participants returned their results to the organizer by end of May. The last participant asked additional time due to a technical problem (device failure). The ILC final report was dispatched to participants on 23th of June 2021. Results obtained by participants were satisfactory at 100% and 93% for qualitative and quantitative results, respectively.

WP5-T3- Inter-lab test on immuno-enzymatic assays

Inter-laboratory test dedicated to ELISA method for staphylococcal enterotoxins was cancelled. See “ WP4 and paragraph 3-Project self-assessment”.

For *Bacillus* ELISA, SOPs were drafted in June 2021. Call for participation is in progress.

WP6. Dissemination, protection and exploitation of results

WP6-T1-Dissemination of information within the partners

Communication and information dissemination between partners was realized through meetings and EJP website or using e-mails. Several face-to-face and web meetings were organized within each WP and between the different WPs. The One Health EJP coordination was invited to each general assembly in order to share One Health EJP news, recommendations, use of the One Health EJP site.

Partners were also invited to join the TOX-DETECT group available on the One Health EJP website. Deliverables and SOPs have been uploaded to the One Health EJP website and are available to all TOX-DETECT partners. The interim reports are posted on the One Health EJP site and distributed by email to partners.

At OH-EJP level, three posters were presented on work implement in WP and WP2 during the three OH-EJP annual meetings.

WP6-T2- Dissemination of information to the outside.

TOX-DETECT project and associated works was presented in:

- Five conferences, in 2019, 2020 and 2021, were presented in France, in Germany, in Spain and in an online meeting, for WPO, WP2 and WP3.
- Five work-shops (European Union Reference Laboratory, Italian reference laboratory, EFSA-ERAM and Astralia group).

Six articles were published in 2019, 2020 and 2021, in the journals Sensors, Food Microbiology, Clinical Microbiology and Infection, and Frontiers in Microbiology, all within the frame of WP2 and WP3.

7 more articles are expected to be published in 2021, for WP1 (1 article), WP2 (2 articles), WP3 (1 article), WP4 (2 articles) and WP5 (1 article).

Therefore, the project will be valorized by at least 10 communications and 13 scientific articles, issued from all WPs.

4 Project self-assessment

WP1: The goal to constitute a reference collection strain was achieved without too much difficulty as well as libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra of these strains. However, the establishment of MTAs for the exchange of strains took a long time and was a source of delay in the accomplishment of the work package. Moreover, transfer of the MALDI Library was limited to all participant using a Bruker spectrometer.

During WP2, methods were set up to characterize the strain cytotoxicity and the presence/expression of toxins. Known and new virulence markers were identified. However, a specific toxin that would differentiate *B. cereus* FBO strains could not be identified. Thus, a complex analytical pathway had to be implemented to analyse the RNAseq data. This induced some delay in the analysis, but allowed to propose a combination of biomarkers able to accurately differentiate clinical from non-pathogenic strains. For *C. perfringens*, it was confirmed that CPE accounted for the strain cytotoxicity. As this WP contained laboratory work, the COVID-19-crisis led to important delays.

WP4:

- The objective to develop specific antibodies against two SEs (WP4-T1-ST3) was only partially reached and, consequently, the development of quantitative immunoassays for two SEs (WP4-T1-ST4) was not reached. The reason for this is a series of problems and delays primarily regarding the fulfilment of safety requirements for the necessary work with toxin producing GMOs. Thus, sufficient amounts of recombinant toxins were only available at a late project stage, which rendered the production of monoclonal antibodies in time impossible. Thus, polyclonal antibodies were tested, which, however, turned out to be cross-reactive.
- Task 1 had to produce three already known *B. cereus* toxins and to setup immunoenzymatic assays against them. The three toxins (CytK2, HlyII and Smase) were produced, shipped to WP3, and sandwich ELISA methods against HlyII and Smase were successfully developed. The third immunoassay development was dropped since CytK2 is highly unstable. The objectives of WP4 task 2, which were to setup immunoassays against new toxins, could not be fulfilled because WP2 did not provide toxin names in time; no toxins specific to FBO strains could be identified. This task was highly impacted by Covid crisis (animals immunisation).

For WP5, the objective was to implement inter-Laboratory tests in order to check the robustness and transferability of methods developed in WP1, WP3 and WP4. The delay observed in these 3 WPs

impacted the implementation of Inter-laboratory tests. Over the 8 expected interlab tests, three were achieved (LC-MS), three were achieved end of June (three pathogens for MALDI-ToF). One interlab test achieved end of July (ELISA for *Bacillus*), and one initially dedicated to staphylococcal enterotoxins was cancelled as the method was not developed (see WP4 comment). Therefore, deliverable D5.2 (report on interlab tests) cannot be submitted on the expected time.

The coordination team faced several management issues mainly related to the changes of deputy coordinator in 2018, change of WP3 coordination twice (2019 and 2020), absence of coordinator and WP6 leader for 4 months.

For the whole project, tasks managed with personnel recruited under “short contract” were highly impacted by Covid crisis.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
05	D0.1	Report of the kick-off meeting	3			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484124#.YTed9I4zZaQ	
05	D0.2	Intermediate report	18			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516312#.YUdnGLgzZaQ	
05	D0.3	Report of the meeting 1	19			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484140#.YTefY44zZaQ	
05	D0.4	Report of the meeting 2	25			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484143#.YTef7Y4zZaQ	

05	D0.5	Report of meeting 3	42		cancelled	Meeting organized on 25 June 2021 Deliverable cancelled as there is no relevant information for scientific community. This is only a management document.	
05	D0.6	Final report	45			Done: One Health EJP: available	
05	D1.1	List of well characterized reference strains of <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. cereus</i> and <i>C. perfringens</i>	5			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: D1.1 TOX-DetectListe of well characterized strains Zenodo	3
05	D1.2	Libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra	33			Confidential, this concern reference strains under MTA and will be published One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516329#.YVIGPbgzZaQ	3
05	D2.1	Report on results from toxicity assays (classical toxicity tests and High Content Analysis)	42			Confidential, technical data under publication One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516345#.YUdrGbgzZaQ	8 Research and development activities

05	D2.2	Report on TR-PCR and RNAseq data analysis	42			Confidential, technical data under publication One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516359#.YUdsV7gzZaQ	8 Research and development activities
05	D2.3	Report on correlation between RNAseq data analysis and toxicity assays (incl. toolbox for toxicity prediction)	42			Confidential, technical data under publication One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516372#.YUdtRLgzZaQ	8 Research and development activities
05	D3.1	Report on MS-based methods for the detection of new enterotoxins (eg SEG, SEH, SEI) from <i>S. aureus</i>	42			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516382#.YUduRLgzZaQ	8 Research and development activities
05	D3.2	Report on MS-based methods for the detection of cereulide analogs and enterotoxins from <i>B. cereus</i>	42			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484152#.YVIA7gzZaQ	8 Research and development activities
05	D3.3	Report on MS-based methods for the detection of CPE	42			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project	8 Research and

		and virulence factors from <i>C. perfringens</i>				One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516390#.YUdvgrgzZaQ	development activities
05	D3.4	Report on the performance criteria for method harmonization	44			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484117#.YVII97gzZaQ	2
05	D4.1	Report on the immuno-enzymatic assays	45			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project. One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516394#.YUdxP7gzZaQ	8 Research and development activities
05	D5.1	Inter-lab tests documents according to ISO/IEC 17043 regulation, adapted to each method	45			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4479096#.YBQYXuhKhMQ	2
05	D5.2	Final report including results from the eight inter-lab tests	45			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5532845#.YVlni7gzZaQ	8 Research and development activities

05	D6.1	Dispatch of SOPs	45			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: OH EJP TOX-Detect projec: Dispatch of SOPs Zenodo	2 Research and development activities
05	D6.2	Dissemination of results (publications, conferences...)	45			One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5532713#.YVIFrgzZaQ	2 Research and development activities

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
05	MS0.1	General decision on criteria to select strains	3	Yes		
05	MS0.2	General discussion on interlaboratory trial scheme	3	Yes		
05	M-JRP5-03	Construction of the reference strains of S.	3	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		aureus, B. cereus and C. perfringens				
05	MS1.1	List of well characterized reference strains of S. aureus, B. cereus and C. perfringens	3	Yes		
05	MS1.2	Exchange of libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra	24	Yes		
05	MS2.1	Culture conditions optimized	24	Yes		
05	MS3.1	Reference materials available	5	Yes		Reference strains are available for WPs depending on the availability of MTA and results of M-JRP5-04. Reference materials were transferred after MTA signature when it was requested by the host. Transfer started month 5 and achieved at the end of the project
05	MS2.2	RT-PCR assays developed	14	Yes		
05	MS2.3	High content analysis methods developed	18	Yes		
05	MS2.4	RNAseq data analysed	38	Yes		
05	MS3.2	Methods developed and assessed	24	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
05	MS2.5	Correlation between toxicity profiles and expression patterns assessed.	30	Yes		
05	MS3.3	Methods transferred to partners	39	Yes		
05	MS4.1	Genetic tools constructed for over-expression of known <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>B. cereus</i> toxins	9	Yes		
05	MS4.2	Antibodies produced against known <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>B. cereus</i> toxins	33	Yes		
05	MS4.3	Immuno-enzymatic assays designed for known <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>B. cereus</i> toxins	32	Yes		Milestone not achieved for <i>S. aureus</i> toxins (see explanation in WP4 paragraph).
05	MS4.4	Genetic tools constructed for over-expression of a new <i>B. cereus</i> toxin/virulence factor	/	No		Milestone not achieved (see explanation in WP4 paragraph).
05	MS4.5	Antibodies produced against new <i>B. cereus</i> toxin/virulence factor overproduced	/	No		Milestone not achieved for (see explanation in WP4 paragraph).
05	MS4.6	Immuno-enzymatic assays designed for a new <i>B.</i>	42	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		cereus toxin/virulence factor				
05	MS4.7	Immuno-enzymatic assays transferred to partners	42	Yes		
05	MS5.1	Dispatch of inter-lab tests documents (according to ISO/IEC 17043 regulation) adapted to each method	M25	Yes		https://zenodo.org/record/4479096#.YBQYXuhKhM0
05	MS5.2	Dispatch of samples and evaluation report to be filled by partners	M44	No	43	Done for LC-MS and MALDI-ToF Expected in M43 for ELISA Bacillus
05	MS5.3	Samples analysed by partners	M42	No	45	Done for LC-MS and MALDI-ToF Expected in M45 for ELISA Bacillus
05	MS5.4	Dispatch of final report	M45	No		Expected in M45 after receivin report on Interlab test for ELISA Bacillus
05	MS6.1	Final report dispatched	M45	No		

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Point-of-Need DNA Testing for Detection of Foodborne Pathogenic Bacteria, Vidic et al, 2019, Sensors</p> <p>DOI: 10.3390/s19051100</p> <p>Uploaded on Zenodo DOI : https://zenodo.org/record/3935799#.YBQaI-hKhMQ</p>	YES	NN	1500\$
<p>Advanced Methods for Detection of Bacillus cereus and Its Pathogenic Factors. Nalini Ramarao, Seav-Ly Tran, Marco Marin, and Jasmina Vidic.</p> <p>Uploaded on Zenodo doi: https://doi.org/10.3390/s20092667</p>	YES	NN	1500\$
<p>Large-Scale Genomic Analyses and Toxinotyping of Clostridium perfringens Implicated in Foodborne Outbreaks in France, Abakabir Mahamat et al, Front Microbiol, 2019.</p> <p>Uploaded on Zenodo https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00777</p>	YES	No	2655 \$
<p>The cytotoxic potential of Bacillus cereus strains of various origins, Gasset et al, Food Microbiology, 2021</p> <p>Uploaded on Zenodo DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2021.103759</p>	YES	No	No
<p>New genetic biomarkers to differentiate pathogenic and clinically relevant Bacillus cereus strains, Kavanaugh et al., Clin Microbiol Infect, 2021.</p>	YES	No	No

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Uploaded on Zenodo DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2021.05.035			
DiagnoTop: a computational pipeline for discriminating bacterial pathogens without database search. Diogo Borges Lima, Mathieu Dupré, Marlon Dias Mariano Santos, Paulo Costa Carvalho, Julia Chamot-Rooke. Journal of the American Society of Mass Spectrometry. Uploaded on Zenodo https://doi.org/10.1021/jasms.1c00014	YES	No	1227\$

Additional output

Other relevant dissemination outcomes can be highlighted here, e.g. non-scientific publications, proceedings, poster, video, tools, guidelines, patents, etc. If the outcome is a deliverable it should not be mentioned here. Please indicate where the item can be found, for instance on Zenodo or any open access repository. Indicate the link and check the functionality.

This project focused on virulence factors produced by some bacteria producing toxins. Tools developed are complementary with those developed in the frame of the H2020 project EuroBioTox focusing on biothreats. In this one, three partners of the One Health EJP TOX-DETECT are present (Anses, Sciensano, Pasteur Insitute). Exchanges between the two consortium and overall presentations of the results will be made during the next meeting of EuroBiotox and during the final meeting of TOX-DETECT which will take place in September 2021.

These two projects enhance European networks focusing on bacterial toxins in a One Health context.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

In this paragraph you have the possibility to draw the attention to remarkable achievements that could be highlighted to illustrate the potential impact of your project.

In TOX-DETECT project, deliverables D1.1 (List of well characterized reference strains of S. aureus, B. cereus and C. perfringens) and D1.2 (Libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra) and D5.2 task 1 (Inter-laboratory test on MALDI-ToF method) represents a complete achievement in term of implementation of new database and method from implementation of reference collection of strains until the transfer of the method to the European Union Reference Laboratory network. The **MALDI-ToF Library** will complete the commercial database with spectra obtained from strains issued from food born outbreaks occurred in European Union. After publication of the work in open access journal, scientific

community can benefit from this new MALDI-ToF library to improve the MALDI-ToF method in term of discrimination potential.

WP2 deliverables and D3.3 (Report on MS-based methods for the detection of CPE and virulence factors from *C. perfringens*) proposes toxicity and enterotoxins data obtained for *C. perfringens* strains issued from food born outbreaks occurred in European Union. A set of complementary tools developed in this TOX-DETECT project can be implemented and used by reference and expert laboratories for food born outbreak investigation, especially RT PCR and LC-MS techniques.

Deliverables dedicated to Staphylococcal enterotoxins study (D3.1 and D4.1) indicate that the egc enterotoxins SEM, SEN and SEO are produced at very low levels of concentration compared to classical enterotoxins. This information was presented to the EURL for coagulase Positive Staphylococci (EURL for CPS) which will use it for further study and methods development as reported in EURL working program 2019 and 2020. Also, enterotoxins and antibodies produced in WP4 were transferred to EURL for CPS in order to use them to enlarge the scope of detection methods for Staphylococcal enterotoxins.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Not relevant

7 One Health impact

In this project, we focused on bacterial producing toxins according to the One Health concept. For this purpose all partners combined isolates coming from food, environmental and clinical samples.

All the selected strains have been fully characterized by partners and were used to perform method developments.

The first outcome is the availability of this large and fully characterized collection of strains. A part of this collection has been already used to feed another OH EJP programme – CARE.

The second outcome is the development of dedicated Maldi-ToF libraries. Robustness of these MSP libraries have been evaluated by a dedicated ILS generating more than 3000 data. We highlighted that the percentage of correct identification of the three pathogens covered by TOX-DETECT significantly increased especially for the identification of the isolates of the *B cereus* group.

As results obtained were highly satisfactory, we will dispatch these libraries among partners as well in the EU networks.

Moreover, thanks to this strain collection we were able to design 15 harmonized SOPs for all the targeted virulence factors and 6 dedicated methods. All of these deliverables contributed to the tool box we would like to design at the beginning of the project to enhance characterization of bacteria producing toxins. These deliverables have been shared and could be used by partners as ILS demonstrated their robustness and efficiency.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	4	5	2
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	5	5	3
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	4	4	4
Integration	5	4	2
Sustainability	5	4	3
Impact of the project	5	5	3
TOTAL	28/30	27/30	17/30

AVERAGE: 24

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The main objectives of the project were satisfactorily fulfilled, addressing the 3 specific goals of the call. Three “non-NGS” methods were developed (MALDI-ToF, LC-MS and ELISA). Methods developed could be used by reference laboratories from different countries (“establishment of EU networks). A reference collection of bacterial strains was generated.

Some goals were not achieved for different drawbacks, generally due to lack of the desired results or difficulties inherent to all experimental processes. In other cases, administrative or bureaucratic issues conspired against the timeline of the project, but this is not a demerit of the participants ...

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project outcomes are fully in-line with the objectives proposed in the initial submission. There are a few deviations or uncompleted tasks (e.g. in WP2 then WP4 for *B. cereus*) but these are satisfactorily justified.

Reviewer 3: POC member

WP1 (collection of strains), WP2 (characterisation of toxins & correlation between cytotoxicity and toxins), WP3 (development & transfert of methods) , WP5 (inter lab trails) and WP6 (dissemination of results) but W4 (dvpt of new immune-enzymatic assays) faced different and numerous difficulties and cannot achieved its goal. However, deviations are correctly explained. Although biological production is uncertain, maybe the impacts on laboratory safety requirements could have be more anticipated ?

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project includes innovative approaches that will be relevant for the implementation of new methodologies aimed at the detection of virulence factors of important food-poisoning pathogens. This project allowed the discovery of at least 2 potential candidates for the development of further detection methods, and characterization of different toxins was achieved.

Also, innovative detection methods were developed for new enterotoxins from all three pathogens under study and were implemented in laboratories of several participants in the consortium.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has produced usable and practical results with full complementarity between partners throughout the project. Once initial outputs were obtained, these were successfully transferred to corresponding partners for method development and then to other partners for inter-laboratory test.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Results are robust

Complementary approach between partners is noted.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Both quality and efficiency of implementation were highly scored in general. Each partner has fulfilled the activities originally proposed. All drawbacks or deviation with the original proposal were properly justified and explained.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has been well coordinated with many meetings, web-conferences and tele-conferences. These were to identify obstacles as early as possible, ensure smooth running of the project, and identify arising opportunities. Some measures have been taken for dissemination of project results but there has been no contact with authorities. Dissemination activities should clearly benefit by attendance to EuroBiotox that is to be held in September 2021.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Measures taken to exploit and disseminate the results are effective; numerous papers, conferences and workshops have highlighted the results.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Integration included the organization of around 60 meetings and web conferences to coordinate activities and discuss the development of the project. Also, for each analytical method developed, detailed protocols and validation reports were written and drafted as SOPs, and further transferred to partners for implementation.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has been successfully managed in integrative activities in preparing joint libraries/databases and harmonized protocols. However, there has been not much contact with stakeholders outside the consortium or cross-sector collaboration to strengthen One Health aspect.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Successful because of development of methods and bank collection. However, to collect strains from different origins (animal, human and environmental) is insufficient to qualify for a “One Health “ approach.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Sustainability seems to be high. All developed methodologies require not as much budget as the NGS-based methods or other expensively implemented techniques. One of the major strengths of the project is in fact de development of detection methods that cab be transferred to different laboratories.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The libraries constructed and the methods developed will be maintained by the consortium members and it seems that they will continue their collaboration to improve results obtained. This is clear in their future plans for the end of 2021. Once the libraries are made public, it will be possible for other institutes to access them. It would have been a positive move to contact authorities to introduce their developed methods for their wide use.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Tools developed in this project can be implemented and used by reference and expert laboratories for food born outbreak investigation.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

This project seems to have satisfactorily achieved one of the main goals of the call, that is the proposal of methodologies with high implementation opportunities, sustainability, and transfer to different laboratories. It has succeeded in the objective of filling the gap of lacking methods to detect bacterial toxins from important and prevalent food-poisoning microorganisms, which is the major hallmark of the project.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has developed novel detection methods that should be applicable for long periods. Timely or early detection using the methods developed will definitely lead to positive secondary effects such as recalling of contaminated food.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Clearly on Food Borne Outbreak investigation.

Final report

1 Consortium composition

The Project Coordinator was Jenny Frössling (SVA) and the Deputy Project Coordinator was Steen Ethelberg (SSI). The coordinators formed a coordination group together with Fernanda Dórea (SVA) and the WP leaders Maria-Eleni Filippitzi (Sciensano), Adeline Huneau (ANSES), Ana de la Torre (INIA) and Håkan Vigre (DTU).

List of project participants

Country	Institution	Name	Designated role	Remark	WP
BE	Sciensano	Maria-Eleni Filippitzi	Leader of WP1, Institute contact	Joined M3	0,1
BE	Sciencano	Valerie de Waele	Leader of WP1	Joined M0, left M21	0,1
BE	Sciencano	Sarah Welby	Leader of WP1	Left M0	1
DE	BfR	Katja Alt	Co-leader of WP2, Institute contact		2
DE	BfR	Jakub Fusiak			2
DE	RKI	Idesbald Boone			2
DE	RKI	Sebastian Haller			2
DE	RKI	Hendrik Wilking	Institute contact		2
DK	DTU	Ofosuhene Apenteng			5
DK	DTU	Håkan Vigre	Leader of WP5, Institute contact person		0,5
DK	SSI	Steen Ethelberg	Deputy project coordinator, Leader of WP2, Institute contact		0,2
DK	SSI	Frederik Møller Trier			2
DK	SSI	Helle Daugaard Larsen			2
DK	SSI	Uffe Braae			2
DK	SSI	Luise Müller			2
DK	SSI	Laura Espenhain			2
DK	SSI	Peter H. S. Andersen			2
DK	SSI	Elsebeth Tvenstrup			2

		Jensen			
DK	SSI	Louise Køhler Olsen			2
DK	SSI	Henrik Bang			2
ES	INIA	Ana de la Torre	Leader of WP4, Institute contact		4
ES	INIA	Irene Iglesias			4
ES	INIA	Antonio Rodríguez			4
ES	UCM	Julio Álvarez Sánchez	Institute contact person		4
ES	UCM	Lucía de Juan Ferré			4
ES	UCM	Kendy Tzu-Yun Teng			4
FR	ANSES	Géraldine Cazeau			?
FR	ANSES	Viviane Henaux			5
FR	ANSES	Adeline Huneau	Leader of WP3, Institute contact		3
FR	ANSES	Renaud Lailier			3
FR	ANSES	Carole Sala			?
FR	ANSES	Briac Virey			3
FR	InVS/SpF	Nathalie Jourdan-da Silva	Institute contact		2
IT	ISS	Rosangela Tozzoli			2
IT	ISS	Gaia Scavia	Institute contact		2
IT	IZS	Luigi Iannetti	Institute contact		2
NL	RIVM	Elisa Beninca			4
NL	RIVM	Eric Evers	Institute contact		5
NL	RIVM	Ingrid Friesema			2
NL	RIVM	Arno Swart			4
NO	NIPH	Gry Grøneng			2,3
NO	NIPH	Zuzana Nordeng			1,2
NO	NIPH	Solveig Jore	Institute contact		1,2
NO	NIPH	Gunnar Rø			3
NO	NIPH	Peter Dougherty			2,3

NO	NIPH	David Swanson		3
NO	NIPH	Clemence Koren		3
NO	NVI	Petter Hopp		3
NO	NVI	Malin Jonsson	Institute contact	3
NO	NVI	Kyrre Kausrud		3
NO	NVI	Madelaine Norström		3
SE	PHAS	Marie Jansson Mörk		2
SE	PHAS	Moa Rehn	Institute contact	2
SE	SVA	Wonhee Cha		3
SE	SVA	Fernanda Dórea		0,3
SE	SVA	Jenny Frössling	Project coordinator, Leader of WPO, Institute contact	0,1,5
SE	SVA	Wiktor Gustafsson		3
SE	SVA	Hyeyoung Kim		4
SE	SVA	Anna Nordenfelt		0
SE	SVA	Thomas Rosendal		5
SE	SVA	Stefan Widgren		4,5
SE	SVA	Estelle Ågren		1,4
UK	APHA	Mark Arnold	Institute contact	5
UK	PHE	Natalie Adams	Institute contact	2
UK	PHE	Lesley Larkin		2

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Background

Zoonotic foodborne diseases constitute a serious **one health problem** throughout the world and are expected to stay high on the infectious diseases risk agenda, fuelled by factors such as globalised trade with food and live animals, modern intensified food production systems, international travel, and the continuous adaptation of known and arising pathogens and hazards, including increased antibiotic resistance. Foodborne diseases, being very prevalent and giving rise to sequelae, pose a serious problem to public health and have significant economic implications in terms of cost of care, loss of productivity and in the agricultural and food industry sectors.

In order to limit the damage and cost caused by zoonotic diseases, it is better to prevent than to cure. **Disease surveillance is a crucial prerequisite** for prevention; it allows us to be able to analyse and understand trends and patterns of disease occurrence and to choose and evaluate intervention strategies. However, surveillance systems are not always working well and they also come with a price tag. Also digital data sources continues to develop, also within the food chain, and should be utilised

if possible for surveillance purposes. It is therefore **important that we continuously develop the ways we do surveillance and that we have methods to measure and compare the performance of different surveillance activities**. This has been the overall **aim** of the **NOVA** project suite.

Methods

NOVA has included project participants from 19 public health and veterinary institutes in 10 countries over a project period of 3½ years. As one of the larger One Health EJP projects, it has addressed improvement of disease surveillance through a large number of separate projects, organised into five main themes, as reflected in its overall work package structure. Below, three results from each theme, which we find particularly interesting, are highlighted. Results are summarised in more depths in *Section 2* of the *Final Report* and presented through published and in prep papers and the formal project deliverable reports.

Results

Theme **A. Basic aspects** (and issues in connection with) performing **One Health surveillance** (WP1):

- Surveillance across the foodchain is as yet far from used enough; it holds (and is perceived by actors as holding) much potential.
- Focus group studies highlighted a complex pattern of barriers and opportunities for OH surveillance. In particular relating to data governance.
- A glossary of terms was developed (together with other One Health EJP projects) to help overcome barriers between veterinary, food and human surveillance activities.

Theme **B. Use of electronic traces of purchase of food** for surveillance and outbreak investigations (WP2):

- Electronic records of the foods we all buy in shops are a powerful tool in the hands of the disease detectives that investigate foodborne outbreaks. A network to promote use hereof was built.
- Methods of analyses of *big datasets* on supermarket purchases can automatically find vehicles and calculate odds ratio's therefore – tapping into supermarket purchase information should be used regularly in the future for foodborne outbreak investigations.
- Foodborne outbreaks in care institutions – hospitals and elderly homes – occur, are preventable and sometimes traceable via electronic invoices food sales.

Theme **C. One Health** developments of **syndromic surveillance** methods (WP3):

- Individual monitoring of *Campylobacter* detections in major broiler slaughterhouses proved effective for enhancing early detection of *Campylobacter* outbreaks in humans
- Parallel monitoring of indicators on cattle health, *Salmonella* detection in food, and human gastro-intestinal syndromes revealed simultaneous temporal abnormalities. Simultaneous alarms may be used to trigger and orientate field epidemiological investigations.
- Predictions based on models combining veterinary, meteorological and medical data in Norway were used to develop a dashboard to provide stakeholders with predictions of gastrointestinal outbreaks one week ahead of other systems.

Theme **D. Use and development of spatial risk mapping** (WP4):

- Development of spatial disease distribution models (for *Salmonella*) have identified provinces in Spain at risk, while taking into account the effect of potential risk factors.
- Risk-based surveillance of *Salmonella*, based on a spatial stochastic disease spread model, was economically favourable -- it relied on only one third of the samples used by traditional surveillance, although the capacity for case detection was also reduced.
- Models and scripts that have been developed for salmonellosis can be applied for other zoonotic diseases and many geographical regions in Europe, depending on data availability.

Theme E. Modelling the **cost efficiency** of surveillance programs (WP5):

- By combining models for disease transmission (SIR) simulating emerging food safety issues with models simulating sampling schedules and models of laboratory procedures, we determined the time such systems will need to detect an emerging infection – thereby providing a tool to optimise emerging risk surveillance systems.
- It is possible (by modelling) to make a holistic assessment of how new laboratory technologies can be used to improve the performance of surveillance systems before the technology is actually implemented in a population.
- We've shown that the performance of surveillance programs of foodborne diseases in any part of the food production can (and should) be measured as the effect on the human risk using an QMRA approach, and the cost of surveillance (both monitoring and control) per prevented human case.

Discussion

Overall, NOVA has contributed to the development of several novel methods that can be used to make surveillance and response more efficient and cost-effective. In parallel to strengthening of modelling and data frameworks, we have explored and started the process to incorporate new data sources in the everyday surveillance that our institutes are involved in. We conclude that modelling the full chain from primary production to the consumer, including environmental aspects, is possible but remains a challenge. Our collaboration confirm that a multidisciplinary approach is needed to combine and understand information from the different surveillance components.

3 *Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes*

WP0. Coordination and project management

WP0-T1- Project management

Monthly meetings with WP leaders were held throughout the project, starting already November 2017. For coordination purposes, the coordinator and/or other members from the coordination group attended the official kick-off of meeting of the full One Health EJP consortium, and various information meetings within the One Health EJP over the years, such as the Project Leaders' Forum. Especially at the start of the One Health EJP collaboration meetings with representatives from the ORION and COHESIVE projects were necessary to sort out potential overlap and create synergies between the projects. We have also attended a One Health EJP Programme Managers' Committee meeting and a few One Health EJP stakeholders' meetings.

Apart from these meetings, project management has included reporting, finding platforms for sharing of information and documents and to summarise information about the project e.g. for the websites of the One Health EJP and our institutes. Management has also involved work with the ethics self-assessment and the data management plan (DMP). The DMP work required attendance of educational

sessions organised by the One Health EJP management, and additional meetings to plan and complete this work process.

A request to extend the project was sent to One Health EJP management in May. Due to slow recruiting processes in several partner institutes, we decided already in 2019 that we would ask for an extension. The COVID-19 pandemic also influenced the work in several partner institutes/countries. The request was endorsed and accepted by the PMT and the members of the SSB in June 2020.

WP0-T2- Organise annual assemblies

The first annual assembly was held in Rome, February 28th to March 1st. The meeting was considered a kick-off meeting where we focused on getting to know each other and pick up the planning of tasks and studies included in the project proposal.

A second annual assembly was held in Brussels, March 7-8, 2019. The purpose of the meeting was to meet, plan and discuss ongoing and coming tasks. To focus this work, three specific topics were addressed in the discussions: 1. International aspects and opportunities for international collaboration, 2. Scientific publications, 3. Novelty of methods and approaches used. To share research results across WPs, a scientific webinar was also organised for all project participants in November.

Organisation of a third annual assembly was started at the end of 2019 and was planned to be held in Madrid, 23-24 April 2020. The meeting was cancelled in March due to the COVID-19 pandemic and instead, a shorter online meeting was held on the 23rd of April, with short scientific presentations from the WPs and general information.

In spring 2021 we had a final assembly that again had to be held online. This time we had a two-day meeting, 18-19 May, combining scientific presentations with general information and concluding remarks from the WP leaders.

WP2-T3- Economic reporting and financial management

SVA participated in the start-up financial One Health EJP meeting at ANSES 2018 but did not coordinate economic reporting for other partners, as the financial reporting for the joint research project within the One Health EJP are performed by each partner institute involved. However, in response to a request by the One Health EJP coordination in 2020, the project partners were asked to report any costs that had been wasted due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Only two partner institutes reported such costs. Later, the One Health EJP coordination also requested that the budget for the third year of the project were updated by each partner and specific budget files were filled in and sent to One Health EJP centrally in June. The conclusion from this update was that partners plan to not underspend but to use potentially remaining resources during the extension period in the fourth year.

WP1. Food chain surveillance mapping

WP1-T1- Definition of a joint food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology

Given the work on a Med-Vet glossary of the participants of ORION WP2 in which members of NOVA WP1 also participated in the first year, in order to complete the deliverable of this WP, a collaboration was established with the ORION team, as well as COHESIVE.

WP1-T1 has collected 274 terms from partners leading all WPs. The NOVA Glossary was delivered to the ORION project leader, BfR, in the second half of June 2019 in order to incorporate the NOVA Glossary into the common OH Glossary. In the period between July and October 2019, there were several exchanges with BfR in order to adjust the NOVA Glossary into the common version. The final result can be found here: <https://aginfra.d4science.org/web/orionknowledgehub/>

The One Health EJP Glossary has 3 main functionalities. First, it is a collection of One Health related terms and definitions in the sectors public health, animal health and food safety. Second, it highlights

similarities and differences of terms and definitions between the sectors. Finally, it provides an infrastructure to references, search and filter terms, and definitions. As an outcome of this cooperation (of all three projects), a joint article was published in May 2021.

WP1-T2- Mapping of surveillance: data, regulatory framework, key stakeholders, opportunities and barriers

The objective of this task was to identify barriers and opportunities for an integrated One Health surveillance of food-borne diseases in selected EU countries. The task was split into two qualitative research studies: one targeting responsible experts and officials (coordination/administration level) of surveillance activities across the food chain in four different countries, and one targeting veterinary practitioners (field level) in one country. The results from these studies can be used to support revision of existing systems, or development of new systems for food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health (OH) perspective.

Coordination level study

In order to identify barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health perspective, information was collected through interviews with professionals with selected profiles on coordination/administration level and from four countries (Belgium, France, Sweden, and Norway). The study methods and preparations included: 1. Mapping of an existing food chain (used as a visual tool for cueing), 2. Development of an interview guide document, 3. Demographic questionnaire, 4. Excel files for collection of data, 5. Training on performing interviews and qualitative research, 6. Interview try-outs.

The profiles of the professionals interviewed in each of the four countries were the following:

- I. A human medicine epidemiologist (e.g. the head of such a unit or an experienced professional with knowledge of different diseases and managing them)
- II. A person from administration in charge of planning the annual programmed food chain surveillance (expected to be placed at the Min. for Agriculture)
- III. A veterinary medicine epidemiologist (same as for human epidemiologist)
- IV. A transversal coordinator of a national agency, positioned on the link between risk analysis and risk management
- V. Persons from laboratories, ideally the coordinators of the human and veterinary National Reference laboratories (RNL).

The participants selected to be interviewed were identified and contacted by the WP1 members representing each country thanks to their professional network. The 20 interviews were performed by three researchers who received the same training on performing interviews. More detailed information is provided in the respective deliverable report, while a manuscript is being drafted.

According to the analysis, which was performed following the thematic analysis methodology, the barriers and opportunities identified by the interviewees were grouped in the following themes: 1. Data governance, 2. Set-up and operations of the surveillance system, 3. Coordination, 4. Communication, 5. Regulations (political legislations and procedures), 6. Industry's challenges, 7. Funding, 8. Training and education.

For all countries, the barriers and opportunities pointed out as being most important belonged to the themes covering Data governance and Set-up and operations of the surveillance system.

Therefore, the results show that there is room for improvement in food-borne disease surveillance of microbiological pathogens towards a One-Health approach, especially regarding the themes identified as most. An analysis of the collected information is also being performed per identified theme, taking into account the particularities of each country.

Field level study

Early detection of zoonotic and emerging infections is critical for successful handling of outbreaks and control of foodborne diseases. Veterinary practitioners have a key role in the detection of such diseases in livestock. Our objective was to explore how the clinical surveillance and reporting zoonotic and regulated diseases in livestock are perceived and performed by veterinarians in Sweden.

In this study, we conducted in-depth face-to-face interviews with 13 field veterinarians selected based on socio-demographic characteristics. The veterinarians were working in large animal practice. A semi-structured interview guide with open-ended questions and prompts was used to collect qualitative data. The interviews started with general questions to capture the veterinarians' profiles. Thereafter, interviewees were asked to describe their actions in cases of suspected emerging and zoonotic infections under regulation. The discussions followed topics that included their awareness of major disease threats, their perceived role in diseases surveillance, and views on its feasibility. The interviews were transcribed in verbatim followed by thematic analysis of the transcripts using a phenomenological approach.

Themes that commonly appeared were veterinarians, for various reasons, disregarding clinical signs possibly associated with the emerging and zoonotic infections; difficulties to take samples under field circumstances and to send these samples for diagnostic tests; and aspects related to a communication network involving those taking part of the surveillance system.

These results can serve as a baseline for the design of questionnaire-based surveys, also targeting veterinarians in other countries, as a complementary quantitative approach to investigate clinical surveillance. The results provide suggestions for improvements in the reporting chain. The final goal is to increase the likelihood that a veterinary practitioner promptly contacts animal health authorities when they encounter animals showing signs indicative of diseases under national or EU legislation.

WP2. Analysis of food purchase data

Those who like to read detective novels or watch police investigation films, know that the investigators often decide to 'follow the money'. The clever police team follows the electronic trail that money transfer leaves when they investigate and solve complicated criminal cases. When trying to crack the sometimes very complicated epidemiological problems of foodborne diseases and foodborne outbreak investigations, one might wonder if not the same logic may be applied – just for food and not money. In this work package, the overall aim was to explore the possibilities of working with electronic records of food purchase and food movements for obtaining a better understanding of the transmission of foodborne diseases.

Work package 2 (WP2) of NOVA aimed to elucidate whether the surveillance potential of food consumption, as reflected by consumer purchasing patterns, may serve as a digital tool to aid our understanding of both outbreaks and general risk factors of foodborne zoonoses. Understanding food consumption patterns is an important part of understanding foodborne diseases, and modern society opens new possibilities to do this using existing data flows. With recent advents of electronic storage of purchase receipts, several countries and food business operators have obtained large but currently unused datasets, which can contribute important information. WP2 was divided into five separate tasks, I) Usage & barriers, II) Outbreak investigations, III) Big data analysis, IV) Hospital outbreaks and V) Trace-back and risk mapping. These five subtasks are described individually below.

WP2-T1- Data availability of purchase and consumer data for outbreak investigations (Formerly: Data availability and barriers)

Some EU countries have several years of experience with use of supermarket purchase data or other consumer data for the investigation of foodborne outbreaks, whereas others have never used it. The objective of WP2.1 was to map actors involved in obtaining and using purchase and consumer data,

get an overview of the data already used, the context they may have been used in and the experience with these data for outbreak investigations. A second objective was to try to map possible barriers and obstacles when obtaining and/or using these purchase data and other consumer data. This was done through two questionnaire surveys inquiring about purchase data. These comprised data from supermarkets, wholesale, the Internet, fast food chains, and organizations who have access to these data (e.g. market surveys and scanning data companies/apps). Other consumer data comprised catering companies for health care institutions, schools, etc., and in house food preparation in health care institutions, schools, etc. All (public health) partners of EJP-NOVA received an email with the links to questionnaires. Secondly, we approached the institute representatives included in One Health EJP and the members of the ECDC Food- & Waterborne Disease (FWD) network via the Epidemic Intelligence Information System for FWD (EPIS-FWD) to complete one or both questionnaires or to give names of (possible) contacts who could.

Eleven countries completed one or both questionnaires on use of purchase and consumer data in (outbreak) investigations and other research. Seven countries reported to have actually used these data in one or more studies. The two main aims for using purchase and other consumer data are source hypothesis-generation and food trace-back investigation. It is seen as an alternative tool to solve outbreaks with advantages including: that it mitigates issues around the inability of people to remember everything they have eaten one or more weeks ago, especially stealth food products and also that it may provide good data which can lead to strong evidence pointing to a product. Purchase data of supermarket chains could become available for use in almost all countries, often with national coverage. Other purchase and consumer data are less often already available and are more often local or regional. To gather purchase data, member/loyalty, credit and cash cards are crucial, as data could not be extracted for any of the data sources when the purchases are payed cash. The most experience appear to be in the area of the supermarkets, mainly chains, but also consortia and individual supermarkets. Overall, actors needed to obtain and use these data were national public health institute – often together with regional public health institute(s) – and the national food safety authority. Depending on where the purchase or consumer data is obtained from, also the company/institution, chain, consortium or interest group is involved.

Three groups of disadvantages were experienced when using the data, namely obstacles on the level of the supermarket/company/institution, the cases, and the handling of the data. Within all responding countries, eight of 11 countries and six of nine countries saw practical and/or technical obstacles for obtaining and using purchase and other consumer data, respectively, with the main threat being a too high workload. Of all obstacles, privacy legislation was conceived as the most important barrier as it was the only barrier mentioned by more than half of the countries.

WP2-T2- Food purchase data for outbreak investigations

Foodborne outbreaks occur with a high frequency in Europe and constitute a high, although partly preventable, burden to health and economy. Unfortunately, the majority of outbreaks are not fully resolved, in part because outbreak investigations are very time consuming and often rely on patient interviews that can be difficult to perform in sufficient scale and in a timely manner. There is therefore much to gain, if information could be easily gathered in an electronic format on which foods, the patients that are part of outbreaks, have bought in supermarkets or shops prior to becoming ill. Then it would theoretically be possible to find the foods, which the patients have in common and perhaps even to do a statistical comparison of purchase frequency with a non-patient consumer population. The aim of WP2.2 was to describe this line of investigation as an outbreak methodology, describe its prior use, and map the obstacles that lies in the way of a wider use and to produce recommendations for how it could be applied in EU member states. This was thus to a large degree a review and networking exercise.

As a first step a structured review of the already published literature was done with the purpose of obtaining an overview of the degree to which the method has been used and how it has found

application so far. This review was published as Møller et al (2017) in Eurosurveillance. For the period 2006–17, scientific articles were found describing 20 outbreak investigations. They were presented and the benefits and shortcomings of the method was discussed in the paper. The term ‘consumer purchase data’ (CPD) was introduced to refer to the method.

As a next step, we invited epidemiologists with experience with CPD to take part in a network. We reached out via the European Public health institutes and the EPIET alumni organisation (EAN) and succeeded in creating a small working group from eight European countries plus Canada. In online consultations, this group has tried to answer the central questions of “When is this method working?” and: “When is it not useful and why?” with the aim of suggesting ways to facilitate its use. It was generally found that perceived obstacles related mostly to lack of guidance in how to use CPD rather than legal issues. A manuscript, which based on these consultations contain a description of a framework for use of CPD as an outbreak investigation method has been submitted. We hope that the work we have so far initiated will lead to a resurgence of use of CPD for outbreak investigations and that this network will keep growing.

WP2-T3- Working with large datasets and novel ways of analysed consumer purchase data
(Formerly: Big data analysis of risk factors for sporadic disease)

The previous task dealt with concrete individual outbreak situations. It is conceivable, however, that access to large datasets could lead to conduction of semi-automated outbreak investigations being possible and that CPD could also be used for general analytical purposes. This was the focus of the work conducted in WP2.3. Two paths were followed:

In one path, we aimed to set-up a case-control study of risk factors for sporadic disease using only CPD. Salmonella was chosen as the model organism and the project concerned Denmark only. The aim has been to build a digital solution into which Danish residents by invitation (cases of salmonella and comparable persons without known infection selected from the population register) can sign up. This solution includes a way of safely logging in to a secure website where the user is presented with study objectives and information about legal rights and with the possibility of further opening up for investigator access into past purchase records. This is possible if the user is already subscribing to a third party solution (an app) that stores the results of credit card purchases – something about 20% of the Danish population do. This technical solution (which was built with additional support from funding outside of NOVA) is now working and is legally compliant. Construction has involved overcoming a large number of practical, technical and legal challenges. Also, the case-control study is ethically and data-technically approved, a draft of a protocol study has been prepared for submission, and invitational letters have been drafted. However, due to the exceptional covid-19 situation, the final legal approval of the data collection platform, that were to be used to collect consumer data, was not approved until early June 2021. Thus, running the case control study has been postponed until end of 2021/beginning of 2022 after the end of NOVA. This is in other words a sustainable activity!

A second independent path has involved trying to obtain large real consumer dataset from Scandinavian supermarket chains. Initially work was done using a very large dataset from a major Danish supermarket chain, however, this work had to stop halfway into the project because of GDPR issues. Following a year of negotiations by the FHI, a second large anonymized consumer purchase dataset was offered to our use by a group of Norwegian supermarket chains. It contains individual weekly purchase histories available for analysis (920,834 unique customers from six Norwegian municipalities in 2019, totalling 222 mill purchases of 30,929 different products). The results of the analysis was presented at the OH_EJP annual meeting 2021 with the title “Simulation and identification of foodborne outbreaks in real consumer purchase data“, and a manuscript is in preparation. The study aimed to use consumer purchase data to simulate outbreaks, identify outbreak vehicles using regression, and examine how performance of selected analytic strategies varied across outbreak parameters.

The simulations generated outbreaks with different attack rates, proportion of background cases (where CPD was not available), and food expiry dates. Further analysis was conducted to evaluate the effect of Item purchase frequency. The proportion of background cases (i.e., those with no available consumer data), was the most important parameter for the number of cases needed to point towards a possible source of the outbreak. Sensitivity analysis was also conducted to address different attack rates (0.01-0.1), expiry length (0-300 days) and incubation time (0-10 days). Not surprisingly, the higher the item detail level (primary product group eg. 'diary', secondary product group eg. 'milk', and GTIN level: product ID, and brand specific product), the less cases were needed before it was possible to point towards an outbreak source. Thus a logistic regression method can identify outbreak vehicles in a real-world CPD, and is, until further methods are explored, a good consensus candidate. Also, analysis of outbreaks using product groups with a granularity that is comparable to most trawling questionnaires, reduces performance compared to outbreaks analysed on item level. The study also indicated that CPD analysis requires participation from all major grocery chains for optimal performance.

WP2-T4- Foodborne outbreaks within healthcare institutions and use of electronic data of patient meals for their control (Formerly: Food distribution data for hospital outbreaks)

The studies described above targeted illness in the community, however foodborne outbreaks may also take place in hospital and other healthcare settings. For these, individual CPD may not be relevant, but data flows of food purchase by the institutions would be the target of investigation. To explore the possibilities within this area was the focus of WP2.4. It contained two connected but separate paths:

This first aimed to describe the epidemiology of healthcare-associated foodborne outbreaks (HA-FBOs) by conducting a literature review and analysing surveillance data on HA-FBOs. This work has been accepted for publication (Eurosurveillance, 2020, Boone et al). It found 85 HA-FBOs that could be included in an analysis in which the top three associated pathogens were *Salmonella spp.*, norovirus and *Listeria monocytogenes*. High mortality was reported in listeriosis HA-FBOs. The most frequently reported food categories for HA-FBOs were mixed foods, such as ready-to-eat sandwiches, vegetables and fruits, and meat and meat products. Associated risk factors included consumption of contaminated ready-to-eat food including risky foods, unprocessed contaminated foods, inadequate heat treatment, insufficient hygiene of kitchen and equipment and pathogen carriers among food handlers. Based on this analysis, it was concluded that the food supply chain for HCFs must be strictly controlled, HCFs should adhere to food safety measures and hold regular food safety trainings for HCF staff. To increase the early detection of HA-FBOs, surveillance of healthcare associated infections should be integrated with surveillance of foodborne diseases which necessitates interdisciplinary collaboration and exchange of information between hospital hygienists, food safety and public health authorities.

The second path aimed to assess whether electronic data of patient meals served in healthcare facilities (HCF) are available and if these data can be used to prevent HA-FBOs and support outbreak investigations.

The study included electronic data records of meals served to patients in hospitals and nursing homes. To investigate the availability, accessibility and usefulness of patient food menu data for outbreak investigations of HA-FBOs, a survey was conducted jointly among 22 HCFs in Italy and 13 HCFs in Germany. HCFs could directly link food menu data to individual patients in 17/19 hospitals in Italy and 3/7 hospitals in Germany, while in nursing homes this linkage was possible in only 1/3, and 1/7 nursing homes Italy and in Germany, respectively. A large variability was reported in the format and the storage duration of patient food data of HCFs. Searchable databases to store patient menu data were more frequently reported among Italian hospitals (15/19) than in German hospitals (3/7), whereas such databases were not reported by nursing homes. Both in Italian and German HCFs, food considered as risky for vulnerable persons were offered on the menu. The survey indicated that the availability and usability of patient food data to support HA-FBO investigations were insufficient in German and Italian HCFs, especially in nursing homes. Therefore, standards should be developed to directly link hospital

menu data with individual patients, and to harmonise storage duration of patient food data. The survey suggested a need to increase the awareness to avoid high-risk foods on the menu in HCFs.

An online workshop with the healthcare professionals from the Italian HCFs who participated in the survey was organised by the ISS on the 19th of March 2021. In this workshop, HA-FBOs were described, results of the survey in Italy and in Germany were presented, and traceability to support HA-FBO investigations discussed. In addition, focus group discussions were organised with the participants in order to identify strong and weak points for the identification and control of HA-FBOs. Participants highlighted the importance of electronic food traceability data for patient meals instead of paper-based data, and the need for training and information on food safety both for healthcare workers and patients/caregivers. In addition, a contribution was made to a publication on a listeriosis outbreak investigation involving HCFs in Germany. In this outbreak, prospective calculation of disease association was not feasible because of the scarcity of hospital menu data. The likely food vehicle for this outbreak was identified because of the identification of HCFs and the following food supply analysis of the involved HCFs. To fine-tune recommendations on the fitness of patient meal data for HA-FBO investigations, it would be useful to set up additional discussions with members of the One Health EJP network.

WP2-T5- Trace back and food risk mapping

Besides data records of food purchases, trace data on a larger geographical scale may also be used to help locate sources of foodborne outbreaks. This was the focus on WP2.5 which centred on the further development of a previously developed risk tool by the BfR: “FoodChain-Lab”. The FoodChain-Lab web application (FCL Web) is an intuitive and user-friendly app that can support public health institutes during foodborne outbreak investigations. It analyses suspicious food items by back- and forward-tracing in the supply chain. The aim of this work was to provide a faster recognition of products potentially involved in foodborne outbreaks. To this end, we implemented the model developed by Kausrud et al. (NVI) that calculates the likelihood of products to be the source of a foodborne-related outbreak based on sales data. This calculation allows investigators to save precious time and resources during outbreaks, since it helps to prioritize food items that should be sampled for laboratory analysis.

Since the calculation of the original model isn't an easy task especially for users lacking IT-skills, we wanted to provide a user-friendly and intuitive solution to facilitate the access to this method. Therefore, we developed a single page user interface using state of the art technology. We created a step by step guide on how to run the model, how to adjust model parameters for improving accuracy, and how the input data should be structured. The user can grade the results of the calculation by reviewing additional information on the data and results displayed on a map. Using EUROSTAT's Local Administrative Unit (LAU) data set, we improved the original model by making it available for the whole European Union, since the original model was designed for Norway.

Besides usability, we also invested quite some effort to make the application as sustainable and secure as possible. Therefore, we followed a modular based approach. This means that elements of the web application are reusable, exchangeable and upgradeable. We re-implemented the original model into a module that can be easily integrated into other solutions. At the same time, it increases the calculation performance of the model and provides reproducible results. Another effect of this modular based approach is that we can calculate the model entirely on the user's machine within the web browser. This increases security, since sensitive data used in the model does not leave the local computer. Hence, the risk of data leakage or hacks of data bases is reduced.

The implementation of the advanced likelihood model into FCL Web increases the availability of this model and provides investigators easy, fast, secure and reliable usage to improve outbreak investigation workflows. It can be accessed at this web address: <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>. In conclusion, integration of a likelihood model for food risk mapping into the state-of-the-art tracing tool FoodChain-Lab allows for open access use in the scientific community.

WP3. Syndromic surveillance

WP3-T1- Identify the opportunities for SyS of FBD

The objective of this task was to identify potential data sources in Member States with partners contributing to WP3, in order to develop specific surveillance components for FBD based on “secondary data” in tasks 3.2 and 3.3. “Secondary data” are already available information, sometimes collected for other purposes than health surveillance that may be of interest for health surveillance.

WP3-T1-ST1- Food chain mapping

The methodology for the inventory of data sources was defined in the NOVA kick-off meeting in March 2018. We drew a comprehensive map of the food chain, from primary production to human consumption (JRP6-WP3-T1-ST1). A general flow chart of the food chain and its environment was drawn, and information flows associated to the material flows were identified.

WP3-T1-ST2- Data source screening: availability, quality and suitability for SyS

In parallel with the food-chain mapping, we worked on a detailed inventory of data sources existing along this food producing continuum. A table was designed to collect data potentially useful and available for data-driven surveillance of FBD. The table was filled in based on expertise of NOVA WP3 members. Forty-nine data sources were identified as relevant for *Salmonella* surveillance along the food chain in the four countries: 28 were dedicated to animal health, 13 to public health, one in feed, one in the environment sector, and six covered at least two sectors. A wide diversity of data sources was observed, from operational surveillance systems producing daily alerts to isolated databases with no centralisation of data. Potential gaps in surveillance coverage were identified. The general flow chart provided a convenient framework to identify existing data sources for inter-sectoral foodborne zoonosis surveillance. This facilitated pinpointing possible but yet unused data sources. As the identified data sources are planned to be used in task 3.2. for the development of univariate surveillance modules, quality of the data for that purpose were critically assessed (JRP6-WP3-T1-ST2).

WP3-T2- Univariate syndromic surveillance development for FBD (and AMR)

Tasks 2 and 3 were launched at the end of Year 1. Task 1 showed that the three countries participating in T2 and T3 do not have the same level of progress in the implementation and use of SyS monitoring tools. We therefore put in place different strategies depending on the degree of progress. However, we chose the same case study in all three countries: the monitoring of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* from animal and food production to human population. We evaluated univariate syndromic surveillance data of many kinds and origins, from high to very low specificity. For example, we tested datasets of *Campylobacter* isolations on broiler carcasses but also syndromic data (digestive symptoms). Datasets had thus various statistical characteristics like stationarity, trend, seasonality, average number of events, etc. These characteristics influenced the results of detection algorithms, based on their configuration. In this context, we applied a wide range of detection algorithms based on various statistical theories with various sensitivity and specificity in order to highlight diverse statistical anomalies. These algorithms were all effective in different ways, with their performance generally being complementary. In order to enhance sensitivity of detection algorithms and thus to increase relevance of identified events, three main points were raised: the combination of several algorithms, the overlap of multiple datasets and, the use of various temporal and spatial resolutions.

WP3-T3- Evaluation of multivariate syndromic surveillance for FBD

We worked on the methods to integrate signals from different univariate syndromic surveillance systems to improve outbreak detection in humans. In Sweden, an explanatory multivariate SyS was developed, in which the value of evidence (Bayesian likelihood ratio) for an outbreak was assessed for each time point (week), by using a Bayesian statistical model. The model could take multiple time series data (human *Campylobacter* cases, positive *Campylobacter* tests in broilers, and weather data)

together and the outcome was available at national level. The Norwegian veterinary and public health institutes worked on adding veterinary data (Campylobacter in poultry) and environmental data (rainfall, temperature) to the current syndromic surveillance system for human gastro-intestinal outbreaks. We compared several methods for outbreak prediction. A real-time pilot study was planned for spring/summer 2020 but had to be postponed due to COVID 19 crisis. A dashboard was developed for evaluating the possible usefulness and benefits of having this system running in real-time. ANSES worked on the development of detection algorithms which processed data from i) bovine sector (cattle mortality, Salmonella isolations in cattle, reports on cattle diseases), ii) food sector (Salmonella isolations in beef and dairy products) and iii) human health (number of human gastro-intestinal outbreaks).

WP4. Spatial risk mapping

WP4-T1- Identification of spatial relationships and patterns in Salmonella prevalence

WP4-T1-ST1- Surveillance in high prevalence regions to detect introduction and changes in prevalence.

The high prevalence region chosen for studies in this task was Spain. Surveillance data (animal, human and food) from national official sources have been recorded and spatially analysed to identify possible links between the main stakeholders to strength the surveillance efforts under the one health perspective.

Recorded surveillance information on human cases could only be linked to the administrative level NUTS 3. A descriptive analysis of the clinical data (hospital burden including hospitalization rates and case-fatality rates, costs, and risk factors) was performed to evaluate changes in the burden of the disease.

Recorded surveillance information on food could not be properly linked to their geographical location as that information was found missing in most cases. From the exploration of the surveillance sources, we concluded that even if food alerts were mainly in meat (particularly pork and poultry with a positive rate around 7%, Salmonella-related food-borne outbreaks were mainly related to eggs.

Recorded surveillance information on pigs (isolation and antimicrobial susceptibility typing of Salmonella) have been georeferenced and explored to identify a spatial pattern in the probability of isolation of Salmonella. Results suggested a West-East increasing risk of Salmonella infection in swine at the province level in Spain, with certain serotype-specific patterns differing (i.e., higher chance of retrieving certain serotypes in certain regions). Association of risk areas with human cases could not be explored because human data does not contain epidemiological information on the possible source of salmonellosis infection.

WP4-T1-ST2- Surveillance in low prevalence regions to reduce prevalence.

The task aimed to develop a disease spread model in the Swedish context (representing a low prevalence region), evaluate different surveillance options, and find direct risks for human salmonellosis using Danish data. Salmonella control has already begun since the 1960s in Sweden, including all serotypes and all animal species. The program gradually reduced the prevalence of Salmonella in Swedish cattle, with the number of cattle found in control programs since the mid-1990s maintained at a low but steady level. To assess potential surveillance strategies, both the within- and between-herd transmission dynamics of S. Dublin infection need to be considered. Within-herd transmission in dairy herds has been extensively studied but approaches to model the between-herd spread of this infection still lack in the literature. In this study, a two-stage transmission model for S. Dublin infections in dairy farms has been developed in the SimInf framework, which is suitable for evaluating the effectiveness of different surveillance strategies in a hypoendemic context. Alternative surveillance options (both traditional and risk-based) to detect infected herds have been evaluated deterministically using simulated disease data. Traditional surveillance could detect 25% of the

infected herds after one year, while risk-based surveillance detected around 15% of the cases. However, risk-based surveillance was economically more convenient, as it utilized one-third of the samples used by traditional surveillance. The task of finding direct risks for human salmonellosis using Danish data was delayed due to the difficulty in data sharing (the inability to share sensitive data between SVA and SSI and the inability to share data due to the Covid-19 between SVA and Swedish public health agency). For that reason, the goal of the task was partially modified to develop a method that can measure risks using the Swedish bulk milk screening data instead of human cases. The developed method allows to describe the spatial distribution of *S. Dublin* in Sweden and quantify associations between *S. Dublin*-positive herds and hypothesized risk factors. The spatial scan statistical analysis was adopted to evaluate the spatial clustering of *S. Dublin* and its temporal changes. To evaluate the effect of potential risk factors on the risk of *S. Dublin*, Bayesian regression models using the INLA-SPDE approach were developed. Two positive clustered areas were detected, which means that these areas are more likely to have high numbers of seropositive cattle to *S. Dublin* compared to other regions. These areas are characterized by slightly bigger herd size, high temperature, low precipitation, and fewer contacts with other herds. It remains unclear which factors may be risk factors for spreading *S. Dublin* infections between cattle herds. Human case data were not available to assess the direct risks for human salmonellosis, but the methodologies applicable to human cases have been sufficiently tested using animal data. The models and methods developed in this sub-task can be applied to other similar diseases or other regions.

WP4-T2- Risk of introduction of Salmonella in pig farms through animal feed.

The focus of this deliverable was changed from its original objective due to the decision to ban formaldehyde in the EU, which was the main scenario that was going to be addressed originally. Because of this, an alternative study, based on the assessment of the usefulness of surveillance AMR data for monitoring emergence of *Salmonella* strains of animal origin, was performed. Preliminary studies performed on resistance data determined in *Salmonella* strains from poultry demonstrated the usefulness of multivariate approaches to detect the emergence of AMR profiles ('resistotypes') that could be then used as targets of surveillance projects (Alvarez et al., 2019). These preliminary studies, conducted on isolates of poultry origin since a large strain panel was available, were further extended for the analysis of swine *Salmonella* strains collected between 2001 and 2017 and subjected to serotyping and antimicrobial susceptibility testing in the frame of the surveillance program for antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella*.

The analysis carried out in a total of 1,318 pig strains belonging to 63 different serotypes included data on AMR to up to 12 different antimicrobials. Resistance data was analyzed using generalized estimating equations in order to assess the existence of trends in the proportion of resistance strain for each of the antimicrobial, and Bayesian network analysis and hierarchical clustering analysis in order to identify links between the presentation of specific patterns of resistance. Furthermore, the spatial distribution of strains presenting specific resistance patterns was analyzed through the use of empirical Bayesian smoothing methods to identify resistance-resistotype specific spatial patterns. The analyses revealed specific groups of phenotypic resistances that were typically presented simultaneously beyond the ones already expected (e.g., antimicrobials belonging to the same class such as nalidixic acid and ciprofloxacin). This suggests the existence of AMR markers that are probably associated in the bacterial genome, such as those found in *Salmonella* Genomic Island 1 (with resistant determinants to beta-lactams, phenicols, aminoglycosides, sulfonamides and tetracyclines). We found that certain serotypes were typically associated with such presentations, and had an uneven spatial distribution over the study period.

In addition, assistance in the development of an IT tool for spatial identification of soil vulnerability areas as regards antibiotic residues and resistances has been done.

WP4-T3- Role of the environment in the occurrence and maintenance of Salmonella infection in extensive farming.

Under this task salmonella data in outdoor pigs and wild boar gathered from official surveillance plans in Spain were explored. Data were analysed and displayed in interactive maps to extend the exploration and interpretation of the Salmonella occurrence (story map).

To explore the role of wildlife, a cartographic map of hotspot areas for Salmonella transmission between wild boar and outdoor pigs was produced based on the extensive pig farm and wild boar density (updated map from Bosch et al, 2015). Spatial autocorrelation was analysed using the Getis and Ord statistical test. The weight of each variable was quantified through a sensitivity analysis (1,000 iterations, Monte Carlo method). The "Density of extensive pig farms" showed a greater influence (0.79) compared to "Density of wild boar" (0.41). Results did not reveal an association between hot spots and salmonella in wild boar, probably due to the scarcity of salmonella occurrence data in extensive pig farms (<1% of total extensive production in the country).

Machine learning algorithms have been implemented to evaluate whether data of salmonella infected farms could be explained by environmental drivers such as temperature, humidity, precipitation or type of soil and vegetation. By using an existing modelling library ('tidymodels'), we were able to apply several machine learning models in one workflow. In particular, random forests and boosted regression trees were explored. Model outcomes were assessed using cross-validation techniques. The model was first successfully validated on surrogate data, and subsequently applied to intensive and extensive farming data. No clear link was identified between infected farms and environmental variables. In particular wild boar density was not identified as a driver. The likely explanation for the failure to detect risk-factors is that the intensive farming system is not affected by environmental factors, while the data on the extensive farming systems were too scarce. As a second case study, we applied the model to data on Salmonella infection in wild boar. Also here, no clear risk-factors could be identified, likely due to the small number of data points. Although the model has not yielded any clearly identified drivers, the developed framework is a valuable outcome that can be readily applied to other settings where there is an interest to correlate spatial absence/presence data on the occurrence of pathogens with environmental and climatic variables.

WP5. Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency

WP5-T1- Adapt infectious disease models for assessing the effect of surveillance programs in primary animal production on consumer exposure to foodborne pathogens.

This task has been addressed from several different perspectives including a focus on 1. development of model-based approaches to evaluate surveillance in primary production and 2. Models of disease surveillance in primary production that extend to include human exposure.

In the development work on evaluation of surveillance in primary production, methods were established whereby disease spread and surveillance could be simulated simultaneously to efficiently account for both temporally dynamic disease spread and compare various risk-based targeting methods and sampling intensity.

In the task, we worked on three different models:

1) To investigate the utility of these new methods, a model was established of the spread of Mycobacterium avium subsp. paratuberculosis (MAP) in the Swedish cattle population. The model illustrated that the approach allowed to compare surveillance strategies on the standard scale of sensitivity of detection of the disease in the population, but also time to detection, cumulative hazard of detection and the number of herds infected at the time of detection. The method established a foundation to be able to model surveillance strategies and the subsequent downstream effects of interventions and how they could depress the prevalence of disease or the likelihood of disease

extinction. In the example of MAP spread in Swedish cattle, the work also illustrated the concept that 'risk based' targeting of herds for surveillance is not always an effective strategy. The results indicate that for MAP, sampling herds randomly resulted in faster detection compared to targeting herds biased towards those that purchase more animals (high in-degree). This finding may be related to the disease dynamics of MAP which is a very slow spreading disease and it is hypothesized that this form of risk based sampling would be more beneficial for a disease with a faster spread because the nodes with higher network centrality are more likely to become infected whereas with slow spread it is more valuable to utilize a strategy that values sampling of more unique herds (Rosendal et al., 2020). The new modelling methods have been made openly available to the community both through publication and sharing of open source developed tools under the GPL3 licence (<https://github.com/trosendal/paratb>).

2. The same modelling approach was also applied for modelling the Salmonella surveillance in Danish broiler production, with focus on the parent flocks. When a parent flock becomes infected, the infection can be transmitted vertically to the broiler flocks, before the parent flock is detected and destroyed, including the eggs at the hatchery. To address this issue, we developed a stochastic dynamic modelling of transmission of Salmonella in parent flocks and combined that with the relation between flock prevalence and test sensitivity for environmental samples in the flock. The model was used to investigate the power of the current and alternative sampling schedules. The results show that in the initial phase of spread of infection it is crucial to collect as much sample material as possible in the flocks to detect infection. The model was developed so that it gave parameter estimates relevant for the decision makers. In this case, the decision needs to be taken is that in a situation when a parent flock is detected as Salmonella positive, which eggs should be destroyed at the hatchery to avoid that Salmonella is transferred from the parent to the broiler flock. The parameter estimated as a response to this was the likelihood of infection of eggs at different ages in relation to the date when the flock was tested positive for Salmonella (Apenteng et al., 2020).

3. To explore the potential impact of a national control programme for Salmonella in pigs, a previously developed model for transmission of *Salmonella* in a breeder-finisher pig herd (Hill et al. 2016) was adapted to include surveillance. The surveillance consisted of quarterly pooled faecal sampling for Salmonella Typhimurium (ST) using a PCR test, and control measures were implemented on farms where the number of positive pools was above a specified threshold. To represent the national population of finisher pigs, the model was run many times, with the prevalence of breeding sows drawn from a probability distribution, this distribution being estimated from a Bayesian model applied to the 2008 EU baseline survey for breeding pigs. The model predicted the impact on the infection prevalence of ST in slaughter pigs for different thresholds of the number of positive pools for control of Salmonella on the farm to be implemented. It showed that the prevalence of ST in slaughter pigs in GB would be significantly reduced by targeting control on farms where there were 5 positive pools (out of 5).

WP5-T2- Assessing the effect of using metagenomics in surveillance of foodborne zoonoses.

Traditionally, the surveillance of foodborne zoonotic antimicrobial resistance is based on phenotypic testing of indicator and zoonotic bacteria isolated in the food production chain. The procedure is that samples are collected at different steps in the production line. The presence of antimicrobial resistance has then been investigated both in zoonotic bacteria such as Salmonella, and in indicator bacteria such as *E. coli* and *Enterobacter* using different cultivation methods (e.g. MIC).

During the last years, the technological development in sequencing of genetic material directly in the sample matrix, gives the opportunity to investigate the total genetic material of a mixed community of organisms in a sample matrix, such as faecal or environmental samples - metagenomics. Thereby, we can investigate both cultivatable and uncultivable microorganisms. Metagenomics is a molecular tool used to analyse the mixed genomic materials extracted from environmental samples, which

provides quantitative information about presence of genes, including genes coding for antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

In this task we have focused on the surveillance of AMR in the pig production using metagenomics, and how this can be utilised in a national surveillance program with the aim to detect newly introduced AMR and to detect significant increase or decrease in AMR widespread in the pig population.

The modelling approach in this task is similar to the approach in task 1, in the way that we simulate the spread and occurrence of AMR genes in the population. In addition to this, we integrate how pooling of samples and stochastic variation in the sequencing procedure influenced the surveillance data.

The output of the simulation model is counts per million (CPM) of the gene(s) of interest detected per million gene fragment sequenced in a matrix, and the interpretation is on population level. The limit of detection of a gene is 1 count, but because the number of gene fragments sequenced per sample (sequencing depth) is varying, the limit of detection is varying between analyses. The output from the model depends on i) the actual occurrence of the gene(s) in the population (farm prevalence, within farm prevalence), the concentration of the gene(s) in the animal (in the simulation we collect faecal samples), numbers of sample collected at each time of sampling and pooled, and sequence depth used for the pooled sample. The model has a stochastic nature, taking into account variation due to sampling and sequencing depth. To model the increase in the occurrence of the gene(s) in the population by time, we used a Susceptible-Infected (SI) model describing the spread between farms.

The input parameters describing the occurrence of gene(s) were based on existing data from research studies and expert.

The number of samples collected, pooling and sequencing depth are variables we can decide in the design of the surveillance. Different scenarios were simulated mimicking realistic scenarios for these variables.

The output data from the model represents surveillance data. The surveillance data was compared to the true status in the population (given as input parameters describing the occurrence of the gene(s) in the population). The comparison was done both retrospectively, using time-series analysis to calculate the time between true increase of occurrence and detected increase of occurrence, and prospectively, forecasting the occurrence based on surveillance data, and compared that with the true future (given as the input parameter in the model).

The overall results from the modelling, shows that an increased occurrence of AMR gene(s) was difficult to detect during the initial stage of increase (either after introduction or after increase in the occurrence of already present AMR-genes). The major reason for lack of detection in the earlier stage was that the collected samples did not contain the gene(s). An increased number of samples that is pooled and a simultaneously increase in the sequencing depth could partly reduce the time gap. When the increase in occurrence took place in a low rate, were it takes 5-10 years before all farms has the gene, to keep the time gap between introduction and detection short, relatively more samples in the pool and increased sequencing depth are needed compared to a gene with a faster increase in occurrence.

The application of forecasting algorithms shows that it is possible to forecast the occurrence of AMR-genes in the population, but the precision is varying depending on several factors such as the dynamics of the spread and variability due to sampling.

WP5-T3- Modelling the effect of surveillance programs in the food production on human health.

Risk based sampling in the retail phase

The risk-based sampling approach focuses on the question how to subdivide sampling capacity the best in order to monitor as much disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) as possible. The basic idea is that sampling for those pathogen-product combinations is preferred, for which surveillance is cheapest in

terms of costs / DALYs monitored. In this study we focus on Salmonella in pig meat in the retail phase. Costs per sample refer to microbiological analysis. The number of samples is set using the criterion of a constant relative uncertainty of estimated pathogen prevalence. The number of DALYS is estimated using an overall pathogen-food animal value, which is subdivided over products using exposure assessment estimates. Risk based sampling methodology was applied to France, United Kingdom, Denmark, Sweden and The Netherlands and this led to two improvements in the methodology, so that the number of food product categories and the number of inhabitants of a country can be taken into account. Ranking of food product groups in terms of costs / DALYs monitored was performed for the respective countries both separately and in combination.

Cost-effectiveness of sampling in the retail phase

We also explored a method to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of product testing in the pre-retail and retail phase, by food industry and the government, respectively, related to food product withdrawal. The criterion is here costs / DALYs evaded. We focused again on Salmonella in pig meat. Costs refer to microbiological analysis, and the number of samples taken as reported. The effect includes a positive effect on public health, expressed in DALYs, as batches with a positive test will not reach the consumer, or will be heat-treated first. Cost-effectiveness can be compared with a criterion set by WHO. This comparison indicates that the short-term effect of product testing is not cost-effective, the more since it is suspected that the present calculations give too favourable an estimate. On the other hand, uncertainty of the calculations is large. We did not incorporate the long-term effect of product testing on hygiene performance of food industry, which is difficult to quantify.

Cost-effectiveness of sampling in the farm phase

We explored a method to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of surveillance in the farm phase, focusing on Salmonella in pigs, and applying it to The Netherlands and Great Britain. The criterion is costs / DALYs evaded. Costs refer to the number of samples taken, and the costs of microbiological analysis per sample. To calculate DALYs evaded, it is assumed that pig meat from Salmonella test-positive farms does not reach the consumer. It is calculated as a decrease in Salmonella prevalence at animal level as a result of surveillance, which is carried through the slaughterhouse- and consumer phase to result in a reduction of DALYs.

It is shown that cost-effectiveness is independent of the number of farms sampled, and decreases with the number of samples taken per farm. Cost-effectiveness is more favourable (lower) for GB than for The Netherlands, 4.78E3 and 8.70E3 euros/DALY, respectively, for comparable scenarios. Both the costs and the DALYs evaded are higher for GB, being a larger country, but DALYs evaded with a higher factor than costs. It must be stressed, however, that the calculations have a high uncertainty.

Cost-effectiveness of sampling in the farm phase is much more favourable than in the (pre-)retail phase, being about 8.5E3 euro's/DALY vs 6.08E4 or 2.26E5 euro's/DALY (depending on sampling system)(Evers et al., 2020). The value of 8.5E3 euros/DALY is also lower than 4.6E4 euros/DALY, the standard value set by WHO for cost-effectiveness of an intervention (WHO Europe, 2014).

Additional data collection and conceptual model improvement will increase reliability of the calculation results.

4 Project self-assessment

Main objectives initially proposed have been accomplished. We have had a collaborative partnership with several new collaborations initiated between veterinary and medicine institutes within countries, as well as between countries. A number of novel tools have been developed, both for research and surveillance (model scripts) and dissemination (story map). Improvement of operational surveillance systems in human health were obtained by adding surveillance components relative to animal health and to environmental conditions.

Covid-19

One of the main problems that occurred during the project period was the covid-19 pandemic. The project was formed to include partners from both animal and public health and from several member states. We were happy to create such a diverse group, but many experts and researchers in NOVA had never worked together before the start of the project. Therefore, it took some time before all participants understood and agreed on the practical implementation of all tasks and subtasks in the project plan. In the second year, work started to speed up, but when the pandemic hit many tasks slowed down and it was a serious disturbance to the project. Well-established everyday working routines were altered, face-to-face meetings were not possible, and many experts, especially in the public health institutes, had to prioritise work tasks directly related to covid-19. The extension of the project into 2021 helped us finish our deliverables but did not fully compensate for the impaired connection in our newly formed network. However, many new links have been created and there are several ideas about how we can capture potential synergies between work that we did and plan for that future, and how we can continue our collaboration.

Data access and quality

Several WPs encountered difficulties to access data and share data between institutions, also within country, due to confidentiality, budget, slow retrieval processes, or data ownership issues. These difficulties were not a surprise, in fact data access was already a focus in our WPs. These obstacles were handled in different ways, for example by aggregating data or changing to another disease of interest. This was not necessarily a problem, as the focus of NOVA has been the epidemiological methods, not one specific disease. However, aggregation of data leads to a loss of information and in a few tasks (in WP4 and WP5), the difficulty or slow process to share human case data resulted in less multidisciplinary outcomes. To compensate for this we have chosen to build tools and models that are general enough to be used for other diseases and data. One approach has been to include synthetic human case data in a model framework, so that the model is fully developed and ready to use once real data are available. In WP2, progress to access large food consumer data was made, but was later withdrawn.

In WP3 problems of data quality were encountered when setting up systems for using secondary data for surveillance. Specific collaborations had to be built with the data owners to improve the usability of their data for an objective of surveillance.

Other deviations and/or problems encountered:

One challenge that appeared already at the start of the project related to the work on one health terminology (WP1, T1). We soon found out that similar work was planned in other One Health EJP projects and in the beginning it was unclear how this overlap should be handled. After discussion we concluded that we wanted to avoid any double work, and that it made sense to contribute to one glossary. The ORION project had a glossary with a broader scope in their plan, and in the end, ORION took full lead in this work. The involvement of NOVA and role in the collaborative work was negotiated and focused on terms related specifically to surveillance.

Deliverable 4.6. was replaced because of changes of legislation in the product that was going to be evaluated (formaldehyde). Alternatively, studies on the use of surveillance AMR data for monitoring emergence of Salmonella strains in swine were conducted.

In WP5 task 1, the transmission model for Salmonella in pigs was originally intended to be a between-herd transmission model. However, **staff departures and delays to recruitment** meant that we had to adapt an existing within herd transmission model. This meant that we had to restrict the evaluation of control measures to finisher pigs, rather than also considering breeding herds.

In WP task 2, **no historical samples were available** that could be re-analysed using new sequencing methods and therefore it was not possible to conduct a comparison based on true emerging health problems in the human population and if it would have been possible to detect it the food production before it became a human health issue. Instead, the task was utilising simulation techniques to estimate how quick an emerging problem can be detected in the primary production.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
06	D-JRP6-0.1	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M3	M3		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497264#.YTsqwP0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	8 (meeting documentation)
06	D-JRP6-0.2	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M20	M20		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497532#.YTsqip0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	8 (meeting documentation)
06	D-JRP6-0.3	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M35	M35		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497307#.YTsrLz0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	8 (meeting documentation)
06	D-JRP6-0.4	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M42	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499696#.YTspCRlxd3g Available on One Health EJP	8 (meeting documentation)

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
06	D-JRP6-1.1	Glossary of terms based on a common food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology	M24	M24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734079#.XoL5Clgza70 Available on One Health EJP	1, 8 (glossary)
06	D-JRP6-1.2	Mapping of food chain surveillance across countries	M41	M42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5045224#.YQ5754gzZPY Available on One Health EJP	1, 8 (interviews)
06	D-JRP6-2.1	Description by member state of data sources, agreements and organisations (e.g. retailer chains).	M10	M12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497406#.YTsoexldPY Available on One Health EJP	
06	D-JRP6-2.2	Description by member state of barriers for use: legal, political, economic, practical and technical obstacles.	M24	M24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497418#.YTszSJ0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	
06	D-JRP6-2.3	Structured review of the field.	M5	M5		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497396#.YTszhp0zY-U	

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						Available on One Health EJP	
06	D-JRP6-2.5	Description of data infrastructure module, including an electronic informed consent tool (Original title: Data infrastructure built, electronic informed consent tool in function.)	M12	M12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497425#.YTzCp0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	
06	D-JRP6-2.6	Case control study of food risk factors for sporadic Salmonella infections. (Formerly: Case control study of food risk factors for sporadic campylobacter infections)	M42	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5500418#.YTt8-hlxd3g Available on One Health EJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of the project	
06	D-JRP6-2.4	Simulation analyses to assess the use of consumer purchase	M42	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5500406#.YTt78Rlxd3g	4, 7, 9

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		data as an analytical tool for outbreak investigations (Formerly: Assessment of the use of the method as an analytical tool, rather than merely hypothesis-generation)				Available on One Health EJP Due to the COVID-19 outbreak and the impact that has had on the possibilities of the SSI to engage in large population studies, this project may need to be redefined. Also, work has been paused throughout the spring of 2020, because the researchers involved have been moved to work on the COVID-19 response exclusively. We would like to propose to move the deliverable and the corresponding milestone (they are part of the same project) to the end of the new project period, i.e. Month 42	
06	D-JRP6-2.10	FoodChain-Lab web application: Description and documentation of software, development of tutorials and training material (Formerly: Description and documentation of software, development of	M42	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497431#.YTsVWJ0zY-U Available on One Health EJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of the project	

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		tutorials and training material)					
06	D-JRP6-2.8	Epidemiological analysis of existing surveillance data regarding ha-FBO and foods involved.	M10	M12		Confidential Available on One Health EJP, NOVA private group only	
06	D-JRP6-2.9	Studies using the German results extended to the partner institutes.	M24	M24		Confidential Available on One Health EJP, NOVA private group only	
06	D-JRP6-3.1	Full mapping of the chain process for three main productions in E.U	M8	M8		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734082#.XoL5b4gza70 Available on One Health EJP	1
06	D-JRP6-3.2	Data inventory with assessment of availability, quality and fitness for SS	M10	M10		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734084#.XoL5q4gza70 Available on One Health EJP	1
06	D-JRP-3.3	Description of the SS components implemented and guidelines for their use	M24	M24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497514#.YTsXGZ0zY-U	1,4

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						Available on One Health EJP	
06	D-JRP6-3.4	Recommendations about the quality standardisation of data produced across the food chain for their use in SyS ()	M30	M30		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497473#.YTsyyp0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	1, 4
06	D-JRP6-3.5	Contribution of multiple syndromic surveillance components in the FBD surveillance	M42	M42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497483#.YTsuX50zY-U Available on One Health EJP Due to the COVID-19 crisis, NIPH employs two-part time workers for working on NOVA since December 2020.	4,5
06	D-JRP6-4.1.	Maps for <i>Salmonella</i> prevalence geographical patterns in intensive livestock and slaughterhouses completed in high prevalence regions	M12	M12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497488#.YTsuUpZ0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	5,6

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06	D-JRP6-4.2.	Identification of periods with higher probability of detection of infection identified in high prevalence regions and temporal evidences for an association with human cases	M24	M24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497506#.YTsdZ0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.3.	Assessment of the spatio-temporal infection dynamics model in <i>Salmonella</i> in low prevalence regions.	M12	M12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497494#.YTstA50zY-U Available on One Health EJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.4.	Assessment of the spatio-temporal infection dynamics model of <i>Salmonella</i> in low prevalence regions – Evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies	M24 (part1), M36 (part2)	M24 (part1), M36 (part2)		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499762#.YTsgjhlxeMp Available on One Health EJP	5,6

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
06	D-JRP6-4.5.	Characterization of the spatial network structure of the pig industry in a Mediterranean scenario and <i>Salmonella</i> data mapped and analysed.	M24	2019-12-20		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497518#.YTSTQ50zY-U Available on One Health EJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.6.	Assessment of the potential effect of the withdrawal of the use of formaldehyde-based feed treatments done	M42	2021-06-05		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497496#.YTSTA20zY-U Focus changed to: Assessment of the usefulness of antimicrobial susceptibility test results for the optimization of surveillance programs for <i>Salmonella</i> of swine origin	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.7.	<i>Salmonella</i> data in extensive farming in Mediterranean scenario mapped and analysed.	M12	2018-12-15		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497498#.YTSS1J0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.8.	Cartographic map of hot spot areas for <i>Salmonella</i>	M24	2019-12-20		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497504#.YTSSIZ0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	5,6

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		transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.					
06	D-JRP6-4.9.	Potential new environmental surveillance indicators identified.	M42	M42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497471#.YTzSZJ0zY-U Available on One Health EJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-5.1	Report comparing performance of surveillance strategies	M42	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497957#.YTzSLp0zY-U Available on One Health EJP D-JRP6-5.1 - Report comparing performance of surveillance strategies” and “D-JRP6-5.2 - Recommendations for metrics to evaluate surveillance performance, will be joined into one deliverable. Deadline after extension of the project is M42 (36+6).	1, 5, 7, 9
06	D-JRP6-5.2	Recommendations for metrics to evaluate surveillance performance	M42	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497957#.YTzSLp0zY-U Available on One Health EJP D-JRP6-5.1 - Report comparing performance of surveillance strategies” and “D-JRP6-5.2 -	1, 5, 7, 9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						Recommendations for metrics to evaluate surveillance performance, will be joined into one deliverable. Deadline after extension of the project is M42 (36+6).	
06	D-JRP6-5.3	An assessment of the public health effects of very different surveillance strategies to detect emerging foodborne infections in a MS or at European level.	M42	M45		Due to lag in recruitment this activity started later than first planned	2, 5, 9
06	D-JRP6-5.4	Report assessing the quantitative effect on human health of changing surveillance capacity across different sources in an MS	M42	M42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497485#.YTsRx50zY-U Available on One Health EJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of the project.	5, 6
06	D-JRP6-5.5	A practical risk based sampling approach that combines exposure to zoonoses with	M42	M42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497451#.YTsRe50zY-U Available on One Health EJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of	1, 5, 6

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		disease burden and costs for sampling at a European level.				the project.	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.1	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M2	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.2	Meeting for information exchange (data, literature, data bases) exchange on exposure assessment, DALY's, consumption data and food handling at home	M6	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.3	Food Chain mapping completed, data sources identification advanced, and ready to start developing the SS components	M7	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.4	Pilot, data availability.	M9	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.5	Case-study choice	M9	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.6	Surveillance strategies to implement into the models agreed	M12	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.7	Basic model describing models describing spread of emerging zoonoses in immunological naïve animal population established	M12	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.8	SOP, best practice description.	M16	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.9	Development of method to handle time and GTIN.	M17	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.10	Prospectively calculation of disease	M24	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		association measures and retrospective analysis of food consumption patterns in hospitals.				
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.11	complete specification of the infectious disease models	M18	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.12	Submodels to be integrated in the model framework identified and coded in common language	M18	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.13	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M19	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.14	SS components developed and tested	M22	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.15	Glossary of surveillance terminology for foodborne surveillance is disseminated.	M24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.16	Result reporting on the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution in	M24	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		intensive pig farms, slaughterhouses and human cases in high prevalence regions and evidences for an association between them.				
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.17	Result reporting on the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution in intensive pig farms, slaughterhouses and human cases in low prevalence regions and evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies.	M24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.18	Result reporting on hot spot areas for Salmonella transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.	M30	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.19	The model parts to detect emerging pathogens in the food-chain and detecting	M24	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		human cases, respectively implemented in the model.				
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.20	Interim report for a practical risk based sampling approach that combines exposure to zoonoses with disease burden and costs for sampling at a European level.	M24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.21	Integration into FoodChain-Lab, release as cloud service.	M27	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.22	Case control study of food risk factors for sporadic salmonella infections.	M40	Yes		Due to the COVID-19 outbreak and the impact that has had on the possibilities of the SSI to engage in large population studies, this project may need to be redefined. Also, work has been paused throughout the spring of 2020, because the researchers involved have been moved to work on the COVID-19 response exclusively. We would like to propose to move the deliverable and the corresponding milestone (they are part of the same project) to the end of the new project period, i.e. Month 40

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.23	surveillance layer added to models	M30	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.24	A dynamic modelling layer of surveillance is overlaid the submodels	M30	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.25	initial set of results circulated to project team	M36	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.26	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M34	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.27	Integration of multiple sources developed and tested	M36	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.28	Result reporting on risk of Salmonella introduction in pig farms by animal feed and the potential effect of the withdrawal of the use of formaldehyde-based feed treatments.	M42	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.29	Result reporting on new environmental	M42	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		surveillance indicators.				

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Identifying emerging trends in antimicrobial resistance using Salmonella surveillance data in poultry in Spain. TBDE, 67(1):250-262. DOI: 10.1111/tbed.13346 https://zenodo.org/record/3660026#.XvyQnGgzZM0	YES		Yes (processing fees: 3750€)
Climatic and topographic tolerance limits of wild boar in Eurasia: Implications for their expansion. Geography, Environment, Sustainability, 13(1):107-114. https://doi.org/10.24057/2071-9388-2019-52 https://zenodo.org/record/4244729#.X6LYN4hKjcc	YES		YES (no processing fee)
Spatial trends in Salmonella infection in pigs in Spain. Frontiers in veterinary science. In Press. (A). ISSN: 2297-1769. DOI: 10.3389/fvets.2020.00345 https://zenodo.org/record/4244797#.X6Li lhKjcc	YES		YES, processing fee 2048 € (2490 USD)
An outbreak of monophasic Salmonella Typhimurium associated with raw pork sausage and other pork products, Denmark 2018–19 https://zenodo.org/record/4249319#.X6UIWmhKjcc	YES		YES (no processing fee for this publication)
Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review https://zenodo.org/record/3747633#.XpCQ_sgzZM0	YES		YES (no processing fee)
Non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi Salmonella related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, comorbidities, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs. 10.1007/s10096-018-3433-1 https://zenodo.org/record/4244788#.X6LhGYhKjcc	YES	YES Embargo length = 24 months Manuscript release	

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
		date = 20 November 2018	
<p>Salmonella Surveillance Systems in Swine and Humans in Spain: A Review.</p> <p>10.3390/vetsci6010020 https://zenodo.org/record/3635293#.XjlyUGhKhPY</p>	YES		YES (no processing fee)
<p>Using stochastic dynamic modelling to estimate the sensitivity of current and alternative surveillance program of Salmonella in conventional broiler production</p> <p>10.1038/s41598-020-76514-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4271431#.X65ljTiWxPY</p>	YES		YES, processing fee 1570€
<p>Modelling spread and surveillance of Mycobacterium avium subsp. paratuberculosis in the Swedish cattle trade network</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2020.105152 https://zenodo.org/record/4450338</p>	YES		YES, processing fee 2837€ (3450 USD), excluding taxes
<p>A one health glossary to support communication and information exchange between the human health, animal health and food safety sectors.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263 https://zenodo.org/record/4769914#.YT9EEp0za70</p>	YES		YES (no processing fee)
<p>What motivates and prevents Swedish veterinarians reporting disease suspicions?</p> <p>Manuscript in preparation by Oliviera V.H.S., Ågren E.C.C., Frössling J., and Nöremark M.</p> <p>Part of D-JRP6-1.2</p>	YES	Not yet published	Not yet published

Additional output

The One Health EJP glossary is available at the ORION project knowledge hub:

<https://aginfra.d4science.org/web/orionknowledgehub/>

STORY MAP: <https://arcg.is/1zHSub>. Summary of main outputs, available online.

SCRIPT REPOSITORY: <https://github.com/SVA-SE/NOVA>. Contains code to explore disease surveillance options in a low prevalence setting of Salmonella Dublin in cattle.

SCRIPT REPOSITORY: soon available. Contains code to evaluate whether data of salmonella infected farms could be explained by environmental drivers.

Boone I., Wilking H., Eckmanns T., Stark K., Ethelberg S. and Haller S. (2019). Healthcare-associated foodborne outbreaks in OECD countries and a special focus on Germany: current status. 1st Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats (22nd-24th May 2019, Dublin, Ireland). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/5244658>

Cha, W., Dórea, F., Grøneng, G.M., Rø, G., Hopp, P., Jonsson, M., Dryselius, R. Development of One Health syndromic surveillance for Campylobacter in Norway and Sweden. In: Proceedings of the 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats; May 27-29, 2020; Online meeting.

Gustafsson, W., Andersson, M.G. Designing multivariate syndromic surveillance for animal diseases in Sweden. In: Proceedings of the 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats; May 27-29, 2020; Online meeting.

De la Torre, A; Rodriguez, A; Álvarez, J; Teng, K; Swart, A; Kim H; Beninca, E. Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain: a story map. ESRI conference. 21-22 october 2020. Madrid, Spain. Online meeting.

Iglesias, M. Martínez, J. Álvarez, K. Teng, A. de la Torre. Spatial distribution and temporal trends for salmonella in pork and humans (2010-2015). I Congreso Virtual de la Sociedad Española de Epidemiología (SEE) y da Associação Portuguesa de Epidemiologia (APE), 21-30 Octubre 2020. Online meeting.

Boone I., D'Errico M. L., Iannetti L., Scavia G., Tozzoli R., Ethelberg S., Eckmanns T., Stark K., Wilking H. and Haller S. (2020). Electronic data on food served in healthcare facilities in Italy and Germany. Feasibility evaluation to support investigations of healthcare associated foodborne outbreaks. 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats (Prague, Czech Republic) (27th – 29th May, Online Meeting). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/5244713>

Iannetti, L., Boone I., D'Errico M.L., D'Orsi F., Ricchiuti L., Centorotola G., Pomilio F. and Cornacchia A. (2021). Foodborne outbreaks surveillance in hospitals and nursery homes: investigation on catering data. 14th European Public Health Conference (Dublin, Republic of Ireland, 20th-21st November 2021, online meeting). Poster. <https://ephconference.eu/programme-at-a-glance-83>. Abstract reference S202100519

Boone I., D'Errico M L., Iannetti L., Ethelberg S., Eckmanns T., Rosner B., Stark K., Haller S., Wilking H. (2021). Training for the Public Health Service in Germany. Healthcare-associated food-borne outbreaks. 24–26 March 2021, Online meeting. Oral communication. <https://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/oegd-2021-programm.pdf>

Boone I., D'Errico M L., Scavia G., Tozzoli R., Iannetti L., Haller S., Wilking H. NOVA Project: results of the study in German Hospitals and Nursing homes. Scavia G., D'Errico M.L., Cattaneo C., Anniballi F.,

Tozzoli R., Boone I., Iannetti L. (2021). Workshop for healthcare practitioners: foodborne outbreak preparedness in healthcare settings. Rome, Online Workshop, 19 March 2021. Oral Presentation

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

We suggest that project outcomes are shared through the NOVA Story Map. Story maps are ideal for dissemination of main achievements to national and international stakeholders and citizens, providing an interactive interface to bring them knowledge through a user-friendly and easy way. It could be published on the One Health EJP twitter account.

Most of the modelling tools (scripts) developed in NOVA are based on freeware and available through open script repositories (see Additional output above).

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

- Deliverables have been and will be shared with **national governments** and **private stakeholder**, specifically with the data owners who shared the data to feed the analysis. In some cases they have been involved in data and results discussion and appears as co-authors of the scientific publications generated.
 - Within NOVA, Anses explored several data sources regarding Salmonella detection in farm animals, food and humans in France. We developed a combination of several algorithms and tools for result visualization that will be transmitted to data owners in order to improve their surveillance systems (2022). The interest of such algorithms is discussed with the National Platform for Animal Health Surveillance (ESA) and the Health monitoring platform for the Food Supply Chain (SCA).
- **Swedish Board of Agriculture**. Our models and methods have been used as effective tools for the national surveillance plan that is adopted by the Swedish Board of Agriculture based on recommendations from SVA
- **Animal health organizations**; Växa Sverige and Gård & Djurhälsan (Sweden)
- **Dutch ministry of public health, welfare & sports, Dutch wildlife health center and centre for monitoring of vectors**
- **Spanish Agriculture Ministry**
- **Spanish Health Ministry**
- **Junta de Andalucía, Spain**
- **French surveillance networks on animal health (ESA) and on food safety (SCA)**. Results from NOVA on *Salmonella* surveillance has been transferred to the ESA and SCA networks. Further works will follow.
- **Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark**. NOVA results used in prediction or the occurrence of AMR in Danish pig production when altering the AMU.
- **Danish National Food Authorities**. As a response to the work done in WP5 task 1 about Salmonella in poultry production, the Danish national food authorities have in cooperation

with the industry revised the legislation about how to handle Salmonella in both the parental and the production part of the production. Three executive orders has been revised based on the output from the research:

- Control of Salmonella in slaughter poultry
 - Control of Salmonella in hatching egg production
 - Control of Salmonella in the production of eggs for consumption
- **Meat industry and Food Safety Authority, the Netherlands.** The use of the Cost-effectiveness measured as [DALY/Euro] for evaluating the performance of surveillance of foodborne diseases (and other diseases) in the food chain (more precisely the retail phase) was discussed with meat industry and food safety authority in the Netherlands.
- Story map link was shared with **EFSA** after the second annual meeting. We have also had contact with EFSA's Advisory Forum Task Force on Data Collection and Data Modelling

7 One Health impact

Overall summary of One Health impact

The project contains cultivation of new methods as well as more efficient utilisation of existing data and methods. It offers ideas for direct surveillance tools, but also for tools directed towards evaluation of surveillance systems. The tools and methods are primarily developed with a focus on the currently most important/frequent zoonotic diseases but may also be adapted to control other hazards or emerging agents.

The surveillance of consumer purchase patterns is currently non-existent in Europe. Results from WP2 shows that this genuinely new surveillance approach is potentially valuable and cost-effective. The methods/tools for surveillance of food exposures and trace-back developed, includes tools that presently do not exist anywhere in the world (WP2).

This project's development and combination of syndromic surveillance systems, machine-learning methods, and use of new data sources, is a first bridge across the Med-Vet gap in the syndromic surveillance context (WP3).

Understanding the geographical transmission of diseases is a cornerstone in epidemiology, yet surprisingly rarely used in surveillance practise – the focus on spatial mapping and analysis will provide better possibilities for actual utilisation in the zoonotic disease community (WP4). It will be possible to apply developed models or analytical methods cross-over to other diseases or objects (different animal species or human).

Mathematical modelling is another cornerstone of modern disease transmission understanding that we are now using to find ways to actually measure surveillance performance, and thereby be able to compare the cost-efficiency of different surveillance strategies, considering potential disease spread across the food chain (WP5).

Finally, our mapping of available data sources and identification of surveillance key actors across the food chain, including the underlying reasons for sub-optimal surveillance, should help clarify surveillance structures and challenges across the EU. Moreover, the development of a One Health glossary is useful in promoting communication between different sectors (WP1).

Specific impact points

- The identification and reporting of barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease

surveillance from a One Health point of view is the result of a research performed for the first time using a scientific methodology (WP1). This information is already requested from national authorities (e.g. Belgium, Sweden, France), while other projects have contacted WP1 members for collaboration and consultation on similar or following tasks (e.g. Matrix).

- Within NOVA, Anses has explored several data sources regarding **Salmonella detection in farm animals, food and humans in France**. We developed a combination of several algorithms and tools for result visualization that will be **transmitted to data owners** (National Authorities, National Laboratories and private stakeholders) in order to **improve their surveillance systems**. Specific detection algorithms that can process temporal signals from correlated time series simultaneously are under development. The interest of such algorithms will be discussed with the National Platform for Animal Health Surveillance (ESA) and the Health monitoring platform for the Food Supply Chain (SCA) in France.
- Methods developed in NOVA WP3 are also used in a **national Campylobacter project in Sweden**. One of the aims for this project is to assess the temporal correlation between Campylobacter surveillance data in broilers and human campylobacteriosis incidence.
- In Norway, we made a **One Health surveillance based on the use of gastrointestinal consultations in human (NorSySS)** and Campylobacter surveillance data from broiler flocks. We combined the data sources with weather data to improve detection and prediction of outbreaks. The NorSySS data was already in daily use for syndromic surveillance for people in Norway and any improvements found can be implemented in the day-to-day surveillance activities. The website and the models will continue to live beyond the One Health EJP NOVA project and also be extended further in the One Health EJP MATRIX project.
- Analyses carried out in task 4.1 will help to assess the reliability of the current surveillance system to capture the underlying variability in terms of serotypes and antimicrobial resistance for Salmonella strains recovered from swine. This can help to assess the power of the sample to describe the spatio-temporal epidemiology of Salmonella infection in a high prevalence area (Spain) in swine, and to identify factors associated with the emergence of specific serotypes/strains in specific areas/farms/production systems in the country but not others.
- Defra (UK) have plans to consider a national control programme (NCP) for Salmonella in pigs. The models built as part of WP5 for the simulation of surveillance strategies in pigs will be useful for evaluating options for such an NCP. The model and its results have been presented to **Defra**. Part of the modelling for Salmonella in pigs required Bayesian estimates of pig slaughter prevalence, derived from abattoir surveys – these estimates were useful for another EU project (**COMPARE**), for the **source attribution** task.
- The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration and the Danish poultry industry has based on the results from the model developed in WP5-task1, **decided about strategies for destroying eggs at the hatcheries after detection of Salmonella** in parent flock, including compensation to the producer. The Danish poultry industry is pioneering industry for controlling Salmonella in the poultry sector.
- The work conducted in WP5 T2 is a part of the **ongoing revision of surveillance of AMR in the Danish animal and food production (DANMAP)**. In the future, this surveillance will be based on **metagenomics** rather than cultivation, that is used today. Thereby the approach and opportunities for collection of samples will be changed. The integration of the surveillance in the animal and food production will increase the opportunity to get the food production more integrated with other sectors of the One Health concept.

- In Sweden, output from NOVA has been used to support the Swedish Board of Agriculture and the animal health organisations in their work **to adapt surveillance activities and Swedish legislation to the new Animal Health Law** within the EU. The models have been used to support decisions about the target confidence level of future surveillance and to compare surveillance alternatives (e.g. different sample size, sample type, frequency of testing).
- As a response to the work done in WP5 task 1 about Salmonella in poultry production, the Danish national food authorities have in cooperation with the industry **revised the legislation about the monitoring and management of Salmonella** in both the parental and the production part of the poultry production.
- Calculations showed that sampling in the veterinary (farm) phase is much more cost-effective (DALY/Euro) than in the retail phase, given that the sampling result has consequences in terms of animal/product withdrawal.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	4	4	4
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	4	4	4
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	5	5	5
Integration	3	5	3
Sustainability	3	4	4
Impact of the project	4	4	4
TOTAL	23/30	26/30	24/30

AVERAGE: 24

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The results largely reflect the objectives as set out in the full proposal. Deviations from the original objectives (as for example research on Salmonella) are mostly justified.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project results align well with the original objectives.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project has fulfilled its main objectives initially proposed. Deviations have been justified and are related mainly to data issues and to the pandemic. Innovative solutions to constraints have been developed, such as the used of simulated human outbreak data for progressing model development.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Tools have been developed to evaluate surveillance systems, and some other ideas for better surveillance, but the results do not seem to bring much light into the question.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

NOVA explores a number of innovative approaches in order to improve surveillance of food-borne disease and minimise food-related infections and outbreaks. Although some of the initiatives have not yet produced actionable results they have laid excellent foundations for further development of novel approaches such as use of purchasing data and syndromic surveillance and eventual implementation of these surveillance systems across Europe.

Reviewer 3: POC member

NOVA has been exploring new and innovative means to develop surveillance, focussing on five different themes. Substantial progress has been made in all fields, despite significant challenges to some of the approaches, such as (anticipated) data access challenges, and also despite initial discussions on overlap with other One Health EJP projects. The themes have been somewhat devoted to separate sectors but there are also many examples of how the complementary expertise has been used to make progress. The consortium has made good use of its broad range of skills.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Several institutions and governmental agencies are mentioned. This should help the implementation of the outcomes of the project.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project management and leadership of NOVA has been exemplary, and the dissemination activities have been broad, incorporating a range of dissemination formats. The use of the story map is an excellent concept that makes findings more accessible to non-specialist audiences.

Reviewer 3: POC member

All deliverables and milestones were reached without any significant delays. The consortium is very large and involves many co-workers of which some have also been replaced during the project runtime. Despite this, continuity has been well managed. All WP leaders have contributed to the final report.

Dissemination has also been active and so far eleven papers (of which one in pipeline) have been produced, and a larger number of conference presentations are also listed. Also, innovative approaches such as story maps have been used and are publicly available.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project has been followed by four general meetings, including the kick-off meeting, some of them online, due to pandemic restrictions. This does seem somewhat insufficient, and a higher number of meetings would have improved the integration between members and helped in the progress of the meeting. Some of the tasks have been done mostly in a single region of the EU, and results may not be transferable.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The level of integration within the project is exceptional and the project team have undertaken a considerable amount of work to ensure that approaches were harmonised and that the work conducted complemented rather than competed with other initiatives. There is clear evidence of interdisciplinarity.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project has successfully built capacity across sectors that will allow partner organisations to further improve their prevent-detect-response tasks. The pandemic put a constraint to the networking, which might have reduced opportunity to integration but the project has still made good progress, albeit with a requested extension. The possibility to align across sectors is perhaps most prominent in the One Health glossary, a task which was shared with ORION.

There are many examples of integration also with other One Health EJP projects.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The final report does not make a big emphasis on sustainability and whether the studies (e.g. the interviews and other surveillance tools) will be maintained and repeated in the future. However, the FCL web, if maintained and updated, will be a valuable resource in the future, and is an important outcome.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

In general resources and tools created are shareable and many are open-access. This exceptional level of integration will form a platform for ensuring future success.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The report lists many examples of already adopted output, and developments that will be maintained within the organisations of the consortium, both capacity-wise, relation-wise and technical procedures, open code, the One Health glossary etc. Stakeholders/adopters are approached and are interested in the output, or have already used it.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

There are several important outcomes in terms of Impact. One of them is the new information about Salmonella in animals and in humans, and how to minimize the negative effect. For example, by identifying factors associated with the emergence of specific serotypes or strains in certain areas. The results of the project will help authorities to modify legislation in order to make a better use of the resources.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The approaches developed and pioneered during this project are likely to have an impact of new foodborne outbreak surveillance in the future and it is positive to see engagement from the project team with a variety of different important stakeholders and indeed there has already been engagement and implementation of some of the strategies at national level

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project is likely to have a positive impact on the economic and social sustainability, making foodborne outbreak investigations more efficient, as well as surveillance activities related to animals and food, some driven by trade and others by the need for early detection. Models for “pre-examination” of surveillance programmes will contribute to reducing the risk of erroneous approaches, and save money.

JRP07-LIST-ADAPT

Final report

1 Consortium composition

Project Coordinator and applicants

Coordinator : Dr Sophie Roussel, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, Anses, Maisons-Alfort Laboratory for Food Safety, Unit SEL (*Salmonelles* and *Listeria*) F-94701 Maisons-Alfort, France

Applicants:

- Dr René Hendriksen (DTU), DK
- Dr Susanne Thisted Lambertz , National Food Agency (NFA), SE
- Dr Ariane Pietzka (AGES), AT
- Dr Franceso Pomilio (IZSAM), IT
- Dr Cesare Camma (IZSAM), IT
- Dr Taran Skjerdal (NVI), NO
- Dr Renáta Karpiskova, (VRI), CZ
- Dr Pascal Piveteau (INRA), FR
- Dr Michel Hebraud (INRA), FR
- Dr Christophe Soumet (ANSES), FR
- Dr Arnaud Bridier (ANSES), FR
- Dr Yannick Blanchard (ANSES), FR
- Benjamin Félix (ANSES), FR

Dr Sophie Roussel is a senior scientist in charge of the research in the *Listeria* team of the Laboratory of Food Safety of ANSES Maisons-Alfort (France). Sophie Roussel has focused for ten years her research on the genetic structure of populations of *Lm* strains, through complementary molecular typing approaches: PFGE, MLST and WGS. **Her expertise will be instrumental for WPs 1, 4 and 5. Benjamin FELIX** is a project leader in the Laboratory of Food Safety of Maisons-Alfort (France). He has been working for ANSES for eight years in the *Listeria* Team in the scope of the European Union Reference Laboratory. His research deals with *Lm* genetic diversity in food, food processing, animal and environment, in particular by using WGS. **His expertise will be instrumental for WP1, WP2 (T2.1) and WP4 (T4.1 and T4.2).**The *Listeria* team is the French National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the European Reference Laboratory (EURL) for *Listeria monocytogenes* in the food chain. The team has access to a wide variety of strains from foods, animals as well as those from human illness across the European Union. Through existing research collaborations and partnerships, Sophie Roussel and Benjamin Felix have a unique *Lm* food and food processing plant strain collection, which is well characterized at phenotypic and genotypic levels. This collection is representative of the genetic diversity observed in France in the food sector (Maury et al., 2016). Of this collection, two hundred complete genomes are available. Moreover, Sophie Roussel and Benjamin Felix are also able to provide sequences of strains considered as persistent in the food processing plants. **All these sequences will be used for WPs.** Moreover, the Laboratory of Food Safety of Maisons-Alfort harbors well-equipped

microbiology labs, in which all the **bacteriology and molecular biology techniques necessary** for the **WP 1** (T1.1) of this project are operational.

Dr Yannick Blanchard is the head of the **national ANSES platform for NGS** and transcriptomic analyses. The platform has on site a NGS sequencer (Proton – Life technologies), the computing capacity (Dell server) and bioinformatics skills for the treatment of the WGS data. Furthermore the platform is member of a scientific community (Biogenouest) which provides access to additional sequencing equipment's (Hiseq, Miseq). The platform is fully equipped for transcriptomic studies with hybridization station (Tecan) and autoloader scanner for microarray (Innopsys) and software's for data extraction. WGS -training sessions are regularly organized by Yannick's team. **All this expertise in WGS will be useful for the WP 2, WP4 and WP5.**

Dr Christophe Soumet is the head of the Unit called antimicrobial, biocide, resistance and residue of ANSES. He has been working in the field of **microbial ecology of food industry** for the last 15 years. Since 2002, his main interests and activities include **characterization of antimicrobial resistance and biocides resistance of different bacterial species by phenotypic and molecular biology** techniques to study changes in microbiota from food environment after biocidal treatment. **Given as his expertise, Christophe is the leader of the WP3 and is also involved in WP4 (T4.1 and T4.2).**

Dr Arnaud Bridier is a microbiologist. He focused a part of his research on the understanding of mechanisms governing biofilms development and resistance to antimicrobials and biocides at INRA Micalis. Currently, he works with Christophe Soumet on the impact of cleaning/disinfection treatments on the emergence of resistance of *Lm* and cross-resistance to antibiotics using an integrative approach associating meta-omics, molecular biology and imaging. **The expertise of Arnaud will be used in WP3 and WP4 (T 4.1 and T4.2).**

Dr. Ariane Pietzka is the head of the **National Reference Laboratory and National Public health Laboratory** for *Lm* at the Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES, Austria). Ariane has developed expertise on new techniques and typing methods including WGS-based methods. Her laboratory is using WGS for the routine surveillance of clinical and food strains. Her lab has a MiSeq and the data is analyzed mainly *via* SeqSphere. **This expertise in WGS will be useful for WP2, WP4 and WP5. Sequences of clinical and food strains will be used in "LIST-ADAPT".**

Moreover her laboratory is hosting the "Special Listeria Culture Collection" (SLCC), which was assembled by Prof. H.P. Seeliger. The collection contains about 6000 strains, isolated between 1921 and 1987. The isolates are from various sources, including humans, animals, food or the environment. **A part of this collection will be used in WP1.**

Assoc. Prof. DVM. Renáta Karpíšková is associated laboratory to NRL and NPHL for *Listeria monocytogenes*, in Czech Republic. She has an experience in the field of food and waterborne borne diseases, outbreak detection, molecular epidemiology, methods of foodborne pathogen detection and **typing, antimicrobial resistance and food safety. Her expertise will be used in WP1, WP4 and WP5.** Her laboratory has access to a large collection of animal and environmental strains. These strains will be used in WP1.

Dr. Rene Hendriksen has been employed at the DTU Food and has a background as laboratory technologist. At the DTU Food, Research Group of Genomic Epidemiology, he is currently employed as senior scientist. He has an expertise in **global epidemiology, surveillance, antimicrobial resistance, and population structure** of mainly foodborne and waterborne pathogens. He chairs the **working group for proficiency testing of the GMI initiative. Given his expertise in WGS, René is the leader of WP4 and is also closely involved in WP2 and WP5.**

Dr Michel Hebraud is a Research Director recruited within INRA in 1989. He works in the Research Unit of Microbiology (UR454) at the INRA Centre of Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, site of Theix. He is the scientific responsible of the **proteomic component of the "platform of metabolism exploration (PFEM)".** His

research activities have focused on the adaptation of *Listeria monocytogenes* to food processing plants. In this context, his work concerned the molecular determinants involved in biofilm formation, the physiology of bacteria in biofilms, their resistance to cleaning disinfection treatments and the mechanisms by which some of them face to technological stresses. **His expertise will be instrumental for all the WP3 and WP4 (T4.1 and T4.2).**

Dr Pascal Piveteau has a strong expertise on the ecology of zoonotic agents and is the group leader of the team working on the **ecology** of *Listeria monocytogenes* in the farm environment in INRA, Dijon. He has been working on the investigation of reservoirs of several bacterial pathogens in outdoor environments and has specialised in the microbial ecology of soil. His research focuses on both **intrinsic and extrinsic factors that drive the fate of pathogenic bacteria** in this habitat. His expertise will be instrumental for the entire proposal, in particular **for WP1, WP3 and WP4 (T4.1 and T4.2).**

Dr. Francesco Pomilio is Responsible of the Hygiene in Food Technology and Animal Feeds Unit at IZSAM and he works in the **Italian National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria monocytogenes***. Dr Pomilio has an expertise in human and animal food safety dealing with *L. monocytogenes*, validation of- microbiological analytical methods, development of the Italian database of isolates and improvements of the SEAP (Italian data collection system on Foodborne pathogens), prevalence and persistence of *L. monocytogenes* in producing factories and biofilm formation by *L. monocytogenes*.. **Francesco' expertise will be instrumental for WP1, WP4 and WP5.**

Dr. Cesare Cammà (MSc) is the leader of the Genomic unit, at the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise (IZSAM). His research activities have focused on the development of molecular methods for diagnosis of infectious animal diseases including zoonosis and in the molecular characterization of viral and bacterial strains by means of several DNA sequence-based subtyping techniques including whole genome sequencing. Specifically, 3 molecular biologists, 1 biotechnologist and 3 bio-informaticians are employed in the Genomic unit and the laboratory is equipped with an Ion Torrent Personal Genome Machine (Life Technologies), a NextSeq 500 desktop sequencing system (Illumina), a MinION device (Nanopore). In addition, two multi-capillary DNA sequencers, the AB Library Builder™ System and two liquid handling workstations are also available. Since January 2015 and up to July 2016, the Genomic unit processed 2440 viral and bacterial strains. IZSAM has an advanced IT infrastructure, including firewalls, automated back-up services and storage units for storage and bioinformatic analysis of NGS data, including metagenomics data. Servers are managed using the virtualization technology and Internet access is provided by the high speed GARR network. The laboratory has participated to two proficiency testing trials for whole genome sequencing and data analysis organized by Global Microbial Identifier (GMI). **His expertise will be instrumental for WP2, WP4 and WP5.**

Dr Taran Skjerdal has more than twenty years' experience of research from research institutes and companies within the areas food quality, food safety, risk assessment and multidisciplinary decision support. The last 10 years she has worked at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute with food safety and bacteriology with focus on growth, survival, pathogenicity and adaptation of *Listeria* and *Staphylococcus* during food processing. The work includes research activities and support to food authorities. **Her expertise will be useful for WP1, WP3 and WP4. Taran is the leader of the WP1.**

NVI has a large and growing collection of *Listeria* strains, in particular of isolates from meat and meat processing facilities and isolates from animals. **These isolates will be used in WP1**

Dr Live L. Nesse, DVM, PhD started working in research 35 years ago. She works at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute The last 15 years she has focused on the importance of bacteria's biofilm forming abilities for persistence in various environments, gene transfer in biofilms and anti-biofilm strategies. She has been the manager of numerous research projects with both national and international partners, and is presently the manager of a large Norwegian project studying persistence of *Listeria* in fish processing facilities with emphasis on the possible role of biofilm. **Her expertise will be useful for WP3.**

Dr Karin Lagesen has a PhD in bioinformatics, and has been employed at the Norwegian Veterinary Institute since 2015. She also holds a 20% position at the Dept. of Informatics at the University of Oslo (since 2010), where her focus is on education in bioinformatics. Her work has primarily been focused around genomics and metagenomics, with an emphasis on bacterial comparative genomics. **Her expertise will be instrumental for WP4 and WP2.**

Dr Susanne Thisted Lambertz is a senior microbiologist at the Swedish National Food Agency (NFA) and at the head of the NRL for *Listeria monocytogenes*. During 2016, she performed a **nationwide *Listeria monocytogenes* (Lm) survey analyzing risk products**. In parallel environmental samples are taken at the **producing plants**, and in addition isolates from listeriosis patients are collected. **In collaboration with the Public Health Agency** of Sweden, all recovered isolates are being typed. Recently, she investigated two large listeriosis outbreaks. The associated isolates have been typed. Continuously her team types *Lm* isolates originating from the **food companies** own control. **Her expertise will be useful for WP1.** Her close collaboration with the Public Health Agency, Swedish Veterinary Institute (SVA), enable us to have access to sequences of clinical strains.

Suzanne died one year after the start of the project and was replaced by Monica Ricao.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

With twenty-one partners, including food, environment, veterinary and public health laboratories, we constructed a dataset of 1575 strains and genomes originating from *Listeria monocytogenes* (*Lm*) strains collected in 20 European countries. This dataset encompasses a large number of Clonal complexes (CC)s occurring worldwide, covers many diverse habitats and is balanced between ecological compartments and geographic regions. This dataset should contribute to improve our understanding of *Lm* ecology and should aid in the surveillance of *Lm*. All the produced genomes in LIST-ADAPT are now available to the scientific community (umbrella *Bioproject* submitted to European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)).

We reported for the first time the occurrence of a CC121 strain isolated from a dolphin brain. Genomic comparisons showed that 16 strains isolated from food were the closest to the dolphin strain. Like most of the food strains analysed here, the dolphin strain included genomic features (transposon Tn6188, plasmid pLM6179) both described as being associated with the strain's adaptation to the Food Processing Environment (FPE). It is likely that the infection of a dolphin by *Lm* may be the result of environmental contamination by anthropogenic activities. The infection of this dolphin by a strain of a clonal complex known to be hypovirulent for human asks the question of the degree of weakness of the animal and its degree of exposure to this clone.

From the 1575 strains, we created a subset of about 200 strains from 34 Clonal Complexes (CC) occurring worldwide. This panel is balanced between three ecological compartments: environment, animal and food. Phenotypic tests were performed to investigate the ability of these strains to survive in the soil. Three groups were identified according to the survival rate (SR): phenotype 1 (SR<2%), phenotype 2 (2%<SR<5%) and phenotype 3 (SR>5%). Genome Wide Association Studies (GWAS) analysis have shown that the ability to survive in the soil was linked to multiple genetic factors. GWAS applied on smaller and more genetically homogeneous subsets (strains from the same CC or from the same origin) successfully identified small effect genomic variations in various transcriptional regulators, stress related genes whose the combination increase significantly the soil survival rate. Moreover, a cluster of 28 prophage-related -genes were associated to soil fitness in the Lineage II. A cluster of 14 phage related genes was associated to poor soil fitness in the CC6 (Lineage I).

We also tested the antimicrobial susceptibility toward 11 antibiotics and 4 biocides. Results revealed that strains isolated from food exhibited overall higher minimal inhibitory concentrations (MIC) for ammonium quaternary compounds (QACs) and peracetic acid (PAC) than strains isolated from animals and natural environments. Conversely, no significant difference was observed among MIC of antibiotics for strains depending on their origins. Interestingly, repeated exposure to QACs recurrently

led to a decrease of susceptibility toward ciprofloxacin (CIP), a fluoroquinolone antibiotic, largely used in human and veterinary medicine and considered as a critically important antimicrobial. Moreover, these lower levels of susceptibility to CIP remained stable in most strains even after subcultures without biocide selection pressure suggesting an adaptation involving modifications at the genetic level. PanGWAS analysis have shown e that accessory genomics elements were causally associated with biocide tolerance. These elements were detected across 197 strains. Prophage-related loci and mobile genetic elements (MGEs), including the Tn6188_qacH transposon and the pLMST6_emrC plasmid, were associated with tolerance to benzalkonium-chloride (BC), a QAC widely used in food processing. In addition to BC, the pLMST6_emrC was associated with tolerance to another QAC, the didecyldimethylammonium-chloride, denoting the pleiotropic effect of such marker. Genomics elements encoding for cell-surface proteins were associated with BC or polyhexamethylene-biguanide (PHMB) tolerance, while no associations were detected for chemically reactive biocides (alcohols and chlorines). PHMB tolerance markers were restricted to lineage I strains from animal and the environment. In contrast, the MGEs related to QACs tolerance were widespread across lineage I and II food strains, emphasizing the high adaptability of such strains, the polygenic nature of tolerance mechanisms and the need to monitor these markers to reduce the risk of tolerant-genotypes in food industrial settings.

3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WPO: Coordination (M1-M30)

The LIST-ADAPT leader, Laurent Guillier, left the project during the summer of year 2 (Y2) for another position in ANSES. The project lead has been transferred to Sophie Roussel, the successor of Laurent Guillier. Sophie Roussel is a senior scientist that has maintained close relationships with all the LIST-ADAPT partners. Indeed, she was a scientist at Anses from 2007 to 2017 working as the head of the molecular typing team of different food-borne bacteria, including *Listeria monocytogenes*. She was closely involved in European projects funded by EFSA and by the European Union (Horizon 2020 PHC7-“COMPARE”). In 2016, with her team, she wrote and set up LIST-ADAPT. Sophie Roussel worked then during two years (2017-2019) as Research Director at INRAe and was coordinator of the International Centre of Microbial Resources (CIRM) set up by INRAe. In this frame, she was involved in different European programs (H2020 -“CIRCLES” project and H2020 EJP One Health “CARE”).

As LIST-ADAPT leader, Sophie Roussel coordinated and organised two face-to-face meetings (M25): (i) the first – one day -17th January 2020- meeting ANSES-INRA specifically dedicated to WP3-WP4 (ii) the second - half a day -24th January 2020- with all the partners. Sophie Roussel was invited to present the project (i) during the annual European workshop EURL / NRL *Listeria* in January 2020 (see JRP7-WP5-T4: Dissemination) (ii) during meetings with different scientific partners such as the LIBio, a laboratory of Lorraine University (24th November 2020) and the main professional federations of the French food industry /ADEPALE) (26th November 2020). In addition, Sophie Roussel was invited by the ANSES management team to present the project to the scientific organisation committee of the Anses (26th May 2020 -60 participants). Sophie Roussel is also invited to present the project and all the results during the annual European workshop EURL / NRL *Listeria* in 2021. The seven LISTADAPT NRL partners will attend the meeting. Sophie Roussel will organize a skype closure meeting in May 2021.

WP1: Constitution of a strains collection representative of the different reservoirs of *Listeria monocytogenes* (M1-M12)

JRP7-WP1-T1: Strain collection (M1-M12)

The LIST-ADAPT strain collection, unique in Europe, is composed of two compartments, one of which (First compartment C1) very original, as it regroups 847 strains isolated in the environment (soil, river, farm environment) along with strains from wild and farm animals (both healthy and animal presenting

clinical symptoms). The second compartment (C2) is composed of 728 strains from five ready-to-eat (RTE) food categories from LIST-ADAPT partners (Table 1). All the 1575 strains are now centralized, long-term maintained and stored within the ANSES bacterial collection. The future use of some of these strains is protected by MTAs (Material Transfer Agreement). At ANSES, typing data (MLST data and cgMLST data) and associated epidemiological information of all the strains are centralized in a molecular database under the software BioNumerics version 7.6.3. A standardized nomenclature has been established with well-defined categories for all epidata (country, origin, matrix and animal condition) in order to improve the homogeneity of strains IDs

Table 1: Repartition by compartments and sub-compartments of strains from the whole LIST-ADAPT collection (1,575)

Animal and environment (C1)				Food products and food production environment (C2)					
Farm animals	Wild animals	Soil and farm environment	Total	Meat	Fish	Dairy	Vegetables	Composite dish	Total
459	194	194	847	246	165	119	95	103	728

JRP7-WP1-T2: Campaigns to collect additional animal and environmental strains (M1-M10)

JRP7-WP1-T2-ST1: External collaborations (M1-M2)

To increase the size and representativeness of the collection, the LIST-ADAPT consortium performed an extensive review of all recent collections of published and unpublished *Lm* strains and then contacted researchers in charge of these collections. Finally, 14 external partners, food and veterinary laboratories and research institutes, all dealing with *Lm* hazards in Europe, collaborated with the LIST-ADAPT consortium (Tables 2 and 3). The initial collection included more strains from animals with listeriosis-associated clinical symptoms than without symptoms. In order to reduce the number of strains originating from animals with listeriosis while maintaining maximum diversity of the dataset, we adopted an original method to select the strains based on metadata (e.g., type of sample, geographic location, isolation time, molecular typing data such as PFGE profiles, animal species and geographic sampling location). This method relies on Gower's coefficient (GC), which is a dissimilarity measure: the “distance” between two units is the sum of all the variable-specific distances (associated with metadata categories). Because this collaborative work, we increased the representativeness and the diversity of animal and environmental *Lm* strains (strains from more countries at the European Union (EU) level and more partners at a national level). We constructed a large dataset comprising 344 animal and environmental *Lm* strains from 6 European countries and published collections (Table 2), as well as 373 animal and environmental *Lm* strains from 15 European countries and non-published collections (Table 3).

Table 2: List of 344 animal and environmental *Listeria monocytogenes* strains from published microbial collections.

Partner	Country (country code)	Category	Origin of isolation	No. of strains	Isolation year	References
Department of Food Hygiene and Environmental Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine of Helsinki (n=132)	Finland (FI)	Wild animals	Wild birds, hare, reindeer [NS]	49	1998, 2001	10,14
		Farm animals	Cow, cow milk in bulk tank and pigs [NS]	62	1981–2011	14,43–46
			Cow (aborted fetus) [CS]	4	1984–1987	14,44,45
		Soil and farm environment	Silage ¹ and soil	17	1987–2004	
Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Munich (n=31)	Germany (DE)	Wild animals	Deer and wild boar [NS]	31	2011–2012	6
Norwegian Veterinary Institute (n=29)	Norway (NO)	Wild animals	Slugs	29	2012	11
Department of Applied Microbiology and Human Nutrition ZUT (n=55)	Poland (PL)	Soil and farm environment	Soil from agricultural area	46	2010–2012	26
			Soil from park on city outskirts	9	2015–2016	
Department of Animal Health, NEIKER (n=71)	Spain (ES)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep and poultry feces [NS]	71	2004–2005, 2014–2016	4,47,48
Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana (n=26)	Slovenia (SI)	Farm animals	Cow and sheep [CS]	13	2011–2015	
		Soil and farm environment	Farm environment, water, pond	2	2008, 2014	25
		Wild animals	Fox brain [NS]	11	2014	

CS, Clinical Symptoms. The reported clinical symptoms included rhombencephalitis, abortion, septicemia and mastitis/subclinical mastitis. The type of clinical samples included

cerebellum/brain tissue, aborted fetus, fetal membrane, liver, internal organs, feces and milk. NS, No listeriosis-associated Symptoms¹ Strains isolated from silage were considered as originating from the farm environment since silage mainly includes fermented forage crops collected directly from fields.

Table 3: List of 373 animal and environment *Listeria monocytogenes* strains from non-published collections

Partner	Country	Category	Origin of isolation	No. of strains	Isolation year
Not communicated by the authors (n=96)	Belgium (BE)	Farm animals	Cow [NS]	96	2017–2018
		Farm animals	Cow, pig [NS]	6	2013–2014
Veterinary Research Institute (n=14)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Soil and farm environment	Mud, algae from pond, soil from farm, decaying vegetation	8	2010, 2014
		Wild animals	Gerbil, mouflon [NS]	3	Unknown
State veterinary institute (n=7)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep [NS]	4	Unknown
		Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat [CS]	24	2014–2018
Veterinary and Food Laboratory (n=25)	Estonia (EE)	Wild animals	Deer [CS]	1	2018
		Farm animals	Cow, pork, goat milk, sheep [NS]	7	1987, 1995, 1998
Faculty of Veterinary Medicine/ Department of Food Hygiene and Environmental Health, Helsinki (n=24)	Finland (FI)	Wild animals	Hare, birds feces [NS]	4	1986, 1987
		Soil and farm environment	Silage ¹ and farm environment	13	2003, 2014–2015
		Farm animals	Cow, poultry [NS], horse [CS]	8	2003, 2014, 2015, 2018
Laboratory for Food Safety ANSES (n=25)	France (FR)	Wild animals	Hare [NS]	3	1986, 1996, 2015
		Soil and farm environment	Manure, soil	14	2004, 2006, 2009, 2012
		Soil and farm environment	Soil, compost, pasture	6	2011, 2012, 2013, 2018
Research Unit OPAALE INRAE (n=6)	France (FR)	Soil and farm environment	Soil, compost, pasture	6	2011, 2012, 2013, 2018
Institute of Food Safety and Food Hygiene, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Freie Universität Berlin (n=15)	Germany (DE)	Farm animals	Pig and sheep at slaughterhouse retention area or immediately after slaughter [NS]	15	2009, 2018–2019
Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment BIOR (n=24)	Latvia (LV)	Farm animals	Cow, goat, sheep, pig [CS]	24	2013–2018
Animal Pathology Laboratory INIAV (n=13)	Portugal (PT)	Farm animals	Cow, goat, sheep, zoo animals [CS]	12	2017–2019
		Soil and farm environment	Corn silage	1	2019
Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana (n=53)	Slovenia (SI)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat [CS]	27	2011–2015, 2018–2019
		Wild animals	Fox [NS]	2	2015
		Soil and farm environment	Cattle farm environment	1	2013
	Croatia (HR)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat [CS]	23	2010, 2016–2017
Department of Biology, Swedish Food Agency (n=16)	Sweden (SE)	Wild animals	Deer, rook, moose, wild boar [NS]	13	Unknown
		Farm animals	Poultry [NS], goat, sheep [CS]	3	Unknown
State Veterinary and Food Institute Dolny Kubin (n=22)	Slovakia (SK)	Farm animals	Sheep, goat [CS]	20	2016–2018
		Soil and farm environment	Feed	2	2015, 2017
Laboratory Feed and Food and Product Safety VWA (n=33)	The Netherlands (NL)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat, poultry [NS]	33	2016–2018

CS, Clinical Symptoms. The reported clinical symptoms included rhombencephalitis, abortion, septicemia and mastitis/subclinical mastitis. The type of clinical samples included cerebellum/brain tissue, aborted fetus, fetal membrane, liver, internal organs, feces and milk ; NS, No listeriosis-associated Symptoms ; ¹ Strains isolated from silage were considered as originating from the farm environment since silage mainly includes fermented forage crops collected directly from fields.

JRP7-WP1-T2-ST2: Sampling campaigns (M1-M10)

Soil, farm, and wild animal samples were collected in eight European countries (Table 4) in 2018 and in 2019. For the collection of soil samples, the LIST-ADAPT project members raised awareness and organised crowd-sampling campaigns. All the soil samples were collected from agricultural or wild areas according to a common procedure provided to the samplers based on the existing recommendations reported in the literature. The integration of feedback from samplers enabled a continuous improvement of the sampling protocol. The sampling campaigns were conducted in 17 areas in seven EU member states, Norway and Switzerland, namely AT, CH, CZ, FR, IT, NO, SE, SI and SK, resulting in the isolation of 75 *Lm* strains. Out of the 1752 available sampling records, the overall prevalence was 3%. We confirm in the present study the low prevalence of *Lm* in soil reported in the literature (below 1% and up to 6% depending on soil type).

Regarding the subcompartments of farm and wild animal, 55 *Lm* strains were isolated from sampling campaigns. Three campaigns targeting shelled gastropods sampled in IT, SK and CH resulted in the isolation of six strains. Sampling campaigns were also carried out for wild deer and reindeer feces in Southern Norway, and from cattle, roe deer, wild boar, wolf, bear and fox feces in the Abruzzo and Molise regions of Italy. Of the 2577 samples collected from vertebrates during the campaign conducted in IT and NO 40 isolates were detected, with an overall prevalence of 1.5%.

Table 4: List of 130 animal and environment strains from sampling campaigns

Partner	Country (country code)	Category	Origin of isolation	No. of strains	Isolation year
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety AGES (n=1)	Austria (AT)	Soil and farm environment	Meadow	1	2018
Veterinary Research Institute (n=21)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Natural and farm environment	Soil, river bank, pond, decaying vegetation, manure	18	2016–2018
	Slovakia (SK)	Natural and farm environment	Soil, river bank	3	2016
Research Unit OPAALE INRAE (n=30)	France (FR)	Soil and farm environment	Soil, compost, pasture	30	2018–2019
Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise G.Caporale (n=59)	Italy (IT)	Farm animals	Cow, goat, sheep [CS]	7	2014–2018
		Soil and farm environment	Soil and river water	16	2016–2018
		Wild animals	Fox, wolf, porcupine, badger, bear, snail, crayfish, roe deer, wild boar [NS]	36	2014, 2016–2018
Norwegian Veterinary Institute (n=10)	Norway (NO)	Wild animals	Deer and reindeer [NS]	10	2017–2018
Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana (n=3)	Slovenia (SI)	Soil and farm environment	Water pond and soil	3	2018
State Veterinary and Food Institute Dolny Kubin (n=1)	Slovakia (SK)	Wild animal	Snail	1	2019
Department of Microbiology, National Food Agency (n=1)	Sweden (SE)	Soil and farm environment	Pasture	1	2018
Agroscope (n=4)	Switzerland (CH)	Soil and farm environment	Pasture soil	3	2019
		Wild animal	Snail	1	2019

CS, Clinical Symptoms. The reported clinical symptoms included rhombencephalitis, abortion, septicemia and mastitis/subclinical mastitis. The type of clinical samples included cerebellum/brain tissue, aborted fetus, fetal membrane, liver, internal organs, feces and milk. NS, No listeriosis-associated Symptoms

JRP7-WP1-T3: Strategy for sequencing (M1-M12)

Completed. The last batch of strains to sequence was sent in December 2019.

JRP7-WP2-T1: Purification of Lm DNA from 2000 Lm strains (M2-M14)

JRP7-WP2-T1-ST1: First batch Purification of DNA from Lm strains available (M2-M4)

The first batch of 140 strains has been used to purify DNA at month 10. Four additional batches of strains have been used at months 11-12, for a total number of 546 strains

JRP7-WP2-T1-ST2: Second batch Purification of DNA from additional Lm strains (M13-M14)

The second batch of strains has been used to purify DNA at month 24.

JRP7-WP2-T1-ST3: Purification of DNA from routine surveillance systems at IZSAM, DTU, AGES (M1-M12)

DNA from strains gathered during routine surveillance were also made available by ANSES, IZSAM, DTU and AGES.

JRP7-WP2-T2: Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) (M3-M14)

JRP7-WP2-T2-ST1: First batch WGS for available Lm strains (M3-M6)

The first batch of 140 strains was sequenced in November 2018.

JRP7-WP2-T2-ST2: Second batch WGS for additional Lm strains (M13-M14)

The second (and last) batch of strains was sequenced in February 2020.

JRP7-WP2-T2-ST3: Ad hoc WGS (M3-M14)

Completed. Four LIST-ADAPT partners (AGES, IZSAM, ANSES and DTU) mainly performed the sequencing. All the genomes were centralized at ANSES. (See WP2-T3).

JRP7-WP2-T3: Genome Assembling and Annotation (M5-M16)

Task completed in April 2019. The next generation sequencing (NGS) paired-reads (2 × 150 bp) were generated during the project with Illumina platforms. The genomes were all *de novo* assembled and annotated with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork (Assembly of reads and typing workflow) used in the ANSES Laboratory for Food Safety. In addition to *de novo* assembly, the ARTwork pipeline also performs genome annotation using Prokka. This whole genome sequencing (WGS) workflow has been described in detail in previous publications including the integrated bioinformatics tools and their corresponding versions, enabling repeatability and comparability of the results (Table 5). Assembled genome files were made publicly available in FASTA format through Figshare. Different WGS metrics and quality criteria were thus employed in the ARTwork pipeline to ensure high-quality WGS data. Reads with an estimated depth of coverage <30× (as estimated by BBmap⁴⁰) as well as contigs and scaffolds with a length of < 200 bp were excluded (n=22). Draft genomes with a total length outside the range of 2.7–3.3 Mb and with a total number of scaffolds > 200 (n=46) were also excluded. In addition, inter- and intra-species contamination of reads was determined using the recently developed ConFindr software (v0.5.1). Since recently demonstrated, inter-and-intra species contamination of 10 single nucleotide variants (SNVs) assessed by ConFindr in the conserved core genes does not significantly impact cluster analysis. We decided to exclude all genomes presenting SNVs lower than this cut-off (n=12) as well as various read- or assembly-related errors (n=34). The employed WGS metrics and quality criteria of the complete LIST-ADAPT genome dataset were reported (available at <https://figshare.com/s/6582ab54ce4fabfa1fc8>). After quality control of NGS and WGS data, the final LIST-ADAPT dataset included 1575 genomes. All metadata and WGS data collected

herein were centralized and processed with standardized criteria for common nomenclature and NGS/WGS quality control before sharing between project partners. Reads normalized to 100× coverage, draft assemblies and annotated genomes were also centralized at the MongoDB database located at ANSES (Maisons-Alfort Laboratory for Food Safety). Raw (non-normalized) reads for all the *Lm* strains sequenced in the LIST-ADAPT collection (n=1508) were submitted to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) for sharing with the LIST-ADAPT project's partners. Raw (non-normalized) reads for 67 *Lm* food strains obtained from previous publications were submitted to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) database and were linked to their existing accession numbers (available at <https://figshare.com/s/6582ab54ce4fabfa1fc8>).

Table 5: Bioinformatics tools implemented in the ARTwork pipeline and their versions

Application	Software	Version
Read mapping	BBMap	38.22-0
Read normalization	BBNorm	38.22-0
Quality assessment of reads	FastQC	0.11.8
Trimming of low-quality reads	Trimmomatic	0.38
<i>De novo</i> assembly	SPAdes	3.13.0
MLST prediction	MLST	2.16.1
Retrieval of the closest reference	Mash	2.0
Reference-based scaffolding	MeDuSa	1.3
Gap closing	GapCloser	2.04
Trimming of contigs <200 bp	Biopython	
Quality assessment of the assembly	QUAST	5.0.2
Genome annotation	Prokka	1.13.3

WP3 Phenotypic characterisation of Listeria monocytogenes strains (M1-M29)

JRP7-WP3-T1: Strategy for selection of strains for phenotyping (M1-M12)

A panel of 200 *m* strains among the 1575 collected and sequenced for the project has been selected on the ground of their reservoirs, sub-reservoirs, sampling area and clonal complex (Figure 1). The three LIST-ADAPT partners (INRA, NVI and ANSES) involved in phenotypic characterization (WP3) received the first set of 100 strains (those isolated from food) in May 2018 then the second (those isolated from environment) in April 2019. The selection was done according to the MLST-CC data, using statistical tests. The most prevalent CCs were selected.

Figure 1: Description of the 200 strains selected for phenotypical tests

JRP7-WP3-T2: The effects of biocides on Lm strains adaptation (M3-M29)

JRP7-WP3-T2-ST1: Antibiotics and biocides resistance profiles of Lm strains (M3-M22)

Completed. The characterization of MICs (minimal inhibitory concentrations) values for 14 antibiotics and 8 biocides was achieved in August 2019. The results were summarized in a paper submitted at the journal Pathogens in December 2020 (cf point 7).

JRP7-WP3-T2-ST2: Adaptation to biocides and cross-resistance development to antibiotics of relevant Lm strains (M12-M22)

Completed. Thirty-four isolates have been tested on three disinfectants (seven different concentrations). The disinfectants used were Didecyl Dimethyl Ammonium Chloride (DDAC), Sodium hypochlorite (HS) and Hydrogen peroxide (Hper).

JRP7-WP3-T2-ST3: The effect of biocides on Lm strains in biofilm (M12-M29)

Completed in May 2020 (M29).

JRP7-WP3-T3: Bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of Lm strains (M3-M29)

Completed. The ability of strains to adhere and to form biofilm was evaluated by using two complementary approaches: the BioFilm Ring Test™ (BRT) and crystal violet (CV) methods which allow to characterize early and late/mature states of biofilm development, respectively. The BRT device (Chavant et al., *J. Microbiol. Meth.*, 2007) makes it possible to evaluate the capacity of a bacterial strain to adhere to an abiotic support and start forming cellular aggregates. For each strain, the BRT were carried out after 6, 24 and 48 h of culture in BHI medium, in microplate wells incubated at 20°C, with three replicates for each time. The CV method is directly related to the biomass formed by bacterial cells in biofilm. In this case, the biomass of the biofilms formed by the different strains growing in BHI medium at 20°C in microplate wells was evaluated after 24 and 48 h of incubation. Six replicates were carried out for each of the two times.

JRP7-WP3-T4: Survival and persistence of Lm strains in different ecological niches (M3-M29)

JRP7-WP3-T4-ST1: Survival of Lm in food products and gastro-intestinal environment (M3-M29)

Completed. The primary purpose of the study was to investigate whether the genetic variation had any influence on the responses. The second was to see whether the strains isolated from food responded differently than the strains from nature and animals. An effect was expected as some of the strains from food probably had been isolated from foods with preservatives. All strains grew well in BHIB at 12 °C. The growth was also significant at 4 °C, but much slower, as expected.

At pH 7, no difference was observed between the 200 strains. The additives had no impact on the growth. The latter was reasonable, as the fraction of undissociated acids at this pH was close to zero at neutral pH. At pH 4.5, the strains responded differently, and a clear effect of the additives was observed. Some strains showed a longer lagphase, some a slower increase in optical density, and some did not reach as high maximum optical density. The inhibiting effect of the additives followed this order: high conc of acetate, low cons of acetate, high conc of lactate and finally low conc of lactate. This order was the same as the concentration of undissociated acids in the four cases.

A co-variation between CC groups and the phenotypic response of the isolates was however not seen. The more than 200 isolates studied represented 26 CC groups. Isolates with different sensitivity to 2000 ppm of acetate were present in 16 of the CC groups, some of them often found in food. The reasons for the different responses is therefore connected to other characteristics is the genome, which will be further explored in GWAS analyses. The impact of the results is that challenge studies of foods and development and validation of predictive models should take strain variation into account when targeted to food with low pH.

The impact of CC group, isolation step in the farm-to-fork chain and possible genetic markers for high or low tolerance of preservatives will be systemised and analysed with classical and bioinformatics tools.

The initial results were presented in an oral presentation at the EJP conference in Prague in May 2020 (cf Point 7).

A similar study was carried out to investigate differences in survival rates during in-vitro digestion. Also here, large variations were seen, but the effect of stomach acid pH largely overruled the effect of strain variation.

The deliverable will be uploaded January 2021.

JRP7-WP3-T4-ST2: Survival of *Lm* in soil microcosm (M3-M16)

Completed in November 2019. As shown Figure 1, the ability of *Lm* to survive in soil was strain dependent. Survival ranged from zero to 22% (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Soil survival phenotype of 230 isolates of *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Ascending Hierarchical Clustering clearly identified 3 groups of phenotypes (Figure 3), possibly indicating that some isolates (Phenotype 3) may be better competitors in complex habitats such as soil.

Figure 3. Ascending Hierarchical Clustering of soil survival data.

WP4: Identification of genetic traits in Listeria monocytogenes underlying adaptation to the ecological niches (M1-M30)

JRP7-WP4-T1: Analyze the distribution / prevalence of clonal complexes among the reservoirs (M1-M14)

This task has been completed in April 2019. This characterization helped to determine the two sets of strains for phenotypic studies. The 1575 strains clustered into 109 MLST STs, which belonged to 52 CCs and 23 singleton STs. For 38 strains, the allele profile was unknown (a presumable novel ST) or incomplete (When six out of seven MLST alleles were present, a CC was assigned when possible). We analysed in depth the strains genetic diversity between the three compartments and we showed the obtained results during (i) a 2-days-meeting at ANSES in April (2019) including all the partners and some external partners and (ii) the EJP general meeting in Dublin (2019).

JRP7-WP4-T2: Literature search of genes or genetic mechanisms responsible for virulence, adaptation and survival (M9-M12)

Completed. The list of genes involved in adaptation and survival was produced from research data obtained during the H2020 COMPARE project;

JRP7-WP4-T3: Biostatistics analysis of annotated genomes (M6-M29)

JRP7-WP4-T3-ST1: Identification of statistically relevant methods and development of analysis (M6-M16)

Completed. During the kick-off meeting of Y1 (March 2018), a list of relevant tools for identifying markers of adaptation to niches (environment, food industry) was established. The LIST-ADAPT partners has identified two alternative methods (DBGWAS and machine learning method from DTU) (Jaillard et al., 2018). Within the full lists, at least three methods are tested (Machine learning, GWAS based on presence/absence matrix and TreeWAS for SNP) (Brynildsdrud et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2018). For the research of genes identified in JRP7-WP4-T2, the LIST-ADAPT partners have chosen to use ABRICATE method (<https://github.com/tseemann/abricate>).

- Scoary:<https://genomebiology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13059-016-1108-8>
- TreeWAS:<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005958>
- DBGWAS:<https://journals.plos.org/plosgenetics/article?id=10.1371/journal.pgen.1007758>

JRP7-WP4-T3-ST2: Processing of all isolates (M22-M27)

Completed

JRP7-WP4-T4: Comparative analysis of phenotypic data / genotypic data (M24-M29)

The results obtained in tasks WP3-T4-ST1; T3 and T2-ST3 will be compiled with all the genomic data for a mixomics approach. All the data will be centralized in a database.

Antibiotics and biocides resistance profiles of Lm strains

Completed. The results (genomic and phenotypic data) were summarized in a publication submitted at the journal “Food Microbiology” in December 2020 (cf point 7)

Adaptation to biocides and cross-resistance development to antibiotics of relevant Lm strains

Genomic investigations on the strain adapted to biocides revealed important insertions and deletion in the Internalin sequence. Those variations impacted mainly Internalin of unknown function. Several biocide-adapted-strains presented also deletion of transposons or plasmids. An analysis on SNPs revealed that resistance to QACs are likely to be caused by the inactivation of a multidrug resistance efflux pump regulator by the insertion of a stop codon, hence explaining the increased resistance to biocide and to fluoroquinolones. A scientific paper is planned (meeting Anses 18th January 2021)

Survival in soil

Completed. We have investigated the correlation between the phenotypes obtained for survival in soil and the characteristics of the genomes from the 200 isolates. Genome Wide Association Studies (GWAS) analysis did not evidence any link between the origin, the lineage or CC and the fitness in soil. This data suggest that the ability to survive in the soil is linked to multiple small effect genetic factors such as variations of transcriptional regulators, stress resistance proteins and cell wall proteins. However, GWAS applied on smaller and more genetically homogeneous subset (strains from the same CC) successfully identified phage-related- genes associated with soil survival rate. In particular, in the CC6, phenotype 1 was associated with the presence of a lysogenic phage corresponding to LP-030-3 and with variations in the transcriptional regulator BglG. A scientific publication ANSES/INRAE combining the phenotypic and genotypic data is in preparation and will be submitted in February for the review “Frontiers in Microbiology” (cf Point 7)

Bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of Lm strains

A statistical study of all these results is now undertaken in order to highlight possible correlations between the origin or clonal complex and the ability to rapidly form a biofilm, and/or a significant biofilm. A publication combining the phenotypic and genotypic data is planned (meeting ANSES/INRAE 12th January 2021).

Survival of Lm in food products and gastro-intestinal environment

Genomic analysis are in progress at NVI. A NVI/ANSES meeting was held in March 2020 and another meeting at the end of January 2021. A publication combining the phenotypic and genotypic data is planned.

WP5 : Trainings and dissemination (M1-M30)

hJRP7-WP5-T1: Implementation of a workshop (M1-M2)

Statistical and bio-informatic tools useful for the project were discussed during the Kick-off meeting (March 2018).

JRP7-WP5-T2: Trainings (M3-M6)

Completed. A training has been organized by the LIST-ADAPT coordinator in April 2019, in parallel with the Y2-meeting. It aimed to train 20 participants to R package methods.

JRP7-WP5-T3: Proficiency Testing Trials (M19-M22)

Given the delay in the project, we decided that there will be no Proficiency testing trial WGS as planned. However, as part of the activities carried out by ANSES as EURL / NRL *Listeria*, a PT trial WGS was organized in 2018, then in 2019, during which four LIST-ADAPT partners (AGES, IZSAM, NVI, ANSES) participated.

JRP7-WP5-T4: Dissémination (M1-M36)

Congresses and Publications –see Point 7

4 Project self-assessment

LIST-ADAPT has resulted in 1575 new *Lm* genomes available to the scientific community. As planned, LIST-ADAPT stimulated Reference laboratories to use WGS for the surveillance of *Lm* in their countries, as recommended by EFSA and ECDC. LIST-ADAPT allows continuing stimulation or implementation of WGS as the method of surveillance of *Lm* in the European countries, as recommended by the EFSA Biohaz panel in 2019 (<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5898>). Given the delay in the project, we decided that there will be no proficiency testing trial WGS as planned. However, as part of the activities carried out by ANSES as EURL / NRL *Listeria*, a PT trial WGS was organized in 2018, then in 2019, during which four LIST-ADAPT partners (AGES, IZSAM, NVI, ANSES) participated. As foreseen, the LIST-ADAPT's partners now share (i) a well-characterized collection of 1575 strains and genomes representative of the different ecological niches and (ii) a database centralizing genomes, strain metadata and all the phenotypic data.

We had originally planned for WP1 to end in December 2018 (M12). However, it was very challenging to collect *Lm* strains isolated from natural environment. That is why we needed to (i) look for more partners (ii) collaborate with them and (iii) perform additional sampling campaigns. This is the reason why WP1 has been extended until December 2019 (M24). This has led to a substantial delay in the project in particular (i) in obtaining all the genomes assembled and annotated (completed in M28 instead of M16) (ii) in selection of the second batch of strains for WP3 (completed in M16) and (iii) in genomic analysis for WP4. WP4 should be completed in the coming months.

We presented in detail the strain and genome collection in a paper, accepted with minor revision in the review Scientific Data of the Nature journal (Impact Factor: 5,7). This dataset is so important and so original that Sophie Roussel's team will be able to promote its use (I) in several other scientific publications, in collaboration with the LIST-ADAPT partners (ii) in the One Health EJP-CARE project. We have planned two more years to publish all the combined WP3- WP4 results. One of the post-doctoral students that worked on LIST-ADAPT for two years continues to work on the WP4 (he is funded by One Health EJP CARE until the end of December 2021). In addition, a scientist specialised in genomic analysis has been recently recruited on a permanent scientific position in Sophie's team and is currently working on completing WP4. LIST-ADAPT allowed us to broaden our network of partners and to discover other scientists. This will allow us to continue to collaborate with them in future research projects on *Listeria monocytogenes*.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
07	D-JRP7-0.1	Consortium agreement	1				
07	D-JRP7-0.2	Internal reporting templates	3	3		https://zenodo.org/record/3733303#.X_2-W-hKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-0.3	Plan for dissemination and exploitation of results.	14	16		The dissemination plan was validated during the face-to-face meeting of April 2019. https://zenodo.org/record/3733315#.X_2-d-hKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-1.1	Description of the panel of strains already sequenced	1	1		Sequenced strains were mainly isolated from food industry/ready-to-eat food. These strains were described with metadata https://zenodo.org/record/3733281#.X_2-f-hKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-1.2	Description of the first panel of strains available to sequence	3	3		https://zenodo.org/record/3686994#.X_2_JuhKjcc	3

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
07	D-JRP7-1.3	Description of the second panel of strains to sequence.	12	24		The last panel of strains to sequence was sent in December (11 December 2019) Deliverable uploaded on web site on 18 December 2019. https://zenodo.org/record/3733232#.X_2-tOhKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-1.4	Report on strain collection and strategy for selection of strains for sequencing.	14	14		The strategy was presented during the One Health EJP conference in May 2019 (Dublin). Deliverable uploaded on website on 16 December 2019 https://zenodo.org/record/3734093#.X_2-ZuhKjcc	3, 4
07	D-JRP7-2.1	Annotation of <i>Lm</i> genomes already sequenced (genomes available before the start of the project).	26	31		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted.	3
07	D-JRP7-2.2	Annotation of the <i>Lm</i> assembled genomes from 1st batch sequencing.	26	26		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted.	3

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
07	D-JRP7-2.3	Annotation of the <i>Lm</i> assembled genomes from 2nd batch sequencing.	26	26		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted.	3
07	D-JRP7-2.4	Annotation of the <i>Lm</i> assembled genomes from <i>ad hoc</i> WGS	26	31		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted.	2, 3
07	D-JRP7-3.1	Resistance profiles to biocide and antibiotics for the 200 <i>Lm</i> strains.	12	20		-Deliverable uploaded on web site on 17 December 2019. Poster presented during the One Health EJP conference in May 2019 (Dublin) and during the IAFP's European Symposium on Food safety in April 2019 (Nantes). Confidential until publication in Pathogens is accepted https://zenodo.org/record/3686934#.X_2_NehKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-3.2	Assessment of the ability to adapt to biocides and develop cross-resistance to antibiotics for	25	26		Confidential until publication in Frontiers in Microbiology is accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/3828737#.X_2-p-hKjcc	9

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		some illustrative <i>Lm</i> strains.					
07	D-JRP7-3.3	Data on the effect of biocides on <i>Lm</i> strains in biofilm.	29	26		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/3734064#.X_2-BOhKjcc	9
07	D-JRP7-3.4	Biofilms phenotypes for the 200 <i>Lm</i> strains.	33	37		Task completed in December 2020 (meeting Anses/INRAE 12 th January 2020). Confidential until publication is accepted. Public. Deliverable uploaded on web site on 22 January 2021.	9
07	D-JRP7-3.5	Collection of data on survival of <i>Lm</i> as planktonic cells in various ecological niches.		27	Deliverable not yet produced. Will be produced at the end of January 2021	Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted. Public	9
07	D-JRP7-3.6	Collection of data on survival of <i>Lm</i> in soil microcosms.	22	20		-Deliverable uploaded on web site on 17 December 2019. -Poster presented at ISOPOL XX in September 2019 (Toronto).	3

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
						https://zenodo.org/record/3686947#.X_2_TOhKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-4.1	Bibliographic study on catalogues of genes	13	13		https://zenodo.org/record/3733308#.X_2-luhKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-4.2	Report on prevalence and distribution of clonal complexes among the reservoirs.	26	26		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734095#.X_2-KOhKjcc	9
07	D-JRP7-4.3	Software chosen for bioinformatics analysis.	16	16		-Validated during the LIST-ADAPT meeting (April 2019). -Deliverable uploaded on website on 16 December 2019 https://zenodo.org/record/3733311#.X_2_vehKjcc	2
07	D-JRP7-5.1	"LIST-ADAPT" workshop program.	2			No workshop was organised. Exchanges and discussions were held during the kick off meeting on methodologies and bioinformatics and statistical tools used in LIST-ADAPT; https://zenodo.org/record/3733319#.X_2-OOhKjcc	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
07	D-JRP7-5.2	Minutes of the training sessions.	10			There has been no minutes on the training sessions. https://zenodo.org/record/3733322#.X_2-hehKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-5.3	Publications and communications	36			Public. Cf point 7	8, 1,3,4

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
07	M-JRP7-1	Kick off meeting	2	Yes		6 th March 2018, located at Anses, Maisons-Alfort, France
07	M-JRP7-2	Selection of the 200 <i>Lm</i> strains based on genomic analyses in WP2.	3	Yes		100 strains have been selected based on their genomic characteristics and context of isolation. These strains correspond to samples collected along the food production

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						chain. They were sent to WP3 partners in April 2018; For the remaining 100 strains (from environment and from animals), the selection was based on the prevalence of CCs and chosen to best represent the diversity at the European level. The strains were sent to WP3 partners in May 2019.
07	M-JRP7-3	Workshop done	3	Yes		Discussions on statistical and bioinformatics methods were held during the Kick off meeting.
07	M-JRP7-4	DNA prepared for 1st batch WGS	4	Yes		The first DNA were prepared in September 2018
07	M-JRP7-5	Strategy for selection of strains for sequencing in place	5	Yes		An <u>original</u> algorithm was developed for selecting strain based on meta-data describing the context of isolation of the strains
07	M-JRP7-6	WGS raw data produced	6	Yes		The sequencing was reported of many months
07	M-JRP7-7	Face-to-face meeting - 2018	8	Yes		Kick off meeting / 6 th March 2018, located at Anses, Maisons-Alfort, France
07	M-JRP7-8	First batch Lm genomes assembly completed	8	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-9	Identification of Lm strains sequenced to be annotated	10	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
07	M-JRP7-10	First batch Lm genomes annotation completed	10	Yes		
07	M-JRP7-11	WGS Training session done	10	Yes		Done
07	M-JRP7-12	All the strain collected and centralized at ANSES	12	Yes		All the 1575 strains are centralized, long-term maintained and stored within the ANSES bacterial collection. The future use of some of these strains is protected by MTAs. Typing data and associated epidemiological information of all the strains are centralized in a molecular database under the software BioNumerics. A standardized nomenclature has been established. (country, origin, matrix and animal condition...).
07	M-JRP7-13	DNA prepared for 2nd batch WGS	12	Yes		Done
07	M-JRP7-14	Selection of some representative <i>Lm</i> strains for the study of adaptation to biocides.	12	Yes		Thirty-four isolates have been tested on three disinfectants (seven different concentrations). The disinfectants used were Didectyl Dimethyl Ammonium Chloride (DDAC), Sodium hypochlorite (HS) and Hydrogen peroxide (Hper).
07	M-JRP7-15	WGS raw data produced.	25	Yes		Done

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
07	M-JRP7-16	Second batch <i>Lm</i> genomes assembly completed.	26	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-18	Second batch of <i>Lm</i> genomes annotation completed.	26	Yes		
07	M-JRP7-19	<i>Ad hoc</i> batch of <i>Lm</i> genomes assembly completed	25	Yes		
07	M-JRP7-20	Bioinformatic analysis done for all the strains	28	Yes		See Table 5
07	M-JRP7-22	<i>Ad hoc</i> batch of <i>Lm</i> genomes annotation completed	20	Yes		Annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork
07	M-JRP7-23	Face-to face meeting -2020	25	Yes		Done in January 2020 (24 th). We plan to present all the results during the 2021 European NRL/EURL workshop (involving the LIST-ADAPT NRL partners).
07	M-JRP7-24	WGS Proficiency Testing trial (PTtrial) done	26	No		Given the delay in the project, we decided that there will be no Proficiency testing trial WGS as planned. However, as part of the activities carried out by ANSES as EURL / NRL Listeria, a PT trial WGS was organized in 2018, then in 2019, during which four LIST-ADAPT NRL partners (AGES, IZSAM, NVI, ANSES) participated.

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
<p>First report on the occurrence of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ST121 strain in a dolphin brain. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7601084/ https://zenodo.org/record/4244051#.X6J4fziWxM1</p>	YES		1250.81 EUR
<p>A European-wide dataset to uncover adaptives traits of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> to diverse ecological niches. In revision for the review Scientific Data (Nature, IF : 5,5) <i>Accepted with minor modifications</i></p>	YES		1100 EUR
<p>Comparative analysis of genetic determinants encoding cadmium, arsenic and benzalkonium chloride resistance in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> of human, food and environmental origin Front. Microbiol., 14 January 2021 https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.599882</p>	YES		1000 EU
<p>Palma F, Radomski N, et al. Genomics elements located in the accessory repertoire drive the adaptation to biocides in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains from different ecological niches. Submitted to the review Food Microbiology in December 2020.</p>	YES	h	
<p>Guérin A, Bridier A et al. Exposure to quaternary ammonium compounds selects resistance to ciprofloxacin in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>. Submitted to the review Pathogens in December 2020</p>	YES		
<p>Sévellec Y, Ascencio Schuttz E, et al. Investigation of genome characteristics underlying fitness of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in soil. In preparation for Frontiers in Microbiology.</p>	YES		
<p>Sévellec Y, Bridier A et al., Assessment of the ability to adapt to biocides and develop cross-resistance to antibiotics for <i>listeria monocytogenes</i> strains In preparation for Frontiers in Microbiology.</p>	YES		

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Torresi M., Orsini M., Acciari V., Centorotola G., Di Lollo V., Di Domenico M., Bianchi D.M., Ziba M.W., Tramuta C., Cammà C., Pomilio F. Genetic characterization of a <i>listeria monocytogenes</i> serotype IVb variant 1 strain isolated from vegetal matrix in Italy. Microbiol Resour Announc. 2020 Aug 13;9(33):e00782-20. DOI: 10.1128/MRA.00782-20	YES		500 EUR

Additional output

Oral communications :

2020

- Skjerdal T, Fagereng T, Osland AM, Lagesen K, Fiskerbeck E, Nesse L, Sévellec Y, Felix B, Roussel S. 2020. Phenotypical responses to stress of in *Listeria monocytogenes* strains of different Clonal Complexes isolated along the nature-to-farm-to-fork chain. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Sévellec Y, Ascencio Schuttz E, Félix B, Guillier L, Roussel S, Piveteau P. Comparative Analysis of the genomic diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* in soil and water and food processing through pan Genome Wide Association Study. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Palma F, Guérin A, Radomski N, Bridier A, Sévellec Y, Félix B, Soumet c, Guillier L , Roussel S. Deciphering the Biocide-Resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* Strains from Europe through Genome-Wide Associations at the pangenomic scale. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Guérin A, Palma F Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C, Sevellec Y, Roussel S. Exposure to quaternary ammonium compounds show resistance to ciprofloxacin for *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Sept 2020: Food Micro Next Generation Challenges in Food Microbiology –Athènes. Reported in September 2021/Three abstracts submitted (Y. Sévellec, S. Roussel)
- Sévellec, Y. An insight in Listeria genomes. Terramo. annual workshop of the ItNRL Lm. 16th September 2020

019

- Felix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M and Roussel S (2019). Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France. 26-27 August 2019, Safepork 2019, Berlin.

- Félix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Desmots M H, Hickey B, Jankuloski D, Karpíšková R, Skjerdal T, Denis M, Gareis M, Zdovc I, Pietzka A and Guillier L (2019). Typing and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in food processing environments, prophages identified as major persistence markers. ISOPOL XX 2019, 24 – 27 September 2019, Toronto.
- Guillier L (2019). Assessment of the Genomic Diversity of a Large Collection of *Listeria monocytogenes* Strains Isolated in EU Natural Environments. One Health EJP Annual scientific meeting, Dublin, 22-24 May 2019
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- Sévellec, Y. 2019. LIST-ADAPT- Study of the Genetic diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* from environment to human; Terramo. annual workshop of the ItNRL Lm. 4th July 2019

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- S. Antoci, V. A. Acciari, V. Di Marzio, I. Del Matto, G. Centorotola, M. Torresi, C. Marfaglia, G. Iannitto, A. Ruolo, G. A. Santarelli, G. Migliorati, F. Pomilio. Preliminary results on prevalence and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* in different dairy and meat processing plants in Central Italy, presented at “International meeting on emerging diseases and surveillance” November 2018, Vienna (Austria).

Posters:

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- Toresi M, Rinaldi A, Marzio D et al. Genomic features of two main Clonal Complex groups of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from European wild animal. 6th World One Health Congress; 30 October - 3 November 2020.

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- Torresi M., Rinaldi A., Cammà C., Di Pasquale A., Skjerdal T., Lagesen K., Felix B., Sevellec Y., Guillier L., Leroux A., Ricao M., Boysen M., Lindström M., Castro H., Korkeala H., Gareis M., Frank E., Bulawova H., Brychta M., Amar C., Grant K., Pate M., Zdovc I., Pomilio F (2019). Diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* associated with wild animals: focusing on CCs with a wide capacity of adaptation. International Symposium on Problems of *Listeria* and Listeriosis ISOPOL XX. 24-27 September 2019 Toronto
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- Skjerdal T, Sevellec Y, Guillier L, , Zdovc I, Pate M, Torresi M, Ricao M, Boysen M, Lindstrøm M, Castro H, Gareis M, Bulawova H, Amar C, Grant K, Leroux A, Pomilio F, Camma C, Di Pasquale A, Lagesen K, Osland Mohr A, Rinaldi A, Karpiskova R, Pietzka A, Ruppitsch W, Szymczak B, Ascencio-Schultz E, Piveteau P and Felix B (2019). Occurrence and diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in environment and wild life in Europe. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
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- Sévellec Y, Torresi M, Orsini M, Centorotola G, Bilei S, Senese M, Terracciano G, Felix B, Guillier L and Pomilio F (2019). Investigation of a dolphin infection by *Listeria monocytogenes* CC121. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Vranckx K, Sevellec Y, Deneweth J and Felix B. Phages in *Listeria*: Who are they, what do they do? ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Guérin A, Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C (2019). Evolution of antibiotics and biocides resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches following in vitro exposure to biocides disinfectants. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Guérin A, Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C (2019). Evolution of antibiotics and biocides resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches following in vitro exposure to biocides disinfectants. IAFP's European Symposium on Food Safety, Nantes, 24-26 April 2019
- Guérin A, Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C (2019). Evolution of antibiotics and biocides resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches following in vitro exposure to biocides disinfectants. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Dublin, 22-24 May 2019

2018

- Felix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M, Roussel S. 2018. Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France. IAFP EU Stockholm 25-27 April 2018

7 One Health impact

The LIST-ADAPT project makes it possible bridging the gap between “Med” and “Vet”: this is the first time a project has focused on such a large and diverse collection of *Lm* strains isolated from farming/wild animals and farming/wild environment in different European countries. Most of these strains and genomes will be useful for the One Health EJP Project “CARE” (2020-2023) (Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union), in close relation with the French National and European Reference Laboratory (NRL and EU-RL). The results obtained in WP3-T4-ST1 will be valuable for EURL activities such as selection of strains for challenge testing of low pH foods, and for risk assessments of foods with preservatives. Further, these results can be used to assess the validity of predictive models that have been developed with few strains for strains with other genetic characteristics.

With LIST-ADAPT project, we are looking for molecular markers of interest such as for instance mobile genetic elements harbouring antimicrobial resistance factors as well as provide insight into the population structure and evolutionary history of *Lm* for epidemiologic investigation. This information could be used for the development of **new diagnostic tests** to screen food, processing environment and animal reservoirs for contamination by *Lm* strains. These new tests represent **key tools** to improve the *Lm* surveillance system and to assist the food industry decision-making around food processing for improving food safety. For instance, a professional federation of the French food industry is interested in results obtained in W3/WP4. Following the presentation of the project in November 2020, they asked Sophie to give them a presentation in next May on the results obtained in WP4. They want to understand the mechanisms of adaptation of the strains in the plant chain from the soil to the finished plant products and wish to set up a research collaborative project with Sophie’s team on this subject.

The detailed characterization of these strains at phenotypic and genotypic level will help to assess the true importance of these strains as sources of foodborne infections for public health. Mechanisms for the survival and adaptation of *Lm* (i) in food processing environment (ii) in wild and farming animals (iii) in natural and farming environments will be identified. The genes identified will be used as targets for developing rapid monitoring tests. With a view to controlling risks in agricultural and agri-food

systems, this project will make it possible to assess the relevance of monitoring plans, for instance in agricultural soils.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	4	4	3
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	4	3	4
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	3	2	3
Integration	4	2	2
Sustainability	4	2	2
Impact of the project	3	3	3
TOTAL	22/30	16/30	17/30

AVERAGE: 18

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The aim of the project was to determine molecular mechanisms of adaptation of *Listeria monocytogenes* to various ecological niches. Impressive number (1575) of strains of this bacterium was collected, and 200 of them were selected for phenotypic and genomic analyses. Such an outline of the study corresponds to the general aims of this project, and the alignment can be evaluated as excellent.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The results align well with the objectives.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Note that the full proposal was not available for benchmarking (and I am not sure alignment with the initial plan is always desirable as there may be good reasons for deviating). But anyway, the final report summary says the project aimed to “decipher the molecular mechanisms of adaptation seen in *Listeria monocytogenes* (Lm) to its various ecological niches by comparing both phenotypic and genotypic data

from a large, balanced set of strains from human clinical cases, animals, food and environments in several European countries”.

A broad collection of Lm strains has indeed been collected, and for a subset of those, a deeper range of phenotypic and genotypic data has been obtained. New knowledge about adaptation in different environments has been explored, and communicated. The project has stimulated NRLs to use WGS for Lm to a higher degree, and output from the project has been taken forward to new projects.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The phenotypic and genomic analyses were performed according to the higher current standards. Of special interest are results of genomic analyses which suggested the association of biocide tolerance with accessory genetic elements, like prophages or plasmids. Nevertheless, despite large-scale phenotypic and genomic analyses, which indicated potentially interesting features, other types of molecular analyses, especially molecular experiments that could test the presented hypotheses, were scarce. Therefore, the presented conclusions, although very interesting, are quite preliminary, and open new fields of further research rather than provide a specific solution of the research problem.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The consortium should be commended on their efforts to compile a broad and truly representative collection of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains which has been sequenced. The consortium also performed a large number of phenotypic tests delivering further insights to the diversity and capabilities of this species. However, the issue of a mismatch or miscoding within the genome data is a potentially serious problem that the investigators must resolve. Until there is confidence that the genomes obtained correspond to the correct strains one cannot be certain that the associations between phenotype and genotype are correct and indeed, this may explain why trends were not identified. I would recommend repeating the GWAS studies once the problem is solved. It is a shame that a relatively simple error could result in a large amount of scientific effort not reaching its true potential.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The large and diverse collection of Lm strains isolated from a broad range of sources, both geographically and species-wise is quite unique, and the type of output that is very difficult to produce in smaller collaborations.

The project has also delivered interesting new knowledge in the fields outlined in the proposal, on the adaptation of Lm to various ecological niches, e.g. places where biocides are used and indications on the development of co-resistance between ammonium quaternary compounds and resistance to ciprofloxacin.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The collection of *L. monocytogenes* strains is impressive, and phenotypic and genomic analyses of 200 of them are extremely valuable. This is a great achievement of this project and indicates good implementation of the project. On the other hand, the weak point is that large parts of results were not published yet, as the analyses are still ongoing. It is a hope that they will be completed relatively soon, and excellent papers will be published, though this is still an assumption. On the other hand, the results were presented during many scientific meetings which indicates that the research team is

active in the field of dissemination of results of the work which makes the above mentioned hope reasonable.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Its not clear from the report how exactly the consortium was co-ordinated as details on this aspect are relatively sparse. In a high-quality collaborative consortium, I would expect to see regular scheduled communications between key parties and oversight by independent advisors as a minimum.

The dissemination of the project was rather limited to a handful of academic papers and presentations but it is acknowledged that the COVID-19 pandemic would have hampered efforts. I would like to see more dissemination in different formats to other researchers as well as research stakeholders and the general public.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project has reached most of its milestones in time, and deliverables have been produced accordingly.

It is indicated that there were some challenges in collecting strains from natural environments, leading to an extension and delays. This may be due to an overly optimistic view on the possibility to achieve this goal with the approach chosen, but overall these shortcomings seem to have been duly managed.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

One of major advances of this project was establishing a great collaboration between many laboratories in different countries. They include both direct participants and laboratories outside the research consortium which provided *L. monocytogenes* strains isolated from various habitats spread along various geographical locations and characterized by various conditions. The network of collaborating laboratories should establish an excellent platform for conducting further research in this very important field.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The final report does not sufficiently clarify the level of integration within the project. While it is clear that many partners contributed strains to the collection, but it seems that almost all of the other work was done by only a handful of institutions, mainly the co-ordinating partner. The description of training was limited and opportunities to broaden capacity and know-how of staff across Europe have been missed. It is not clear to me how much knowledge exchange took place

Reviewer 3: POC member

The consortium itself has primarily represented institutes active in the animal-food sector but through its collaborations managed to collect strains from a broad range of sources. In this sense the network and the skills of the team have been complementary. The core team of partners most active seems small and most of the examples of continuation and impact are from France.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project is crucial for understanding biology (especially adaptation) of one of human pathogens. This may affect health of many people. Thus, results of the project should be important for sustainability. Moreover, creation of a large and effective research network should ensure

continuation of this line of studies in the future, leading to better understanding of mechanisms operating in the investigated bacterium. Thus, I found sustainability of this project excellent.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

It's positive to see that the genomes will be made available to the larger scientific community and that the phenotypic data and GWAS data are to be used in future research and development. I would like to see more concrete plans for the future maintenance and sharing of the strain collection itself described.

Reviewer 3: POC member

There have been some issues with the integrity of the genome database used by the project coordinator. This problem was not solved by the time the final report was submitted. It is said that some publications are pending until the problem is solved, and this means that there is some uncertainty as to how the project will be finalised and the key output will be maintained. A worst case might mean that a lot of work is undone. This might influence the sustainability of the output.

The collaboration is said to be maintained in new projects.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The realization of this project resulted in construction of a large and excellent collection of *L. monocytogenes* strains, and characterization of 200 of them. This provided a large body of data which is important to understand adaptive capability of this bacterium. As such, the impact of this project is great. However, molecular experiments were scarce and publication process of results is not completed yet, making my evaluation of the impact of this project "very good" rather than "outstanding". Nevertheless, I am impressed by the obtained results, especially the collection and genomic data, anyway.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Provided the issues with the genome sequencing mix-up are resolved, the project is expected to achieve positive impact, aiding genomic surveillance of *Listeria monocytogenes* and allowing for new diagnostics and control strategies to be devised.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project output will help to assess the importance of Lm strains as sources of foodborne infections for public health. Mechanisms have been identified for the survival and adaptation of Lm in food processing environment, in wild and farmed animals and their environments, and the French food industry has shown interest in the results.

Some results will impact Listeria EURL activities such as selection of strains for challenge testing of low pH foods, and for risk assessments of foods with preservatives. The project has also led to more use of WGS in NRL's.

Examples of carry-over: Output from the project will be used to better understand persistent intracellular Lm, in order to propose solutions for at-risk human populations, in a French project.

The material is also reused in a Danish project where a machine-learning approach is used for genome exploration.

Also, results from the project are being taken on board by the One Health EJP integrative project CARE and genomes will also be shared through ENA.

The LIST-ADAPT project has also strengthened the collaboration between institutes; examples mentioned are France and Slovenia, and also France and Latvia.

Foreseen future impacts relate to possible development of rapid monitoring tests, and for assessing the relevance of monitoring plans in agricultural soils, for example. These are tentative future solutions, and have not been produced in this project.

Final report

1 Consortium composition

Name of the Project Coordinator and of all applicants, with full affiliations

- Project Coordinator: Molecular Platform Team; Scientific directorate Animal Infectious Diseases; **Sciensano**,; Ukkel (Brussels), Belgium: Steven Van Borm.
Additional Sciensano partners include:
 - **Sciensano**, Scientific directorate Infectious Diseases in Animals, Exotic and Particular Diseases Unit. Ukkel, Belgium. Kris De Clercq, Andy Haegeman, Frank Vandebussche
 - **Sciensano**, Scientific directorate Expertise and Service provision, Transversal activities in applied genomics unit, Elsene (Brussels), Belgium: Sigrïd De Keersmaecker, , Kevin Vanneste, Nancy Roosens
 - **Sciensano**, Scientific directorate Infectious Diseases in Humans, Elsene (Brussels), Belgium: Vanessa Suin, Sarah Denayer, Michael Peeters.
- Deputy Project Coordinator: Institute for Virus Diagnostics; **FLI**, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut; Greifswald, Germany: Dirk Höper.
 - **FLI**, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Institute for Viral Diagnostics, Greifswald, Germany: Martin Beer, Dirk Höper, Anne Pohlmann
- **SVA**, National Veterinary Institute, Uppsala, Sweden: Lihong Liu, Mikhayil Hakhverdyan
- **ANSES**, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety: Nicole Pavio, Sandra Martin-Latil, Yannick Blanchard, Fabrice Touzain, Isabelle Kempf
- **EMC**-Erasmus Medical Center, Netherlands Center for One Health: Marion Koopmans, Sander van Boheemen, Bas Oude Munnink, Miranda de Graaf.
- **WUR**-Wageningen University Bioveterinary Research, Netherlands: Wim van der Poel, Alex Bossers, Marcel Hulst.

Sciensano, Scientific directorate Infectious Diseases in Animals. Molecular Platform Unit. The Molecular Platform team (MOLPLAT) has > 10 years of experience in the application of NGS technology to RNA viruses. **Steven Van Borm (M)** coordinates the team and holds a PhD in Biological Sciences (2002, Leuven University). He has 15+ years of experience in RNA virus molecular diagnostics (viral nucleic acid purification, PCR, sequencing) and molecular epidemiology and is an expert in sequencing technologies (including Sanger sequencing and next generation sequencing). He is author of 76 peer reviewed publications and numerous presentations in international meetings. Steven was recently coordinator of a European transnational research project (EMIDA Era-Net www.episeq.eu) focussing on the application of NGS technology to animal virus molecular epidemiology, and was partner in international projects (FP7-RapidiaField, FP6-Flutrain, FP6-InnFlu) and networks (EPIZONE, ESVV, EAVLD), as well as in national projects (AIDAPT, AVIVAC). **Frank Vandebussche (M)** is a senior scientist and research leader in the Molecular Platform team. He holds a PhD in Bioscience Engineering and has 15 years of experience in RNA and DNA virus (including BTV, FMDV and Pox viruses) molecular diagnostics (real-time PCR, PCR) and molecular characterization. Moreover, he has an extensive experience in the optimization of the purification of viral nucleic acids from difficult sample matrices, automation of molecular diagnostics, and accreditation of molecular diagnostic workflows. He is currently involved in the development of NGS based sequencing strategies for animal pathogens. Dr. Vandebussche is author of > 40 peer reviewed publications and numerous publications in international meetings. He was a partner in national projects, including EpidiaCap. **Kris De Clercq (M)** is Doctor in Veterinary Medicine (1981, Ghent University), and 'Master of Science in Animal

Production' (1983). Since 1985 working at the former CODA-CERVA (Brussels, Belgium). Head of the Unit Exotic and Particular Diseases. Main activities are in foot-and-mouth disease, bluetongue, lumpy skin disease and sheep and goat pox and swine vesicular disease. Vice-President of the OIE Scientific Commission since 2009. Head of the OIE Collaborative Centre and the FAO Reference Centre for Vesicular Diseases. Was coordinator of two EC research projects and a project for the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. **Andy Haegeman (M)** holds a PhD in Veterinary science (2003, Ghent University). Since 2003 working at former CODA-CERVA (currently Sciensano, Brussels, Belgium). Main activities are in foot-and-mouth disease, bluetongue, lumpy skin disease and sheep and goat pox and swine vesicular disease. Member of the expert group on 'Recombinant viral vectors, virosomes, vaccines, gene therapy' of the national "Biosafety Advisory Council". Assistant coordinator in two EC research projects (2004-2010) and researcher in national and international research projects (CSFgoDIVA, CSF WILDBOAR, RP-POX, LSDV_FAO, Bill & Melinda Gates, RCO, OrbiVac, Arbo-Zoonet).

Sciensano, scientific directorate Service provision and expertise, unit Transversal activities in Genomics (TAG). TAG is centralising and developing biotechnology applications for Sciensano users, including a platform for next generation sequencing (with in-house Illumina MiSeq platform) and a bioinformatics platform (with hardware and expertise). **Nancy Roosens (F)**, head of TAG, holds a PhD in Molecular Biology (1998, Free university of Brussels VUB), is International Expert in Quality Control for Molecular Detection (ISO), Expert of European Union and NRL, coordinator of the Belgian NRL-GMO, partner in several FP6 and FP7 projects (GMOSEEK, GMOVAL), coordinator of national research projects (UGMMONITOR, .Be READY). Specific interests include development of a technical platform including Next Generation Sequencing technology and research projects in the context of public health, with emphasis on molecular biology. She is author of 53 peer-reviewed publications, reflecting expertise in molecular biology, plant sciences, GMO and pathogens. **Sigrid De Keersmaecker (F)** holds a PhD in Bioscience Engineering (molecular biology, bacterial genetics, University of Leuven, 2003). She has extensive experience in Molecular biology, biotechnology, microbiology, microbial genetics, systems biology, immunology; bioinformatics applications; project and team management; accreditation ISO17025. Dr. De Keersmaecker is currently involved in the development of new methods in support of a proactive public health policy (e.g. pathogen detection & characterization, human genetic and epigenetic biomarkers), a Sequencing Center (Sanger and NGS) and supervision of several PhD students. She is author of 74 peer-reviewed papers and 6 patent applications. **Kevin Vanneste (M)** holds a Master's degree in Biology (Ghent University, 2009) and a PhD in Bioinformatics (Ghent University, 2014). He is currently coordinating the Bioinformatics Platform at Sciensano, where his main focus is the implementation and development of this novel entity to enhance the diagnosis, surveillance, control and characterization of potentially harmful organisms (pathogens, allergenic organisms, GMOs); and to promote public health genomics by the integration of bioinformatics into public health policy. He has a strong interest in the analysis of large and complex biological datasets by means of computational approaches for practical implementations, and is author of 13 peer-reviewed publications.

Sciensano, scientific directorate of Infectious Diseases in Humans. The **Viral Diseases unit** groups five Belgian national reference centers for viral pathogens including the national reference centres for influenza virus and hepatitis viruses B, C, D and E. **Vanessa Suin (F)** is currently the responsible of National Reference Centre of viral hepatitis. PhD in biological sciences (Namur University, 2010), 6 years of experience in the field of virology, viral disease, public health, emerging viruses and zoonosis. She is authors of 9 peer-review publications. **Michael Peeters (M)** holds a PhD in biomedical sciences (Université catholique de Louvain, 2018). Since 2018, he works for the Unit for Viral Diseases at Sciensano. He has experience in the fields of virology, viral diseases, emerging viruses and zoonosis. He is the author of 3 peer-reviewed publications and several presentations in national and international meetings. **Foodborne pathogens unit.** **Sarah Denayer (F)** heads the scientific programme on Food-borne outbreaks and toxins that hosts the NRL of Foodborne Outbreaks, NRL Food Microbiology, NRL Pathogenic E. coli, NRL Salmonella-Food, NRL for botulism and the NRC for C. botulinum and C. perfringens and the NRL for Coagulase positive Staphylococci. She holds a PhD in

Applied and Biological Science (Free University of Brussels, 2008). She wrote several papers on the detection and typing of food-borne pathogens, including outbreak investigation and VTEC. She has 10 years of experience in molecular detection and typing methods for food-borne pathogens (under ISO accreditation). She is involved in several research projects dealing with food safety, including pathogenic *E. coli*.

FLI - Friedrich Loeffler Institut, Institute of Diagnostic Virology. Martin Beer (M); Dr. med. vet. 1995; Director of the Institute of Diagnostic Virology of the FLI since 2004, and external professor at the Ludwig-Maximilians-University (LMU) Munich since 2014; 325 publications (30% international collaboration); h-index 40; More than 20 years expertise in working with different animal viruses, in particular pestiviruses (BVDV, BDV and CSFV), animal herpesviruses (BHV-1), and Influenza A viruses (including HPAIV H5N1, H5N8 and H7N7), with special emphasis on diagnostics, genetic characterization, phylogeny, and in vivo characterization. Research projects are focused on new diagnostic systems like real-time PCR, microarrays and next-generation sequencing. Work package leader in EU-funded COMPARE-project. **Anne Pohlmann (F)**; Dipl. Biol. 1995, Dr. rer. nat. 2001, Senior scientist (NGS, data handling), Curator of GISAID Epiflu database; 23 publications (30% international collaboration); h-index 12; In depth knowledge in bacterial and viral WGS using classical Sanger and NGS technologies especially focusing on sequence assembly and annotation. Work package Coleader in EU-funded COMPARE project; Coordinator of DetektiVir, a BMBF-funded project. **Dirk Höper (M)**; Dipl. Biol. 2000, Dr. rer. nat. 2005, senior scientist, head of the Laboratory for Next-Generation Sequencing and Microarray Diagnostics in the FLI Institute of Diagnostic Virology; 65 publications (26% international collaboration); h-index 19; working in the field of second generation sequencing since 2006; in-depth knowledge of second and third generation sequencing and sequencing data analysis with a special focus on sequencing-based virus detection and characterization; in-depth knowledge of data mining and analysis using R, e.g. for microarray / RNA-Seq data and viral population analysis.

SVA - Swedish National Veterinary Institute is a governmental agency working for good animal and human health. Research and development is one the main processes at SVA. As a researcher at division of bioinformatics and molecular biology, **Lihong Liu (M)** holds PhD in Virology (2009, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences) and has extensive experiences on virology, molecular biology, diagnostic assay development, phylogenomics and evolution, viral metagenomics and bioinformatics application. He has been involved in several research EU projects such as CSFV_goDIVA and RAPIDIA-FIELD, and network projects EPIZONE, and LinkTADs. He has published 47 peer-reviewed articles since 2006. He has worked on determination and characterization of the first complete genome of swine hepatitis E virus in Europe. He has experiences on metagenomics and RNA-Seq data analysis via Uppsala Multidisciplinary Center for Advanced Computational Science. **Mikhail Hakhverdyan (M)** has a PhD in Zoology (Moscow). He is a senior scientist at SVA, and his research has focused on new and emerging technologies, such as high-throughput sequencing. Since 2012 he has worked within unknown pathogen discovery research field using an in-house Illumina MiSeq platform. He has participated in two EU-projects, MULTIPLEX PCR (2000-2004) and LAB-ON-SITE (2005-2008), through which he has gained extensive experiences in project management and reporting.

Wageningen Bioveterinary Research. Prof. Wim H.M. van der Poel, DVM, PhD (M): Senior scientist at WBVR and special Professor of 'Emerging and Zoonotic viruses' at Wageningen University. He is a principal investigator within the Netherlands Centre of One-Health (NCOH) and coordinator of the EPIZONE European Research Group, the network on epizootic animal diseases research. The research work of Prof. Van der Poel involves at least three main areas: New and emerging viruses, Foodborne and Zoonotic viruses, including Hepatitis E virus, and 'Global One-Health'. In the first three areas his research has primarily been focusing on the detection and characterization of viruses in the different hosting animals, as well as in food and environmental matrices. Controlling the risks of infectious diseases and chronic diseases are crucial to food security, public health, climate change and biodiversity. A Global One-Health research approach is needed to achieve that. **Marcel Hulst (M)** is a scientist in molecular biology and functional genomics at Wageningen Bioveterinary Research of

Wageningen university (WUR). He has a Ph.D in molecular virology and has 20 years of experience as leader of projects in which “omics” technology and NGS are applied in the research fields of viral and bacterial infectious diseases of farm animals, gut health, and feed/food safety and quality. He is an expert in translating experimental gained functional genomics data into biological processes using bioinformatics approaches. **Alex Bossers**, PhD, MSc (M): Research scientist, project- and group leader. As a lead scientist he focuses on multi-omics and bioinformatics applications in the fields of molecular epidemiology, infectious agent characterization, diagnostics- and vaccine development. Current focus is mostly on microbiome/virome/resistome characterizations using deep-sequencing applications and bioinformatics. One day a week he is an assistant professor at the Institute of Risk Assessment Sciences (University of Utrecht, NL) with specific focus on using metagenomics and microbiome applications for surveillance in the OneHealth domain.

Erasmus Medical Centre Rotterdam (Third Party via WUR). Marion Koopmans (F) is directing one of the four research pillars in the NCOH, the Emerging infectious disease theme. She heads the Viroscience department at Erasmus Medical Center, which is National and EU reference laboratory for emerging viral diseases and WHO collaborating center. She is deputy coordinator of the COMPARE project which aims to develop open access infrastructure and analytical tools to facilitate implementation of NGS in clinical and public health laboratories. Her research interests are in understanding virus ecology, epidemiology and evolution, with an emphasis on the use of genomic epidemiology to identify sources of infection and track pathways of transmission. **Miranda de Graaf (F)** is an assistant professor at the Erasmus Medical Center Virosciences Department. Her research focuses on clarifying the role of viral and host factors in the emergence and evolution of norovirus, combining phylogeny, molecular biology, glycobiology and virology. In collaboration with the RIVM she is responsible for the coordination of global Noronet. She authored more than 50 papers in international peer-reviewed journals and was awarded a Marie-Curie Fellowship (IEF) to work on the role of receptors in the evolution of influenza viruses at Cambridge university (UK). **Bas Oude Munnink (M)** is a postdoctoral researcher that received a PhD from the University of Amsterdam in 2016. In recent years he has been part of a study aiming to implement a Dutch zoonosis surveillance system to enable the early detection of the emergence of mosquito-borne and tick-borne viruses in ecological hotspots. He has a wide experience in wet-lab work, performing metagenomic sequencing on different platforms and consequent data analysis. In addition, he has been involved in different consortia and also works on the European funded project RECOVER, SHARP and VEO and the Dutch OH-PACT and a specific SARS-CoV-2 sequencing grant from ZonMW. **Sander van Boheemen (M)** is a scientist working at the clinical diagnostics unit of the department of Viroscience at the Erasmus Medical Center. He received his PhD from the Erasmus Medical Center working on virus discovery and virus characterization using novel sequencing applications leading to the discovery of MERS-CoV and identification of key mutations that render the H5N1 virus transmissible via aerosol droplets in ferrets. His research focus is aimed at implementation of novel sequencing techniques in the diagnostics unit and developing innovative assays within the diagnostics.

ANSES- French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, Viral genetic and biosafety unit has a more than 20 years’ experience in the Sanger sequencing of viral genomes and has developed, within the last 5 years, expertise in whole genome sequencing (WGS). Dr **Yannick Blanchard (M)** is a senior scientist (Ph.D 1992), head of unit Viral Genetic and Biosafety and in charge of the national ANSES platform for WGS and transcriptomic analyses. The platform has on site a NGS sequencer (Proton – Life technologies), the computing capacity (Dell server) and bioinformatics skills for the treatment of the WGS data. Furthermore the platform is member of a scientific community (Biogenouest) which provides access to additional sequencing (Hiseq, Miseq) and computing equipment’s. The team has been involved in several European projects and network within the last years (NADIR, EPIZONE, COMPARE, Novimark, MRSA-Bacteriophages, CAMPYBRO)

ANSES - Enteric virus and species barrier unit. Nicole Pavo (F) (PhD, HDR). Senior scientist at ANSES since 2005. Head of the team Enteric Viruses and Species Barrier crossing of the Virology unit at the

ANSES Animal Health Laboratory. Main research interests: detection and characterization of Hepatitis E virus in animal reservoirs and food products to evaluate transmission risk to human. Other activities: scientific support to the Ministry of Agriculture in France and member of the ANSES BIORISK panel. In 2016, appointed as an EFSA expert for the working group on HEV. Experience in the management of international projects: from 2011 to 2016 appointed as the HEV Pathogen Leader in the PREDEMICS consortium supported by the European Commission (FP7); deputy Leader of the WP31 of the MedVetNet European project (2005-2009). Co-author of more than 50 peer-reviewed papers. H-index = 20. **ANSES – Laboratory for food safety. Sandra Martin-Latil (F)**, PhD in virology is a scientific project leader at ANSES since 2009. Her current research interests are varied and focus on food virology: improvement of the existing methods for detecting viruses in complex food matrices, development of methods for measuring infectivity of enteric viruses in food (using cellular systems and/or combined molecular approaches) and understanding of the mechanisms used by enteric viruses for crossing the intestinal epithelial barrier. She has supervised several students and authored or co-authored 25 several peer-reviewed publications. She is also a member of the CEN TC275/WG6/TAG4 ‘Viruses in foods’ working group responsible for writing the draft technical specification “Microbiology of food and animal stuffs - Horizontal method for detection of hepatitis A virus and norovirus in food using real-time RT-PCR”. In 2016, she participated to the FSA/EFSA workshop on foodborne viruses.

ANSES – Mycoplasma Bacteriology Unit. Isabelle Kempf (F) is a microbiologist, specialist of antimicrobial resistance of bacteria of animal origin, including surveillance and detection methods, impact of practices and alternatives to antimicrobials. She is a Research Scientist at ANSES since 1983. She is Head of the Mycoplasma Bacteriology Unit of ANSES – Laboratory of Ploufragan, France. Her scientific production reaches 83 publications in international journals and six book chapters (h-index of 19 in Scopus, <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8912-3044>). She coordinated a national project funded by the French National Research Agency and four projects funded by the Ministry of Agriculture.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

One Health EJP-JRP8-METASTAVA investigated how to bring diagnostic use of metagenomic high throughput sequencing methods (mNGS) for unbiased pathogen detection closer to public vet/med/food labs. Work focused on providing guidelines for informed mNGS experimental design, standardised methods for generating and analysing data (WP1); providing quality control metrics, tools and interlaboratory assessment (WP2); and assessing the analytical properties of mNGS for pathogen/sample matrix combinations relevant to the One Health EJP (WP3). In addition, cross-cutting work packages ensured integration with other ongoing research efforts and dissemination (WP4) as well as project management (WP5).

WP1 standardised the methods for mNGS data generation (D-JRP8-1.1) and data analysis (D-JRP8-1.2) in METASTAVA. An investigation of publicly available NGS raw data indicated that mNGS public datasets on pathogen/sample matrix combinations relevant to METASTAVA lacked sufficient sample and methodological metadata (D-JRP8-1.3), necessitating a focus on the datasets produced within the project. A general guidance document for informed implementation of mNGS methodologies in a diagnostic context was published (D-JRP8-1.6), pointing scientists to the wealth of published information and past and ongoing research efforts on mNGS, as well as documenting possible validation and quality monitoring measures for metagenomics methods.

WP2 thoroughly evaluated a commercial standardised spike-in external control for mNGS of viruses (D-JRP8-2.2), offering QC metrics during the workflow (on extracted RNA) and during data analysis (using normalised control read numbers). In addition, the detection of RNA viruses in technical replicates of swine faeces was shown to be reproducible and insensitive to the effect of different reagent batches (D-JRP8-2.3). A METASTAVA proficiency test (D-JRP8-2.5) evaluated the interlaboratory reproducibility and tested the robustness of the methods for data generation and analysis selected in WP1. Aliquots of swine faecal samples naturally infected with several porcine

astrovirus species were dispatched to all participants, which handled the data generation using METASTAVA methodological modules described in D-JRP8-1.1, while a standardised data analysis methodology was used by all (D-JRP8-3.2). The results indicated excellent reproducibility in terms of astrovirus species detection, while considerable variation was detected in the reported normalised read counts, due to varying methods for data generation. METASTAVA protocols, expertise and resources were used in parallel research and diagnostic efforts by the different partners (T2.4). This research included the characterisation of the virome in farms with consistent neonatal piglet diarrhea, the characterisation of Sars-CoV-2 during the ongoing pandemic; the validation of METASTAVA protocols for the characterisation of animal coronaviruses, and the investigation of animal samples giving false positive results in Ag LFD (antigen detection lateral flow devices) quick tests for SARS-CoV-2.

WP3 investigated the analytical properties of mNGS for model pathogens based on suitable sample collections (D-JRP8-3.1) and using a standardised procedure for data analysis (D-JRP8-3.2). Based upon the characteristics of the different model pathogens, the required taxonomic resolution, and the complexity of the relevant sample matrices investigated, differences were found for the detection using completely random and enrichment free mNGS workflows for hepatitis E virus (in human and animal samples & food, D-JRP8-3.3), Norovirus (in human samples and food, D-JRP8-3.4), animal zoonotic pox viruses (in animal samples, D-JRP8-3.5), Shiga toxin expressing E. coli (food samples D-JRP8-3.6), and antibiotic resistance genes (in animal samples D-JRP8-3.7). This suggests that the most important power of random mNGS (its access to nucleic acids from all pathogens in a sample) is also its Achilles' heel, indicating that for some diagnostic applications enrichment methods or targeted sequencing approaches are needed.

3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Collect reference data from other metagenomic projects, select the metagenomic methods to be used for the project, and provide guidance data for informed metagenomic workflow design (M1-M30)

JRP8-WP1-T1: broad survey to collect information about sample selection and data generation methods for metagenomics (M1-M12)

We successfully organized several meetings about data generation methods, including one live meeting (during the project kickoff meeting) and three teleconferences. A detailed survey was finalized in m6 and listed all methodologies used by the partners (integration ensured by partners also participating in COMPARE and EFFORT, as well as the integration activities with these projects undertaken in WP4). A conclusion report listed the methods that would be used as standardized methods for the METASTAVA project and was discussed in a follow-up teleconference. A modular approach was selected, offering alternative technical solutions for sample disruption or homogenization, nucleic acid extraction, cDNA synthesis and double stranding, library preparation, and sequencing. Partner FLI generated extensive comparative validation data for the cDNA synthesis modules (IonS5 NGS sequencing of 15 samples with both alternative modules). The objective is to maximize the use of the selected methodology modules. Where their use is not possible, parallel validation of in-house methods to the selected modules should be provided.

D-JRP8-1.1 includes a report on the questionnaire + a conclusion with selected methods for generating short read metagenomic NGS data from clinical methods.

JRP8-WP1-T2: broad survey to collect information about data analysis methods for metagenomics (M1-M12)

Data analysis methodology was initially discussed in a session during the kickoff meeting. A detailed questionnaire (finalized 15.06.2018) collected information about IT capacity, tools, and databases used

by the partners and was discussed in a follow-up teleconference. It was decided to select one fast mapping approach (Kraken) and one more inclusive iterative assembly/mapping approach (Riems) as standardized tools. Due to time constraints and availability problems for all partners, commercial solutions were not evaluated (CLC genomics was the most prevalent commercial solution).

D-JRP8-1.2 includes a report on the questionnaire + a conclusion with selected methods for the metagenomic analysis of short read NGS data.

JRP8-WP1-T3: identifying available sequence datasets (M1-M36)

An initial survey of publicly available short read NGS data (NCBI short read archive; SRA) indicated that although raw randomly generated data for relevant animal and human sample types is publicly available they lacked sufficient sample and methodological metadata to reconstruct the exact biological context of the sample and the way the data was generated. Moreover, the combination of model pathogens/sample matrices studied in METASTAVA was rare (cf. D-JRP8-1.3). as a result, we focused on listing shared datasets that were generated by METASTAVA, and for which we have high quality metadata. At the date of this report, these include the data related to D-JRP8-2.2 (publicly available in the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under BioProject accession number PRJNA615303). Reproducibility data from the METASTAVA proficiency test will be included with a manuscript that is currently being written, as will selected datasets from WP3 and WP2. Currently, this already includes all raw datasets related to task 2.2 regarding the use of endogenous internal process controls (NCBI SRA BioProject accession number PRJNA615303).

JRP8-WP1-T4: Propose a standardised framework for the description of the application scope and analytical properties of a metagenomics assay (M18-M36)

Scheduled for the last 6 months of the project (prolongation), and is heavily linked to task 2.1. METASTAVA jointly decided to deliver a guidance document (D-JRP8-1.6) for labs considering diagnostic use of metagenomic workflows (joining the original intention of deliverables 1.4, 1.5, and 2.1) referring to the richness of recently published studies, norms, and guidelines since the start of the project. The resulting opinion document by METASTAVA avoids being “yet another diagnostic metagenomics review” and guides readers interested in diagnostic implementation of metagenomic NGS methods to:

- High quality review papers on the topic
- Relevant norms and validation guidelines for metagenomic NGS, as well as for targeted diagnostic use of NGS methods
- Past and ongoing collaborative research projects on diagnostic metagenomics
- Suggestions on quality control measures and metrics to include in mNGS workflows.

The goal of this guidance document, entitled “Key considerations for the implementation of high throughput sequencing based metagenomics (mNGS) in diagnostic clinical, food and veterinary labs : a no-nonsense pointer” (D-JRP8-1.6) is to promote informed decisions on metagenomic workflow choices, as well as careful interpretation and follow up research on metagenomic results. The document will not be published as a classical review article, but rather as an interactive document with clickable links to the information sources. It is Intended to draw diagnostic scientists into critical reflections on how they should set up and interpret mNGS methods. It will be published on the One Health EJP website and further dissemination will be investigated with the One Health EJP communications team.

WP2. Quality assurance tools for the validation and interpretation of metagenomics (M1-M30)

JRP8-WP2-T1: The development of quality metrics to evaluate the significance of the outcome of a metagenomics experiment (M10-M36)

As stated above, and in the context of increasing availability of high quality research and publications on the topic, METASTAVA decided to join the objective of this tasks with heavily linked task 1.4. An extensive overview of quality metrics to monitor mNGS workflows and to ensure proper interpretation of mNGS results is included in our guidance document entitled “*Key considerations for the implementation of high throughput sequencing based metagenomics (mNGS) in diagnostic clinical, food and veterinary labs : a no-nonsense pointer*” (D-JRP8-1.6).

JRP8-WP2-T2: development and evaluation of external controls for metagenomics (M1-M18)

Deliverable report D-JRP8-2.2 uploaded on 15.06.2020 and publication accepted in J.Vir.Meth. PMID: 32574649 DOI: 10.1016/j.jviromet.2020.113916.

Metagenomic next generation sequencing (mNGS) is increasingly recognized as an important complementary tool to targeted human and animal infectious disease diagnostics. It is, however, sensitive to biases and errors that are currently not systematically evaluated by the implementation of quality controls (QC) for the diagnostic use of mNGS. We evaluated a commercial reagent (Mengovirus extraction control kit, CeraamTools, bioMérieux) as an exogenous internal control for mNGS (after reviewing the literature on available exogenous controls for viral metagenomics). It validates the integrity of reagents and workflow, the efficient isolation of viral nucleic acids and the absence of inhibitors in individual samples (verified using a specific qRT-PCR). Moreover, it validates the efficient generation of viral sequence data in individual samples (verified by normalized mengoviral read counts in the metagenomic analysis). We show that when using a completely random metagenomics workflow: (1) Mengovirus RNA can be reproducibly detected in different animal sample types (swine feces and sera, wild bird cloacal swabs), except for tissue samples (swine lung); (2) the Mengovirus control kit does not contain other contaminating viruses that may affect metagenomic experiments (using a cutoff of minimum 1 Kraken classified read per million (RPM)); (3) the addition of 2.17×10^6 Mengovirus copies/ml of sample does not affect the virome composition of pig fecal samples or wild bird cloacal swab samples; (4) Mengovirus Cq values (using as cutoff the upper limit of the 99% confidence interval of Cq values for a given sample matrix) allow the identification of samples with poor viral RNA extraction or high inhibitor load; (5) Mengovirus normalized read counts (cutoff RPM>1) allow the identification of samples where the viral sequences are outcompeted by host or bacterial target sequences in the random metagenomic workflow. The implementation of two QC testing points, a first one after RNA extraction (Mengoviral qRT-PCR) and a second one after metagenomic data analysis provide valuable information for the validation of individual samples and results. Their implementation in addition to external controls validating runs or experiments should be carefully considered for a given sample type and workflow.

JRP8-WP2-T3: reproducibility and batch effect evaluation (M1-M12)

The repeatability between technical replicates (including the effect of different production batches of critical reagents) was investigated for the metagenomic detection of RNA viruses in swine fecal material (D-JRP8-2.3). Reproducibility needs to be considered when performing metagenomic diagnostics and research studies. Indeed batch effects may mask true biological differences between groups, e.g., healthy vs diseased individuals, due to variations in reagents/kits lot, personnel, or laboratory procedures. Of particular importance for metagenomics with its wide scope, kit contamination may result in false discovery of causative agents. Two technical replicates were mNGS-sequenced from 12 swine fecal samples, showing reproducible detection (but variation in terms of the normalised number of reads reported) of RNA viruses. A follow up investigation looked at technical replicates of porcine astrovirus infected swine feces serially diluted in fecal suspension collected from

a specific pathogen free (SPF) pig. This demonstrated reproducible detection, although the limit of detection was as expected higher than for astrovirus specific realtime RT-PCR. Near the mNGS detection limit, repeatability issues were evident between technical replicates, showing the value of including either technical or biological replicates in mNGS studies where low viral titres are expected in the tested samples. A final investigation looked at technical replicates of swine fecal samples using different library prep and sequencing kit reagents showed very reproducible virus detection for astroviral species. At the virus detection level, only questionable read numbers (1-4) reads for a species were not reproduced in the technical replicate using the other sequencing reagents batches. As our guidelines (D-JRP8-1.6 and specific cutoff of RPM>1 in D.JRP8-2.2) indicate, such low read numbers should always be critically investigated, certainly in a diagnostic context.

JRP8-WP2-T4: evaluation of QC metrics on additional parallel datasets (M13-M24)

The methodologies and expertise developed in METASTAVA was used by several partners in parallel diagnostic and research efforts. The methodologies and expertise has been proven particularly relevant in response to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

- Exogenous IC (cf. D-JRP8-2.2) and METASTAVA sequencing and analysis methods (D-JRP8-1.1 and D-JRP8-1.2) were used for the study of the virome in swine farms with persisting neonatal piglet diarrhea (Van Borm et al. published in *Virus Genes*).
- In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, partner Sciensano set out to validate the METASTAVA metagenomic protocols on clinical samples and isolates of animal coronaviruses (avian infectious bronchitis virus, genus *Gammacoronavirus*), where we proved the modules for RNA virome analysis set out in D-JRP8-1.1 (Trizol/Rneasy – SSIV/NEBNext – NexteraXT – Kraken) allowed the determination of complete *Gammacoronavirus* (Infectious Bronchitis virus) genomes from chicken clinical samples (tissue pools and swabs), while at the same time allowing robust characterisation of co-infecting chicken Astrovirus, Sicinivirus, and avian leucosis virus (Alpharetrovirus).
- METASTAVA methodologies and expertise was helpful for the characterisation of swine astroviruses from swine fecal samples (partner WUR).
- Similar coronavirus protocol validation was done on porcine epidemic diarrhea virus (PEDV, *Alphacoronavirus*) and avian coronaviruses from Guineafowl (by partner Anses).
- METASTAVA expertise was used in response to the COVID-19 pandemic for sequencing of human (partner ErasmusMC) and animal (partner WUR) SARS-CoV2
- More indirectly, several METASTAVA experts were recruited into crisis response projects including the development and use of targeted molecular diagnostic assays, as well as targeted whole genome sequencing methodologies. This highlights the relevance of the developed expertise for emerging threats, but resulted in operational delays for the research tasks planned in METASTAVA.

JRP8-WP2-T5: Metagenomic proficiency test (M13-36)

Within METASTAVA, modules suitable to build standardized metagenomics next-generation sequencing (mNGS) workflows were selected and tested. These modules represent the main steps of the mNGS workflow, namely sample disintegration, RNA extraction, double strand cDNA synthesis and library preparation. For each of the modules, two methods were chosen as outlined previously in report D-JRP8-1.1. Likewise, common procedures for analysis of sequencing data were chosen (D-JRP8-1.2 and D-JRP8-3.1 v1.3). To finally evaluate the selected modules in terms of (i) suitability to detect viruses in native samples and (ii) simultaneously assess their reproducibility, a proficiency test (PT) was carried out as part of METASTAVA. For this PT, a pre-analysed swine faeces sample containing a porcine astrovirus and RNA extracted from that sample were distributed among the participants. Most importantly, using the abovementioned methods comprised in the METASTAVA modular mNGS workflow, all participants identified the same viral species belonging to the family *Astroviridae* in both the clinical sample and in the distributed RNA. In detail, all participants classified the majority of viral

reads to two species of porcine astroviruses (PAstV2 and PAstV4), regardless of the used analysis method (Kraken and Bowtie2). Moreover, participants performed well in terms of repeatability when the faecal sample was tested in duplicate, resulting in a low coefficient of variation. Therefore, this PT showed that the methods selected as METASTAVA mNGS modules are (i) well suited for virus identification even from challenging matrices like faeces and (ii) the selected methods can reproducibly be applied.

Detailed results of this proficiency test can be consulted in deliverable report D-JRP8-2.5, while a manuscript is currently being written to publish the results.

WP3. evaluation of the analytical properties of metagenomics workflows (M1-M30)

An inventory of relevant samples available in sample repositories for the different model pathogens was made with the involvement of all participants in the task teams. The emphasis was put on naturally infected samples with different pathogen loads. Where this was not available, samples were spike with a model pathogen. The inventory of samples to be sequenced for each task was finalised during the first year of the project (D-JRP8-3.1).

JRP8-WP3-T1: analytical sensitivity, HEV (M1-M36)

Here the potential of the METASTAVA workflow to detect HEV in samples from various origins was investigated and positively demonstrated for some matrices (serum, cell culture and meat pork) but not for highly complex matrices like pig feces. We were able to detect HEV in samples until about 100,000 IU/ml (Cq of 26 with our protocol). Bioinformatics analyses showed that Bowtie2 is more sensitive than Kraken for analysis. Nevertheless, a proper reference genome is essential to detect the target otherwise false negatives may arise. For instance, this can be seen in the Kraken analysis when the RefSeq sequence used in the Kraken database poorly represents HEV diversity, resulting in a poor sensitivity. Another issue are low complexity regions, which induced false positive detections of HEV. This lack of specificity was partially improved by masking poly-A/T/N tails longer than 15 nucleotides in the reference genomes and by trimming reads with Prinseq. Despite these adaptations, false positive reads were still detected in the negative control samples and it is essential to tackle these in the future. In particular, more detailed experiments, requiring more starting material, are essential to delineate a reliable cut-off for the presence or the absence of HEV in a sample.

For the very complex matrices that are pig feces, the metagenomics approaches in this study has failed to identify the HEV for real life samples corresponding to loads of 10E6 genome per ml. The reduction of the sample complexity by molecular technics, for example DNase SISPA, as demonstrated by WBVR, can be an alternative procedure but the successful detection of HEV in human positive serum suggests blood samples are probably a best alternative for HEV detection in swine if a viremia is induced. However, METASTAVA protocols have shown reproducible detection of astroviruses (D.JRP8-2.5: METASTAVA proficiency test) as well as diverse other swine intestinal viruses (Van Borm et al 2020b) from swine feces, and Norovirus (D-JRP8-3.2) in human feces. Assay sensitivity should always be verified for a specific model pathogen/sample matrix combination and that the specific conditions of each disease should be considered (e.g. asymptomatic carrier such as HEV in swine vs. symptomatic animal such as diarrhetic pigs with astrovirus infection).

Importantly, high amounts of HPgV (human pegivirus) reads were detected in a HEV-negative patient serum sample, showing that our approach also allows for the identification of pathogens we did not hypothesize for.

D-JRP8-3.3 reports the detailed methodologies and results of the HEV investigations in METASTAVA

JRP8-WP3-T2: analytical sensitivity, norovirus (M1-M36)

This study has shown the potential of metagenomics to detect norovirus in fecal suspensions and in food matrices such as strawberries, but also raised some issues needing further improvements.

The direct RNA extraction (NucliSens® easyMAG™ platform, Biomérieux) for virus extraction from human stool suspensions, and the ISO 15216 method for virus extraction from food are the most suitable for viral metagenomics sequencing purposes.

The limit of detection obtained by metagenomics approach was estimated in this study for fecal suspensions to 1.4E+05-1.8E+05 cg of NoV/g of stool. This concentration is rather low compared with median viral loads detected in the stools of NoV-infected patients (8.4E+05 and 3.0E+08 for NoV GI and NoV GII respectively) (2).

On the other hand, the limit of detection obtained by metagenomics approach was estimated in this study for food (NoV-spiked strawberries) samples to 5.6E+03-7.3E+03 cg of NoV/g of food sample, which is a high contamination level compared to naturally contaminated food samples. Our laboratory established that 71% of NoV-positive food samples suspected in foodborne outbreaks had NoV genomic levels $\leq 1E+03$ cg/g of sample (3).

The METASTAVA project assessed generic metagenomics workflow modules for viral and bacterial nucleic acids preparation and sequencing, harmonized for all sample types. Although this assessment deviated from the METASTAVA selected nucleic acid extraction methods due to laboratory organizational restrictions, it has shown that direct nucleic acid extraction allows metagenomic detection of NoV in patient samples with a relevant analytical sensitivity to contamination levels seen in the diagnostic lab. However, these direct nucleic acid extraction methods do not seem the most suitable for the detection of RNA viruses in food samples. Even using the ISO 15216 nucleic acid extraction method for food samples, the analytical sensitivity of metagenomics methods was poor in relation to diagnostically (qRT-PCR) observed contamination levels. These findings stress the importance of a careful workflow design and validation fit-for-purpose, i.e. fit for a combination of pathogen and sample matrix in a diagnostic context.

D-JRP8-3.4 documents the detailed methodologies and results of the Norovirus investigations in METASTAVA.

JRP8-WP3-T3: analytical sensitivity, large DNA viruses (M1-M36)

Several DNA viruses of the family *Poxviridae* pose a zoonotic risk. These include members of the genus *Parapoxvirus* that can result in skin lesions (Orf or ecthyma contagiosum) in humans handling the small ruminant animal reservoir (goat and sheep). Cow pox (genus *Orthopoxvirus*) represent another zoonotic occupational risk. This task investigated the diagnostic value of metagenomic methods for the detection and characterisation of Orf virus in small ruminant clinical samples (work at partner Sciansano) as well as other pox viruses in naturally infected samples (work at partner FLI).

This report presents the data on *Parapoxvirus* and needs to be updated as additional data need to be added.

Although randomly generated metagenomic datasets generated from *Parapoxvirus* skin lesion samples are dominated by host (small ruminant) DNA sequences, this study suggests sufficient *Parapoxvirus* specific sequence information is generated both quantitatively and qualitatively. High normalized *Parapoxvirus* read numbers do not only allow for confident identification, but yield high genome coverage both in clinical samples and in clinical samples diluted in negative tissue homogenate (until 1/100). Complete open reading frame coverage for most commonly used *Parapoxvirus* phylogenetic markers (B2L, E3L, I3L, F1L, A4L) directly from clinical samples. Where a loglinear relationship was observed between *Parapoxvirus* realtime PCR Cp values and normalized readcounts in samples diluted in negative tissue homogenate, this was not the case for the panel of clinical samples tested (most likely due to the diverse preservation and sampling history with samples from 2003, 2011, and 2018). Altogether these data suggest that randomly generated mNGS data from poxviral skin lesion samples (1) allows a confident identification of poxviruses with an analytical sensitivity covering the observed range of virus concentrations in tissue samples and (2) yields high resolution genetic

information including near-complete genome sequences and good coverage of all frequently used phylogenetic markers.

D-JRP8-3.5 documents the detailed methodologies and results of the Poxviridae investigations in METASTAVA.

JRP8-WP3-T4: analytical sensitivity, STEC (M1-M24)

During foodborne outbreak investigations, the required response time can be long due to the time needed for isolation/cultivation of the responsible pathogen(s). Moreover, often the isolation of these pathogens from food is not possible. Metagenomics could significantly reduce the detection time. The goal of this task is to evaluate the generic harmonized METASTAVA workflow to generate and analyse metagenomics data for the foodborne bacterial pathogen Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (VTEC/STEC), and to compare the analytical sensitivity and specificity with standard diagnostic methods (i.e. qPCR).

Minced beef meat purchased at a local store and free of prior STEC contamination was artificially spiked at different concentrations (10 colony forming units (CFU) (representative of a naturally occurring contamination load), 10^8 CFU and 10^{10} CFU) of a culture of STEC in 25g of matrix previously stomached with 225ml buffered peptone water. mNGS data (on average $2.6 \cdot 10^6$ reads per sample) was generated and analysed using METASTAVA protocols (WP1). *E. coli* reads were identified in all samples, even in the blank meat that contains only the DNA extracted from the matrix. However, only in the sample spiked with 10^{10} CFU could reads be assigned to a lower taxonomic level *E. coli* O157:H7. Finally VirulenceFinder and SerotypeFinder could only identify NGS reads mapping to virulence genes in the sample with the highest spiking level.

Although completely random mNGS on complex food matrices generates data allowing species-level detection of *E. coli*, the required taxonomical resolution in this particular diagnostic context necessitates higher sensitivity. Indeed, natural STEC contamination levels in food samples are in the range of 10 CFU, while only extremely high contamination levels allowed the needed taxonomic resolution and detection of virulence genes using the completely random METASTAVA protocols on complex food matrices. As a consequence, targeted approaches (or extremely high sequencing effort per sample) are needed to allow the necessary strain typing (culture enrichment or targeted NGS approaches). These targeted approaches are outside of the scope of METASTAVA, which critically investigated the potential diagnostic value of truly random mNGS approaches.

D-JRP8-3.6 documents the detailed methodologies and results of the STEC investigations in METASTAVA.

JRP8-WP3-T5: analytical sensitivity, detection of ABR genes (M1-M36)

Detection of antimicrobial –resistant bacteria from animals can be performed by culture. Then the resistant bacteria can be studied by phenotypic or genomic methods. However, the diversity of the bacterial species and resistance genes possibly present in a sample makes such an approach a challenge. For this reason, global approaches, such as metagenomics, seem a relevant option. The aim of this task of the METASTAVA project was to evaluate the robustness and sensitivity of the metagenomics for antimicrobial resistance and to compare the analytical sensitivity and specificity with bacteriological methods including isolation on supplemented media. For this purpose, fecal samples containing bacteria with resistances of public health importance were used.

In a first step, the workflows for generating mNGS data and bioinformatic steps to identify ABR genes were validated on isolates of ABR bacteria, resulting in the confirmation of all phenotypically determined ABR markers. Secondly, spiking of pig fecal samples with *E. coli*, *Campylobacter coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* strains with characterized ABR spectra at concentrations ranging from 10^2 to 10^7 colony-forming units per 1g of feces indicated the presence of a diverse spectrum of ABR genes that were not specific to the spike strains, while only at the highest concentration (10^7 colony-forming

units per 1g of feces) spike strain specific ABR genes were detected. Of note, high sequencing efforts were done per sample (>130 million reads per sample). Lastly, mNGS on fecal samples from swine in vivo inoculated with ABR *E. coli* strains yielded similar results with the documentation of a huge diversity of circulating ABR genes, but poor sensitivity for the detection of ABR genes specific to the inoculum strain.

The highly diverse microbial community in swine fecal samples, with a diversity of circulating AMR genes in the swine population, represent a difficult “needle in the haystack” situation for direct detection of AMR genes using random mNGS sequencing from fecal samples, where the sensitivity seems to be limited to 10^7 colony-forming units per 1g of feces (spiking experiment) and where inoculum specific ABR markers are not detected in experimentally infected pigs. As a result, studies envisaging specifically the detection of ABR genes (unlike METASTAVA that studies hypothesis free detection of all pathogens in a sample) may require specific sample enrichment, pretreatment, or sequencing approaches.

D-JRP8-3.7 documents the detailed methodology and results of the ABR gene detection investigations in METASTAVA.

JRP8-WP3-T6: bioinformatics and statistical analysis of analytical performance experiments (M1-M24)

After concertation between the different partners involved in WP3, a standardised workflow for the data analysis was decided (M-FBZ2.METASTAVA.4) and an SOP was written (current version D-JRP8-3.2 v1.3 after consecutive minor updates). In addition, a standardised database for metagenomic classification was build and shared between partners to avoid bias introduced by different databases used.

Overview of the analytical procedure

The Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) data of a sample generated by means of the Illumina platform is analysed by following the sequential steps listed below, with the tools used in parentheses:

- Raw reads quality check (FastQC)
- Reads poly A/T tail trimming (Prinseq)
- Reads quality trimming (Trimmomatic)
- Trimmed reads quality check (FastQC)
- Reads taxonomy profiling (Kraken)
- Taxonomy profile report generation (Kraken)
- Optional: Taxonomy profile visualization (Krona)
- Read mapping against target species (Bowtie2)
- Target species reads counting (Samtools)

The detailed information about each step is described in deliverable report/SOP (D-JRP8-3.2)

WP4: Concertation with ongoing efforts and dissemination (M1-M36)

JRP8-WP4-T1: concertation with ongoing initiatives (M1-M24)

The concertation with other initiatives investigating the use of NGS for the detection or characterization of microorganisms (viruses and bacteria) was ensured in two ways. First, several METASTAVA partners were actively involved in the research consortia COMPARE, EFFORT against AMR, Global microbial identifier, relevant ISO workgroups etc. (details listed in D-JRP8-4.1). The continuation of the developed expertise was ensured by participation of METASTAVA partners in One Health EJP second call projects including One Health EJP-JRP16-TeleVIR and One Health EJP-JRP12-Farmed. Secondly, public deliverables of other initiatives were taken into account and METASTAVA participated

in interactive workshops with other initiatives. . Steven Van Borm participated in three cogwheel workshops organized by the OH-EJP, one with COMPARE (12.04.2018), and one with EFFORT (26.10.2018), and one with IRIDA and INNUENDO. Participation in a cogwheel workshop with VEO (versatile Emerging Infectious Disease Observatory) is planned (25.20.2021). Closest fit was observed with COMPARE. However, the exchange possibilities (e.g. protocols) were limited by reporting restrictions of COMPARE (e.g. COMPARE deliverables had to be validated by EC before becoming public). Public deliverables of COMPARE were taken into account when published (<https://www.compare-europe.eu/library>) and where still possible integrated in the METASTAVA conclusions. However, given the short time frame available to METASTAVA, we could not reconsider e.g. the decisions we made regarding methodologies (WP1). It should be stressed that several METASTAVA partners also participate in COMPARE, resulting in an indirect integration of e.g. methodologies and participation of several METASTAVA partners in the COMPARE proficiency tests. Of particular interest was the participation of Steven Van Borm in the Second conference on NGS for adventitious agent detection in biologics for human and animal use (IABS – International Association of Biological Standardisation), generating new insights from the pharmaceutical and quality assurance of biological products fields and giving access to the latest insights of IABS' Advanced Virus Detection Technologies Interest Group (AVDTIG). An integral report of the later meeting, including a summary of our presentation on METASTAVA was published (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32660862/>).

JRP8-WP4-T2: formal dissemination (M1-M36)

METASTAVA produced both procedures, SOP's, and guidelines, as well as formal scientific publications. The later are listed in the dedicated section of the present report. The SOP's and guidelines are listed in D-JRP8-4.2, and include methods for the generation of metagenomic data, for their analysis, for the use of external controls, and guidelines for informed design and interpretation of metagenomic experiments and suggested metrics for their quality assurance.

JRP8-WP4-T3: dissemination of recommendations to stakeholders (M1-M24)

METASTAVA output was disseminated to the following stakeholders at scientific meetings:

Presence and presentations at the One Health EJP kickoff meeting (30-31/01/2018), annual scientific meetings (2019, 2020), and programme owners committee meeting (19/06/2019) and programme management committee (9/05/2019).

Presentation at [Workshop: ESCV Next Generations Sequencing in Clinical Virology \(European Society for Clinical Virology\)](#). 20-21 nov 2018

Presentation at the International Association for Biological Standardization(IABS)) conference on next generation sequencing for adventitious virus detection in biologics for humans and animals, Ghent, 13-14 Nov. 2019

Presentation at the Belgian branch of the World Veterinary Poultry Association (WVPA). Ghent , 27/02/2020.

Presentation at the SVA science day (12 november 2019)

2x (2019, 2020) One Health EJP@Sciensano day with invited Belgian stakeholders (food safety agency, ministry of health, etc...)

Presentation at Joint 11th International Congress for Veterinary Virology and 12th Annual meeting EPIZONE. (27-30 aug 2019)

JRP8-WP4-T4: Organization of a scientific meeting (M20-M24)

We focused on maximum participation in the One Health EJP Annual Scientific meetings to take advantage of a wider forum. D-JRP8-4.3 reviews the scientific discussion during our annual scientific meetings and the presentations at the One Health EJP ASM's. A separate scientific dissemination

meeting was originally planned for the last 6 months of the project. However, the ongoing COVID-19 meeting made the organisation of a physical meeting impossible, while several key scientists were recruited into crisis-response teams. As a result, METASTAVA could not organise a scientific dissemination meeting.

WP5: Project management (M1-M36)

JRP8-WP5-T1: Consortium agreement (M1-M6)

The grant agreement of the entire Onehealth EJP covers all necessary agreements between partners and includes the work plan of our project as it was submitted. There is no need for a joint research project – level consortium agreement.

JRP8-WP5-T2: Internal communication (M1-M24)

Pre-kickoff meeting phone calls with work package leaders. Kickoff meeting (21.02.2018, Brussels). WP1 phone calls (coordinator- WPL) about standardization. Internal WP1 questionnaires on data generation and data analysis + follow up teleconferences. Mailings to all collaborators or partner contacts about general EJP-OH information. Teleconference on WP1 standardization (end of M6). Internal WP1, WP2 (19/07/2018) and WP3 (5/10/2018) teleconferences. Internal WP3 questionnaire to document the sample collections. WPL/general assembly progress teleconference (11/12/2018). Yearly annual meetings + periodic WP specific teleconferences (summarized in D-JRP8-5.2)

The METASTAVA general assembly managed severe shifts in responsibilities (changes in work package leadership and deputy workpackage leadership).

Moreover, the integration of a Third partner (Erasmus Medical Center) via WUR was formalized, while two no-cost extension requests were submitted and obtained to manage project-related delays (initial 6 month extension) as well as serious COVID-19 crisis related delays (extension until December 2020).

JRP8-WP5-T3: reporting and liaising with the EU (M20-M24)

Completed, see first, second, and third intermediate reports (2018 and 2019 and 2020) and the present final report.

4 Project self-assessment

In our opinion, all scientific objectives of the METASTAVA project were met as documented in the present final report and more detailed in the corresponding deliverable reports. These objectives include building a small One Health community of labs investigating diagnostic use of metagenomics, standardisation of methodologies, validation of analytical aspects of metagenomics, and assessment of control strategies and formulation of guidelines for informed implementation and interpretation of metagenomics results. Importantly, the generated results have indicated a huge potential of mNGS methods but have also highlighted the importance of a critical investigation and informed decisions in the implementation of NGS based assays.

However, the long-lasting impact of the current COVID-19 pandemic seriously hit all partners. This included lock-downs and reduced access to laboratories, as well as the direct involvement of METASTAVA staff in the management of varying aspects of the pandemic, including the implementation of molecular diagnostic SARS-CoV2 assays, contribution to diagnostic capacities, sequencing of SARS-CoV2 genomes, etc. Insights, methods and expertise developed in METASTAVA were useful in these crisis response efforts. For some partners this resulted in a high investment in pandemic management activities for the most of 2020, without an immediate view on improvement during the first half of 2021.

As a result of this unprecedented situation, METASTAVA struggled to formally disseminate its fulfilled deliverables in the form of scientific publications (several are seriously delayed) as well as its

dissemination to the wider scientific and stakeholder community. Importantly, we did not manage to organise the planned scientific dissemination meetings due to practical constraints as well as unavailability of key personnel as a consequence of the pandemic. This limited the dissemination activities of the project to what was already achieved in 2018 and 2019. Realising this weakness, METASTAVA published an easily accessible document (D-JRP8-1.6) regrouping guidelines for the diagnostic implementation and validation and the correct interpretation of metagenomic methods aimed at (1) scientists envisaging mNGS diagnostic applications and (2) stakeholders envisaging to estimate the potential diagnostic value and complexity of implementing mNGS for diagnostic purposes.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
08	D-JRP8-1.1	Dataset: reference data metagenomics data generation	12	2/10/2018		One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486754#.YBgYmuhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4486763#.YBgY9OhKjcc	
08	D-JRP8-1.2	Dataset: reference data metagenomics analysis	12	28/06/2018		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486767#.YBgZO-hKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4486769#.YBgZguhKjcc	
08	D-JRP8-1.3	List of sequence datasets	27	16/12/2020		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486773#.YBgZ5uhKjcc	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
08	D-JRP8-1.4	SOP: guidelines for the description of scope and analytical properties of a metagenomic method in a diagnostic context	30	36 as D-JRP8-1.6		D1.4, D1.5, D2.1 will be joined in a single guidance document for labs envisaging mNGS as a diagnostic method = D-JRP-1.6	2
08	D-JRP8-1.5	Review paper	30	36 as D-JRP8-1.6		D1.4, D1.5, D2.1 will be joined in a single guidance document for labs envisaging mNGS as a diagnostic method	2
08	D-JRP8-1.6	Review document with guidelines on diagnostic applications of metagenomics: METASTAVA guidelines for informed mNGS implementation	New D	36 as D-JRP8-1.6		Public One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486779#.YBgapOhKjcc	2
08	D-JRP8-2.1	SOP: use of quality metrics for metagenomics dataset evaluation	30	36 as D-JRP8-1.6		D1.4, D1.5, D2.1 will be joined in a single guidance document for labs envisaging mNGS as a diagnostic method	2
08	D-JRP8-2.2	Report and guidelines for the use of exogenous process controls in metagenomics	26	30		Public One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486781#.YBga5OhKjcc	2&3

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
08	D-JRP8-2.3	Report on batch and contamination effects in metagenomics	12	16		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486807#.YBghSuhKhMO	
08	D-JRP8-D-2.5	Report on proficiency test	M24	34		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486809#.YBgdjOhKjcc	
08	D-JRP8-3.1	Spiked sample panels ready for analysis	6	m12	12	Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486821#.YBgd6-hKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4486823#.YBgeJ-hKjcc	
08	D-JRP8-3.2	Procedure for analyzing analytical sensitivity and robustness datasets	12	17		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo:	

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						https://zenodo.org/record/4486827#.YBgecOhKjcc	
08	D-JRP8-3.3	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , hepE	30	04.01.2021		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486829#.YBgeqehKjcc	2 & 3
08	D-JRP8-3.4	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , NoV	30	04.01.2021		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486834#.YBge5ehKjcc	2&3
08	D-JRP8-3.5	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , pox	30	06.01.2021	34	Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486840#.YBgfMuhKjcc	2&3
08	D-JRP8-3.6	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , STEC	30	30		Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486844#.YBgfa-hKjcc	2

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
08	D-JRP8-3.7	Report: analytical sensitivity and robustness , ABR genes detection	30	06.01.2021	35	Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486850#.YBgfvehKjcc	2&3
08	D-JRP8-4.1	Report of meeting with ongoing initiatives to assure input in WP1: METASTAVA integration with ongoing research efforts in diagnostic metagenomics and diagnostic NGS use	7	9.05.2018 Cogwheel workshop report		Confidential Cogwheel workshop report =EJP deliverable 4.3. https://zenodo.org/record/4486854#.YBggB-hKjcc	
08	D-JRP8-4.2	SOP's, guidelines, scientific papers, presentations	30	17/12/2020	36	Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486860#.YBggTOhKjcc	2
08	D-JRP8-4.3	Minutes of scientific meeting	30	Not realised		Organisation impossible: COVID19	10
08	D-JRP8-5.1	Consortium agreement	6			Not needed: One Health EJP level	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
08	D-JRP8-5.2	Progress and final meeting minutes	30	36		We focused on producing a complete list of all METASTAVA meetings throughout the project instead of providing detailed minutes of individual meetings (which are documents for internal use in the consortium) Confidential One Health EJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4486864#.YBggjOhKjcc	8
08	D-JRP8--5.3	Half term report	M13	13		Not delivered on group website: report to PMC	8
08	D-JRP8-5.4	Final report	30	36		Not delivered on group website: report to PMC	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
08	M-JRP8-M1	Concertation meeting with ongoing initiatives	6	Yes		Cogwheel workshop with COMPARE and EFFORT. Additional contacts are ongoing.
08	M-JRP8-M2	Public and own dataset identified	30	Yes	36	see D-JRP8-1.3
08	M-JRP8-M3	Proficiency test panel ready for shipping	20	Yes		
08	M-JRP8-M4	Procedure for analysing analytical sensitivity and robustness datasets agreed	12	Yes 17		
08	M-JRP8-M5	Progress meeting	12	Yes 13		
08	M-FBZ2.METASTAVA.6	Scientific meeting	M30	No		COVID-19 impact
08	M-JRP8-M7	Scientific meeting	30	Yes		3x METASTAVA annual meeting + 2x participation One Health EJP ASM
08	M-JRP8-M8	Dissemination to various stakeholders including joint communication with ongoing initiatives	30	Yes		Various presentations to national and international stakeholder's meetings
08	M-JRP8-M9	Final meeting	30	Yes		online meeting on 30/11/2020

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Evaluation of a commercial exogenous internal process control for diagnostic RNA virus metagenomics from different animal clinical samples https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jviromet.2020.113916	YES		GOLD
COVID-19 in health-care workers in three hospitals in the south of the Netherlands: a cross-sectional study https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30527-2	YES		GOLD
Monitoring SARS-CoV-2 circulation and diversity through community wastewater sequencing https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.09.21.20198838	YES		GOLD
Increased viral read counts and metagenomic full genome characterization of porcine astrovirus 4 and Posavirus 1 in sows in a swine farm with unexplained neonatal piglet diarrhea. 10.1007/s11262-020-01791-z https://zenodo.org/record/4244782#.X6LfzYhKjcc	YES	GREEN, 12 months	
Detection of Norovirus Variant GII.4 Hong Kong in Asia and Europe, 2017-2019. doi: 10.3201/eid2701.203351.	YES		GOLD
Rapid SARS-CoV-2 whole-genome sequencing and analysis for informed public health decision-making in the Netherlands. doi: 10.1038/s41591-020-0997-y	YES		GOLD
In preparation: “A proficiency test of metagenomics as a diagnostic tool for the detection of RNA viruses in swine fecal material”. Lihong Liu, Mikhayil Hakhverdyan, Kevin Vanneste, Pierrick Lucas, Yannick Blanchard, Bas B. Oude Munnink, Sander van Boheemen, Claudia Wylezich, Dirk Hoepfer, Alex Bossers, Marcel Hulst, Steven Van Borm	YES		

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
<p>In Preparation: Metagenomic sequencing of avian coronavirus positive clinical chicken samples: complete genome characterization of circulating infectious bronchitis vaccine strains and detection of co-infecting poultry viruses including avian leucosis virus, chicken astrovirus, sicinivirus, avibirnavirus and chicken calicivirus. Steven Van Borm, Mieke Steensels, Elisabeth Mathijs, Frank Vandenbussche, Thierry van den Berg, Bénédicte Lambrecht</p>	YES		
<p>In preparation: Metagenomic characterization of Orf virus circulating in small ruminants, Belgium, 2003-2018. Steven Van Borm, Andy Haegemans, Kevin Vanneste, Raf Winand, Kris De Clercq, Frank Vandenbussche.</p>	YES		

Additional output

- Liu L, Hakhverdyan M, Leijon M. The influence of sample preparations on high-throughput sequencing detection of viruses in clinical samples. The 11th International Congress for Veterinary Virology. Vienna, Austria, 27-30 August 2018.
- Sander van Boheemen. Sample Pretreatment: Challenges in Virology. Workshop: ESCV Next Generations Sequencing in Clinical Virology. 20-21 November, 2018
- Van Borm S. One Health EJP-METASTAVA: Joint efforts in standardization and analytical validation of diagnostic metagenomics approaches in public (animal) health laboratories. 2nd IABS (International Association for Biological Standardisation) conference on next generation sequencing for adventitious virus detection in biologics for humans and animals, Ghent, 13-14 Nov. 2019
- Van Borm S. Next Generation Sequencing from sample to result : how does it work, what is the current status, and what is the added diagnostic value? World Veterinary Poultry Association, Belgian Branch. Study day 27/02/2020.

7 One Health impact

METASTAVA has provided important guidelines, standardised protocols and results indicating the potential diagnostic added value of metagenomic NGS based workflows, as well as current hurdles and the importance of properly informed selection of workflows and careful interpretation of results. These results and guidelines provide important information for stakeholders considering the potential inclusion of such methodologies as complementary wide-scope orientation diagnostics to supplement highly sensitive and specific targeted diagnostic assays.

The developed methodologies and insights in principle bridge the med/vet/food boundaries as they can be applied to any pathogen and sample type. However, careful consideration is needed to assess the suitability of the approach for a particular research or diagnostic question. METASTAVA's results

not only echo the huge potential of metagenomic methods but also highlight where current hurdles still prevent their widespread use as catch-all diagnostic methods. The output of the project contributes to clarifying for which particular diagnostic questions metagenomics provide a huge added benefit (e.g. detection of novel emerging viruses) and for which diagnostic questions metagenomics' current analytical properties do not provide added benefit (e.g. detailed typing of bacterial strains in a complex food sample matrix with low pathogen loads). Especially our "METASTAVA guidelines for informed mNGS implementation" urges diagnosticians, researchers, policy makers, and stakeholders alike to critically consider the potential benefits and remaining hurdles when considering metagenomics as a diagnostic tool and to select methods that suit the diagnostic question.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	4	4	3
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	4	3	5
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	5	4	3
Integration	4	4	4
Sustainability	5	3	4
Impact of the project	4	4	4
TOTAL	26/30	22/30	23/30

AVERAGE: 24

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

METASTAVA aims to bring metagenomics to the routine diagnostic laboratory by developing reference data, by harmonizing both experimental and data analysis workflows, and also by validating protocols targeting major bacterial and viral animal pathogens. The results of the project fit the initial objectives as it reflects the accomplishment of the deliverables proposed in the DoW (reports, interactive documents, and publications) despite the COVID pandemics. One important aspect of this project is also the complementarity/alignment of METASTAVA with priorities of scientific agendas and other major funded related projects (COMPARE, EFFORT,..) (see below integration and impact sections).

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project fully responded and is in alignment with both topic FBZ 2.5, and the initial objectives set in the proposal. A huge amount of work has been performed in WPs 1 to 4, comprising 19 individual defined tasks. Except for some milestones (e.g. dissemination of the deliverables) that were hampered due to the Covid pandemic, the majority of the objectives have been met.

Reviewer 3: POC member

METASTAVA aimed to bring metagenomics data generation and analysis tools closer to diagnostic laboratories by providing guidance for method selection, validation and quality assurance. All scientific objectives were met including building a small One Health community of labs investigating diagnostic use of metagenomics, standardisation of methodologies, validation of analytical aspects of metagenomics, and assessment of control strategies and formulation of guidelines for informed implementation and interpretation of metagenomics results.

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic METASTAVA struggled to formally disseminate its fulfilled deliverables in the form of scientific publications as well as its dissemination to the wider scientific and stakeholder community.

The planned scientific dissemination meetings could not be organised due to practical constraints as well as unavailability of key personnel as a consequence of the pandemic.

As a substitute METASTAVA published an easily accessible document regrouping guidelines for the diagnostic implementation and validation and the correct interpretation of metagenomic methods aimed at (1) scientists envisaging mNGS diagnostic applications and (2) stakeholders envisaging to estimate the potential diagnostic value and complexity of implementing mNGS for diagnostic purposes.

In conclusion : scientific objectives of the project were achieved but the proposed communication and dissemination objectives were hindered by the Covid-19 pandemic.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1:full proposal evaluator

As mentioned in the former inform, the project was promising and faced unmet needs including the accurate detection of foodborne zoonotic pathogens (FBZ), antimicrobial resistance genes (AMR) and emerging microbial threats (ET), by optimizing standard methodology and resources. Deliverables include reports, datasets, scientific papers and interactive documents. However, some of these resources are still confidential and some of the papers remain unpublished which made difficult to appreciate the level of excellence reached. The reviewer misses some further information about the approaches used and compared in WP3 R (e.g. mNGS methods used to analyse resistomes or antibiotic resistant bacteria) as well as the interpretation of the results to establish ranking risks in Public Health. One of the strengths of the proposal is the work plan, the modular structure of the WPs that will provide analysis of the different parts in the mNGS workflow and the possibilities of improving weak parts.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The main goal of the project was to facilitate the use of mNGS into a diagnostic approach for pathogen detection. Therefore, protocols were standardized, and data-sets built (WP1). Attention was paid to validation and quality monitoring measures for m-genomics methods, which are indeed definitely needed (WP2). Members of the consortium contributed in the evaluation of m-genomic workflows (WP3) and the findings and outcomes were disseminated and concerted with other research platforms (WP1). As such, the research approach is logical and needed, but does not reflect an innovative or excellence approach rather an ongoing progress in the current research applications.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project delivered excellent scientifically qualified results with progress beyond the state-of-the-art. A fair number of research papers was published in high level journals. A fruitful collaboration between project partners was established.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Different results in WP1 and WP2 resulted in a guidance document entitled “Key considerations for the implementation of high throughput sequencing based metagenomics (mNGS) in diagnostic clinical, food and veterinary labs: a no-nonsense pointer” (D-JRP8-1.6) which was designed for helping different scientists/professionals to decide when and how apply metagenomics. Such guidelines were used in WP3 and were useful in the analysis of SARS-COVID-19 performed by different METASTAVA partners during 2020 in their institutions. In fact, this led to different publications related these viruses. Because the cancelation of many activities during 2020 and 2021, generation and dissemination of the results have been seriously ameliorated but the activities performed were adequate and seem to be continued in further projects.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The report provides a good overview of the work that has been done, and required definitely a good organization and management. Attention has clearly been paid in reporting and communication within the consortium (WP5).

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project was adequately managed. Shifts in responsibilities in the consortium were properly addressed. Communication with all partners and with the EU was active.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

One of the strengths of METASTAVA is its complementarity with other major funded related projects (COMPARE, EFFORT,..) and the activities performed to share and maximize efforts with cross-cutting work of such projects. Time limitations precluded checking the synergistic effects of these combined initiatives. More elaborated discussions and comparative analysis of the outcomes beyond the end of the projects mentioned could greatly maximize the results obtained. The involvement of the partners in ongoing One Health EJP initiatives and the upload of results and documents at the One Health EJP website is excellent news that will help to promote the dissemination, updating, and further integration with future and ongoing initiatives.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project clearly demonstrated integrative activities such as the harmonization and validation of the methodologies, as well as their application on existing and newly created data sets, in which the partners contributed.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project was successful in achieving integrative activities and output.

Methods for mNGS data organisation and data analysis were standardized. External controls for metagenomics were developed and evaluated. Reproducible metagenomic detection of RNA viruses in swine fecal material was shown. The methodologies and expertise developed in METASTAVA was used by several partners in parallel diagnostic and research efforts. A metagenomic proficiency test was organised showing that the methods selected as METASTAVA mNGS modules are (i) well suited for virus identification even from challenging matrices like faeces and (ii) the selected methods can reproducibly be applied. A standardised workflow for the data analysis was decided between partners and an SOP was written.

The developed methodologies and insights in principle bridge the med/vet/food boundaries as they can be applied to any pathogen and sample type. The project showed that metagenomics has its limits for detailed typing of bacterial strains in a complex food sample matrix with low pathogen loads. By contrast metagenomics proved its added value for detection of novel emerging viruses.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Besides the comments made in the previous section, the expertise and findings developed in METASTAVA continue in further projects funded by One Health EJP in other calls including One Health EJP-JRP16-TeleVIR and One Health EJP-JRP12-Farmed in which METASTAVA partners participate. However, the authors and the One Health EJP should be aware of the number of projects and organizations (e.g. JRC) that provide approaches of different aspects of the problem. To maintain alive the update and collaboration with other stakeholders is a challenge and will be important and useful for the scientific community.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The standardized methodologies, and especially the validation of the analytical aspects of the analysis methods have already contributed to a onehealth community between the partners of the consortium, and certainly has the potential to expand towards other institutes.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The methodologies and expertise developed in METASTAVA was used by several partners in parallel diagnostic and research efforts. The methodologies and expertise has been proven particularly relevant in response to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

The proficiency test showed that the methods selected as METASTAVA mNGS modules are well suited for virus identification even from challenging matrices such as faeces and that selected methods can reproducibly be applied.

The continuation of the developed expertise was ensured by participation of METASTAVA partners in One Health EJP second call projects including One Health EJP-JRP16-TeleVIR and One Health EJP-JRP12-Farmed. Secondly, public deliverables of other initiatives were taken into account and METASTAVA participated in interactive workshops with other initiatives.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The major impact of METASTAVA is the set of guidelines, standardized protocols, and results, of potential use in workflows for diagnosis of diverse microbial threats. This is an unmet need highlighted by the ECDC and EFSA (besides FDA and CDC) for years and any effort is highly valuable and welcome. The analysis of different modules in the metagenomic workflow is especially important. Finally, this reviewer wishes to highlight what was mentioned above in the section related to sustainability. Impact of the topic continues beyond the end of METASTAVA and diffusion and updating of the results are important to maximize the efforts and resources already invested.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project contributes to an novel approach of pathogen detection in governmental and public laboratories, based on the m-genomics technology. With this approach, faster and more accurate detection should be possible, as well as the elucidation of transmission routes and the identification of new mutants or emerging organisms. The technology is definitely the way forward, though it

requires more technical and scientific skills in the correct application and even more important interpretation of (large) datasets.

Reviewer 3: POC member

As there is a continuous evolution in diagnostic methods the impact of METASTAVA will be transient as new methods and procedures will become available. The results of METASTAVA will have an impact on the broad application of this technique by international stakeholders. The generated results have indicated a huge potential of mNGS methods but have also highlighted the importance of a critical investigation and informed decisions in the implementation of NGS based assays.

JRP09-AIR-SAMPLE

Final report

1 Consortium composition

Name of the Project Coordinator and of all applicants, with full affiliations

1. Jeffrey Hoorfar (coordinator) & Mette Fachmann, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark.
2. Gro Johannessen, Mona Torp & Camilla Sekse, Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI), Norway.
3. Renata Karpiskova & Ivana Koláčková, Veterinary Research Institute, (VRI), Czech Republic.
4. Kinga Wieczorek & Jacek Osek, National Vet Research Institute (NVRI), Poland.
5. Giuliano Garofolo, & Elisabetta Di Giannatale, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise (IZSAM), Italy.

Short CV of each participating key scientist (at least one per participating organization) (see annex)

This part summarise the major activities and competencies of the person over the last 5 years. Include information that indicates the coordinator's skill to manage international projects.

The partners have previous record of history of successful collaboration in the chicken farms, including cooperation on practical laboratory work, and joint publication. The partners have been selected carefully to include European regions with different climate and with negative, low, medium or high (negative or positive controls) flock prevalence of *Campylobacter*. DTU (Denmark) has during the FP7 CamCon project, which was led by NVI (Norway), carried out joint field studies with NVRI in Poland and Denmark. VRI (The Czech Republic) has been an active partner in three EU projects led by DTU (Food-PCR, Food-PCR II, and BIOTRACER), which has produced joint methods and publications. All partners have access to broiler farms, either through ongoing national surveillance programs, or will establish a sentinel sampling plan in collaboration with the national food safety authorities or famer organizations. Exchange of students and joint workshops are planned to fully integrate the collaborators.

Jeffrey Hoorfar (M), PhD, DVSc, is a professor of Food Microbiology at DTU. He has worked for 25 years with microbial food safety, in particular rapid detection and characterization of foodborne pathogens. He has coordinated three large EU projects with up to 62 partners (BIOTRACER in FP6) and a budget portfolio of up to M€ 15 (Food-PCR, Food-PCR II part of MedVetNet, and BIOTRACER), several Nordic funded projects and a large number of national R&D projects. He is certified NLP Coach Practitioner, has completed a one-year course in Assertive Leadership, and has received intensive education as research manager at Copenhagen Business School. He has >100 publications according to WoS with an h-index of 28, and has edited four books in food microbiology. He has been a member of ISO and CEN standardization working groups on food microbiology.

Role in this project: Project leader, WP leader, link to the EJP coordinator, development of sample preparation methods, qPCR detection protocols, metagenomics and reference culture methods.

Gro S. Johannessen (F), PhD, is a senior research scientist since 2005 at NVI (Norway). She has broad experience in detection of pathogens along the food chain, from environmental samples and raw material to ready to use food products, using both classical culturing methods and molecular methods. According to WoS, she has 21 publications with an h-index of 10. She is currently the Chair of the microbiological subcommittee in NMKL and has participated in working groups in ISO and EFSA.

Role in this project: She has been leader of WP2 and has participated in Task-1-2, and both tasks in WP2.

Mona Torp (F), DVM, PhD, is a senior research scientist at NVI (Norway). She has had this position at since 2011, and from 2004 – 2011 she worked at the Norwegian Food Safety Authority. She is experienced in detection of pathogens and toxin producing fungi from samples of animals, food and feeds, mainly using classical culturing methods. She has 15 publications according to WoS with an h-index of 14. She has been in charge of the Norwegian surveillance program for *Campylobacter* in broiler flocks since 2011 and is familiar with the national poultry organizations. **Role in this project:** She has participated in Task-1-1 and in both tasks in WP2.

Camilla Sekse (F), Cand. Scient, PhD, is a senior research scientist since 2009 at NVI (Norway). She has broad experience in molecular microbiology and bacteriology. Her key areas of research are foodborne pathogens, antimicrobial resistance, molecular typing, molecular risk assessment and comparative genomics. She has 28 international peer-reviewed publications with an h-index of 16.

Role in this project: She has participated in Task 1-2 and task 2-1. Participates in development of DNA extraction protocol, organizing a pilot study on metagenomics and a large metagenomics study including samples from all partners.

Renáta Karpíšková (F), Ph.D. ,DVM is an associated professor in Food Microbiology at VFU and a head of Bacteriology Department at VRI (The Czech Republic). Since 1986 has been working in the field of food hygiene, food microbiology and food control. Since 1995 has an experience in the field of food and waterborne borne diseases, outbreak detection, molecular epidemiology, methods of foodborne pathogen detection and typing, antimicrobial resistance and food safety. She has an expertise in research as a principal investigator or co-investigator of three international (EU), two bilateral, twelve national research projects and four University Funded projects. Since 1996-2012 has been nominated as a head of NRL for *Listeria monocytogenes*, from 2013 plays a role as subcontracting laboratory to NRL for *Listeria* in the field of molecular typing and outbreak investigation. She is national expert for the Czech Republic in the area of foodborne diseases FWD – ECDC and a member of VetCAST network group (EUCAST). She published 84 articles in journals with impact factor (WoS), is a co-author of 3 textbooks, with WoS h-index: 13.

Role in this project: Pre-slaughter sampling, sample preparation methods, qPCR detection protocols and standardization of detection methods.

Ivana Koláčková (F), Ph.D., DVM is the head of NRL for *E. coli* and a senior researcher at the Department of Bacteriology, VRI (The Czech Republic). Since 2001, she has been working in the field of bacteriology and food microbiology. She has experience in the field of food and waterborne borne diseases, molecular methods, bacteria detection and typing and antimicrobial resistance. She has expertise in research as a principal investigator or co-investigator national research projects. She published 14 articles in journals with impact factor (WOS), with WoS h-index: 5.

Role in this project: Pre-slaughter sampling, sample preparation methods, qPCR detection protocols and standardization of detection methods.

Jacek Osek (M), DVM, PhD, ScD, is a professor of veterinary sciences. Since 2008, he is the head of Department of Hygiene of Food of Animal Origin and National Reference Laboratories for food microbiology and chemistry in NVRI (Poland). He has participated in the EU (e. g ProSafeBeef, CamCon) as well as he has coordinated several national projects. He is a member of Task Force (Scientific Network) for zoonoses data collection of European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the Technical Committee (microbiology) of the National Normalisation Board. He is an author of > 120 publications with an h-index of 18.

Role in this project: Participation in development of preparation methods, qPCR detection protocols, validation of air sampling and DNA extraction methods.

Kinga Wiczorek (F), DSc, PhD. Since 2008, she is deputy head of Department of Hygiene of Food of Animal Origin at NVRI (Poland). She is in charge of National Reference Laboratories for *Campylobacter* together with antimicrobial resistance, Shigatoxigenic *E. coli* (STEC), *L. monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* in

food and bacteriological contamination of bivalve mollusks located in NVRI. She has coordinated the EU project MICRORISK (FP7). She was involved in others EU (ProSafeBeef, CamCon) and national projects. She has participated in many international training courses in microbiological and molecular identification of food-borne pathogens (EU, USA, Australia, and New Zealand). She is an author of > 40 publications with an h-index of 7.

Role in this project: Creation of sample banks, method development, qPCR protocols, validation of air sampling and DNA extraction methods.

Elisabetta Di Giannatale (F), DSc, MSc, is the head of the National Reference laboratory for *Campylobacter* and head of the Bacteriology unit at the IZSAM. She has coordinated the IZSAM unit for the CamChain project (EMIDA) and she coordinated several Italian R&D projects with budget portfolio up to M€ 1. She participated with coordinator responsibility to several OIE and EU twinning projects for food safety issues. She has extensive work experience on food safety and bacteriology, particularly focused to molecular characterization and culture method development. She has 37 publications on international peer reviewed journals with an h-index of 8 according to the SCOPUS citation database.

Role in this project: Coordinator of IZSAM unit and leader for IZSAM activities in the WP2: validation and standardization of methods.

Giuliano Garofolo (M), DVM, MSc, is a researcher microbiologist at the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* of Italy, IZSAM. He has experience in conducting research with task leadership in several national and international projects: Bru-EPIDIA, CamChain and BrucMedNet in the framework of the ERA-Net EMIDA, ANIHWA, ARIMNET funds and FastD funded by the Italian Ricerca Corrente 2013 funds. He is particularly interested in the molecular evolution and diagnostic of pathogenic bacteria to understand the dispersion over time and space. Thus he works mostly on application novel methodologies to support public health such as MLVA, MLST, WGS and metagenomic to track diseases and outbreaks. He has 31 publications on international peer reviewed journals with an h-index of 11 according to the SCOPUS citation database.

Role in this project: leader for the IZSAM unit in the WP1 activities: development of methods.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

During the first year, we harmonized the methodologies within the consortium and made a repository list of *Campylobacter* strains and technologies to detect rapidly *Campylobacter* in bio secured chicken houses. We made a preliminary trial in each country using the existing air sampling protocols and equipment from Sartorius GmbH, which made reagents and equipment available to the consortium. During the second year, we modified the protocols and harmonized the actual flock sampling, pre-analytical sample treatment and methods for analyses across the member institutions in order to enable data comparison. In addition, the second year included development of implementation of metagenomics diagnostic using filter samples. Substantial work was devoted to DNA bioinformatics that used different software at different partner labs. Finally, we conducted a multi-centre evaluation of our harmonized protocols using samples taken in the five participating countries. The third year has focussed on producing publications, SOPs and guidelines. An online video clip was prepared for the education of broiler industry (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S9mapXSM8tw&t=95s>). Substantial work has been put into writing the second publication that has been published in AEM. The final air sampling protocol has been converted into a user guideline for wider communication to the public and stakeholders (<https://youtu.be/LMD03UAAPUw>). The final guideline has been also disseminated to all relevant authorities in the EU, because the results showed that air sampling together with real-time PCR improved detection. The project has conducted field-testing in five European countries in Northern, Southern, Central and Western Europe with different prevalence of *Campylobacter* in their broiler production; from a low prevalence (Norway) to countries with higher prevalence. In Norway (low-prevalence country), the air sampling together with real-time PCR gave the same results as the

cultivation method indicating that it is also suitable in countries with low prevalence of *Campylobacter*. The results also show that the likelihood of detecting *Campylobacter* in a chicken flock has quadrupled with the new method (air sampling together with real-time PCR). That is, up to four times more chicken flocks show signs of *Campylobacter* being present when the new method is used compared to sock samples. The method is especially useful to farmers to confirm the cleanliness of their house BEFORE inserting new chick.

3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Method Development (M1-M13)

JRP9-WP1-T1: Sampling activities and creation of a sample bank (air and boot-swab samples) from different regions (M1-M6)

For the creation of a sample bank of air samples, the method of culturing, size of gelatine filters, temperature, time, volume of samples and samples preparation were optimised. The work has been done by inoculating the gelatine filters with different levels of *Campylobacter jejuni*.

The same results were obtained for the incubation of ½ filters in Bolton Broth for 44±4 h and the incubation of boot socks ISO 10272-1. It were no false results from gelatin filters. In addition, the PCR results from the filters corresponded to the results obtained with the culture-based method.

Optimisation of protocols for boot swab samples were provided by NVI. The protocols were optimised with regard to ISO 10272-1 for the detection of *Campylobacter* in the boot socks of own choice. Both protocols were shared among the partners. The protocols include the sampling step, cultural method, optimised PCR step and the storage (Figure1).

Figure1. Protocols for culture-based detection of *Campylobacter* from chicken farms.

For the sample bank, a “Farm questionnaire” was designed. The metadata associated with sample collection includes:

- Type of farm with biosecurity measures: organic or conventional farm (open housing farms must be exclude)
- Size of the farm (number of houses)
- Size of the house (square meters; or length x breadth)

- Size of flock (number of chicken per house)
- Type of bedding: Shavings, sawdust, straw, paper, peat, etc.
- Age of chicken coming in and out the house
- Feed composition or feed compound type
- Additional equipment (floor heating, fly net, etc.
- Type of chicken breed
- Chicken supplier
- Number of breeding cycles per house and year
- Type of disinfection
- Biosecurity measures (rodent and insect control, dead-bird disposal, water sanitation, litter removal, visitor's control, owner's pets on the farm)
- Health care anamnestic data (use of antibiotics; first week mortality)
- Date
- Age of animals (days)
- Outdoor temperature
- Indoor temperature
- Farm region (not exact address, because identity of farms participating in the sampling plans Are not be revealed.)

The data was stored on the drives of the participating institutions. All stored samples were linked to the farm's questionnaire lists. The 1mLx2 of each positive enriched samples and the extracted DNA were stored at minimum -70°C in the facilities of each partner. The data was shared among the partners. The data (results) are associated with the analyses of electronic journals/ reports stored in the institutional servers of the participating countries. The raw data was stored in Mx3000P and Mx3005P QPCR Systems instruments, Microsoft Excel files, Microsoft Word in the institutional servers of the project participants.

In the first sampling round, the samples (boot socks and air samples) were all analysed by cultivation. The use of real-time PCR was voluntary, and not all partners carried out PCR. It was also variation between the partners that used real-time PCR on which steps PCR was used.

Sampling activities for creation Sample bank.

The DTU sampled at three farms with five different houses. One house was found to be positive for both boot socks and air filter. Overall, it was found that the results from the incubation of ½ filters in Bolton broth for 44±4 h are the same as the results of the incubation of boot socks (ISO), with no false results from gelatin filters. In addition, the PCR results from the filters corresponded to the results obtained with the culture based method.

In June 2018, the NVI sampled eight flocks from seven farms by collecting one pair of sock samples and one air filter sample from each flock. In September, NVI also sampled two flocks from one farm. Here, one pair of sock samples and two air filter samples were collected from each flock. NVI found three flocks positive for boot socks, while all the air filters were negative.

The VRI sampled ten different houses from four farms. From each house, two pair of socks and two air filters were sampled. According to the cultivation method, all the flocks were negative. Nevertheless, the molecular methods retrieved two positive samples out of the ten samples. Gelatine filters do not seem to be able to keep campylobacters alive, and a 15-minute air sampling does not seem sufficient. The cultivation methods do not seem sensitive enough, whereas the PCR method (direct DNA extraction) is more effective in some filter samples.

The NVRI sampled from two farms with three houses at eight different time points. The first two samplings showed positive PCR results from filters, but they could confirm the results through strain isolation only from socks for sampling no. 2, and only after 24h incubation in Bolton broth. For the

remaining samplings, two out of six were positive in culturing from socks but only in one of the air filters *C. jejuni* was isolated. Finally, three filters showed positive PCR results. In conclusion, for the socks samples, plating out after incubation in Bolton broth for 24h, seems better, perhaps due to a high level of background microflora present in direct plating. Air filter-culture based detection gave one positive result, while in real-time PCR, the air filters resulted in three positive results. In one case (sampling no. 3), for the positive samples, 100% correlation was observed (the same results for socks, filter culturing and real-time PCR). For the negative samples, four times (sampling numbers 4, 5, 7 and 8) resulted in 100% correlation for different type of samples. Three samplings gave divergent results for various kind of samples.

The IZSAM sampled in ten different houses from two farms. From each house, two boot socks pairs and two air filters were sampled. The culturing was performed using direct plating and enrichment using the Bolton broth. The DNA was extracted directly from air filters and boot socks. For the first five houses the culturing from boot socks revealed one positive sample using the direct plating while all the enriched samples were negative, and the air filters were all negative. The other five houses were positive to the direct plating and negative to the enrichment method, while one air filter was positive to the enrichment. Direct plating for boot socks was shown to be the best option while enrichment with Bolton Broth was not the appropriate method for the isolation of *Campylobacter* from boot socks.

Summary results of field studies shown in Table 1 below:

Country	No of samples (n)	Number of positive samples							
		Boot socks				Air filters			
		cultivation methods		real-time PCR		cultivation methods		real-time PCR	
		direct plating	enrichment	Direct	enrichment	direct plating	enrichment	direct	enrichment
Italy	10	6	0	7	5	0	1	8	5
Czech R.	10	-	0	-	0	-	0	2	0
Norway	10	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Poland	8	-	3	-	-	-	1	3	-
Denmark	6	-	1	-	-	-	1	1	-

JRP9-WP1-T2: Development of a protocol for non-complex DNA extraction for diagnostic qPCR and metagenomics analysis from gelatine-filter samples (M3-M13)

Based on the intensive in-house studies at several participating labs, the consensus protocol enclosed was agreed. It consists of two steps: Pre-treatment of gelatine filters taken by AirPort8 device, and DNA extraction using QIAgen DNeasy Blood&Tissue Kit, according to manufacturer’s instruction with several modifications. The main step in the filter preparation is the addition of the Protex protease to completely dissolving the gelatine. The modifications that we found to be important to performance of the commercially available DNA extraction kit were: 1) Addition of RNase (due to our intended later use of the DNA product for downstream metagenomics analysis); 2) The replacement of kit elution buffer with TE-EDTA buffer; 3) The addition of AL buffer. A metagenomics pilot project was performed that included a standardized MOCK community. Based on the pilot project sequencing technology,

sequencing depth and bioinformatics analysis for a larger metagenomics project were agreed upon, including samples from all partners. The samples from all partners were collected and sequenced. The bioinformatics analysis and interpretation of data including writing manuscripts has been carried out by NVI (Norway). Two metagenomics manuscripts are in preparation, one for the pilot study and one for a large metagenomics study. The pilot study was performed by NVI and a preliminary title for this manuscript is “[Detection of *Campylobacter* in air samples from poultry houses using shot-gun metagenomics – a pilot study](#)” by the following authors; Thomas H.A. Haverkamp, Bjørn Spilberg, Gro Johannessen, Mona Torp, Camilla Sekse to be submitted to BMC Microbiome (Gold Open Access). The second manuscript will involve all partners.

[WP2: Validation and Standardization \(M13-M30\)](#)

JRP9-WP2-T1: Validation of air sampling and DNA extraction methods.

Three harmonized protocols were prepared for 1) field air sampling, 2) DNA extraction, 3) PCR testing. The protocols were evaluated on field air samples from chicken farms around Europe collected during the summer 2019. A sample bank was established for later use for shot-gun metagenomics. The protocols were planned to make the basis for draft standards to be submitted to CEN and EFSA for consideration as part of the continued standardization work for *Campylobacter* detection in chicken farms. This part of the work was planned for Spring 2020. A second manuscript was planned based on the outcome of the summer sampling in 2019 and was published autumn 2020 (see 7. Publications).

JRP9-WP2-T2: Statistical analysis, Standardization and dissemination.

The work in 2020 departed from the achievements of the first annual period and took place over the second annual period and extended in 2020. Validation is important to regulatory approvals before the methods can be used. Hence, the air sampling protocol from WP1 was evaluated. Following statistical data analysis of the results obtained, the best performing protocol was drafted as a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP). This was planned to be demonstrated among the EJP partner laboratories involved in testing of *Campylobacter*, but due to the Covid-19 pandemic and cancellation of the physical meeting in Prague, the physical demonstration was cancelled. Following agreement by the One Health EJP coordinators, this has been done as an online video demonstration (<https://youtu.be/LMD03UAAPUw>). The project and SOP were presented in Sept 2020 by Gro S. Johannessen at the virtual EU Reference Lab meetings for *Campylobacter*. A manuscript describing the final results has been published in AEM: Hoorfar J, Koláčková I, Johannessen GS, Garofolo G, Marotta F, Wiczorek K, Osek J, Torp M, Spilberg B, Sekse C, Thornval NR, Karpíšková R. [Foodborne *Campylobacter*: A multi-center proposal for a fast screening tool in biosecured chicken flocks](#). Appl Environ Microbiol. 2020 Aug 7:AEM.01051-20. doi: 10.1128/AEM.01051-20.

Online video animation material for the education of broiler industry: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S9mapXSM8tw&t=95s>

Possible dissemination through a hands-on, wet-lab workshop, in the case the pandemic is eased.

4 Project self-assessment

The project has followed more or less the initial plan, naturally by some modifications. The outcome has been more profound than envisaged, since the new protocol can detect up to four times more colonized flocks than the stool sampling. It was initially planned to submit a draft standard to CEN/ISO, however, due to the Covid-19 pandemic situation no meeting was held in 2020. For this reason, our effort mostly focussed on publications and virtual demonstration through YouTube, which is completely open to the public. In addition, a targeted effort was done with the professional help by the One Health EJP coordinators to communicate the results to EU regulators, EFSA and ECDC. This deviated slightly from the original plan that involved more interaction with the standardization

organizations. The project and results have been presented at the annual workshop for EURL *Campylobacter* with positive response.

An interesting observation from the first round of sampling was the different interpretations of the initial dilution steps of boot swabs among the partners, although a standardized method (ISO 10272-1) was used. This was discussed in the first paper (Johannessen et al, 2020) and has been brought to the attention of both EURL *Campylobacter* and ISO TC 34/SC 9. A short-coming with this project is that the detection of *Salmonella*, which is important in broiler production, is not included. It is believed that this sampling technique and the samples can be expanded to include more pathogen targets thus being a simple tool for sampling of several relevant organisms. This could be followed up by further studies if funding opportunities arise.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JI P code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
23	D-JRP9-1.1.	Prototype laboratory method to detect and enumerate <i>Campylobacter</i> in air samples.	9	3 August 2018		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3676374#.Xk-zfqaWwj9	2
23	D-JRP9-1.2.	Prototype metagenomics method for characterization of <i>Campylobacter</i> in air samples.	12	Dec 15 2018		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3754239#.YBQ1vOhKhM0	2
23	D-JRP9-2.1.	Online video demonstration of air sampling for farmers.	M24	M18		YouTube demonstration video https://youtu.be/S9mapXSM8tw	1
23	D-JRP9-2.2.	Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for air sampling.	M24	M24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3676376#.Xk-ztaaWwj9	2
23	D-JRP9-2.3	Publication in AEM.	M30	May 2020		Confidential; to be made public after the end of the embargo (Green Access with 6 months embargo)	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
						TD	
23	D-JRP9-2.4	Hands-on, wet-lab workshop for relevant EJP partners.	M29			This deliverable was cancelled – the workshop in Prague was not held because of Covid-19. As alternative solution, a video demonstration was prepared: https://youtu.be/LMD03UAAPUw	5

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M-JRP9-1	Sample bank is established	9	Yes		A decentralized sample bank at partner organizations involved.
03	M-JRP9-2	Sample preparation method is selected	9	Yes		QiaAMP Tissue&Blood kit

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
03	M-JRP9-3	Local field studies completed.	M18	Yes		All partners have conducted local field sampling in chicken farms, as described the project plan. (Initially M15, adapted in AWP-Y2)
03	M-JRP9-4	Statistical analysis completed.	M29	Yes		Delivered as part of the manuscript submitted.

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of <i>Campylobacter</i> isolated from carcasses of chickens slaughtered in Poland – a retrospective study 10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107159 https://zenodo.org/record/3676306	Yes	No	Yes (3 060 €)
<i>Campylobacter</i> in chicken – critical parameters for international, multicentre evaluation of air sampling and detection methods https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2020.103455 https://zenodo.org/record/3663545#.XkPEvGhKiUk	Yes	Yes – 6 months.	No
Foodborne campylobacter: a multi-center proposal for a fast screening tool in biosecured chicken flocks for the foodborne pathogen <i>Campylobacter</i> 10.1128/AEM.01051-20 https://zenodo.org/record/4244138#.X6KEbDiWxM1	Yes	Yes – 6 months	No
MLST-based genetic relatedness of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> isolated from chickens and humans in Poland 10.1371/journal.pone.0226238 https://zenodo.org/record/3628110#.X6FsFjiWxPY	Yes	No	Yes (PloS One)
Thornval, N., Hoorfar, J. (2021). Progress in detection of <i>Campylobacter</i> in the food production chain. <i>Current Opinions in Food Science</i> (In Press).	Yes	Yes – 6 months	No
T.H.A. Haverkamp, B. Spilsberg, G. Johannessen, M. Torp, C. Sekse. (2021). Detection of <i>Campylobacter</i> in air samples from poultry houses using shot-gun metagenomics – a pilot study. (In prep)			To be submitted to BMC Microbiome
All partners (2021). Large metagenomics study (In prep). Contact person: Gro S. Johannessen			
Marotta, F., Janowicz, A., Di Marcantonio, L., Ercole, C., Di Donato, G., Garofolo, G., & Di Giannatale, E. (2020). Molecular Characterization and	Yes	No	Yes

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Antimicrobial Susceptibility of <i>C. jejuni</i> Isolates from Italian Wild Bird Populations. Pathogens, 9(4), 304.			

Additional output

Dissemination to EFSA and EC (enclosed).

7 One Health impact

For the first time, the EU has published a guideline for the maximum number of *Campylobacter* in chicken meat (1000 CFU/g). This is a good start. However, controlling the pathogen at the farm level is hampered by the lack of a low-cost and harmonized protocol that can be handled by farmers themselves. The case is that farmers are reluctant or not willing to let outsiders in to sample for *Campylobacter*, or any other pathogen. This is due to the risk of flock contamination by avian flu, coronaviruses, or other externally introduced pathogen risks. The protocol we have presented here enables the use of a smooth and hand-held device, similar to a vacuum cleaner that can be easily handled by farmers. The filter can be taken out and shipped by ordinary mail to any service lab that does qPCR. The advantage of such protocol is that it can gradually be expanded to include an increasing number of pathogen targets, depending on the need of chicken farmers. Furthermore, the sample pre-analytical DNA/RNA extraction method can be more or less used for other pathogens. Thus, the protocol presented may be a game-changer in rapid diagnostics.

What is missing in our approach is the inclusion of detection of *Salmonella*, which is highly important in chicken production. We acknowledge this shortcoming but this was not the main aim of this small project. It is thus recommended to follow up on the inclusion of *Salmonella* (and other pathogens) as a possible future effort.

The project results and SOP have been presented at the EURL *Campylobacter* workshop in 2020 and was well received. The project partners have been in contact with national authorities and stakeholders to inform about the project and also the results to make them aware of this new approach for *Campylobacter* testing.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer1 (new evaluator)	Reviewer1 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	4	3	3
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	3	2	3
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	5	3	3
Integration	5	4	4
Sustainability	4	4	4
Impact of the project	5	2	4
TOTAL	26/30	18/30	21/30

AVERAGE:22

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The primary goal of the project was to develop a robust, non-complex, and low-cost protocol to detect *Campylobacter* strains in broiler production. The protocol was planned to be easy to implement.

It is clear that the project has ended successfully developing a pretty standardized and sensitive method that is noncomplex for farmers to perform with no help. The method has been made publicly available. However, it is unclear if the aim to develop a low-cost (< 2 Euros/sample) protocol, as indicated in the proposal, has been reached. There seems to be not much discussion on the total cost.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project responds to the original call within the priority research topics for food-associated zoonoses to develop NGS-based fast and reliable analysis methods. On the basis of the report, it can also be stated that the predetermined objectives defined within the project have been achieved.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The results are well aligned with the general project objectives as set out in the proposal. Most of the specific objectives are achieved except for the organisation of wet-lab workshops for EJP partners due to the Covid-19 pandemia. The following KPI's were not achieved:

- Uptake of the method by all relevant EJP partners,
- Successful industry and regulatory workshop,
- Acceptance of the air sampling method by European regulators.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The approach, air-sampling for detection of *Campylobacter* strains to reduce the risk of contamination, is a clever idea. This is the heart of the project. However, this approach has previously been reported by the partners of the project (<https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X.JFP-13-268>). I think this limits innovation.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The research project delivered an alternative method to determine the presence of *Campylobacter* in poultry houses, and the collaboration between the partners was predominantly in the harmonization and validation of the protocols and application on the field in high and low *Campylobacter* prevalence poultry farms/countries. This approach is novel compared to the traditional approach that included stool sampling by overshoes and culture identification of *Campylobacter*s.

The report is however very briefly in presenting what was exactly compared and validated, and results in text and table that are hard to interpret, with non-corresponding numbers. However, based on the report and the protocols published on the Onehealth RJP website, it can be concluded that the research work successfully resulted a harmonization of the methodologies (both air sampling and DNA extractions methods). The developed method and approach seems to result in better detection of *Campylobacter* in a chicken flock compared to the traditional method. Research results have been published in two papers and the Journal's A1 peer review. The third claimed publication, the characterization of human and poultry isolates by MLST in Poland, seems however not to be part of the aims of this project.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The results are of good scientific quality and are convincing. The innovative approach of this applied research project consists of testing a practical air sampling method in different countries under different field circumstances with low and high *Campylobacter* prevalence in broiler flocks and combining this sampling method with real-time PCR for better *Campylobacter* detection. This resulted in excellent performances compared to the conventional boot sock sampling technique. The new protocol enabled to detect four times more colonized flocks than the conventional stool sampling.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Despite the Covid-19 pandemic, the implementation of the project has been very well managed. Due to cancellations of in person activities, alternative online video demonstrations have been organized. I guess they plan, as future activities, hands-on and wet-lab workshops, in the case the pandemic eases, to increase the awareness on their developed protocol. They have also prepared Standard Operating Procedure (SOP), which further strengthens the efficiency in its implementation.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Based on the brief report, management seemed to be appropriate as the deliverables and the dissemination of the results were achieved. The harmonization and validation of the protocols, resulting in two prototypes of protocols and a SOP for air sampling were successful. Dissemination of the results has also been achieved with an online video demonstration on youtube to instruct the

samplers at the farm. As such, partners have demonstrated the feasibility, and further implementation may be the next step.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The quality and efficiency of the implementation is very good. Most deliverables and milestones were achieved in time. Effective dissemination and demonstration activities of the project results amongst EJP partner laboratories have been hindered by the Covid-19 pandemic. However, the consortium succeeded to disseminate the results through video which is a good alternative to physical meetings under the present circumstances. It is not mentioned however how the you-tube instruction videos were perceived and taken up by the partners and if it enabled them to apply the demonstrated methods themselves.

It is not specified in the report which use has been made of the questionnaire data.

An adequate number of scientific publications have been published or are in the process of being published.

A final guideline has been disseminated to all relevant authorities in the EU, however the consequent application hereof is not mentioned.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project brought together researches from different countries for a well standardized protocol for air sampling of broiler flocks in production houses. There has been well coordination between the different groups throughout the project. I guess, this makes the protocol to be safely used in different regions of Europe.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project clearly demonstrated integrative activities such as the harmonization of the methodologies, creating a repository of Campylobacter strains, the preparation of standard operations and analysis tools, and the validation of the method in the field. All partners contributed.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Three harmonised protocols were prepared (for field air sampling, for DNA extraction and for PCR testing). A sample bank was established for later shot-gun metagenomics. Measures were taken to enable data comparison. A Standard Operating Procedure for field sampling was drafted but its degree of integration by other partners is not mentioned.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project proposes a novel method for detecting Campylobacter strains using air samples. Since farmers are reluctant to let outsiders for sampling due to contamination risk, development of a method that could be carried out by farmers themselves is critically important. Thus, the non-complex nature of the protocol has a positive impact on its sustainability. However, I believe, cost will be the major concern for its wider use in the future.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

As analysis methods and SOP have been developed and are available on the internet, as well as the validation behind it published in peer reviewed journals, it expected that these developments will remain and that other institutes can apply the outcomes.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The sustainability of the outcome of the project is excellent. The project has shown that the air sampling technique for Campylobacter detection in poultry houses is a reliable and low-cost practical method applicable in the sector. The report claims that this method could be used to confirm efficiency of cleaning and disinfection techniques in empty houses, however this statement is not substantiated by data.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

In the EU, monitoring of Campylobacter in poultry is mandatory. From the project description, I understand that sampling for detection or monitoring of pathogens in broiler flocks in production houses is a problematic issue, mainly due to contamination risk that would be coming from outsiders. The possibility of simple air-sampling for monitoring the presence of the pathogens would therefore be a powerful approach since this could be achieved simply by farmers with no specific technical excellence. The protocol can also be expanded for monitoring other pathogens. Thus, I would expect it to have a high impact.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project contributes towards a more sensitive method in the determination of Campylobacter-status in poultry houses before entering a new flock. In that perspective the project has been successful. However, data on the impact of its implementation on the speed of performance and cost effectiveness compared to traditional sample-culture method, was not included, and additional screening for other pathogens, in particular Salmonella would have been valuable. Therefore, its definite impact cannot be fully assessed.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The results of the project may have an impact on the further elaboration of Campylobacter control in the poultry sector as a readily applicable air sampling method has been validated for routine use determining the status of the flock with regard to Campylobacter contamination. The focus on validation and standardization, has led to improved harmonization of protocols and thereby comparability of data generated for sub-typing and source-tracing.

Final report

1 Consortium composition

Participant No *	Participant organisation name	Country
18 Dr. Velge Philippe (COORDINATOR) Dr. Laroche Béatrice	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (INRA)	France
1 Dr. Martine Denis	AGENCE NATIONALE DE SECURITE SANITAIRE DE L'ALIMENTATION, DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT ET DU TRAVAIL (ANSES)	France
6. Pr Hristo Daskalov	National Centre of Food Safety, NDRVMI, BFSA	Bulgaria
8. Dr. Rychlik Ivan	VETERINARY RESEARCH INSTITUTE (VRI)	Czech Republic
16. Pr Rodríguez Bertos, Antonio	VISAVET HEALTH SURVEILLANCE CENTRE- UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID (VISAVET-UCM)	Spain
22. Pr La Ragione Roberto	UNIVERSITY OF SURREY, School of Veterinary Medicine	United Kingdom
27. Dr Barbara Chirullo	Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS)	Italy
29. Pr Alborali Giovanni	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia Romagna (IZSLER)	Italy
30. Dr Hagenaars Thomas J.	Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek (CVI/ DLO) including Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (formerly CVI)	The Netherlands
32. Dr Naseer, Mohammed Umaer	Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH)	Norway
41. Pr de Jong, Mart	Netherlands Centre for One Health (NCOH)	The Netherlands

Short CV of each participating key scientist (at least one per participating organization)

This part summarizes the major activities and competencies of the person over the last 5 years. Include information that indicates the coordinator's skill to manage international projects.

Partner 18 INRAE (Coordination):

Partner 18-Tours: Dr. **Philippe Velge** (male, 56 years old) has been graduated from the Lille University in life science and Health. He is Director of Research at INRA. He was Deputy Director of the Federative Research Institute: IFR136 "Agents transmissibles et Infectiologie" between 2008 and 2012, and was co-responsible for the "pole bactériologie" of the ISP department (40 permanent scientists).

Since 2000, he is the head of the group "Signalisation, Portage et Virulence Bacterienne" within the Infectiology and Public Health department (ISP). Currently, this research group consists of 7 permanent Scientists and 3 permanent technicians. This research group has analyzed the virulence mechanisms of *Salmonella* and the asymptomatic carrier state induced in chicken.

He is an expert in analysis the interactions of bacteria with the host. He has worked mainly on the virulence mechanisms of *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. He also analyzes the *Salmonella* carrier state in poultry. His fields of interest are Microbiology, Cellular Microbiology and Infectiology.

He participated in four European projects: Heritability (1998-2001), Novacsal (1998-2002), Salarray 2000-2004), Supasalvac (2003-2008), two Network of excellence (Eadgene, 2005-2009; Eadgene-S (2009 – 2012)) and an Integrated Project SABRE (2006-2010). He coordinated the ANR project Genanimal "Resisal" (2006-2009) and 3 other National projects. He has participated to three Transnational Emida or Anihwa projects: Heathy gut (2010-2014), coordinated by P. Barrow (U. of Nottingham, UK), DIFAGH (2012-2015) coordinated by A. Smith (Oxford U., UK), AWAP (2016-2018) coordinated by M. Dawkins (Oxford U., UK), and one European FP7 project Prohealth coordinated by I. Kyriazakis (Newcastle University, UK).

Dr P. Velge has more than 90 articles published in books or in international journals (h-index of 24 in Scopus).

Partner 18-Tours: Dr. **Mustapha BERRI** (gender: M) received his PhD degree in Biochemistry in 1995 from the University of Blaise-Pascal of Clermont-Ferrand in France. He completed also a three years postdoctoral training at the University of Madison-Wisconsin in the USA in 1998, and joined the French National Institute of Agronomic Research as a biochemist to work at Lymphocytes and Mucosal Immunity laboratory previously directed by Dr. Henri Salmon. His scientific research interests involved the development and trafficking of immune cells within mucosal surfaces of pig as a model. He used cellular and molecular immunology approaches to characterize the basic mechanisms underlying the induction and dissemination of mucosal immune response between the respiratory, the gastrointestinal tracts and the mammary gland. His team have improved the scientific knowledge to elicit and enhance maternal lactogenic protection in sows to develop earlier active mucosal immunity in the neonate piglet in order to increase the animal's resistance at the weaning, and to decrease the use of antibiotics. His research is also focusing to study the cellular and molecular host/pathogen interactions in the pig model, and to test candidate vaccines or new potential therapeutic molecules such as probiotics, prebiotics or feed additives. He coordinated research programs funded by the French minister of agriculture and participated in several scientific projects including ANR-funded Sus-Flora and Piglet Biota. He is the author of 50 scientific publications and a co-inventor of 4 exclusive operating licences granted to private companies.

Partner 18-Jouy: Dr **Béatrice Laroche** (female, 57 years old) graduated from the Ecole Normale Supérieure and Paris 6 University in Applied Mathematics. After several years spent in R&D in industry and in university, she was appointed research director in the Applied Mathematics and Computer Science department at INRA in 2011 in the MaIAGE research unit of Jouy-en-Josas. She is the author of more than 40 articles in peer reviewed proceedings and journals. She is or has been involved in various collaborations based on epidemic as well as digestive physiology, system biology and gut microbiota modelling, in the framework of projects funded by INRA (gut metagenomic data integration through modelling), by the French National Research Agency (ANR AlimIntest 2007-2009 digestive physiology and microbiota modelling, CADENCE 2016-2019 epidemic modelling at landscape scale, WP leader in DALLISH, 2016-2019, modelling & system biology) and by the EU (COST Infogest, 2011-2015). She is currently a member of the coordination team of a national INRA program, "Holobionts and Microbial Flux within Agri-food Systems", focused on microbial communities in interaction with their host in agricultural systems.

Partner 1 ANSES: **Martine DENIS** (female, 52 years old, HDR), is Doctor in Biological Sciences from the university of Rennes, France. She is Deputy Head of the research unit "Hygiene and Quality of poultry and pork products" director of research project in pig production and responsible of the NRL of *Campylobacter*, at ANSES Laboratory from Ploufragan. The unit (30 peoples including 9 Scientifics) is National Reference laboratory for *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, avian salmonellosis and avian botulism, and develops its research activities for the Control of zoonotic bacterial agents through a multidisciplinary approach in the poultry and pig productions. The projects focus on *Campylobacter*,

Salmonella, *Yersinia*, *Listeria* and *Clostridium botulinum*. Her research activities are divided into three thematic areas : 1) Prevalence, risk factors and molecular epidemiology for obtaining data on prevalence, quantification, risk factors and genetic diversity along all the food chain, and tracking bacteria from reservoir, animal, to human (development of techniques for detection / numeration / typing (classical or molecular methods), 2) Host-pathogen relationship for a- obtaining knowledges on colonization of animals by bacteria, on the spread of bacteria between animals in link or not with the digestive microbiota, on the relationship of the pathogen with different matrices, b- characterizing the field strains and human strains by studying virulence mechanisms / phenotypic characteristics of the strains (development of animal models / methods for virulence and phenotypic characters), 3) Control measures at farm by reducing excretion of bacteria by animals under the action of molecules, feed or vaccination, at abattoir by reducing the spread of bacteria in slaughterhouse under the action of technological parameters (development of animal models / technological tools). She is the author of more than 50 scientific publications.

Annaëlle KEROUANTON (female, 44 years old) is project leader in the the research unit “Hygiene and Quality of poultry and pork products”. She received her PhD degree in life and health science in 1999. She is researcher at the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety since 2000. She has been currently involved in national research or European projects on foodborne pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *Listeria*). In the research unit “Hygiene and Quality of poultry and pork products”, she is in charge of research projects on foodborne zoonoses related to pigs. Current research interests include characterization of pig response to *Salmonella* infection.

Partner 6: NDRVMI, Prof. Dr **Hristo Yordanov DASKALOV**, PhD, DVM (Male, 61 years old); Head of NRL Salmonella, Campylobacter, Staphylococci and Antimicrobial Resistance; National Centre of Food Safety, NDRVMI, BFSa. Former Deputy President of AGRICULTURAL ACADEMY, BULGARIA, May 2015 – Present (1 year 10 months) Sofia, Bulgaria; Professor at National Center of Food Safety, NDRVI, BFSa, March 2013 – Present (8 years). Head of National Center of Food Safety of Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, Sofia, BULGARIA , December 2011 – Present.

Scientific projects – Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, UK, 1996-1998, Colorado State University, CO, Fort Collins, 2003; Bourlag Program, USDA, Colorado State University, CO, Fort Collins, 2006, EFFORT project, 7th frame scientific program EU, 2013-2018, One Health EJP, Horizon 2020, EU, 2018 – 2022.

Publications - https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=lx1_eWcAAAAJ&hl=en;

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hristo_Daskalov2

Partner 8: VRI, **Ivan Rychlik** (gender: M) graduated in 1989 at the Faculty of Science, Masaryk's University, Brno, Czech Republic. Since 1989 till presence he has been employed at the Veterinary Research Institute, Brno, Czech Republic where he has been a leader of *Salmonella* group since 2004. Currently this group consists of 15 people. He is an author or coauthor of more than 100 publications listed in Web of Science database with H-index 21. Current research interests include characterization of chicken response to *Salmonella* infection, design of live attenuated *Salmonella* vaccines for oral administration to chickens, analysis of composition and function of chicken gut microbiota, use of defined microbiota members for prevention of chicken colonization with *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* and chicken immune response to the inoculation with microbiota of different composition.

Partner 16: VISAVET-UCM ; **Lucas Dominguez** (gender: M) is a Doctor in Veterinary Medicine and Head of the VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre. He is full professor at Veterinary Medicine Degree at Complutense University of Madrid being involved as well in Master classes teaching. Throughout his career he has given over 400 lectures and participated in 20 books. At present, he has an index h of 37, 296 published articles having SCI cited over 5000 times. Most of his work has been included in high impact journals in the first quartile of the category of Microbiology and Veterinary Science. He has directed 22 doctoral theses, 7 of them with European Mention, and 6 PhD Extraordinary Award. He has been principal investigator of 47 research projects and has participated in other 30 projects. He has particular expertise in Foodborne Zoonoses and Antimicrobial Resistance, including *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E. coli*, *Yersinia* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Dr. Lucas Domínguez is in charge of several

lines of research on the characterization of important foodborne pathogens for Public Health and the mechanisms involved in the emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistance by using molecular techniques as well as sequencing.

María Ugarte-Ruiz (gender: F) is Doctor in Veterinary Medicine (2015) and Bachelor of Veterinary Medicine (2003-2008), University Complutense Madrid (UCM). Since 2009, she has been working at VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre and participated as Assistant teacher at Veterinary Medicine Degree at Complutense University of Madrid. She realized stays in the "London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine" and the "U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Ohio". She is responsible of the Foodborne Zoonoses and Resistance Antimicrobial Unit, which is focused on the study of Foodborne Zoonoses and Antimicrobial Resistance, including *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E. coli*, *Yersinia* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Her research resulting to date in eleven scientists articles, five of them as first author, as well as nine participations in international conferences. She is also co-authored the chapter of a book published by Springer.

Antonio Rodríguez Bertos (gender: M) is professor of the Veterinary Faculty since 1991, obtaining his PhD degree in Veterinary Pathology in 1994. He has published over 40 articles in the JCR and participated in over 20 research projects funded by private and public companies. He is currently Lecture Professor in the Department of Internal Medicine and Animal Surgery (Veterinary Faculty – Complutense University of Madrid). He has a wide knowledge designing experimental procedures to evaluate pathological alterations induced for different bacterial infections. His work as a veterinary technical expert in detection techniques in Spanish National Accreditation Body (ENAC) and EQA (Entity Management System Certification - ISO 9000 and ISO 14000 Environmental Verification) support its capacity as auditor evaluator. Recently, Dr. Rodriguez-Bertos has started a new research line in the spectrophotometry field in veterinary by using MALDI TOF Imaging, which could be applied as an useful tool in Healthy Gut studies.

Susana Gómez-Barrero (gender: F) is Doctor in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. Her career has been centered in Human Genetics, diagnosis and research in hereditary diseases. She has won a National research award on Darier-White disease, and has directed a doctoral Thesis of Medicine and Surgery. Since 2007, she has been working at VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre, involved in several lines of research based on molecular characterization of several zoonosis, mainly *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. She has contributed to the writing and performance of several research projects, she is co-author of several published articles and participated in a number of Congresses.

Partner 22: University of Surrey; **Prof Roberto Marcello La Ragione** (gender: M) is a specialist in veterinary microbiology and pathology with special interest in food-borne pathogens and antimicrobial resistance. After a PhD thesis at the government Veterinary Laboratories Agency (VLA) (1996-99), a post-doctoral position at Royal Holloway (University of London) (1999-2001), he was appointed as a Senior Scientist in the Department of bacterial diseases, VLA, Weybridge (2001-05). He was Head of pathogenesis and control at the AHVLA (2005-15) and after being Senior Lecturer in veterinary microbiology (2009-10), he was appointed Professor of Veterinary Microbiology and Pathology at the University of Surrey in 2010. He gained the FRCPath in 2010 and in 2012 was appointed the Associate Dean for Veterinary Strategy in the new School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey. He is the past president of the Med-Vet-Net Association and the Head of Pathology and Infectious Diseases and Deputy head of the School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey. He is the author of over 160 publications (h-index of 45).

Partner 27: ISS ; **Barbara Chirullo** (gender: F, PhD) is working at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità since 2010. as researcher at the unit Prophylaxis and Control of Bacterial Zoonoses, Department of Veterinary Public Health and Food Safety, Istituto Superiore di Sanità; Director.

As scientist she is currently involved in the study of the interface between pathogens and immune system as an approach to understand the pathogenicity of infection diseases and to develop new or more efficient vaccines to control infections. From 2019, she is part of the group of expert for the Italian Technical and scientific Committee for Nutrition and Animal Health, sections Veterinary

Medicine and Pharmacovigilance, on veterinary medicines, for scientific and technical evaluation on immunological products and, from 2020, of the Group of Experts no. 15V Veterinary vaccines and sera of European Pharmacopea.

Paolo Pasquali (gender: M, DVM, PhD) is working at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità since 2000. Director (2008-today), unit Prophylaxis and Control of Bacterial Zoonoses, Department of Veterinary Public Health and Food Safety, Istituto Superiore di Sanità; Director (2013-today), FAO Reference Centre for Veterinary Public Health, Istituto Superiore di Sanità.

As scientist he is currently involved in the study of the interface between pathogens and immune system as an approach to understand the pathogenicity of infection diseases and to develop new or more efficient vaccines to control infections. He authored or co-authored more than 70 research papers in peer reviewed journals and he is serving as editor in chief of the journal *Research in Veterinary Science*.

In the last few years he took part as coordinator or key person at several projects funded by national or international organizations

Partner 29: IZSLER ; **Alborali Giovanni Loris** (gender: M, DVM) is working in IZSLER since 1999 where he is the head of the department of diagnostic. He is spending the most part of time with porcine and bovine diagnostic, infection disease and health management. The mainly lines of research in which he has participated are the following: Antibiotic- resistance; monitoring program about principal bacterial diseases, with particular attention to the role of respiratory diseases (APP and *H. parasuis*) and enteric diseases (*Salmonella* spp. and *Brachyspira* spp.); Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome Virus (PRRSV); Aujeszky Disease Virus (ADV); disease associated with Porcine Circovirus 2 (PCV2), Swine Influenza Virus.

Partner 30: Wageningen Bioveterinary Research/Wageningen Research; **Thomas J. Hagenaars** (gender: M, PhD) (CVI, Wageningen UR, NL) is a mathematical epidemiologists working as a senior researcher and project leader in veterinary epidemiology group at the Central Veterinary Institute, part of Wageningen UR. He has more than 20 years of experience in research quantifying livestock disease spread using mathematical transmission models, and employing transmission models to assess the effectivity and/or risks of both preventive and reactive intervention strategies. In this research he has modelled the spread of wide variety of infectious agents in livestock and humans, including bacteria, viruses and agents causing transmissible spongiform encephalopathies. Most of this work was carried out to inform veterinary policy making, e.g. of the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs. Thomas combines attention to sound modelling with the ability to apply the modelling in a fashion relevant to the practical policy-making context. Much attention in his research is devoted to estimating model parameter values either from appropriate field data or from suitably designed experiments. Thomas is an Associate Editor of "BMC Veterinary Research".

Partner 32: NIPH; **Mohammed Umaer Naseer** (gender: M, PhD) completed a Philosophiae Doctor (PhD) degree in medical microbiology from the University of Tromsø in Norway (2009) building upon a Masters in Technology (Molecular Biotechnology) from the same institute in 2005. Expert on the molecular epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance. His postdoctoral research focused on the identification of virulence factors, mutation potentials and transfer mechanisms of resistance with emphasis on plasmid biology using whole genome sequencing tools. Since 2013 employed at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), now at the Department of Zoonotic, Food- and Waterborne Infections. In 2016 completed the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Controls (ECDC) two-year competency based training programme in public health microbiology (EUPHEM).

Partner 41: NCOH ; Prof **Mart C.M. de Jong** (male, 1957) is currently the chair of quantitative veterinary epidemiology at Wageningen University. His research interest is the quantification of transmission of infectious agents in animal populations and the effect of interventions on this transmission. His publications (2021: number of publications 210, h-index=43, citations: 5,984) are on stochastic/statistical models to quantify transmission from transmission experiments and observational data. Furthermore, most publications are about the application of these methods to

data on a large number of infectious agents important for animal husbandry or because they are zoonotic. For example the effects of vaccination on transmission of important OIE listed infections. Currently, the main line of research is on the role of the environmental phase of infectious agents on the transmission. He is an expert member of the official advisory board on animal disease control in the Netherlands.

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The **MOMIR-PPC project** aimed to develop new approaches to predict, identify and prevent the appearance of animal and human super-shedders based on immune response and gut microbiota composition. The vast majority of the planned objectives were achieved despite the many problems encountered during the project, and thanks to the time extension granted to us.

This project led to

- 1- Reproduce the heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection, characterized by the super- and low-shedder phenotypes in all the species studied (Human, pig, chicken mouse), beside the use of different infection models.
- 2- Original and interesting results, which allow better understanding of the heterogeneity of excretion and to predict and differentiate between these different shedding phenotypes. Moreover, the project allowed the development of original epidemic mathematical models and methods for data analysis.

Among the most important advances, we can highlight:

- **The key role of animal-animal recontaminations** in the spread of *Salmonella* infection at the flock level, which are mainly related to the presence of Super-Shedders, functioning as a reservoir for the pathogen. Our results, have shown that variation in the presence/absence of bacterial virulence cannot explain the super and low shedding phenotypes. However, in contrast, host factors and gut microbiota composition play a crucial role. For example, the gut microbiota composition before infection determines in chicks the super and low shedder phenotypes. Moreover, although the risk of human-to-human transmission of *Salmonella* from asymptomatic carriers is considered low, our study indicates a 10-fold higher rates (24%) of nontyphoidal *Salmonella* shedding than previously suggested.
- **The development of original mathematical models** of epidemics and methods of analyzing intra-animal transmission data. A mathematical model of indirect transmission of bacteria between broilers was also developed. The model can be used for designing and quantitatively assessing candidate bio-security based intervention strategies against indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*.
- **The identification of several control strategies** based on the importance of the ventilation in farms and the identification of the animals at risk. For that purpose, the MoMIR-PPC project identified several predictive biomarkers, based on gut microbiota composition and immune parameters. The identified biomarkers, which still need to be further confirmed, can either predict the levels of *Salmonella* shedding (in pigs or in chickens) if animals are infected, or can differentiate between the *Salmonella* shedding levels. We also identified the major factors associated with the long term shedding of *Salmonella* in humans.
- **The identification of several preventive measures based on the use of pre- and probiotics.** To prevent salmonellosis, we isolated, characterized and tested the efficacy of probiotics and prebiotics for use in pigs and poultry. The studies were undertaken in experimental infections and in field conditions. For example, we were tested the interventions in 72640 chicks in Bulgaria and 130 000 chicks in Czech Republic. These probiotics and prebiotics can be used as an alternative to antibiotics and may help reduce AMR. Samples were also taken from a number of challenge and intervention studies for metagenomic analysis. Finally, a draft inventory of relevant intervention measures against *Salmonella* in poultry has been developed and the cost effectiveness (utility) of intervention strategies using probiotics against *Campylobacter* has been calculated.

- These results have been or will be disseminated in Joint scientific articles and in congresses.

3 Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP0. Management

WP0-T1- Draft and agree Consortium Agreement

As consortium agreement was signed between the EJP coordinator ANSES and the EJP beneficiaries, we considered at the first MoMIR-PPC meeting that it was unnecessary to sign a particular consortium agreement at the MoMIR-PPC level (**Deliverable.0.2**).

WP0-T2- Produce project-planning, control documentation and Data Management Plan

The project planning has been modified several times due to the left of SAIM from the EJP consortium, and of the Vet-DTU, which has been closed by its Government. The work, which should be performed by these partners, has been taken into account by a new partner (NNDRVMI). We also modified the project planning of the Norwegian Institute of Public Health because Astrid Louise Wester left her institute. The final project planning was decided in June (month 6). The data management plan was updated several times during the project. A final version has been produced in Excel format (**Deliverable.0.1 ; D.4.2**).

WP3-T3- Control and manage activity progresses, the timely delivery of project tasks and outputs

Numerous exchanges have been performed to coordinate the work performed by the members. This has been done during the intermediate and final meetings and during video-conferences. Informal meeting were organized between few partners to exchange information, to define who will test what (especially concerning the pro and prebiotics, which were tested in farms) and to build joint articles. We discussed also how to store and exchange the bacterial strains developed in the project. Many experiments were postponed due to the COVID-19 crisis, which had an impact on the work of other Partners. This was managed through the extension of the project (**Deliverable.0.2**).

WP0-T4- Control and manage the project closure and outputs

The final meeting took place in video-conference on 10-11 May 2021. During this meeting, all partners presented their results, but they also provided the necessary information for the final report. All partners read, completed and validated the final report (**Deliverable.0.3**).

WP1. Risk prediction for Super-shedder animals and human asymptomatic carriers through the use of gut microbiota and immune status analyses (M1-M12)

The goal of this WP was to identify immunological and microbiota markers that are associated to super/low shedding before and/or after infection, which allow us to predict and identify the animals which will be Super shedders. For this WP, we used experimental infection models and also naturally infected animals and humans in “field condition”. Taking into account the great adaptability of pathogens for their hosts, the virulence and immunogenicity of *Salmonella* strains originated from Super- and low-shedders were compared.

WP1-T1- Predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

The goal of the task was to identify immune markers able to identify the super-Shedders and other able to predict the most susceptible animals and/or the animals that will become super-shedders, if infected. The activities focused on the most prevalent serotypes: *S. Typhimurium* for pig, and *S. Enteritidis* for chicken.

Four Partners were involved in this task (ANSES, ISS, IZLER and INRAE), which were done with pigs (ANSES, ISS, IZLER and INRAE), chickens (INRAE) and mice (ISS). A Post doc who, undertook her PhD in the ISS lab, was recruited by INRAE-Tours to manage part of the work devoted to SAIM.

The results obtained by **ISS** and **IZLER** showed in mice and pigs that IFN gamma gene expression (and protein level) correlates to *Salmonella* burden. Moreover, a higher INF-gamma production increases the ability of animals to control infection. In contrast, a specific pro-inflammatory response and stimulation of inflammation pathways is predictive of super-shedder phenotype (**Deliverable.1.1**).

ANSES performed a trial with a total of 45 piglets divided into five groups: one group with five piglets as control and four groups each with 10 piglets (n=40) as inoculated pigs. At 7 weeks of age, piglets were infected with 10^9 CFU/piglets of a monophasic variant of *Salmonella* Typhimurium strain. Pigs were followed during 3 weeks after inoculation before being necropsied. The level of *Salmonella* shedding allowed us to identify three significantly different classes ($p < 0,01$) corresponding to high (n=13), intermediate (n=16) and low shedders (n=11) pigs. Regarding the blood cell number, 12 parameters showed a significant difference (p -value $< 0,05$) between inoculated pigs and controls, at one or several days after infection, most of them were white cells. The difference was also confirmed to be also significant between super- and low-shedders for 5 parameters, Lymphocytes, basophile, Granulocytes, and Haematocrite). Quantification of TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6 and IFN- γ , showed that a significant difference ($p < 0,01$) was observed on the median production level between super- and low-shedders for IL1- β and IL6 at 1DPI (**Deliverable.1.3 ; D.1.7**). As in part observed in chicks, Low shedders pigs seroconverted earlier than intermediate and high shedders pigs (**Deliverable.2.11**). The results obtained by **ANSES** and **INRAE** suggested that the expression of one immune related gene could be a predictive biomarkers (**Deliverable.1.6**). The expression of several host genes could be biomarkers able to characterize the low- and super-shedder phenotypes. Moreover, a strong pro-inflammatory immune response is correlated to the super-shedder phenotype. This is counter-intuitive but could be explained by the articles describing that *Salmonella* requires intestinal inflammation to sustain its replication in the intestinal tract. Indeed, intestinal inflammation leads to availability of nutrients that are otherwise not accessible in the uninflamed gut and to a better competition with the resident microbiota by creating microaerophilic conditions.

The results obtained from the chick studies performed by **INRAE** showed that the number of blood immune cells circulating in the blood could not be used as a predictive marker for the appearance of the low and super-shedder phenotypes (**Deliverable.1.6**). Moreover, the analysis has shown no differences, after infection, when low and super-shedders are compared with the control group. Similarly, to identify predictive immunological markers associated to high and low shedders, we analysed the differences of the humoral immune response of low and high-shedders and compared their response to non-infected chicks by measuring the production of total (non-specific) IgA, IgY, IgM before and after infection. Generally, the analysis has revealed that the total antibody responses follow a classical pattern with a rise in levels of total IgM preceding the rise in IgY. The total immunoglobulin response was low before infection and increase after infection. Moreover, no significant differences were observed between naïve/low shedders and high shedders. This result shows that level of immunoglobulin cannot be a predictive marker for low shedders and high shedders. Interestingly, a statistically significant increase in IgY level has been observed at 7 days post infection in high-shedders when compared with low-shedders and control groups. Finally, the evaluation of anti-*Salmonella* LPS IgA levels has revealed a lack of response in all the samples analyzed except for two of them, suggesting that anti-*Salmonella* IgA response is not a good candidate to investigate differences between low-shedders and high-shedders in contrast to total IgM response (**Deliverable.1.6 ; D1.7 ; 2.11**). This work had been performed in collaboration with the Bernd Kaspers's lab (U. Munich), **during a short stay, funded by EJP**.

In the same way, the immuno-histological work performed by **VISAVET-UCM** on caecal samples did not show any major histopathological changes between low and super-shedders. In contrast, the inoculation of four commensal bacteria the day of hatch, and which protect chicks from *Salmonella* infection (see WP2), modified both the number of immune cells circulating in the blood during *Salmonella* infection and the host immune response to the pathogen (**Deliverable.2.6**).

WP1-T2- Predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

The goal of the task was to analyse the gut microbiota composition before and after *Salmonella* infection to identify predictive microbiota markers associated to the super and low shedders in chickens and pigs. Samples from representative pigs and chickens originated from activities of task 1.1 were analyzed based on Illumina sequencing of V3/V4 variable region of 16S rRNA genes. The same experiments were used to analyse both the immune response and the gut microbiota composition.

Four Partners (ANSES, ISS, IZLER and INRAE) were involved in this task for the animal experiments performed with pigs and chicks. UoS sequenced all samples from pigs while VRI sequenced all samples from chicks. Sequencing data were analyzed by UoS, VRI and INRAE.

The work performed by INRAE and VRI with chicks demonstrated the role of gut microbiota in the susceptibility to *S. Enteritidis* infection and in the appearance of the low and super-shedder phenotypes. We especially demonstrated that (1) axenic and antibiotic-treated chicks are more prone to become super-shedders; (2) super or low-shedder phenotypes can be acquired through microbiota transfer; (3) specific gut microbiota taxonomic features determine whether the chicks develop a low- and super-shedder phenotype after *Salmonella* infection in isolator Figure 1 (Deliverable.1.8). It has been especially described that presence of *Enterococcus* could be a predictive markers of low *Salmonella* susceptibility (Deliverable.1.9; 1.10). This study demonstrates the key role plays by gut microbiota composition in the heterogeneity of infection and the possibility to increase resistance to *Salmonella* colonization with pro and prebiotics (see WP2). An article describing this work has been accepted for publication in Microbial Biotechnol.

Figure 1: PCA analysis of the genus frequencies observed before infection (i.e. at 5 and 7 days of age), in order to highlight predictive markers among the three shedding level categories (Low (resistant), intermediate and high (super) shedder phenotypes). Chicks were orally infected at 7 days of age and fecal samples were recovered before and after *Salmonella* infection. Gut microbiota composition was analyzed by 16S rDNA sequencing.

For pigs, ANSES, UoS and INRAE showed that numerous taxa are specific to the low and super-shedder phenotypes (Deliverable.1.9; 1.10). A Co-inertia analysis between the immune genes dCt and microbiota features abundances, conducted at INRAE did not show a correlation between the gut microbiota composition and immune gene expression (Deliverable.1.15). A joint article is in preparation.

Similarly, ISS and IZLER performed experiments in pigs and sent the samples to UoS for microbial community analysis. The samples have been analysed in conjunction with metadata related to the animal's overall health and shedding status, to test the hypotheses regarding the association of the gut microbiome with *Salmonella* shedding status. No clear correlation was observed (Deliverable.1.9 ; 1.10). However, It should be noted that both studies were carried out using pigs with different genetic

backgrounds and *Salmonella* strains, therefore this created an opportunity to test the association between the microbiome and *Salmonella* shedding in two different scenarios.

WP1-T3- Risk factors associated with prolonged convalescent *Salmonella* shedding in humans
FHI driven this Task.

The goal of the task was to investigate the risks factors associated with chronic *Salmonella* infection in human population. This Task was managed by NIPH. A cohort study was carried out on all nonthypoidal- (NT) salmonellosis cases registered in the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS). All potential participants were asked to send a stool sample and to respond to an online/paper questionnaire to collect information. Stool samples were processed at NIPH for *Salmonella* growth. Participants with long-term shedding (stool samples positive for *Salmonella* growth by direct culture approximately 5 weeks post infection) were compared to participants with short-term shedding of *Salmonella* (stool samples negative for *Salmonella* growth by direct culture approximately 5 weeks post infection) in order to identify associated factors with long-term shedding. (**Deliverable.1.11**).

Figure 2: Process describing collection of data

Furthermore, all initial *Salmonella* isolates submitted to NRL were serotyped, screened for antibiotic susceptibility and whole genome sequenced (Illumina) (Deliverable.1.12). The analysis of host risk factors associated with long-term shedding shows that the percentage of long-term shedders is higher (25%) than previously reported (1-2.2 %) (Gal-Mor O. Clin Microbiol Rev. 2018;32(1):e00088-18). Moreover, NIPH identified the main risk factors to become long term shedders (Deliverable.1.12):

- Younger people are *more at risk* (OR 3.5, 95%CI 1.05- 11.56)
- A lactose free diet (OR 5.19, 95%CI 1,21 - 22,31)
- Taking regular medication (OR 2.51, 95%CI 1,42 - 4,41)
- Taking food supplements, vitamins and health foods (OR 2.45, 95% CI 1,09 - 5,49)

No specific pathogen characteristic was identified: no association was found between serotype, sequence or Complex type and long-term shedding. The association with Fosfomycin resistance is tentative due to the small sample size. In conclusion, these results suggested that long term shedding seems more dependent of host factors than pathogen characteristics (**Deliverable.1.5**).

Recent studies indicate that transmission of *Salmonella* is controlled by indigenous intestinal microbiota. We had planned to select pairs of cases (Long-term shedders and Short-term shedders) that shared pathogen or host specific characteristics, with the aim to analyze the host microbiota. However, due to the shortening of the sample collection period, the sample size was considerably reduced and we were unable to perform analytical statistical analysis. The findings are based on univariable and descriptive analysis, and as result, the scientific merit of completing metagenomics is compromised. As our assessment was that metagenomic analyses of fecal samples would not add weight to our descriptive findings, we have therefore concluded that more data is needed to

substantiate the associations that have been uncovered in our study before metagenomics will add scientific value.

WP1-T4- Virulence of Salmonella strains originated from high and low shedders

The goal of the task was to determine whether the super and low-shedder phenotypes could be related to a modification of the virulence level of the *Salmonella* strains during infection.

In vitro virulence of *S. Typhimurium* and *S. Enteritidis* strains collected from super-shedders and low-shedders pigs (ANSES) and chickens (INRAE) were evaluated by INRAE in pig and chicken epithelial and macrophage cell lines.

Salmonella strains from two super-shedders and two low-shedders animals were used in each experiment in comparison with the strain, which was inoculated. INRAE evaluated *Salmonella* adhesion, invasion and intracellular multiplication to an intestinal pig epithelial cell line (IPEC-1) and a pig macrophage cell line (3D4) as well as with a chicken epithelial cell line (LMH). No differences were observed between *Salmonella* strains, whatever the serotype, for any of the parameters evaluated (Deliverable.1.5). In addition, the gene expression of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory genes was evaluated. No differences were observed in the gene expression of CXCL8, IL8 or TGF β for any of the conditions evaluated. In conclusion, our data do not show any alteration in the *in vitro* virulence of *Salmonella* strains from super-shedder and low-shedder origin (Deliverable.1.14). These results strongly suggested that the super-shedder and low-shedder phenotypes are not related to a modification of the virulence level of the bacterial strains. These results are in line with those obtained in human (Deliverable.1.15).

WP2. Prevention of the appearance of Super-shedder animals and asymptomatic carriage in humans and animals by modifying feed and/or microbiota (M1-M12)

The goal of this WP was focused on the development of preventive and control measures. We tested especially the protective activity of pre-biotics, pro-biotics or nutraceutical formula and assess their effects on immune response, gut microbiota composition, gut physiology and animal performance.

WP2-T1- Development and use of probiotics in chickens and pigs

In this Task, we identified and characterized probiotics and tested their protective effect in pigs and chickens.

Four Partners were involved in this task (VRI, UoS, NDRVMI and INRAE), which were done with pigs and chickens in field and experimental conditions.

VRI has developed an extensive library of commensal bacteria from chicken gut, which currently consists of more than 450 isolates with known genomic sequences (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/study/?acc=SRP101913&o=acc_s%3Aa). These strains were used for oral inoculation of chicks on the day of hatching followed by verification of their presence 7 days later. The conclusion is that in this type of experimental design, bacterial species expressing outer membrane, i.e. Bacteroidetes, Proteobacteria and Veillonellaceae, can efficiently and persistently colonise chicken caeca. Rather unexpectedly, they never succeeded with the colonisation of newly hatched chicks with Gram positive bacteria from phylum Firmicutes and families Lachnospiraceae, Ruminococcaceae or Lactobacillaceae, despite the fact that these species are common microbiota members. Recently VRI changed the protocol for culture of gut anaerobes and this seems to provide novel opportunities for culture of yet unculturable species. This modification consisted of culture under microaerophilic conditions and using Karmali agar. Several experiments have been performed to understand 1- why the inoculation of Lachnospiraceae, Ruminococcaceae or Lactobacillaceae which are otherwise common in gut microbiota on chickens 1 to 2 weeks old, were unable to colonise chicks after oral inoculation and 2- the origin of these bacteria in the caeca of chickens.

Other experiments were performed to determine whether the colonisation of chicken intestine with some strains modified on the long term the faecal and/or caecal microbiota composition. For this

purpose defined mixtures consisting of bacterial species which can colonise chicken caecum after a single dose on day of hatch were gradually tested in real commercial farms. Altogether, over 130 000 chickens were treated with different mixtures consisting mainly of different *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella* and *Megamonas* species. Due to the financial scopes, these experiments were co-funded also by other projects of VRI. Central issue when upscaling from laboratory to field level was the administration of chicken gut anaerobes to flocks consisting of more than 10, 000 chickens. This was done via drinking water, resuspension of liquid cultures to pre-starter feed, jellyfying liquid probiotic cultures before their spread over the pre-starter feed or even feed fermentation by the probiotic strains. The control of gut colonisation showed that tested probiotic strains persist in the caeca of treated broilers till day 35 of life. Moreover, since some of the flocks were formed by reproductive birds, bacterial species were detected in these flocks till week 20 of their life. Thus, the persistence of selected and tested species seemed to be quite long if not permanent (Deliverable.2.3; D.2.6; D2.5).

UoS isolated a large panel of potential probiotic candidates from pig faeces. Following identification by 16s and basic *in vitro* characterisation a subpanel was selected for further study. A panel of 30 lactobacilli were phenotypically and genotypically characterised. These studies included growth curves, survival in acid/bile, whole genome sequencing and tissue culture studies (pig cell line) to determine safety and inhibitory ability of whole cells and CFS against *Salmonella* adhesion/invasion (ongoing). To date the studies have indicated that a number of strains are suitable probiotics that meet the EFSA requirements. Four probiotic strains (2 isolated from chicken faeces in a related project) and 2 isolated from pig) were sent to Bulgaria (NDRVMI) for efficacy evaluation in chickens and pigs, respectively (Deliverable.2.3; D.2.6). If required, strain will also be shared with the EU AVANT H2020 project."

NDRVMI has analysed the effect in field conditions of several probiotics and prebiotics obtained from the UoS. They used 4 groups of day-old broilers (18,160 in each group). In groups with probiotics 1 and 2, the birds were raised without antibiotics, as well as any other side effects. Growth rates and food consumption were also excellent and mortality was a little lower than in the control group (where antibiotics were still used). In the third experimental group, where probiotics 1 and 2 were used and a prebiotic was added to stimulate probiotic microorganisms, there were some issues in the middle of the experiment with a sharp increase in mortality observed, this was due to the presence of a pathogenic strain of *E. coli* and for 5 days they were treated with an antibiotic after which the mixture of probiotic 1 and 2 and prebiotic were delivered until the time of slaughter. This group was not a linear hybrid Ross like the other groups, but a linear hybrid Cobb, which appeared to be much more susceptible to disease. The experiment was repeated only with this compromised third group and the control, as the linear hybrid was Ross. Probiotics were used on farms with a long history of *Salmonella* infection and periodic treatment with antibiotics allows the birds to be free of *salmonella* at the time of slaughter. It is noteworthy that *Salmonella* were not detected only in group with probiotic 1, which leads us to think that probiotic 1 has a more pronounced anti-*Salmonella* effect in the gastrointestinal tract. However, the combination of the two probiotics did not result in the elimination of *S. Infantis* throughout the growing period (Deliverable.2.5; D.2.7). Moreover, in the group with both probiotics and prebiotic a reduced incidence of intestinal disorders and better food conversion ratios was observed compared to the control group (Deliverable.2.5; D.2.6 ; D.2.7).

The experiments with pigs started on September 2020, when 3 experimental groups of weaned pigs were formed, 25 in a group and transferred to individual boxes without a connection between boxes. An additional group of pigs of the same age, reared conventionally (in the same way as those receiving the intervention) on the farm, were used as controls. The pigs in all four experimental groups received the same feed etc., with the only difference being the respective probiotic or a mixture of the two probiotics tested with the addition of prebiotic fed through the drinking water. Particular attention was paid to the safety of supplying a sufficient amount of water containing at least one billion living cells in a milliliter of broth culture dissolved in drinking water. It should be noted that treatment of pigs with *Lactobacillus reuteri* SAP 3319 or a combination of both probiotics and a prebiotic resulted in a reduced incidence of intestinal disorders and the absence of *Salmonella* in the faeces (Deliverable.2.5 ; D.2.6 ; D.2.7).

After completion of the experiment with the broilers and the pigs, all samples were sent to the **UoS** for 16s microbial community analysis, which is ongoing (**Deliverable.2.8 ; D.2.9**).

In WP1 **INRAE** identified *Enterococcus faecium* as a predictive biomarker for the most resistant phenotype. To test the protective activity of this commensal bacteria against *Salmonella* colonization, a candidate *E. faecium* strain was isolated, purified and orally inoculated to a group of 30 chicks reared in a large isolator (CFU=1x10⁹ per chick) at 1 and 6 days of age (i.e. before *Salmonella* infection) (**Deliverable.2.3**). However, no significant difference was observed between the *Salmonella* shedding levels of the *E. faecium*-inoculated and control groups (at any time point). To go further we tested the impact of four commensal bacteria containing *E. Faecium* but also *E. coli*, *Lactobacillus* and *Clostridium* strains. When administrated the day of hatching, this cocktail induced a partial protection against *Salmonella* infection at 7 days of age (**Deliverable.2.5**). The data obtained shows the protective effect of the four commensal bacteria on *Salmonella* excretion and their major impact, on the long term, on gut microbiota composition and immune response. This study paved the way for developing a protective mix of probiotics. An article describing this work has been accepted for publication in Microbial Biotechnol. The impact of the four commensal bacteria on the gut microbiota composition and the immune response was done by **INRAE** with a 16S metabarcoding approach in collaboration with **VRI** and with the Biomark approach. One publication is in preparation (**Deliverable.2.5; D.2.6 ; D.2.10**).

WP2-T2- Use of pre-biotics and nutraceutical already defined by the consortium partners in chicken and pig

The goal of this Task is to measure the effect of several pre-biotics and nutraceuticals on intestinal barrier, gut microbiota composition and protection against pathogens in farms and in experimental conditions.

Mainly three Partners (**VRI, VISAVET-UCM and NDRVMI**) were involved in this task, which was undertaken with pigs and chickens in field and experimental conditions.

To identify bacterial species, which are dependent on particular supplements or growth substrates, **VRI** tested specific supplementation of nutrient broths used for growth of commensal strains. At the beginning of the experiment, caecal contents of adult hen are decimally diluted and inoculated to nutrient broth. Nutrient broths are then anaerobically incubated and after 3 days, microbiota composition is determined by 16S rRNA sequencing. WCHA agar and BHI medium supplemented with lactate, glucose, starch, cellulose, mucin, bile salts, panthenol, biotin, vitamin B12 or whole vitamin B complex were tested. In addition, in the last experiment **VRI** inoculated BHI supplemented with sodium acetate, propionate, lactate, succinate, pyruvate, fumarate, ascorbate, glucose, maltose, saccharose, trehalose, fucose, rhamnose, pectin and inulin. These experiments allowed us to i) determine metabolic potential of individual gut microbiota members, ii) define conditions under which it had been possible to enrich target gut anaerobes and obtain them in pure cultures (see WP2-T1) and iii) map characteristics of different supplements which can be used as prebiotics (**Deliverable.2.6**).

VISAVET-UCM tested the protective effect of fermented defatted “alperujo” against *Salmonella* infection in chickens. The objective of these experiments was to analyze the modification of the microbiota and intestinal mucosa changes before and after the challenging, comparing treated and control groups.

The first experiments performed with laying hens demonstrated the positive effect of fermented defatted “alperujo”. Indeed, a significant increase of duodenal villi height and crypt depth (duodenum and cecum) was observed in the treated group at early life stages. A higher abundance of Actinobacteria, Firmicutes and Proteobacteria was also assessed in the treated group at early life stages as well as decreased number of broken eggs in the treated group (**Deliverable.2.6**).

A second experiment performed with broilers leads to similar conclusion. Significant increase of duodenal villi height was observed in the treated group from 14 to 35 days-old, as well as significant body weight increase at 35 days-old. Fermented defatted “alperujo” consumption also favours

microbiota modulation, that may control the spread of pathogenic bacteria by means of competitive exclusion.

Several experiments have demonstrated, *in vitro*, the effect of “alperujo” on *Salmonella*. To test its effect *in vivo*, chicks were divided in two groups: one that was fed with conventional feed and a second one that was fed with “alperujo” since their arrival. After a week of adaptation, animals were challenged with a *Salmonella* strain resistant to colistin. Besides, a subgroup of animals was challenged after 21 days consuming the “alperujo”. The analysis of the data shows a significant reduction of *Salmonella* in the cecum, with both traditional culture and qPCR approaches, at 7 and 14 dpi. However, no significant differences were observed at 21, 28, and 35 dpi (28, 35, and 42 days old, respectively) in the cecal *Salmonella* load among groups by culture ($p > 0.05$) or by qPCR ($p > 0.05$) (see Figure) (**Deliverable.2.7**).

Figure 1. Results of the *Salmonella* spp. count in selective agar in broilers challenged with *Salmonella* Typhimurium at day 7 (purple lines) and day 21 (red lines) of life. Continuous lines represent control groups, whereas discontinuous lines represent treated groups, fed with fermented defatted ‘alperujo’. The *Salmonella* spp. count by culture (CFU/g) is shown on the vertical axis, and samplings (7, 14, 21, 35, or 42) on the horizontal axis.

The intestinal histopathology measures revealed only few differences in the duodenum between the control and the treated group. In the caeca, there was a reduction in the intensity of lamina propria lymphocytic infiltration and GALT hyperplasia in the treated group compared to the control group. In 7-day-old challenged chickens, duodenum villi height was significantly improved in treated chickens on days 7, 14, 28, 35, and 42 ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the crypts in the duodenum were deeper in all treated samplings ($p < 0.05$). Regarding ceca morphology, crypts were seen to be deeper in 7-, 21- and 42-day-old treated chickens ($p < 0.05$) but not at 28 days of life. Broilers in the treated group challenged at 21 days of age showed a significant improvement in the duodenum villi height at 28, 35, and 42 days of life ($p < 0.05$). The depth of the crypts in the duodenum was significantly improved by the treatment on days 28 and 42 ($p < 0.05$). The ceecal crypt was deeper in treated chickens on days 35 and 42 of life ($p < 0.05$).

Treatment with fermented defatted “alperujo” has no significant impact on caecal microbiota (**Deliverable.2.8**). In chickens challenged at 7 or at 21 days of age, there were no statistically-significant differences among the groups established.

WP3. Modelling the transmission of zoonotic agents to improve intervention strategies on livestock farms (M1-M12)

The third WP was focused on the development of multiscale computational models (from within-host to between-host scale) of heterogeneous pathogen transmission by integrating data from WP1 and 2 and already available datasets by consortium partners in order to design and assess intervention strategies. The models was designed to allow assessment of the efficiency and/or cost-effectiveness of different intervention strategies.

WP3-T1- Transmission modelling at within-host and between-host scales

The goal of the task was to develop simplified, but relevant models of the host including key features of the gut microbiota dynamics and key features of the immune system response.

Three partners (NCOH-WU, INRA-Jouy, WUR-WBVR) were involved in this Task with fruitful discussion with the other partners.

WP3-T1-ST1- Within-host scale: modelling individual responses and shedding

INRAE-Jouy designed a generic mathematical model of the dynamic interplay between the gut microbiota, the pathogen and the host's immune response at the within and between-host scale. A paper has been published (**Deliverable.3.1**).

To improve the model with a better representation of the microbiota and pathogen dynamic, **INRAE-Jouy** completed the realization of a C++ software and the corresponding Matlab and R plugins allowing to analyse time series of microbial concentrations. This software implements a non parametric, robust inference approach for fitting Generalized Lotka-Volterra_model on time series data. It will be made publicly available in a near future on INRAE gitlab repository (<https://forgemia.inra.fr/>), a publication is currently being written.

The model was used to analyze a first set of time series of gut microbiota composition in chicken (with **INRAE-Tours** and **VRI**) in order to infer interactions between the pathogen (here *Salmonella*) and the resident microbiota. However, the results were not satisfactory because the time series were very short. In collaboration with **UoS** and **INRAE-Tours** we recently started analysing longer microbiota time series from WP1 (ANSES pig experiment) with this software, together with other data analysis approaches, to better understand and model the interplay between of the immune response and the microbiota. To conclude, this task allowed the development of original epidemic models and methods for data analysis. However, the opportunity to work on the pig data came very late in the course of the project, so we will be able to provide an output on data analysis only close or after the end of the project.

WP3-T1-ST2- Between-host scale: modelling transmission, linked to within-host results

Mathematical modelling analyses were carried out of the outcomes of tailor-made experiments studying the indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* between broilers. In previous research also consisting of a combination of experiments and mathematical modelling, a mathematical model of indirect transmission of bacteria between broilers was developed. This model assumes that bacteria are transferred from inoculated animals (source animals) to spatially separated susceptible animals (recipient animals) through random displacement of infectious material in the environment in combination with a loss of viability of the bacteria in time. Technically this model uses diffusion equations to describe the random displacement of material in the environment between the source and recipient animals. New experiments carried out during the MOMIR-PPC project served to validate and refine this mathematical model by testing predictions in an experimental setting, and to do so consisted of four different spatial setups that were each studied in two repeat animal rooms. . The refined model can be used for designing and quantitatively assessing candidate bio-security based intervention strategies against indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* (Deliverable.3.2).

This model not only allows to test biosecurity/hygiene measures, but also offers desired biological insight. In particular it explains the distance-dependence of the indirect transmission rate observed in the experiments, as well as an observed distance-dependent time delay of transmission. The model does so using only three parameters: 1) a 'loss-of-viability' rate describing how fast the pathogen is becoming inactivated in the environment; 2) a diffusion coefficient describing how the spatial distribution of infectious material in the environment changes in time; 3) a transmission parameter summarizing host-dependent processes (shedding and dose response). As a consequence, the model enables to quantify processes occurring in the environment separately from host-dependent processes.

WP3-T2- Interventions strategies: Identification and evaluation tools

The goal of the task was to include the different other intervention strategies with those described in WP3-T1. Three partners (WUR-WLR, WUR-WEcR and INRAE) were involved in this Task.

WP3-T2-ST1- Systematic inventory of relevant intervention measures

A systematic inventory of relevant intervention measures against *Salmonella* in broilers and laying hens has been developed.

WP3-T2-ST2- Inclusion of potential interventions into the modelling

At within-host scale, **INRAE-Jouy** obtained first encouraging results on the use of microbiota and inflammatory response data in **ANSES** pig experiment to discriminate pigs according to their shedding pattern, in collaboration with **UoS** and **INRAE-Tours**. A publication is currently started. The resulting knowledge, as well as knowledge from probiotic strategies in WP2 will be used in the future to include probiotic based strategies in the model developed in WP3-T1-ST1.

WP3-T2-ST3- Development of economic analysis tools

The economic analysis tools allow to evaluate the cost effectiveness (utility) of intervention strategies using probiotics to reduce *Campylobacter* prevalence in broilers. The work performed by WUR WEcR has been done with results of other MOMIR-PPC work packages and model developed in CamCon1) (EU 7th framework programme). The tools determine the cost per averted disease burden (in €/Disability-Adjusted Life Year, DALY), by taking into account the attribution of DALY's to broiler sector, and correcting for import/export. The cost-utility is obtained by calculating the cost per averted disease burden as a function of the on-farm efficacy. The model has been parameterized for four different European countries (Denmark, Netherlands, Poland, Spain) spanning a range of differently structured poultry sectors: taking into account differences in technical and economic farm performance, and scale of poultry production. A scientific paper has been published (**Deliverable.3.3 ; D.3.5 ; D.3.6**). The main results obtained with the model suggested:

- Assuming an efficacy between 10% and 20%, costs per avoided DALY were lowest in Poland and Spain (4,000–30,000 Euro per avoided DALY) and highest in the Netherlands and Denmark (70,000–340,000 Euro per avoided DALY)
- In Poland and Spain, using probiotics is a moderately expensive intervention if efficacy is more than 10%, otherwise it is relatively expensive
- In the Netherlands and Denmark, using probiotics is a relatively expensive intervention irrespective of efficacy
- However, if probiotics were assumed to enhance broiler performance, the intervention would become relatively cost-effective even at low efficacy levels of 1 to 10%.

WP4. Communication and Dissemination for Impact (M1-M12)

WP4-T1- Dissemination of data within the project and management of data

Participation to the One Health EJP-ASM conferences in Dublin (2019) and to the virtual conferences (2020 and 2021) with several posters and conferences.

As described in the report, Partners have exchanged for analysis numerous samples and thus the corresponding data from animal experiments. A synthetic Excel file summarized the animal experiments as well as the samples recovered (**Deliverable.4.3**). UoS and VRI have sequenced the samples from pigs and chickens, respectively. UoS, INRAE-Tours and VRI Have analyzed the data and thus the gut microbiota composition of the different samples. VISAVET-UCM has performed histological analyses, INRAE-Tours has performed virulence assays with strains recovered by other Partners. INRAE-Tours and ISS have performed immune responses analyses. UoS, IZLER and ISS have sequenced and analyzed the data and thus the gut microbiota composition of the different samples.

IZLER and NDRVMI have performed field experiments with strains of UoS. Data obtained by other Partners during experimental infections have been sent to INRAE-Jouy and to U. Wageningen. Consequently, an impressive collaboration has made it possible to analyze many parameters of the in vivo experiments performed with pigs and chickens.

WP4-T2- Dissemination of data outside the project and management of data

Participation to several congresses outside the EJP. Several articles have been accepted for publication in open access journals (**Deliverable.4.4**). These articles often involved two or more partners. Several joint articles are in preparation. Due to the Covid19 crisis the high strategic meeting has been cancelled and the budget devoted to this activity has been reimburse to EJP (INRAE) and (NCOH)). After the international lockdown, we will disseminate our results in international congresses and to stakeholders (**Deliverable.4.5**).

4 Project self-assessment

The vast majority of the planned objectives are achieved despite the many problems encountered during the project, and thanks to the time extension granted to us.

An **exceptional extension of 12 months** of the project at no extra expense has been indeed obtained by the EJP Project Management Team. This extension was motivated by:

- The withdrawal of SAIM from the EJP consortium after the approval of our project. Part of the work has been performed by INRAE with the help of a Post doctorant.
- Astrid-Louise Webster has left the NIPH, just before the beginning of the project, so that we have adapted the project with Anke-Stüken. These modifications have delayed the ethics committee approvals, resulting of one year delay in the human experiments, but the majority of the aims have been achieved.
- The fact that after the beginning of the project, Vet-DTU has been closed by its Government. To compensate for this loss, we looked for new partners in the EJP consortium and in June 2018 (6 months after the beginning of the project), H. Daskalov (NDRVMI) has joined our consortium. Consequently, part of the work related to WP2 has been delayed by one year.
- Finally, several partners had had difficulties to obtain the ethics committee approval for animal experiments, which has also delayed some experiments.

Moreover, a supplementary **6 months extension**, in addition to our previously 1 year extension has been obtained because some partners have been highly impacted by the COVID-19 crisis. Indeed, several experiments had been cancelled or postponed (especially those with humans and in field conditions) due to the lockdown. Finally, the cancellation of all the meetings has led us to cancel the high strategic meeting with stakeholders (the money was returned). **This project led to:**

- Reproduce the different shedding patterns in all the animal species and with all the models developed.
- -Original and interesting results, which allow better understanding of the heterogeneity of excretion and to predict and differentiate between these different shedding phenotypes. These results have been or will be published in international scientific journals and at One Health EJP ASM congresses (1st, 2nd, 3rd ed.). The project allowed the development of original epidemic mathematical models and methods for data analysis.
- Important and fruitful exchanges, where one partner analyzed the samples from another partner and which led to joint articles. Moreover, the exchanges between experimental scientists and mathematicians offers a great opportunity to test our methods on very complete datasets.

Several difficulties have been detected regarding the variability of the gut microbiota composition of chicks from one experiment to another, which raises the question of how can we standardise or normalise the gut microbiota of farm animals? Another observation has been that analysis of immune response in blood of chicks seems less relevant than the mucosal immune response (this is not true for pigs).

Several interesting results have been obtained from a One Health perspective, but as different protocols and methods were used in pigs, chickens and humans, it has been difficult to generalize the results obtained in humans to farm animals and vice versa.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D.0.1	Project initiation, Kick off meeting, Project-planning and management documentation	2	2		https://zenodo.org/record/5079519#.YOWoQzNxdPY	
10	D.0.2	Approved and signed Consortium Agreement	6	1		This has been done at the EJP level	
10	D.0.3	Minutes of project meetings (Kick off, midterm and final meeting)	2, 13, 24	2, 24, 41		https://zenodo.org/record/3685528#.XIOVuWhKiUk	report
10	D.0.4	Financial and scientific reports for the EJP Coordinator (Intermediated report)	12, 24	12, 24, 36, 42		https://zenodo.org/record/3685530#.XIOV_WhKiUk	report
10	D-1.1	Panel of immunological markers to assess in pig and chicken	3	6		https://zenodo.org/record/5082034#.YOblwzNxdPY	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-1.2	Development of the immune-signature chips	12			This deliverable has been cancelled due to the left of SAIM at the beginning of the project (see new version of June 2018).	
10	D-1.3	Identification of risk factors for shedding of <i>Salmonella</i> in pigs and poultry farms	12	41		https://zenodo.org/record/5081949#.YObAjjNxdPY Another article is in preparation	5
10	D-1.4	Identification and purification of commensal bacteria present before <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in low shedders (first round)	12	36		https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc	3
10	D-1.4	Identification and purification of commensal bacteria present before <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in low shedders (second round)	20	41		https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc	3
10	In AWP2021 : D-1.04	<i>In vitro</i> virulence levels of different	36	41		this deliverable has been merged with D-JRP10-1.5 Confidential	8 report

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		<i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (first round)					
10	D-1.5	<i>In vitro</i> virulence levels of different <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (second round)	36	41		https://zenodo.org/record/5082103#.YObSKTNxdPY CO: until the publication. Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo Joint publication is in preparation with ANSES, UoS and INRAE (in AWP2021 : D-1.05)	8 report
10	D-1.6	Definition of predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	20, 34	36		this deliverable has been merged with D-JRP10-1.7	
10	D-1.7	Definition of immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	20, 34	36		https://zenodo.org/record/5079723#.YOWv1zNxdPY CO: until the publication. Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo Joint publication is in preparation with ANSES, UoS and INRAE	1 ; 7 ; 8 report

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-1.8	Characterization, evolution and comparison of the microbiome of pig and poultry with different shedding status of <i>Salmonella</i>	18	NO		Delayed due to Covid19, No clear comparison can be done due to the differences in age between chicks and pigs. No Deliverable	
10	D-1.9	Definition of predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	40	36		(in AWP2021 : D-1.09) https://zenodo.org/record/5082178#.YObcrzNxdPY One publication accepted on chicks https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc , others are in preparation	1 ; 7 ; 8 report
10	D-1.10	Definition of microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	40	36		This Deliverable has been merged with D1.9 One publication accepted: https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc , others are in preparation	1 ; 7 ; 8 report
10	D-JRP10-1.11	Recovery of all human samples	42	42		Delayed due to Covid19, This Deliverable has been merged with D1.12	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-JRP10-1.12	Antimicrobial susceptibility testing, serotyping and whole genome sequencing of all <i>Salmonella</i> isolates from participants submitted to the Norwegian Reference laboratory	34	42		Delayed due to Covid19, https://zenodo.org/record/5078733#.YOWeazNxdPY A manuscript is in preparation	
10	D-1.12	Identification risk factors for patients with long term shedding	20	42		Due to change of project leaders at the NIPH,, this Deliverable has been modified and merged with the D-JRP10-1.12 (see version of June 2018).	
10	D-1.13	Description of the differences in immunological, gut-microbiota markers but also in resistome before and after travel to high-risk areas	22		cancelled	Due to change of project leaders at the NIPH, this Deliverable has been cancelled	
10	D-1.14	Identification, from <i>in vitro</i> studies, of immune parameters related to high and low shedders	42	36		This Deliverable has been merged with D1.7 No difference has been detected in chicks. One joint publication is in preparation	8 report

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-1.15	Understanding whether high and low shedder phenotypes are mainly related to <i>Salmonella</i> strain variation, immune status, or microbiota composition.	24	42		https://zenodo.org/record/5079547#.YOWqITNxdPY One joint publication is in preparation	report
10	D.1.16	A predictor, based on the designed set of mimotopes, using machine learning techniques to discriminate between the diagnostic groups.	24		cancelled	This deliverable has been cancelled due to the left of SAIM at the beginning of the project (see new version of June 2018). The immunoglobulin response cannot be used as a predictive factor	
10	D-2.1	<i>In vitro</i> effect of already characterized probiotics on <i>Salmonella</i> growth and cell invasion	36	42		Delayed due to Covid19, (in AWP2021 : D2.01) CO: until the publication. Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5085459#.YOhVtzNxdPY	8 report
10	D-JRP10-2.11	Evolution of the immune-signature in	34	36		This Deliverable has been merged with D2.10	report

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		pig, chicken and/ or human according to the context (infection, treatment...)				The immunoglobulin response cannot be used as a predictive factor	
10	D.2.2	Description of the microbiome and resistome in farms	12, 36	46		The experiment has been delayed due to the Covid19. The experiments have been completed. The gut microbiota were sequenced, Data analysis is ongoing This Deliverable has been merged with D-2.8	
10	D-2.3	Characterization of protective commensal bacteria able to inhibit <i>Salmonella</i> colonization (two rounds)	40	40		https://zenodo.org/record/5082203#.YObhrDNxdPY One article accepted for chicken, https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc One joint publication on pigs is in preparation (in AWP2021 : D2.04)	7,8
10	D-2.4	Determine the influence of defined and undefined probiotics on the microbiome signature, the immune response, gut physiology and welfare of pig and/ or chicken	42	42		This deliverable has been merged with D-JRP10-2.5 (in AWP2021 : D2.05)	7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-2.5	Impact of defined and undefined probiotics on <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in pig and chicken	42	42		https://zenodo.org/record/5082213#.YObjrTNxdPY (in AWP2021 : D2.06) One article accepted https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc One article in preparation.	7
10	D.2.6	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on the immune parameters, the microbiome and resistome, gut physiology and welfare of pig and chicken.	42	42		This Deliverable has been merged with D2.08 (D2.7) (in AWP2021 : D2.07) One article accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/4114070 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015 https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics8040215 https://zenodo.org/record/3648214#.XvyTJygzZM0	7
10	D.2.7	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in pig, chicken and human. Effect on the super-shedders and low-shedders.	42	36		https://zenodo.org/record/5079336#.YOWkYDNxdPY (in AWP2021 : D2.08) One article accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/4114070	7
10	D.2.8	Dynamics of the microbiome and resistome in the	24	46		The experiments have been delayed due to the Covid19. They are now completed. The gut microbiota were sequenced, Data analysis is ongoing	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		different groups and conditions				This Deliverable has been merged with D-2.2	
10	D.2.9	Validation of immunological and microbiota markers, identified in WP1 and associated to high/low shedding, in the control groups of WP2	24		No done	Delayed due to Covid19, The great variability in the gut microbiota composition hampered us to conclude.	
10	D.2.10	Evolution of the immune-signature in pig, chicken and/ or human according to the context (infection, treatment...)	20	42		https://zenodo.org/record/5079202#.YOWilzNxdPY Delayed due to Covid19, One article in preparation Not done for human	5
10	D.2.11	Differences in the resistome before and after travel to high-risk areas and after pre-biotic administration	24		cancelled	Due to change of project leaders at the NIPH, this Deliverable has been cancelled (see version of June 2018)	
10	D-3.1	Models at within-host scale taking into account the interactions between	22	42		https://doi.org/10.1051/proc/202067015 https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxM0	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		infection and microbiota and mechanisms of interventions					
10	D-3.2	Models at between-host scale, linking to the within-host modelling and taking into account the mechanisms of interventions	22	42		https://doi.org/10.1051/proc/202067015 https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxM0	5, 7
10	D-3.3	Intervention measures inventory	40		46	(in AWP2021 : D3.03) https://zenodo.org/record/5500249#.YTtd-YgzY2w	5, 7
10	D-3.4	Economic analysis tools combined with D-JRP10-3.06	30			(in AWP2021 :D3.04) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003 https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc	
10	D-3.5	Definition of intervention measures to target super-shedders	42			(in AWP2021 :D3.05) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015	5, 7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-3.6	Evaluation scheme for cost effectiveness of the intervention strategies combined with D-JRP10-3.04	30			(in AWP2021 :D3.06) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003 https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc	5, 7
10	D-4.1	Development and production of MoMIR-PPC website	4	12		We have used the EJP website	
10	D-4.2	Data management policy and strategies	4	42		The final DMP version has been sent	report
10	D-4.3	Creation of a database of each animal group included in the study (age, conformation, diet, clinical status, previous antibiotic treatments, infectious status, etc.)	2	36		https://zenodo.org/record/5082319#.YObuYDNxdPY Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo	3
10	D-4.4	Publication, and presentation at conferences	24	42		Information included in this report, see paragraph 5: Publication and additional output... Several publications will be finished after the end of	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						the project	
10	D-4.5	Dissemination to lay-public communities, to policy-makers and regulators, farmers and companies	24	42		Information included in this report, see paragraph 8. Several disseminations will be finished after the end of the project	5

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.1	Update of the members of the steering committee and of the leader and deputy leader for the WPs and tasks	2	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.2	Organization of the consortium kick off meeting	1	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.3	Protocols and ethical committee requests for the different experiments	1	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.4	Recovery of samples from the first round of experimentally infected animals	8	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.5	Identification and selection of farms	4	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.6	Recovery of samples from selected farms ; Identification of super-shedders and low-shedders in poultry and pig farms	8	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.7	Comparison of immune response of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs	11	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.8	Histological characterization of different intestinal lesions	12	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		between high and low shedder in chickens and pigs. Immunohistochemical studies on intestinal mucosa.				
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.9	Comparison of microbiota composition of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs.	11	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.10	Comparison of the predictive markers obtained in pigs with those obtained in chickens.	12	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.11 (or 10?)	<i>In vitro</i> infection of cell lines and organoids with the <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (from the first experiments)	36	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.12	Comparison of the transcriptomic immune response induced <i>in vitro</i> between different strains to identify immunological markers	12	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.13	Four sets of NGS derived 10 ⁵ mimotope sequences – positively and negatively enriched in IgM and IgA	8	NO		Due to the left of SAIM, this milestone has been cancelled. The role of immunoglobulin levels was investigated, but these levels cannot be used neither as a predictive

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						marker nor as a marker to differentiate between shedding phenotypes
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.14	A selected set of 100 mimotopes for the immune-signature chips.	12	NO		Due to the left of SAIM, this milestone has been cancelled (see version of June 2018). The role of immunoglobulin levels was investigated, but these levels cannot be used neither as a predictive marker nor as a marker to differentiate between shedding phenotypes
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.15	Inclusion and sampling of volunteers	12	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.16	Selective cultivation of commensal bacteria correlated to low shedding in pig and/ or chicken	10	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.17	Define the panel of probiotics for use in pigs and chickens	2	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.18	Define the panel of pre-biotics and feed for use in pigs, chickens and humans	2	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.19	Recovery of samples from experimentally infected animals and from farms, pretreated with pre-biotics or neutraceuticals	8	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.20	First version of within-host models completed	12	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.21	First version of between-host models completed	12	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.22	First inventory of intervention measures completed	12	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.23 (or 21?)	First version of economic analysis tools completed	12	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.23 (or 22)	Organization of consortium meetings (intermediate and closure)	40	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.24 (or 12 ?)	Comparison of immune response of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs	36	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.25	MALDI TOF Imaging processing and workflow on the paraffin wax slides of intestine wall in high and low shedder from chickens and pigs	18	In part		Only the histological analyses were done on all samples
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.26	Comparison of microbiota composition of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs.	18	yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.27	Comparison of the predictive markers obtained in pigs with those obtained in chickens.	19	yes		Poor correlations have been observed due to the different ages of pigs and chickens
10	M-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.28	<i>In vitro</i> infection of several cell lines and organoids with the different <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (second round)	18	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.29	Comparison of the transcriptomic immune response induced <i>in vitro</i> between different strains to identify immunological markers	20	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.30	Comparison of the immune signature of high and low shedders in chicken and pig.	18	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.31	Inclusion and sampling of volunteers	15	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.32	First selective cultivation of <i>Salmonella</i> from human rectal swabs to be use in WP1	13	NO		The experiment with human was postponed due to the Covid19. The <i>Salmonella</i> strains were not included in the analysis
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.33	Selective cultivation of <i>Salmonella</i> and antibiotic-	20	yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		resistant bacteria from 1000 human rectal swabs				
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.33	Recovery of samples from experimentally infected animals and from farms, pretreated with probiotics	16	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.34	Updated version of within-host models completed	21	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.35	Updated version of between-host models completed	21	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.22 (or 32?)	Final inventory of intervention measures completed	39	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.36	Updated version of economic analysis tools completed	22	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.37	Potential interventions included in between-host modelling	22	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC.38	Organization of the high strategy meeting	24	NO		Due to the lockdown, this meeting has been cancelled and the money returned

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>A Multi-Scale Epidemic Model of Salmonella infection with Heterogeneous Shedding. A first draft was accessible on HAL repository. https://doi.org/10.1051/proc/202067015 https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxMO</p>	YES	GREEN 0 MONTHS	
<p>Reduction of Salmonella Typhimurium Cecal Colonisation and Improvement of Intestinal Health in Broilers Supplemented with Fermented Defatted 'Alperujo', an Olive Oil By-Product. 10.3390/ani10101931 https://zenodo.org/record/4114070</p>	YES		GOLD – 1,334.20 €
<p>Cost-effectiveness analysis of using probiotics to control Campylobacter in broilers (submitted). https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003 https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015</p>	YES		GOLD – 2000 €
<p>Dietary Supplementation with Fermented Defatted 'Alperujo' Induces Modifications of the Intestinal Mucosa and Cecal Microbiota of Broiler Chickens. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015 https://zenodo.org/record/4017817#.X6LRjYhKjcc</p>	YES		GOLD – 1 720 €
<p>Effects on Intestinal Mucosal Morphology, Productive Parameters and Microbiota Composition after Supplementation with Fermented Defatted Alperujo (FDA) in Laying Hens.</p>	No		GOLD – 435.89 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics8040215 https://zenodo.org/record/3648214#.XvyTJygZM0			
Gut microbiota composition before infection determines the <i>Salmonella</i> super- and low-shedder phenotypes in chicken. https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc	YES		GOLD – 2 100 €

Additional output

2018

Oral presentation

A spatially structured model to investigate key drivers of the gut microbiota biogeography” B. Laroche, S. Labarthe et al. Oral presentation MB2 workshop in Besançon, 2018, “Modelling the gut microbiota”

2019

Poster

F. Kempf, P. Menanteau, I. Rychlik, E. Guitton, J. Trottereau, I. Virlogeux-Payant, P. Velge (2019). *Faecal gut microbiota composition of chicks can predict resistance to Salmonella Enteritidis colonization*. Poster communication at **Gordon Research Conference** “Molecular Mechanisms, Evolution and Treatment of *Salmonella*”

Poster in One Health EJP ASM 2019. Rebollada-Merino, A.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Mayoral-Alegre, F.J.; Maasoumi-Nouha, N.; Tomé-Sánchez, I.; Rivero, E.; Porrás-González, N.; García, M.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A. Changes on Caecal Mucosa Morphology and Microbiota in Laying Hens Supplemented with a Nutraceutical Product Obtained from Olive Oil Production.

2020

Poster

Participation to the ASM virtual EJP OneHealth meeting (UoS, INRAE)
Posters/

Metagenomic Analysis of The Pig Gut Microbiota and association with *Salmonella* status. Poster. Guido Cordoni, Daniel L Horton, Helen Louise Brown, Roberto La Ragione

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342123925_Metagenomic_Analysis_of_The_Pig_Gut_Microbiota_and_association_with_Salmonella_status/stats

Metagenomic Analysis of The Pig Gut Microbiota and Association With *Salmonella* Status. Presentation. RCE 2020 event at UoS. Guido Cordoni, Daniel L Horton, Helen Louise Brown, Roberto La Ragione.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346943667_Metagenomic_Analysis_of_The_Pig_Gut_Microbiota_and_Association_With_Salmonella_Status

Velge P. Faecal gut microbiota composition determines susceptibility to *Salmonella* Enteritidis primo-colonization. ." One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Pragues, 27th-29th May 2020.

Poster in One Health EJP ASM 2020. Rebollada-Merino, A.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Miguela-Villoldo, P.; Fernández-Manzano, A.; García, N.; Gómez, S.; Bárcena, C.; de Juan, L.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A. Fermented Defatted Alperujo (FDA) Reduces Histopathological Lesions and Excretion in Laying Hens Naturally Infected with *Brachyspira* spp.

Oral presentation

Porcs artificiellement contaminés par *Salmonella*: liens entre niveau d'excrétion, microbiote et immunité. A. Kerouanton. 2020, Meeting ANSES Ploufragan : Information and exchanges meeting pig farming sector.

2021

Poster

F. Kempf, R. Drumo, Anne Marie Chaussé, T. Kubasova, I. Caballero, S. Roche, P. Menanteau, E. Guitton, I. Rychlik, P. Velge-Immune response, gut microbial composition, *Salmonella* super- and low-shedder phenotypes can be modulated by the inoculation of four commensal bacteria in chicken. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Copenhagen, 9th-11th June 2021. **Poster**

16S RRNA MICROBIAL COMMUNITY ANALYSIS AND RELATIONSHIP WITH SALMONELLA SUPER SHEDDER STATUS IN PIGS Guido Cordoni One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (Poster)

Albena Dimitrova, Gergana Mateva, Gergana Krumova-Valcheva, Eva Gyurova, Mihail Milanov, Helen Brown, Guido Cordoni, Daniel Horton, Roberto La Ragione, Hristo Daskalov. INFLUENCE OF ORAL ADMINISTRATION OF LACTOBACILLUS REUTERI PROBIOTIC STRAINS AND GOS PREBIOTIC ON THE PRESENCE OF SALMONELLA SPP. IN FATENNING PIGS. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Copenhagen, 9th-11th June 2021. **Poster**

Gergana Mateva, Krasen Penchev, Gergana Krumova-Valcheva, Albena Dimitrova, Eva Gyurova, Mihail Milanov, Helen Brown, Guido Cordoni, Jade Passey, Daniel Horton, Roberto La Ragione, Hristo Daskalov. INFLUENCE OF ORAL ADMINISTRATION OF LACTOBACILLUS REUTERI PROBIOTIC STRAINS AND GOS PREBIOTIC ON THE PRESENCE OF SALMONELLA SPP. IN BROILERS. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Copenhagen, 9th-11th June 2021. **Poster**

Poster in One Health EJP ASM 2021. Rebollada-Merino, A.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Miguela-Villoldo, P.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A. Histomorphological Changes in the Bursa of Fabricius Associated with *Salmonella* Typhimurium Infection in Animals Feed with a Nutraceutical Derived from the Olive Oil Production

Oral presentation

Oral communication in Programa de Doctorado en Veterinaria. Rebollada-Merino, A. Efecto sobre la mucosa intestinal y la microbiota cecal del alperujo fermentado desengrasado en pollos de engorde experimentalmente infectados con *Salmonella* Typhimurium (2020)

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Key role of animal-animal recontaminations in the spread of *Salmonella* infection at the flock level. The high level of *Salmonella* transmission between chicks is related to the presence of Super-Shedders, functioning as a reservoir for the pathogen. *Salmonella* can be transmitted by air through contaminated dust particles. It is crucial to decrease these transfers (Importance of ventilation on farms) and to identify the animals at risk.

Identification of predictive biomarkers, based on gut microbiota composition and immune parameters, which can either predict the levels of *Salmonella* shedding (in pigs or in chickens), or which can differentiate the *Salmonella* shedding levels (in pigs or in chickens).

In humans, Long-term *Salmonella* shedder phenotype may be associated to host factors such as young age, disease manifestation, taking food supplements and regular medication. Moreover, although the risk of person-to-person transmission of *Salmonella* from asymptomatic carriers is considered low, our study indicates a 10-fold higher rate (24%) of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* shedding than previously suggested. Our results support current recommended control measures to prevent the occurrence of secondary cases especially in children. Presentation at ECDC Nordic Mini Module.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Participation to PoC projects COOPERATE funded by stakeholders in Paris-Saclay University (starting 2021). Interest of stakeholders for OTU clustering and for detection method. Design of probiotic consortia based on endogeneous microbiota bacteria

Development of probiotics for use in pigs and poultry, which can be used as an alternative to antibiotics and which may reduce AMR.

With approval of national authorities **VRI** tested the developed probiotics in more than a half million of broilers in 2020. Farmers are interested in further collaboration as the product may be used instead of antibiotic treatment during first days of life. The probiotic product is being prepared for registration in the Czech Republic though we are still improving its commercial formula – lyophilisation of strict anaerobes without losing viability is quite challenging.

Collaboration with commercial companies on the use of prebiotics (UoS, UCM-VISAVET). UoS will communicate results to stakeholders FSA, Defra and VMD.

7 One Health impact

Asymptomatic carrier animals and humans are a serious food safety and health issue resulting in a significant loss to agri- food industry as well as a substantial burden on the healthcare system. The MoMIR-PPC project has led to major advances 1- in the understanding of heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection, which has been confirmed in all models studied: human, pig and chicken ; 2- in the control measures, which could be used, and in the identifications of the super-shedder animals; 3- in the development of prevention measures able to either predict the most susceptible animals (or flocks) or to prevent infection by the use of pre and probiotics.

- **Understanding heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection.** This project has shown the key role of animal-animal recontaminations in the spread of *Salmonella* infection at the flock level. The high level of *Salmonella* transmission is related to the presence of Super-Shedders, functioning as a reservoir for the pathogen. The data have shown that the gut microbiota composition before infection determines in chicks the super and low shedder phenotypes. **It**

is thus possible to prevent infection with pre and probiotics or nutraceuticals. Moreover, although the risk of human-to-human transmission of *Salmonella* from asymptomatic carriers is considered low, our study indicates a 10-fold higher rates (24%) of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* shedding than previously suggested. Our results support current recommended control measures to prevent the occurrence of secondary cases especially in children. **The results obtained will have direct applications for the control measures.**

- **Modelisation of infection.** The project allowed the development of original epidemic models and methods for data analysis based on a generic mathematical model of the dynamic interplay between the gut microbiota, the pathogen and the host's immune response at the within and between-host scale. **This model will help to decipher the impact of modifications based on gut microbiota and immune response.**
- **Modelisation of transmission.** A mathematical model of indirect transmission of bacteria between broilers was developed. The results showed no transmission at longer distances (above 130 cm), which is consistent with the existence of a threshold distance. **The model can be used for designing and quantitatively assessing candidate bio-security based intervention strategies against indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*.**
- **Control strategies.** In general, the control of *Salmonella* is based upon the implementation of preventive actions throughout the whole production chain. More specifically, measures should be addressed to (i) the prevention of introduction of *Salmonella* into the herd/ flock, (ii) the prevention of within-herd transmission, and (iii) the increase of the resistance to the infection. Our results have shown at least in chicks, that *Salmonella* can be transmitted by air through contaminated dust particles. It is thus crucial to decrease these transfers with the important ventilation on farms. It is also important to identify the animals at risk. For that purpose, **the MoMIR-PPC project identified several predictive biomarkers**, based on gut microbiota composition and immune parameters. These biomarkers, which need to be confirmed, can either predict the levels of *Salmonella* shedding (in pigs or in chickens) if animals are infected, or can differentiate the *Salmonella* shedding levels.
- **The cost effectiveness (utility) of intervention strategies** using probiotics to reduce *Campylobacter* prevalence in broilers was evaluated. Interesting results showed that using probiotics is a moderately expensive intervention in Poland and Spain, if efficacy is more than 10%, otherwise it is relatively expensive. In contrast, in the Netherlands and Denmark, using probiotics is a relatively expensive intervention irrespective of efficacy. However, if probiotics were assumed to enhance broiler performance, the intervention would become relatively cost-effective even at low efficacy levels of 1 to 10%.
- **Prevention measures.** To prevent salmonellosis, we purified, characterized and tested the efficacy of probiotics and prebiotics for use in pigs and poultry, in experimental infection but also in field conditions. For example they were tested on 72640 chicks in Bulgaria and 130 000 chicks in Czech Republic. **These probiotics and prebiotics can be used as an alternative to antibiotics and may reduce AMR.**

The benefits of our project for the livestock industries, authorities, veterinarians and medical doctors should be rapid as we have already identified new control measures for risk managers for the prevention and control of salmonellosis. It will also have a short- and long-term impact on the industry, especially with regard to pro and prebiotics. The existence of a market for well characterized and defined probiotics is attested by the success with undefined avian caecal cultures in competitive exclusion, which are now banned by the EU. The results obtained will be disseminated to stakeholders through specialized congresses like the “Animal microbiome congresses” and the “International Conference on Poultry Intestinal Health”.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	5	4	3
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	5	5	2
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	5	4	3
Integration	5	3	2
Sustainability	5	3	2
Impact of the project	5	5	2
TOTAL	30/30	24/30	14/30

AVERAGE: 23

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

All objectives as set in the full proposal were achieved. Delay due Covid 19 pandemic and changes of some partners did not make deviation from the main goals of the project and provide good value to scientific excellence of this research project.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The results align very well with the project objectives.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The vast majority of the planned objectives have been achieved and are in line with the project proposal. However, obtained results are sometimes difficult to interpret due to the complexity of the pathogenesis of the carrier status phenomenon in animals and men.

Experiments showed the difficulty of identification of predictive immune markers for identification of super Salmonella shedders in pigs and chickens. Level of immunoglobulins cannot be a predictive marker for low and high shedders in chickens. Experiments showed that the gut microbiota composition plays a key role in the heterogeneity of Salmonella infection in chicks. In pigs this

observation could not be confirmed. Risk factors for longtime Salmonella shedding in humans were identified. Results suggested that long term shedding seems more dependent of host factors than pathogen characteristics. Also in pigs and chickens results strongly suggested that super- and low shedder phenotypes were not related to a modification of the virulence level of Salmonella strains.

With regard to the prevention of super shedder animals, experiments showed a protective effect of a mixture of commensal bacteria on Salmonella excretion in chicks. However, fermented prebiotics did not protect chickens from experimental Salmonella infection.

Assessment of the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of different intervention strategies were tested using computational models which were developed during the project. Interactions between Salmonella and gut microbiota could not adequately be studied due to lack of data. A model was developed for assessing candidate biosecurity-based intervention strategies against indirect transmission of Campylobacter and Salmonella in chickens. The model enabled to quantify processes occurring in the environment separately from host-dependent processes. An economic analysis tool allowed to evaluate the cost effectiveness of intervention strategies using probiotics to reduce Campylobacter prevalence in broilers.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Project scientific data is beyond state of the art following initially submitted proposal. Detecting immunological markers associated to the high and low Salmonella shedders in pigs, determination of Enterococcus and gut microbiota composition role in Salmonella infection and influence of prebiotics and probiotics to resistance of Salmonella colonisation, detecting the risks factors associated with chronic Salmonella infection in human population, development of multiscale computational models (from within-host to between- host scale) of heterogeneous pathogen transmission by integrating data from previous research and developing economic analysis tools to evaluate the cost effectiveness (utility) of intervention strategies using probiotics to reduce Campylobacter prevalence in broilers showed great multidisciplinary integration between microbiologist, risk assessment, veterinary , public health and animal nutrition specialist.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The scientific quality of the project is impressive. The consortium has performed an enormous amount of work and progressed our understanding of factors underlying shedding of Salmonella spp. in different host species. A number of innovative experimental approaches have been combined with more traditional methods to yield good quality results.

Reviewer 3: POC member

A sound scientific approach was applied in the many experiments executed by the partners of the consortium. Interesting results have been obtained but have shown in the same time the difficulty of generalizing the observations from one experiment to another and within different species. The difficulty of standardization of experiments in farm animals (and men) of studying the effect of gut microbiota on health and disease is a known bottleneck in animal and human science and this was no different in this ambitious project.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Scientific achievements showed well organised project management, especially keeping in mind participants from 8 countries and multidisciplinary approach to this project. Scientific results were

published in respected journals like environmental microbiology, and microbial biotechnology. Some other publications are in preparation. The results obtained will be disseminated to stakeholders through specialized congresses like the “Animal microbiome congresses” and the “International Conference on Poultry Intestinal Health”.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Project management and dissemination activities were appropriate. Dissemination could have improved further by including activities to disseminate the research to the general public and non-academic stakeholders such as farmers and veterinarians.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project management was not easy. The project planning had to be modified several times due to the leave of one of the partners, the closure of another partner by its government, and the departure of a scientist. A new partner had to be contracted. The data management plan was updated several times. Many meetings were organized to coordinate the work. Many experiments had to be postponed due to the Covid-19 crisis. The strategic meeting with stakeholders had to be canceled due to Covid. The project had to be extended for 18 months. Under those difficult circumstances the management of the project has been as efficient as possible.

Participation to several congresses outside EJP. Several articles have been accepted for publication in open access journals.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The project is successful in achieving relevant integrative activities. All topics results (role of animal to animal recontaminations in the spread of Salmonella infection at the flock level, which are mainly related to the presence of super-shedders functioning as a reservoir for the pathogen, identification of several preventive measures based on the use of prebiotics and probiotics, development of mathematical models and detecting biomarkers for salmonella shedders) helps veterinarians, stakeholders and public health specialist in ranking and setting priorities regarding intervention strategies and control of salmonella and campylobacter infections.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project partners have clearly worked well together, with a variety of different partners from several disciplines each contributing to the outcomes and working together as a team. Integration could have been improved further by developing more joint protocols, databases and other resources.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Partners have exchanged for analysis numerous samples and the corresponding data from animal experiments. A good functioning collaboration has made it possible to analyse many parameters of the in vivo experiments performed with pigs and chickens. Cross-sector collaboration and alignment remains a point of attention.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Created mathematical models and project results are available for other scientist and institutions.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The achievements by the consortium are considerable and there are plans to transfer knowledge to new projects and stakeholders. The partners must work together ensure the considerable know-how they have developed is preserved by ensuring that databases, protocols etc. are appropriately stored and shared in the future.

Reviewer 3: POC member

By publication of the results of the many experiments sustainability of the project results is guaranteed in the scientific community. Collections of bacteria which have been exchanged between partners can be used in future experiments. The economic analysis tool can be further used in other situations.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Project results will have impact over a long period of time due to new approach to resolving tasks in the project. Also results have very good secondary effect on learning, understanding and control of salmonella and campylobacter infections in pig, chicken farms and understand salmonella shedding in humans.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has led to several key discoveries regarding the role of shedders in Salmonella spp. transmission and furthermore it has begun development of a number of promising control strategies. It can therefore be expected that its long-term impact on this field will be significant.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Several interesting results have been obtained from a One Health perspective, but as different protocols and methods were used in pigs, chickens and humans, it has been difficult to generalize the results obtained in humans to farm animals and vice versa.

JRP11-MEDVETKLEBS

Final report

1 Consortium composition

List of applicants: #	Applicant Name	Short name	PI	Country
1	Institut Pasteur	IP	Sylvain Brisse	FR
2	National Institute for Agronomical Research & Env.	INRAE	Pascal Piveteau	FR
3	French Agency for Food, Env. and Occupational Health Safety	ANSES	Jean-Yves Madec	FR
4	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Security	AGES	Franz Allerberger	AT
5	Statens Serum Institute	SSI	Eva Møller Nielsen	DK
6	Technical University of Denmark	DTU	Sara Pires	DK
7 (not funded)	University College Dublin	UCD	Shea Fanning	IE
8	Veterinary Institute Teramo	IZSAM	Francesco Pomilio	IT
9	Netherlands Center for One Health	NCOH	Rob Willems	NL
10	National University of Ireland Galway	NUIG	Dearbhaile Morris	IE

2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Klebsiella pneumoniae (Kp) is a bacterial pathogen of increasing public health concern given the emergence of highly multidrug resistant strains. Kp is also a model of ubiquitous bacteria that should be analysed in a One Health perspective, given its broad ecological distribution in animals (including humans) and the environment, and its capacity to contaminate food. The MEDVETKLEBS project aimed at enhancing Kp research and surveillance by developing and harmonizing study methods and by investigating its ecology and transmission across sources.

Protocols were developed for *Klebsiella* isolation from various sources (food, water, animal and human faecal material) and for molecular detection through a highly sensitive qPCR method, the ZKIR assay, which detects Kp and its closely related species from soil, food, faeces and other complex matrices. Novel taxonomic classifications (four novel *Klebsiella* species and subspecies) and novel biomarkers and laboratory identification tools (MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry) were also defined. Our protocols were disseminated through publications and the open platform protocols.io. Further methodological developments will be finalized in the short term, including a combined qPCR method for detecting and differentiating at the same time the medically most problematic *Klebsiella* species, *K. pneumoniae*

sensu stricto, from related Kp species. An additional short-term goal stemming from MEDVETKLEBS is the setting-up a publicly accessible MALDI-TOF *Klebsiella* identification web site.

Using our harmonized protocols, broad sampling of varied sources was accomplished in order to investigate the presence of Kp. In total, nearly 4000 samples from different sources (food, environment, healthy animals and humans) were analyzed. Among the food sources tested, chicken meat and vegetables (mainly ready-to-eat salads and onions) presented the highest Kp recovery rate (35% and 20%, respectively). In the environment, all sources tested showed a high prevalence of Kp. Based on this broad sampling campaign, we have sampled more deeply some specific sources of potential relevance for One Health transmission and of scientific interest: chicken meat, ready-to-eat salads, onions, seawater and soil, as well as human carriage.

Genomic sequencing of Kp isolates from the chicken/salads and soil has been performed. A very high strain-level genetic diversity was found but importantly, with low prevalence of antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes. We have also started to analyse by genomic sequencing, strains from other sources. In addition, we are still exploring Kp prevalence and diversity in human gut colonization using a targeted metagenomics approach.

Finally, we have explored a mathematical modelling approach to simulate the diversification of a bacterial lineage that contaminates food, as a function of time and mutation rate of the bacteria. This approach will be used to define clusters of related Kp isolates that result from single contamination and transmission chains. The model can be generalized to all foodborne or environmental bacterial species, and will help defining short-term transmission of pathogens to animals and humans.

So far, 10 manuscripts and one preprint related to MEDVETKLEBS were published, and 10 more are being prepared. Although COVID-19 restrictions have hampered physical meetings and some experimental work, the MEDVETKLEBS project was highly successful in delivering novel analytical methods and scientific knowledge on Kp ecology and transmission. By achieving its scientific tasks and dissemination activities, fostering novel collaborations among partner institutions, and integrating and harmonizing *Klebsiella* study strategies among partners and beyond, the MEDVETKLEBS project has contributed significantly to enhance our collective research and surveillance capacity on this important pathogen.

3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

Klebsiella: taxonomy and definitions

Bacteria of the genus *Klebsiella* are human and animal pathogens with wide ecological distribution. The genus *Klebsiella*, a member of the family *Enterobacteriaceae*, encompasses a huge diversity in terms of phylogenetic lineages, genomic content, pathogenic properties, and ecological distribution. Two major subdivisions of *Klebsiella* are the *K. pneumoniae* species complex (KpSC) and the *K. oxytoca* species complex (KoSC). The KpSC currently includes five taxonomic species, two of which comprise two subspecies. These taxa were initially defined as seven distinct phylogroups, Kp1 to Kp7.

K. pneumoniae (phylogroup Kp1) is one of the most problematic pathogens associated with antibiotic resistance worldwide. This species is phylogenetically closely related to *K. quasipneumoniae* [subsp. *quasipneumoniae* (Kp2) and subsp. *similipneumoniae* (Kp4)], *K. variicola* [subsp. *variicola* (Kp3) and subsp. *tropica* (Kp5)], '*K. quasivariicola*' (Kp6) and *K. africana* (Kp7).

In turn, the KoSC comprises 6 species and 7 phylogroups (4): *K. michiganensis* (Ko1), *K. oxytoca* (phylogroup Ko2), *K. spallanzanii* (Ko3), *K. pasteurii* (Ko4), *K. grimontii* (Ko6) and *K. huaxiensis* (Ko8). *K. oxytoca* is well known as a cause of opportunistic human infections and post-antibiotic hemorrhagic diarrhea.

WP1. Methods for Kp detection and isolation

JRP11-WP1-T1: Evaluation and optimization of culture-based approaches (M1-M12)

Productivity and specificity tests – two partners were involved in this task (IP, IZSAM). The tests were performed in accordance with the ISO 11133:2014 and using a collection of 57 reference panel of strains from our IP internal collection, that included members from the Kp complex and also other related species (*K. oxytoca*, *Raoultella* spp., *K. aerogenes*). Three different media - SCAI, *Klebsiella* Selective ChromoSelect Agar Base from Sigma and other not yet commercialized from Liofilchem - were compared with a non-selective agar media. The results showed similar recovery rates (productivity) for the three different media tested, but higher specificity for SCAI compared to the other selective and differential media tested. In addition, SCAI appeared easy to prepare and to identify *Klebsiella* colonies from. Furthermore, productivity tests with SCAI at two different incubation temperatures (37°C and 44°C) were also performed. This was done because at 44°C, we detect less interferences of other species besides *Klebsiella* spp., and we wanted to be sure that all Kp complex members are able to growth at 44°C. Our results revealed similar productivity rates in SCAI at both temperatures. All this work will be disseminated via a publication in preparation.

Klebsiella isolation tests from different sources - We designed protocols for the detection and isolation of *Klebsiella* strains using SCAI medium from different sources (human and animal fecal carriage; food; water; soil). Seven partners were involved in this task (AGES, ANSES, IP, IZSAM, INRA, SSI, NUIG). In the case of human and animal fecal carriage, the protocol established includes an enrichment step in lysogeny broth (LB) plus ampicillin (or amoxicillin) (10 µg/mL) at 37°C/18-24h and then streak to isolate single colonies using a 10 µl loop in SCAI plates (37°C/48h) (<https://www.protocols.io/view/isolation-of-klebsiella-strains-from-human-or-anim-662hhge>). The protocol for soil samples, is the same described for human and animal fecal carriage with the only difference being the incubation temperature in the enrichment step (28-30°C instead of 37°C). In the case of food samples, the protocol was optimized using chicken meat (legs and chest with and without skin from free-range and not free-range chickens). The best strategy achieved includes an enrichment in buffer peptone water (BPW) at 37°C/18-24h and then plating 10 µL of the enrichment in SCAI (44°C/48h) (<https://www.protocols.io/view/isolation-of-klebsiella-strains-from-food-samples-baxtifnn>). For water samples the strategy is similar to the one for food samples, with differences in the incubation temperatures (enrichment in BPW at 42°C/18-24h, and SCAI incubation at 37°C/48h) (<https://www.protocols.io/view/isolation-of-klebsiella-strains-from-water-samples-baxuifnw>). Following the four protocols mentioned above, all suspected colonies typical of *Klebsiella* spp. (large, yellow, moist colonies) are then identified using MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry.

IN SUM, we validated the SCAI medium and defined source-adapted strategies to isolate *Klebsiella* from complex sources. This work represents a foundation for the harmonization of *Klebsiella* isolation and detection for surveillance and research. It represented a milestone for subsequent tasks of the project dedicated at looking for *Klebsiella* in a variety of sources.

JRP11-WP1-T2: Detection and quantification (M1-M12)

Although the culture strategies outlined above represent important advances for *Klebsiella* ecology and One Health transmission studies, molecular detection methods have higher throughput. We have therefore also developed a real-time PCR (qPCR) assay for the direct detection of Kp in complex samples. Two partners were involved in the methodological development component (IP, INRA). The targets for the qPCR were chosen based on a *K. pneumoniae* pan-genome analysis. Candidate genes exclusive for, and conserved within, the KpSC were searched, leading to define six optimal target genes (target for KpSC; and targets for phylogroups Kp1, Kp2, Kp3+5, Kp4 and Kp6). A sequence between *zur* (zinc uptake regulation protein) and *khe* (annotated as coding for a haemolysin) intergenic region (ZKIR) was used with a SYBR green strategy. The ZKIR qPCR for detection of KpSC members in different matrices was published in March 2020 (Barbier *et al.* Applied Env Microbiol). Besides, we had

disseminated the protocol ahead of publication (<https://www.protocols.io/view/detection-of-klebsiella-pneumoniae-and-closely-rel-7n6hmhe>).

The protocol metrics show nearly 1000 views and 100 downloads. The Norwegian consortium Nor-Kleb-Net (<http://www.nor-kleb.net/>) has adopted the ZKIR method for quantification and detection of Kp in gut samples of a large cohort (project Kleb-GAP), testifying on the rapid adoption of our methods by the international community.

Additionally, we sought to combine the detection of the entire KpSC (using the ZKIR target) with a specific detection of phylogroup Kp1, its most abundant subgroup. The methodological component was optimized by our INRA (Dijon) partner, and tested at SSI (finished) and NUIG (in progress). This qPCR assay has already been tested on a panel of environmental, food and sewage samples and worked very well. One initial issue was the non-detection of a minor phylogroup, Kp6, due to a specific Kp6 DNA polymorphism where the probe hybridizes. To address this lack of detection, INRA developed a second probe (ZKIR P2), specific to Kp6, and the problem was solved. The protocol has already been distributed to all the consortium members and as soon as all tests are completed it will be posted on the protocols.io platform. This novel method will be useful for studies aiming at differentiating Kp1, the clinical most relevant KpSC member, from other phylogroups which are rare and less well understood ecologically and epidemiologically.

Finally, we have tried to implement a second duplex qPCR using the previous defined targets in different combinations (Kp3+5 and Kp2; Kp3+5 and Kp4) but we were not successful. In fact, the specific probes for each of the species of the complex work in simplex and were validated in a panel of reference strains at INRA, but the combination in a single multiplex does not give good results.

Due to its complexity, the task of quantification of Kp in samples was not addressed during the project. However, the developed qPCR will allow this to be done in future dedicated studies.

IN SUM, we have developed two novel molecular detection methods useful for One Health studies of *Klebsiella* ecology and epidemiology.

JRP11-WP1-additional tasks: taxonomic updates and MALDI-TOF MS

To achieve precise detection and identification of *Klebsiella* members, it is important to define the target species precisely. Although not initially planned, taxonomic updates of the genus *Klebsiella* were therefore performed. First, two novel taxa of the KpSC were described: *K. africana* and *K. variicola* subsp. *tropica* (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003> and <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0923250819300956>). Second, in collaboration with the JPIAMR-funded SpARK project (<https://www.jpamr.eu/supportedprojects/third-joint-callresult/>), two novel species previously misidentified as *K. oxytoca* were described: *Klebsiella pasteurii* and *Klebsiella spallanzanii* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.02360>).

To facilitate and improve laboratory identification of *K. pneumoniae*, we evaluated and validated the potential of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry (MS), a fast and cost-effective technique that is well established in clinical microbiology laboratories for microbial identification (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30581423> and both taxonomic publications above). As reference spectra of novel *Klebsiella* taxa are not readily incorporated into the reference MALDI-TOF MS databases used in microbiology laboratories, we have developed a publicly-accessible web-based tool, *Klebsiella* MALDI TypeR (<https://maldityper.pasteur.fr>), a user-friendly application that enables users to upload their MALDI-TOF data and identify *Klebsiella* isolates using our reference taxonomic database. Our database also includes new *Klebsiella* biomarkers. The *Klebsiella* MALDI TypeR tool will improve identification of *Klebsiella*.

IN SUM, although these tasks were not initially planned as deliverables of our project (because the novel species were not discovered yet, and because the successful application of MALDI-TOF MS was not anticipated), they represent important advances for the refinement of *Klebsiella* definition and identification in One Health studies. For example, the SpARK consortium

(<https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=MR%2FR00241X%2F1>) has adopted our novel nomenclature and MALDI work to characterize *Klebsiella* isolated from a massive (> 6000 samples from diverse environmental, animal and human sources) sampling effort, and a high-profile bioinformatics tool that aims at harmonizing the study of *Klebsiella* genomes has incorporated our nomenclature outputs (<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.12.14.422303v1>).

JRP11-WP1-T3: Harmonization and alignment (M1-M24)

Protocols for Kp isolation by culture from various food sources were disseminated/made publicly available through the protocols.io platform in a project called '*Klebsiella* Research and Surveillance' (<https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/klebsiella-research-and-surveillance/publications>).

We have pursued our additional objective of setting-up a MALDI-TOF MS based identification web site for *Klebsiella*. A pilot web site is functional (<https://maldityper.pasteur.fr>), and the work was submitted for publication and is available at BioRxiv platform (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.10.13.337162>).

IN SUM, our novel culture, molecular and MALDI-TOF methods for *Klebsiella* detection and identification have been implemented within the consortium partner Institutions and beyond.

WP2. Sampling

JRP11-WP2-T1: Broad sampling of potential reservoirs and sources of Kp (M1-M12)

To define the ecological distribution and reservoirs of Kp, broad sampling from varied sources was performed. In total, 3781 samples from food, environment, healthy animals and humans were analyzed by the MEDVETKLEBS partners. Among animals, swine and rabbits showed the highest prevalence (to be confirmed on more samples in the future), whereas in poultry and bovine samples the prevalence was around 20%. Among the food sources tested, chicken meat and vegetables (mainly ready-to-eat salads and onions) presented the highest recovery rate of Kp (35% and 20%, respectively), whereas in the environment all sources tested (seawater, fresh water, wastewater and soil) showed a high prevalence of Kp (>40%). Carriage among healthy humans was between 15-20%, similar to rates reported from other projects (SpARK and Nor-Kleb-Net projects, pers. comm.). Sampling results will be disseminated via several publications in preparation (soil prevalence was published in part in the ZKIR qPCR [Barbier et al.] publication).

IN SUM, our project demonstrated the ubiquity of Kp in the environment, food and mammalian animals including humans, and demonstrated the higher prevalence of phylogroup Kp1.

JRP11-WP2-T2: Deep sampling of selected sources (M13-M24)

To study in more depth *Klebsiella* from particularly Kp-rich sources, we have further focused on six sources of potential One Health relevance and of scientific interest: chicken meat and ready-to-eat salads (multicentric study), soil, veal calves, seawater and onions. Sampling of onions and seawater has been slowed by COVID-19, but is re-starting currently. Sampling of veal calves turned out to be mostly negative and this sub-study was therefore abandoned (veal calves results will be disseminated within our future broad sampling reports). One partner (IP) has also been looking at Kp carriage and transmission in patients from a rehabilitation hospital.

In the multicentric study (five sampling centers involved), a total of 305 samples were analyzed, with 160 from chicken meat and 145 from ready-to-eat salads. Chicken meat showed a prevalence of Kp twice as high as salads (58% versus 30%, accordingly to ZKIR qPCR results). A total of 131 Kp isolates were recovered. The antibiotic susceptibility tests revealed that the majority (82%) of the isolates presented a wild-type phenotype, being susceptible to all the antibiotics tested (except ampicillin, for which all Kp are resistant).

To analyze the transmission and ecology of Kp in a local "One Health" context, we have focused on a restricted geographic setting, Burgundy in France. We first collected 664 environmental samples in a

single French administrative locality (Department of Côte d'Or, Burgundy, France) from July 2018 to July 2019. Most samples were collected monthly in a market gardener farm (n = 329) and in an organic cattle farming (n = 304) and consisted in soil/mud (n = 219), roots (n = 189), leaves (n = 106), water (n = 34), cow bedding and faeces (n = 50) and fertilizer/compost (n = 35). In addition, water and sludge were sampled in 31 wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) in the same department (n = 31). For comparison purposes, 47 clinical isolates collected in 2018 and 2019 by the Department of Bacteriology from the University Hospital of Dijon (the capital city of Côte d'Or), France, were included. Environmental samples screening with ZKIR qPCR assay followed by culture on SCAI media allowed the isolation of Kp strains in 24.7 % (164/664) of the environmental samples. Phylogenetic and genomic analysis are ongoing to evaluate the diversity of Kp in these environmental niches across one year, and to compare them with sewage and clinical isolates in terms of strain subtype, virulence factors and antimicrobial genes.

In order to understand better the pattern of transmission of ESBL *K. pneumoniae* in health care settings, we used data from i-Bird (Individual-Based Investigation of Resistance Dissemination, PI Didier Guillemot, IP; Collaboration with Dr Lulla Opatowski), a 4-month study that took place in 2009 in a rehabilitation hospital and followed up more than 600 patients and health care workers. Weekly rectal swabs and human-human proximities recorded from wireless captors were recorded. In total, 604 ESBL-*Enterobacteriaceae* were isolated from 84 patients. Within the project, we have sequenced 61 *K. pneumoniae* and the data is being processed.

Additional work: *Klebsiella* sampling and characterization work: Some MEDVETKLEBS partners have engaged in additional *Klebsiella* sampling and characterization work, which was not initially planned but was nevertheless closely related to the project by its goals, and personnel supported by MEDVETKLEBS contributed to these studies. We describe these completed studies below:

Work by Huynh et al.: prevalence of Kp in gut carriage. Although most Kp infections are caused by endogenous intestinal carriage, little is known about the prevalence and microbiological characteristics of Kp in asymptomatic human carriage, and attached risk factors including environmental sources exposure. In this work, 911 pregnant women from communities in Madagascar, Cambodia, and Senegal were screened for gut colonization by Kp. Characteristics of Kp strains (antimicrobial susceptibility, genomic diversity, virulence, and resistance genes) were defined, and associated risk factors were investigated. Kp carriage rate was 55.9%, and Kp populations were highly heterogeneous. One third of Kp isolates had acquired antimicrobial resistance genes. MDR-Kp (11.7% to 39.7%) and extended spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing Kp (0.7% to 14.7%) varied among countries. Isolates with virulence genes were detected (14.5%). Environmental exposure factors including food, animal contacts, or hospitalization of household members were associated with carriage of Kp, antimicrobial resistance and hypervirulence. However, risk factors were country-specific and Kp subpopulation-specific. This work was published: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19490976.2020.1748257>

Work by Loncaric et al.: Analysis of resistant *Klebsiella* in horses. The aim of this study was to investigate the diversity of broad-spectrum cephalosporin-resistant clinical *Klebsiella* isolated from horses in Austria. A total of seven non-repetitive cefotaxime-resistant *Klebsiella* isolates were obtained during diagnostic activities from autumn 2012 to October 2019. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed. The isolates were genotyped by whole-genome sequencing (WGS). Four out of seven *Klebsiella* isolates were identified as *K. pneumoniae*, two as *K. michiganensis* and one as *K. oxytoca*. All isolates displayed a multi-drug resistant phenotype. The detection of resistance genes reflected well the phenotypic resistance profiles of the respective isolates. Besides resistance genes, a variety of virulence genes, including genes coding for yersiniabactin were detected. Considering the high proximity between horses and humans, these results undoubtedly identified a public health issue. This work was published: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32093201/>

Work by Lepuschitz et al.: Analysis of resistant *Klebsiella* in rivers. This study reports on the characterization of carbapenem resistant and ESBL-producing *K. pneumoniae* isolates from Austrian

river water samples, compared to 95 clinical isolates recently obtained in Austrian hospitals. Ten water samples were taken from four main rivers, collected upstream and downstream of major cities in 2016. The presence of AMR genes, virulence genes and plasmids was extracted from whole genome sequence (WGS) data. In total three ESBL-producing strains and two carbapenem resistant strains were isolated. WGS based comparison of these five waters isolates to 95 clinical isolates identified three clusters. Cluster 1 (ST11) and cluster 2 (ST985) consisted of doublets of carbapenem resistant strains (one water and one clinical isolate each). Cluster 3 (ST405) consisted of three ESBL-producing strains isolated from one water sample and two clinical specimens. The cities, in which patient isolates of cluster 2 and 3 were collected, were in concordance with the water sampling locations downstream from these cities. The genetic concordance between isolates from river water samples and patient isolates raises concerns regarding the release of wastewater treatment plant effluents into surface water. From a public health perspective these findings demand attention and strategies are required to minimize the spread of multiresistant strains to the environment. This work was published: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30690357/>

Work by Wisgrill et al.: analysis of an outbreak and clinical management of infections because of a highly virulent yersiniabactin-producing, non-multiresistant *K. pneumoniae* strain in a neonatal intensive care unit. An outbreak investigation and effectiveness assessment of multidisciplinary infection control measurements to prevent patient-to-patient transmission of highly pathogenic *K. pneumoniae* were undertaken. Outbreak cases were identified by isolation of *K. pneumoniae* from blood or stool of infants. Clinical data were abstracted from medical charts. *K. pneumoniae* isolates were genotyped using whole genome sequencing, and yersiniabactin production was evaluated by luciferase assay. Fourteen cases were confirmed with 8 symptomatic and 6 colonized patients. Symptomatic patients were infants of extremely low gestational and chronologic age with fulminant clinical courses including necrotizing enterocolitis and sepsis. Whole genome sequencing for bacterial isolates confirmed the presence of an outbreak. All outbreak isolates produced yersiniabactin. Yersiniabactin-producing *K. pneumoniae* can display a high pathogenicity in extremely premature infants with low chronologic age. This outbreak also underlines the considerable potential of today's infection control systems for recognizing and controlling nosocomial infections in highly vulnerable populations. This work was published: <https://doi.org/10.1097/INF.0000000000002258>

Work by Chiarelli et al.: Most clinical Kp isolates produce capsule as a major virulence factor. Here, we explored the genetic causes of *in vitro* switching from capsulated, mucoid to non-mucoid, non-capsulated phenotype in eight clinical carbapenem-resistant Kp isolates. We compared capsulated, mucoid colony variants with one of their non-capsulated, non-mucoid isogenic variant. The two colony variants were distinguished by their appearance on solid medium. Whole genome comparison was used to infer mutations causing phenotypic differences. The frequency of phenotypic switch was strain-dependent and increased along with colony development on plate. We observed, for 72 non-capsulated variants that the loss of the mucoid phenotype correlates with capsule deficiency and diverse genetic events, including transposition of insertion sequences or point mutations, affecting genes belonging to the capsule operon. Reduced or loss of capsular production was associated with various *in vitro* phenotypic changes, affecting susceptibility to carbapenem but not to colistin, *in vitro* biofilm formation and autoaggregation. These results suggested heterogeneous selective advantage for capsular loss according to the strain and the mutation. Based on our results, we believe that attention should be paid in the phenotypic characterization of Kp clinical isolates, particularly of traits related to virulence and carbapenem resistance. This work was published: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33109078/>

IN SUM, we have launched and largely completed, several large studies on the ecology and transmission of Kp in specific settings. These works provide original data on the ecological diversity and transmission of Kp across sources.

WP3. Genomics and Modelling

JRP11-WP3-T1: Analyses of genomic sequences (M13-M24)

Genomic analysis of Kp isolated from our above studies will enable defining medically and ecologically relevant features such as strain subtypes, virulence genes and resistance genes, and their distribution across sources.

We have completed the genomic analyzes of the 131 Kp strains from the chicken-salad multicentric study, of 338 Kp isolates from the Burgundy project and of 61 Kp from the ESBL study. Genomic sequencing of Kp from other sources including onion and seawater is in progress. Overall, a high genetic diversity was found among these sources.

Additional task: Analyses of metagenomic sequences. We are also exploring Kp prevalence and diversity in human gut colonization using an innovative ‘targeted metagenomics’ approach. In short, in parallel to single colonies, the bacterial mass growing on the SCAI medium plated from fecal material were harvested, DNA extracted, and Illumina sequenced *en-masse*. Sequence data analysis algorithms developed in the SpARK project (Ed Feil, PI) will be applied to the generated ‘targeted metagenomics’ data to quantify reads from *K. pneumoniae* or other *Klebsiella* species, and hopefully to define the diversity of clones within the samples. This project involves the coordinator center (IP) and UMCU partner (Rob Willems) and is performed in collaboration with SpARK partners.

Additional task: Analyses of an ST66 isolate. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kp) reference strain Kp52.145 is widely used in experimental *Klebsiella* pathophysiology. Since 1935, only one other strain of the same sublineage (sequence type ST66, capsular serotype K2) was isolated (AJ210, Australia). In the course of the MEDVETKLEBS project, we have described a community-acquired invasive infection caused by a ST66-K2 Kp strain (SB5881) in France. The ST66-K2 strain presented a full antimicrobial susceptibility profile, including to ampicillin, and was more closely related to strain AJ210 (135 SNPs) than to reference strain Kp52.145 (388 SNPs). Colibactin and yersiniabactin gene clusters were present on the integrative and conjugative element ICEKp10 in the chromosome. The two plasmids from Kp52.145 were detected in SB5881. In addition to carrying genes for virulence factors RmpA, aerobactin and salmochelin, plasmid II has acquired in SB5881, the conjugation machinery gene cluster from plasmid I. We thus reported the first case of community-acquired infection caused by a hypervirulent ST66-K2 Kp strain in Europe and demonstrated the long-term persistence of the high-virulence and laboratory model ST66-K2 sublineage. The combination of a conjugative apparatus and major virulence genes on a single plasmid may contribute to the co-occurrence of hypervirulence and multidrug resistance in single Kp strains. This work was published: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32749955/> .

IN SUM, genomic sequencing was slowed down by the COVID-19 crisis but a majority of the data was obtained. A prominent result is that different from the clinical setting, a low number of antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes are found in environmental or food isolates. This is a very significant result in the perspective of Kp antimicrobial resistance ecology and transmission. Analysis and publication of the results are still in progress.

JRP11-WP3-T2: Modelling and source attribution (M1-M24)

Based on our genomic sequence data, a huge diversity of Kp subtypes (strains) was present in all sources where we have isolated Kp strains. As a consequence, the initially planned source attribution approach, which relies on the differential distribution of subtypes across sources, was deemed impossible to follow. While we are still exploring what best could be done in this direction (partners IP and SSI), we have decided to adapt our initial objectives and address a related, less risky and high impact objective: we are exploring models to simulate the evolutionary diversification of a bacterial lineage that contaminates food, as a function of time and mutation rate of the bacteria. This approach will be used to define in an innovative and evolutionary biology-informed way, isolates that belong to

a cluster (for example an outbreak of infections, or a set of cross-contaminated food items). The high potential impact of this approach lies in the generalization to the modelling work to all foodborne or environmental bacterial species, and in the fact that it addresses a long-standing but still unresolved question in molecular epidemiology: ‘what is a strain?’.

This task started in December 2019 with the recruitment of Audrey Duval, a post-doctoral fellow in mathematical modelling. We propose a forward model of bacterial evolution to simulate mutation within a population maintaining its size in a given source during a certain time. An algorithm is being implemented to return the expected distribution of SNP (or cgMLST) distances given the specificities of a given contamination event. In addition, we will provide a web site for users to define the expected genetic distance threshold. This forward model will help defining short-term transmission of pathogens from food to animals or humans. We are currently preparing the corresponding publication.

IN SUM, classical approaches for modeling transmission and source attribution in a One Health context are difficult to apply given the huge diversity of Kp subtypes disclosed in the MEDVETKLEBS project. We have therefore shifted our initial objectives into providing a novel tool to define short-term transmission of Kp or any other bacterial pathogen that contaminates food or a given environmental source.

WP4: Management, dissemination, exploitation

JRP11-WP4-T1: Implementation of the project management structure (M1-M24)

Nothing specific to report here.

JRP11-WP4-T2: Administrative, legal, financial and ethical support to the consortium (M1-M24)

Nothing specific to report here.

JRP11-WP4-T3: Exploitation of results and Intellectual Property rights management (M1-M24)

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 9. Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Diallo TA, Criscuolo A, Brisse S. Description of *Klebsiella africana* sp. nov., *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *tropica* subsp. nov. and *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *variicola* subsp. nov. *Res Microbiol*. 2019 Apr-May;170(3):165-170. doi: 10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003. Erratum in: *Res Microbiol*. 2019 Sep - Oct;170(6-7):300.
 10. Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Brisse S. Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola* and Related Phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry. *Front Microbiol*. 2018 Dec 7;9:3000. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000.

Preprint:

1. Bridel S, Watts SC, Judd LM, Harshegyi T, Passet V, Rodrigues C, Holt KE, Brisse S. *Klebsiella* MALDI TypeR: a web-based tool for *Klebsiella* identification based on MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. bioRxiv 2020.10.13.337162; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.10.13.337162>.

4 Project self-assessment

The initial proposed MEDVETKLEBS aims were to:

- develop and harmonize methods of detection, isolation and quantification of Kp.
- define the major environmental niches that act as reservoirs of Kp, and more specifically its high-risk subtypes and associated antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes and plasmids;
- define the main vehicles of contamination, quantify the role of different foods and feeds in exposure of humans and animals to Kp; and trace the transmission of Kp subtypes, resistance genes and plasmids;
- inform the scientific community and decision makers in order to optimize current practices.

As testified in this report, we consider that most initial objectives were achieved. Regarding ongoing work, MEDVETKLEBS partners have agreed to continue to meet regularly after the project end date, and to finalize ongoing collaborations (and possibly define novel ones). Therefore, the ongoing tasks will be completed in the near future.

Some tasks of the project were not achieved: quantification of Kp in sources, and modelling of Kp transmission across sources. The first one was deemed too complex and not feasible within the project. However, we have developed tools that will facilitate this task in future work; and in fact, quantification of Kp in some sources is already ongoing in at least one other consortium (KlebGAP) using our ZKIR qPCR. The second unachieved task turned out to be scientifically impossible based on findings from the initial tasks, as the huge diversity of Kp subtypes means statistical power in tracing sources of subtypes will be very low. An alternative related task was therefore addressed.

Of note, in addition to initially planned tasks, the MEDVETKLEBS consortium has achieved supplementary tasks: MALDI-TOF identification of *Klebsiella*, description of four novel *Klebsiella* species or subspecies, additional sampling and characterization studies, a targeted metagenomics study, and the novel modeling approach to define transmission.

The significant scientific output of MEDVETKLEBS is testified by 10 publications, one preprint and 10 additional publications in preparation. MEDVETKLEBS experimental procedures were posted on open web sites, have high consultation metrics and have been adopted by ongoing consortia and One Health *Klebsiella* research projects.

As a consortium, we therefore consider that the MEDVETKLEBS project was highly successful in achieving its scientific tasks, fostering novel collaborations among partner institutions, providing novel analytical methods and understanding of Kp diversity, ecology and epidemiology, and integrating and harmonizing *Klebsiella* study methods among partners and beyond.

5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
11	D-JRP11-1.1	Optimized culture protocols	12	OCTOBER 2018		PUBLIC. Productivity and specificity of SCAI medium tested. Best enrichment steps and incubation temperatures defined according to the different sources. Protocols disseminated/made publicly available through the protocols.io platform in a project called ' Klebsiella Research and Surveillance ' (https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/klebsiella-research-and-surveillance/publications).	1, 2
11	D-JRP11-1.2	qPCR protocols	12	NOVEMBER 2018		PUBLIC. qPCR for the detection and identification of Kp complex members designed and validated. Article published and protocol made publicly available through the protocols.io platform in a project called ' Klebsiella Research and Surveillance ' (https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/klebsiella-research-and-surveillance/publications).	1, 2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
11	D-JRP11-additional-1	MALDI-TOF MS	12	DECEMBER 2018 DECEMBER 2020		<p>PUBLIC. Demonstration and validation of the potential of MALDI-TOF MS to correctly identify <i>Klebsiella</i> strains at the phylogroup level. Articles published. (http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3678153)</p> <p>PUBLIC. Additionally, we have set-up a MALDI-TOF MS based identification web site for <i>Klebsiella</i>. A pilot web site is functional (https://maldityper.pasteur.fr), and the publication has been submitted and it's available at BioRxiv platform (https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.10.13.337162).</p>	1, 2, 3
11	D-JRP11-2.1	List of high-Kp occurrence sources	12	DECEMBER 2019		<p>PUBLIC. Multiple (3781 in total) samples were screened by the consortium. This task gained impetus due to the availability of the qPCR detection method. Some sources where Kp is prevalent were already identified including wastewater, seawater, soil, chicken meat, vegetables and ready-to-eat food (http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4499266)</p>	1, 2, 5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
11	D-JRP11-2.2	Prevalence in selected sources	24	DECEMBER 2019		PUBLIC. Multicentric study – chicken meat and ready-to-eat salads. Manuscript in preparation. (http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4499275)	1, 5
11	D-JRP11-2.3	Prevalence in selected sources	30	JANUARY 2021		PUBLIC. Soil project. Includes 664 environmental samples recovered in a single French administrative locality (Department of Côte d’Or, Burgundy, France) from July 2018 to July 2019. In addition, water and sludge were sampled in 31 wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) in the same department (n = 31) (http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4499292).	1, 5
11	D-JRP11-2.4	Prevalence in selected sources	30		MARCH 2021	The sampling of onions and seawater has been impacted by the COVID-19 crisis, and is re-starting currently.	1, 5
11	D-JRP11-2.5	Genome sequence data	28		During 2021	PUBLIC. Genome sequence data are available for internal analyses so far (see deliverable; http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4499296); a few were published in the Barbier et al paper and put on public repositories (ENA, BioProject PRJEB34643). Sequences will be released once the	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						corresponding publications are accepted.	
11	D-JRP11-2.6	Quantification of Kp in selected sources	30			Due to its complexity, the task of quantification of Kp in samples was not addressed during the project. However, the developed qPCR will allow this to be done in future dedicated studies.	
11	D-JRP11-3.1	Source distribution of clonal groups, plasmids and genes	30		During 2021	PUBLIC. Although some data are available already (see deliverable, http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4499308), more data is still being analysed and will be added to each publication.	4
11	D-JRP11-3.2	Source attribution models by microbial subtyping and comparative exposure assessment	30		APRIL 2021	PUBLIC. This objective will be rediscussed among involved partners given (i) the huge diversity found in our sampling surveys (see deliverable 3.1) and (ii) the presence of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> in all sources where we looked (deliverable 2.1, January 2020). Therefore, we will provide an alternative deliverable, before the end of the project. It will consist of a document (D-JRP11-3.2alt) containing a description of scenario for source attribution approaches as a function of pathogen ecological distribution and genotypic diversity.	4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
11	D-JRP11-3.3	Computer program for dynamic models simulation	30		During 2021	<p>PUBLIC. Objectives corresponding to deliverables 3.3., 3.4 and 3.5 were abandoned given (i) the huge diversity found in our sampling surveys (see deliverable 3.1) and (ii) the presence of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> in all sources where we looked (deliverable 2.1, January 2020). Instead, we are proposing a novel deliverable, which will consist of a computer programme and attached publication, useful to model genomic diversification within food as a function of time and mutation rate (D-JRP11-3.345alt). https://zenodo.org/record/4576821#.YD-oOGhKhMO</p>	7
11	D-JRP11-3.4	Estimates of the attribution proportion for different food, animal and environmental sources for the countries included.	30		During 2021	<p>PUBLIC. Objectives corresponding to deliverables 3.3., 3.4 and 3.5 were abandoned given (i) the huge diversity found in our sampling surveys (see deliverable 3.1) and (ii) the presence of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> in all sources where we looked (deliverable 2.1, January 2020). Instead, we are proposing a novel deliverable, which will consist of a</p>	7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						computer programme and attached publication, useful to model genomic diversification within food as a function of time and mutation rate (D-JRP11-3.345alt). https://zenodo.org/record/4576821#.YD-o0GhKhM0	
11	D-JRP11-3.5	Estimates of the relative contribution of different transmission routes for exposure to Kp in the different countries included.	30		During 2021	PUBLIC. Objectives corresponding to deliverables 3.3., 3.4 and 3.5 were abandoned given (i) the huge diversity found in our sampling surveys (see deliverable 3.1) and (ii) the presence of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> in all sources where we looked (deliverable 2.1, January 2020). Instead, we are proposing a novel deliverable , which will consist of a computer programme and attached publication, useful to model genomic diversification within food as a function of time and mutation rate (D-JRP11-3.345alt). https://zenodo.org/record/4576821#.YD-o0GhKhM0	7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
11	D-JRP11-4.1	Project Periodic Reports	9, 13, 21, 25, 30	9, 13, 21, 25, 30		PUBLIC	8
11	D-JRP11-4.2	Consortium meetings – Review of work done/progress made and definition of priorities for next period	1,12,24	1,12,35		PUBLIC (http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4499317) Regarding consortium meetings, in the impossibility of a live meeting planned for April 2020 due to COVI-19 restrictions, we have organized a one-day video meeting (17/11/2020) where all partners presented the advances in the project in this last year. A final after-project follow-up meeting is prevue on April-May 2021.	8
11	D-JRP11-4.3	Communication strategy plan	12	DECEMBER 2019		PUBLIC. A first version has been produced, validated by all partners and sent to the One Health EJP responsible on Nov 20 th , 2019. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4451400	8
11	D-JRP11-4.4	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (data management plan)	18	APRIL 2019 (1st version DMP) DECEMBER 2019 (2nd version DMP)		PUBLIC. A second version has been produced, validated by all partners and sent to the One Health EJP responsible on Nov 20 th , 2019. The final version of the DMP has been sent to One Health EJP coordinators. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4451409	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted : Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
				JANUARY 2021 (DMP final version)			
11	D-JRP11-4.5	Final Report	36	JANUARY 2021		PUBLIC	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
11	M-JRP11-1	SCAI medium culture protocol validated on sites	3	Yes		Best enrichment steps and incubation temperatures defined according to the different sources. Protocols made publicly available through the protocols.io platform in a project called ' Klebsiella Research and Surveillance ' (https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/klebsiella-research-and-surveillance/publications).

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
11	M-JRP11-2	Preparation of draft of the strategic communication plan	10	Yes		A first version has been produced, validated by all partners and sent to the One Health EJP responsible.
11	M-JRP11-3	Project reporting template	10	Yes		All periodic and final reports have been delivered to One Health EJP coordinators.
11	M-JRP11-4	Standard culture methods defined	12	Yes		Productivity and specificity of SCAI medium tested. Best enrichment steps and incubation temperatures defined according to the different sources. Protocols made publicly available through the protocols.io platform in a project called ' Klebsiella Research and Surveillance ' (https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/klebsiella-research-and-surveillance/publications).
11	M-JRP11-5	qPCR protocol available for detection, isolation and quantification	12	Yes (partially)		qPCR for the detection and identification of Kp complex members designed and validated. Article published and protocol made publicly available through the protocols.io platform in a project called ' Klebsiella Research and Surveillance ' (https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/klebsiella-research-and-surveillance/publications). Due to its complexity, the task of quantification of Kp in samples was not addressed during the project. However, the developed qPCR will allow this to be done in future dedicated studies.
11	Additional	MALDI-TOF MS	12	Yes		Demonstration and validation of the potential of MALDI-TOF MS to correctly identify strains of the <i>Klebsiella</i> at the phylogroup level. Articles published.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						Additionally, we have set-up a MALDI-TOF MS based identification web site for <i>Klebsiella</i> . A pilot web site is functional (https://maldityper.pasteur.fr), and the publication has been submitted and it's available at BioRxiv platform (https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.10.13.337162).
11	M-JRP11-6	Broad survey of Kp in multiple sources complete	24	Yes		Multiple (3781 in total) samples were screened by the consortium.
11	M-JRP11-7	Development of model frameworks for dynamic modelling and source attribution	29	No		Please see comment for Deliverable 3.2 to 3.5
11	M-JRP11-8	Initial prevalence, quantification and genomic data for model refining	28	Yes		
11	M-JRP11-9	1st batch of clonal groups, plasmids and genes defined, for refinement of models	24	Yes		
11	M-JRP11-10	Compilation and integration of the data produced in WP1 and WP2 to be used in the dynamic and source attribution models	31	No		Please see deliverables 2.4, 3.1 and 2.1
11	M-JRP11-11	Identification of a list of scenarios for control measures to be assessed through model simulations	30	No		Please see comment for Deliverables 3.2 to 3.5

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
11	M-JRP11-12	Consolidated prevalence, quantification and genomic data for modeling of Kp transmission	28	No		Deliverables 2.4, 3.1 and 2.1
11	M-JRP11-13	Application of dynamic and source attribution models to data collected from different countries	30	No		Please see comment for Deliverables 3.2 to 3.5
11	M-JRP11-14	Reporting of transmission and source attribution estimates	30	No		Please see comment for Deliverables 3.2 to 3.5

6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Community-acquired infection caused by the uncommon hypervirulent <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ST66-K2 lineage. https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000419 https://zenodo.org/record/4436269#.X_8DxS_5Q6U	YES		GOLD 1795€
Whole genome sequencing reveals resemblance between ESBL-producing and carbapenem resistant <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> isolates from Austrian rivers and clinical isolates from hospitals 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.179 https://zenodo.org/record/4249232#.X6UhA2hKjcc	YES		GOLD 2765€
Diversity of mucoid to non-mucoid switch among carbapenemase-producing <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-020-02007-y https://zenodo.org/record/4456731#.YBtD7C_5TjA	YES		GOLD 1870€
Broad-spectrum cephalosporin-resistant <i>Klebsiella</i> spp. isolated from diseased horses in Austria https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10020332 https://zenodo.org/record/3929408#.Xv8m_ygzZM0	YES		GOLD 1482€
Description of <i>Klebsiella africanensis</i> sp. nov. <i>Klebsiella variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropicalensis</i> subsp. nov. and <i>Klebsiella variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i> subsp. nov. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003 https://zenodo.org/record/3660879#.XkEmO2hKiUk	YES	GREEN 12M	
Description of <i>Klebsiella spallanzanii</i> sp. nov. and of <i>Klebsiella pasteurii</i> sp https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.02360 https://zenodo.org/record/3660875#.XkEICGhKiUk	YES		GOLD 2399€
Identification of <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Klebsiella quasipneumoniae</i> , <i>Klebsiella variicola</i> and Related Phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry. 10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000 https://zenodo.org/record/3660887#.XkEm5mhKiUk	YES		GOLD 2399€

Publication title and DOI reference	Is One Health EJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Klebsiella pneumoniae carriage in low-income countries: antimicrobial resistance, genomic diversity and risk factors https://doi.org/10.1080/19490976.2020.1748257 https://zenodo.org/record/3929396#.Xv8lrSgzZM0	YES		GOLD 2399€
Outbreak of Yersiniabactin-producing Klebsiella pneumoniae in a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit 10.1097/INF.0000000000002258 https://zenodo.org/record/3661013#.XkFq-OSWwj9	YES	GREEN 12M-	
The ZKIR Assay, a novel Real-Time PCR Method for the Detection of Klebsiella pneumonia and Closely Related Species in Environmental Samples 10.1128/AEM.02711-19 https://zenodo.org/record/3730608#.Xn3Kk4hKi70	YES		GOLD 2033€

Additional output

One Health EJP ASM (2019, 2020) and IMMEM-XII:

1. Carla Rodrigues, Sylvain Brisse on the behalf of MEDVETKLEBS consortium. The MEDVETKLEBS project: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from Ecology to Source Attribution and Transmission Control (poster).
2. Carla Rodrigues, Virginie Passet, Andrianiaina Rakotondrasoa, Sylvain Brisse. Suitability of MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry to Discriminate Species within the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Complex (poster).
3. Carla Rodrigues, Marisa Haenni, Maxime Bour, Cécile Ponsin, Jean-Louis Pinsard, Virginie Passet, Jean-Yves Madec, Sylvain Brisse. Genomic Diversity, Antimicrobial Resistance and Virulence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from Healthy Food-producing Animals and Horses (oral).
4. Elodie Barbier, Carla Rodrigues, Géraldine Depret, Virginie Passet, Laurent Gal, Pascal Piveteau and Sylvain Brisse. Design, Development and Validation of a Real-Time PCR Assay for Detection of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Complex in Environmental Matrixes (poster).
5. Elodie Barbier, Juan Sebastian Lopez-Fernandez, Carla Rodrigues, Virginie Passet, Laurent Gal, Sylvain Brisse, Pascal Piveteau. Development of Phylogroup-Specific Taqman Real-Time Assays for Identification of Members of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Complex (poster).
6. Małgorzata Ligowska-Marzęta, Katrine Grimstrup Joensen, Carla Rodrigues, Sylvain Brisse and Eva Møller Nielsen. Broad Sampling for Presence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in Different Sources from Denmark (poster).
7. Violeta Di Marzio, Gabriella Centorotola, Cristina Marfoggia, Alessandra Cornacchia, Maria Antonietta Saletti, Carla Rodrigues, Sylvain Brisse, Francesco Pomilio. A Comparative Study of Productivity, Selectivity and Specificity of Three Selective Culture Media for *Klebsiella spp.* Detection (poster).
8. Carla Rodrigues, Marisa Haenni, Maxime Bour, Cécile Ponsin, Jean-Louis Pinsard, Virginie Passet, Jean-Yves Madec, Sylvain Brisse. Genomic Diversity, Antimicrobial Resistance and Virulence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from Animal Carriage: a Comprehensive Analysis in an One Health Perspective (oral).

9. Alessandra Cornacchia, Maria Antonietta Saletti, Violeta Di Marzio, Aurora Ciarrocchi, Gabriella Centorotola, Cristina Marfaglia, Carla Rodrigues, Sylvain Brisse, Francesco Pomilio. Detection of *Klebsiella* spp. in chicken meat: methods performance study (poster).
10. Violeta Di Marzio, Gabriella Centorotola, Aurora Ciarrocchi, Cornacchia Alessandra, Cristina Marfaglia, Maria Antonietta Saletti, Carla Rodrigues, Sylvain Brisse, Francesco Pomilio. Evaluation of antimicrobial resistance of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains in foods (poster).

7 One Health impact

A significant impact of the MEDVETKLEBS project results is anticipated in several directions.

First, our methodological developments and validations (culture and isolation methods, molecular detection, MALDI-TOF identification, taxonomic descriptions) will improve laboratory work, and thereby impact positively laboratory capacity in detection, identification, surveillance, epidemiology and ecology of *Klebsiella*. Our novel methods and tools (e.g., *Klebsiella* MALDI-TypeR) have already been adopted by research consortia on *Klebsiella* and may be adopted by microbiology laboratories, including reference laboratories, in their workflows.

Second, the data on the prevalence and resistance/virulence of *Klebsiella* in varied sources, generated by the MEDVETKLEBS project, will contribute to better assess the risk associated with potential sources or reservoirs of *Klebsiella*.

Third, our modelling approach may provide a very useful tool to define outbreaks of Kp and other food-borne or environmental pathogens.

Finally, the genomic data generated in this study, integrated into the *Klebsiella* genomic library and nomenclature server BIGSdb-Pasteur, will contribute to define *Klebsiella* subtypes and track their spread more efficiently.

Examples of interactions with relevant stakeholders are described below:

ECDC and EFSA we contacted along with multiple international scientists by the MEDVETKLEBS coordinator in the frame of the organisation of the KlebNET project meeting (April 2020, which was cancelled due to COVID19). We have reinitiated contacts with ECDC and have agreed on collaborating on genomic nomenclature of strains for pan-European tracking purposes.

The international network Kleb-NET – H2020 EU JPIAMR 7th call on surveillance - <https://research.pasteur.fr/en/project/klebnet-a-one-health-network-bridging-science-and-surveillance-on-antimicrobial-resistant-klebsiella/> (PI: Sylvain Brisse) was successfully built upon initial networking activities within the MEDVETKLEBS project.

SpARK – JPIAMR 3rd Joint Call on Transmission Dynamics - <https://www.jpiamr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/SpARK.pdf> (PI: Edward Feil): This project includes S Brisse as partner, and benefitted from our MEDVETKLEBS validated SCAI culture method – more than 6000 samples from soil, animals, humans and food were searched for Kp presence by culture and metagenomics methods.

KLEB-GAP - Bergen Research Foundation grants - <https://www.vetinst.no/en/research-and-innovation/ongoing-research-projects/kleb-gap-klebsiella-pneumoniae-a-key-driver-in-the-global-spread-of-antimicrobial-resistance-and-a-target-for-new-approaches-in-diagnostics-surveillance-and-alternative-therapeutics> (PI: Arnfinn Sundsfjord and Co-PI Iren Høyland Löhr). S Brisse is a partner in this project, and provided expertise, culture and qPCR protocols developed in the MEDVETKLEBS project, ahead of public dissemination.

NOR-KLEB-NET – funded by the Norwegian Research Council - <http://www.nor-kleb.net>. Sylvain Brisse is a partner in this project, and provided expertise, culture and qPCR protocols developed in the MEDVETKLEBS project, ahead of public dissemination. The Kp sampling performed through this project has benefited from MEDVETKLEBS outputs.

Evaluation of the final report

Numerical scores

CRITERION	PROJECT		
	Reviewer 1 (full proposal evaluator)	Reviewer 2 (new evaluator)	Reviewer 3 (POC member)
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal	5	4	3
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach	4	5	4
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	4	4	4
Integration	4	5	5
Sustainability	4	4	4
Impact of the project	4	3	4
TOTAL	25/30	25/30	24/30

AVERAGE: 25

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

This is directly aligned. There were a couple areas where work deviated from the initial plans. However, this had limited impact on the objectives and when it was done, it was a logical change based on early findings. I would consider this a strength rather than a weakness. Results for later workplans are less well developed and reported, based presumably on the more recent completion and impacts of COVID-19. Overall, the alignment is good and the results indicate strong efforts to address the stated objectives.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

MEDVETKLEBS met the majority of the objectives:

1. Develop and harmonize methods of detection, isolation and quantification of Klebsiella pneumoniae (Kp).

Comment: harmonized methods to detect and isolate Kp were developed. However, the project did not develop methods to quantify Kp in different matrixes and reasons for that has been stated in the final report. It is further described that the group will continue to work on this since this was too complex task to perform within the length of the project.

2. Define the major environmental niches that act as reservoirs of Kp, and more specifically its high-risk subtypes and associated antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes and plasmids.

Comment: this objective was completed.

3. Define the main vehicles of contamination, quantify the role of different foods and feeds in exposure of humans and animals to Kp: and trace the transmission of Kp subtypes, resistance genes and plasmids.

Completed: a source attribution to define main vehicles of contamination and roles of different foods were not performed. It was mentioned the reason for this was the high degree of heterogeneity in isolated Kp strains. The task was thus replaced by one aiming to develop models to identify related clusters of Kp strains.

4. Inform the scientific community and decision-makers in order to optimize current practices.

Comment: the project has met the objective to inform the scientific community. However, from the report it is not clear how decision-makers and other stakeholders were informed. The group also took the opportunity to add additional tasks that contribute to the overall objective of the project. Some of these tasks adjusted already included tasks and some were new.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The project was very ambitious considering the objectives of WP 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, that had finally to be abandoned considering the findings concerning the diversity of *K. pneumoniae* as observed in the other WP. It is to be underlined that the excellence and the in depth work performed in these previous WP opened a new understanding of the *K. pneumoniae* family, opened new avenues for research, and the WP 3 is highly dependent of these results. Our understanding is that if delayed, this link between environment and *K. pneumoniae* will be much more efficiently worked upon and understood from the strong works preformed in the previous WP. Hence, even if all deliverables are not fulfilled, the project remains a strong success.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Overall, this is very strong. The limited depth of results hampers assessment of this to some degree, as results are quite superficial. I see nothing of concern, but the limited result (esp for WPs 2 and 3) limits the assessment that can be made.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The research group is highly skilled and high-quality results have been produced from the project. As of the time of submitting the report ten articles have been published in peer-reviewed scientific journal, one is in pre-print and additional ten are in progress, which shows high scientific excellence. The scientific quality of the outputs produced is high and the research partners have complementary expertise enabling the group to address highly complex issues.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Much praise to be given here to the excellence of the work performed. This publication production is really impressive, in number, quality and scientific interest, reference protocols have been made available for the community in the field, and the MEDVETKLEBS demonstrated a strong willingness to interface with other actors in the Klebsiella world to generate synergies in research.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

This is harder to assess but I see no issues. The program has resulted in good activities amongst a wide range of partners and the results that are briefly described would have required quality efforts and efficient interaction, particularly given the COVID-19 barriers that have occurred.

Successful completion of most objectives with good quality inputs suggests that program management and implementation were strong.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

Research results have been disseminated efficiently in scientific journals and at congresses. Research data are easily available at various platforms, which has been described in detail in the data management plan. The communication strategy likely fits the purpose for this kind of project. In the communication plan and in the project objective there are some aspects that were more difficult to target in this project, for example addressing decision-makers and the general public.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The consortium included 10 partners from 6 countries, and that is impressive. As seen from the report, and the productions in terms of publications and protocols, and from the link with other partners outside of the consortium, the projects appears to have been well managed and re-oriented according to the generated results, which is fine. If some part of the project was not achieved, unplanned results were generated as the opportunity arose, and this will serve the community efficiently.

Integration

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

The flow through the first 3 WPs required an integrated approach, moving from basic lab to applied, and subsequent molecular epidemiological approaches. This type of integrated work is essential for studies such as this and seems to have been successful. Cross sector alignment was necessary and provides a strong One Health approach to the area.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project succeeded in integrating relevant activities and included, for example, capacity-building, development of harmonized protocols, close collaboration between the partners. The final report concludes the project has led to enhanced research and surveillance capacity. There are potentials for national agencies, research institutes and academia to adopt the methods developed within the project. The project fully integrated a One Health approach and thereby managed to address complex issues associated with the ubiquitous bacteria Kp.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Integration can be considered from various angles: ascientific animation around the project seems to have been interesting, although not that many publication are common between consortia partners, or engaging more than 2 partners. Not all partners published yet from work done on this project. However, the publications listed reveal a network largely beyond the current consortium, and links with the global Klebsiella network and with non European countries. As common work appears to be continuing despite the end of the project, integrations is considered successful.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

This seems to be very good. The program has made good progress and numerous related activities have been reported. This indicates good research momentum that is not solely dependent on the program. Collaborations seem to have been successful and objectives have been largely met. These factors provide reasonable optimism for sustained work in this area that was fostered by the program. The methods that were developed have a high likelihood of being used by other research groups, further providing sustained impact.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The developments achieved by the project have potentials to last over longer times. The research consortium is strong and the members have links to other consortia/networks/agencies than those represented within the MEDVETKLEBS. Other institutes will be able to take on board, for example, the developed detection and isolation methods, the molecular method and typing using MALDI-TOF, in some cases, this already happened.

Reviewer 3: POC member

Considered positive as works seems to be continuing despite the end of the project. However, at any rate, such projects can not be self- sustainable.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1: full proposal evaluator

Impact is always difficult to assess in the short term. Yet, there are several outputs from this study that should have strong impacts on research methods and understanding of the epidemiology and microbiology of Kp. The work presented here provides a solid foundation for future efforts.

Reviewer 2: new evaluator

The project has shed light on the epidemiology and biology of Kp in the environment, in humans, in animals and in foods. Thus, the project has laid a foundation for future research on Kp. Given national agencies, institutes and research laboratories find the developed protocols and methods useful, and additional evaluations confirm results generated from this project, the impact of the project might last for a long time. The project contributes to the ambition of the One Health EJP.

Reviewer 3: POC member

The research done on Klebsiella, phylogeny definition, protocols to detect and characterize, is very important and shall have a strong impact.

Annex

Guidelines for the evaluation of the final Joint Research Project (JRP) reports, based on D3.9

General information on the One Health European Joint Programme (EJP) is available on the website OneHealthEJP.eu.

For more insight in the guidelines for project leaders to report on their Joint Research Project (JRP), deliverable D3.1 should be consulted. Guidance for the WP3 Team to monitor the JRPs is described in deliverable D3.5 (all public deliverables are available on www.onehealthjep.eu/deliverables).

The current procedure details the evaluation process of the JRP final reports by evaluators external to the One Health EJP consortium. It is based on D3.9 and takes into account the final reports expected in January 2021.

	Proposal writing		Project		
PL JRP	D3.3 Submission		D3.1 Reporting	D3.1 Reporting	D3.1 Reporting
PL JIP	D3.3 Submission		D4.1 Reporting	D4.1 Reporting	D4.12 Reporting
WP3 / WP4			D3.5 Monitoring	D3.5 Monitoring	D3.5 Monitoring
Experts		D3.6 Evaluation proposal			D3.9 D4.19 Evaluation final report

Contact details of the One Health EJP WP3 team and the Support Team

The Support Team may be contacted for general questions related to this procedure. Detailed research related questions should be forwarded to the WP3 team.

- One Health EJP Support Team: Arnaud Callegari and Lucyna Haaso-Bastin, Email: ohjepcoord@anses.fr
- One Health EJP WP3 Team (Joint Research Projects): Hein Imberechts and Racha El Mounaged, Email: ohjep@sciensano.be

Role of the One Health WP3 team

Project leaders submit their final reports according to the instructions laid out in D3.1. The WP3 team will then administer their evaluation. Its role is as follows:

- To remind projects leaders to submit their final report according to the guidelines and using the appropriate template (D3.1);
- To verify that the self-assessment in which the project leader compares the project outcomes with the initial objectives as described in the full proposal (see further) has been appropriately dealt with;

- To contact external experts and stakeholders or “end users” for the evaluation of the final reports following the current procedure, and to collect the evaluation forms;
- To transfer the evaluated final reports and accompanying documents (e.g. evaluation sheets) to the Support Team;
- To disseminate the final reports to the Project Management Team, the Scientific Steering Board, the Research Executive Agency.

Identification of External Experts for Evaluation

The final reports will be evaluated by external evaluators who are recognized experts in the fields of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats. Contact will be sought with at least one of the experts that evaluated the project’s full proposal and with one additional expert, based on the existing list of experts (D3.6, see [website](#)). The experts must not currently be engaged in or have had close collaboration with the project leader or deputy leader of the One Health EJP project in the past 5 years prior to the submission of the final report, i.e. as from January 2016 for reports submitted in January 2015.

In addition, one Programme Owner Committee (POC) representative (i.e. “end user”, e.g. experts from ministries or regional food agencies) will be invited to assess the general outcome of the project, i.e. the integration among consortium partners, the One Health efforts and impact of the project, including on the longer term (project sustainability). POC members are per definition not independent from the One Health EJP beneficiaries and will therefore not be invited to sign a “No Conflict of Interest” document.

Scientific experts and Programme Owner Committee representatives will be contacted and invited to register through an online questionnaire (see further).

Each report will thus be evaluated by three experts (i.e. 2 scientific and one stakeholder expert).

Evaluation process

The WP3 team will invite the scientific experts and the Programme Owner representatives to the evaluation process. The email will include:

- a short description of the One Health EJP with a link to the website OneHealthEJP.eu
- the following information relevant for the assessment of the reports:
 - ✓ a hyperlink to the webpages of the projects for which the final report needs evaluation
 - ✓ a hyperlink to the procedure for project leaders to report on JRP (D3.1)
 - ✓ these guidelines for the evaluation of the final reports
 - ✓ specifically for the external expert who initially assessed the project full proposal, that evaluation form will be attached to the mail
- specifically for the new external evaluators and the POC members, a hyperlink to an online registration form “Registration as evaluator of final JRP reports for One Health EJP”. This form includes a “Confidentiality Agreement” statement (Annex A) and information regarding protection of personal data, GDPR (Annex B). The external experts who initially assessed the project full proposal will return by email the signed copies of the “Confidentiality Agreement” (Annex A) and the information regarding protection of personal data GDPR (Annex B).

The selected expert who has successfully registered online will receive digital copies of the following documents:

- the project final report(s)
- a confirmation of “No Conflict of Interest” (Annex C) (this does not apply to the POC representatives since they are end users of the One Health EJP outcomes and therefore not independent from the One Health EJP by definition)
- a template to mark the evaluation scores and comments (Annex D)

Each scientific expert will have to send a scanned copy of the signed “No Conflict of Interest” document (Annex C) to ohelp@sciensano.be prior to evaluating the report. In case of a conflict of interest, the external expert is excluded from the evaluation process and she/he will be asked to destroy the documents.

Criteria for evaluation

For the report evaluation, the following criteria will have to be assessed according to the scoring scheme below. The criteria are:

- Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal: How well do the project outcomes meet the initial objectives of the project? Is any deviation justified?
- Scientific excellence and/or quality of the outcome: Did the project deliver sound and scientifically qualified results with progress beyond the state-of-the-art, following the proposal initially submitted? Did the multi-disciplinary, complementary approach between the consortium partners deliver successfully?
- Quality and efficiency of the implementation: In general, was the management appropriate? Evaluation of the effectiveness of the measures taken to exploit and disseminate the project results, to communicate on the project, and to manage research data.
- Integration: Was the project successful in achieving relevant integrative activities (i.e. improved capacity building, development of harmonised protocols, joint strains and biobank collections, joint databases, harmonised surveillance strategies, addressing legal aspects of general interest) that will allow partner organisations to further improve harmonization or alignment in order to better support their prevent-detect-response tasks? Has sufficient attention been paid to cross-sector collaboration and alignment (One Health aspect)?
- Sustainability: Will developments achieved by the project be maintained within the organisations of the consortium (procedures as well as capacities, collections or databases, etc.)? Will other institutes be able to take on board (some of) the results?
- Impact of the project: Will the impact of the project last over a long period of time or is it likely to generate a more limited effect (e.g. for national and/or international stakeholders)? Is the project outcome likely to have positive secondary effects such as a positive impact on the economy (free travel over borders, trade of animals and food, recall of contaminated food stuffs etc.) or the environment (impact of preventive and mitigating measures, reduce transportation, etc.)?

The external evaluators will assess the report as follows:

1. To score all criteria providing whole numbers from 0 to 5, which leads to a maximum score of 30;
2. To comment on each criterion in a few lines; this will help to give feedback to both the project leaders and the Scientific Steering Board.

The duly filled in evaluation forms (Annex D) have to be sent back to ohelp@sciensano.be before the deadline.

0	Weak	The report shows severe imperfections for the criterion under examination. The criterion is not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.
1	Poor	The results show that insufficient progress was made for the criterion under examination or it was addressed in an inadequate manner. The report shows serious weaknesses for this criterion.
2	Good	The report broadly addresses the criterion under examination; however, the outcome is moderate. The results are rather average of what could have been expected.
3	Very good	The report addresses most of the criterion under examination well; however, the expected outcome could be better.
4	Excellent	The outcome of the criterion under examination is of high quality or the results related to that criterion are excellent.
5	Outstanding	The outcome of the criterion under examination stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation or progress of science at a global level.

Discussion of the evaluation reports (JRP)

WP3 team will present the evaluation reports to the Project Management Team, the Scientific Steering Board and the EC (REA).

Annexes

Annex A. Confidentiality Agreement

Although the final project reports are public deliverables, One Health EJP documents such as mails, letters, evaluation forms, etc. regarding the evaluation of the projects are confidential and should therefore be handled and stored with due care and confidentially.

Experts are therefore not allowed to disclose any information concerning project documents or evaluations to outsiders, nor are they allowed to use this confidential information to their own benefit or anyone else’s benefit or disadvantage. In addition, they may not reveal to outsiders (including the partners of the project) that they are assessing reports of a particular researcher. Anyone who has questions about the project documents or evaluation reports shall be advised to contact ohelp@sciensano.be.

Once the evaluation has been completed, experts are requested to destroy all project documents and any copies made of them. Confidentiality must be maintained until all valorisations of the outcomes are completed (e.g. publications).

I hereby confirm that I have read and accepted the Confidentiality Agreement.

Name of expert:

Evaluated project(s) name(s):

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohelp@sciensano.be

Annex B. Protection of personal data (GDPR regulation)

Information concerning the protection of the expert's personal data

The One Health EJP organises the online registration of evaluators at Sciensano, Brussels, ["Registration as evaluator of final reports for One Health EJP"] to identify experts in the field of the One Health EJP and to facilitate their assignment to a reading panel that will evaluate reports.

The online tool collects personal data of candidate experts and includes questions on their availability and their expertise.

If the expert agrees to participate in the evaluation process, he/she needs to sign the consent form.

Objective of the registration tool

The aim of this online tool ["Registration as evaluator of final reports for One Health EJP"] is to facilitate the assignment of the experts to one or more reports for evaluation. Its outcome will only be used for this particular purpose.

Reimbursement

If the expert decides to review One Health EJP reports, he/she will be reimbursed a fee of €225 for evaluating 2 final reports (i.e. the actual fee for experts working for the EC, which equals €450 reimbursement for 1 working day). The actual fee to be paid will be calculated pro rata the number of reports read, i.e. €112.25 per report.

Confidentiality

The expert's data will be stored for use by Sciensano. The expert's identity who has participated in the evaluation may also appear in official One Health EJP documents, which will be validated by the EC (Research Executive Agency) and become public. Sciensano will not reveal the identity of the experts per project. This process is conducted in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of May 25, 2018. The expert can access he/she collected data at any time.

Concerning the protection of the expert's personal data

The information requested will be used in accordance to the permission the expert has given to the Belgian law of 30 July 2018 concerning the protection of individuals in relation to the use of personalized data and the European regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and the Council of 27 April 2016 (in place since 25 May 2018) concerning the protection of people in relation to the use of personalized data and the free flow of data (GDPR).

If the expert decides to fill in his/her personalized data in the online tool, he/she confirms to have gone through these privacy conditions.

The personal data Sciensano collects in the online registration tool is the following

- The expert's first name and family name
- The organisation for which the expert works
- The country where the expert works
- The expert's professional e-mail
- The expert's availability in a defined period of time

Sharing the expert's data

The expert's data will be shared with Pikka Jokelainen (SSI, DK), Karin Artursson (SVA, SE), Manuela Caniça (INSA, PT) and Arnaud Callegari (ANSES, FR) who support and supervise the evaluation process of the project reports (JRP and JIP, see www.OneHealthEJP.eu for details).

Saving and protecting the expert's personal data

The expert's data will be saved in electronic form (LymeSurvey, csv table).

Sciensano will save the expert's personal data until the end of the One Health EJP project, foreseen for December 2022.

The expert's choice regarding his/her personal data

The expert has the right to ask Sciensano whether his/her data were used. He/she may ask to rectify and delete the data, he/she can oppose the further use of the data or limit the use of the data. All requests have to be motivated.

To do this, the expert will have to write a formal request in which is specified what he/she wants to know, rectify or delete. This request has to be dated, signed and accompanied by a copy recto-verso of the expert's ID-card, together with contacting details. If the conditions are fulfilled, Sciensano will in the shortest delays honour the request and inform the expert about it.

How can the expert contact us?

For questions regarding the use of personal data by Sciensano in the framework of the One Health EJP tool, the expert can contact us:

Sciensano

Juliette Wytzmanstraat 14
1050 Elsene
Belgium
T. : +32 2 642 51 11
F. : +32 2 642 50 01
info@sciensano.be
www.sciensano.be

The Sciensano service Data Protection and the Officer for Data Protection can be contacted by email at dpo@sciensano.be.

The expert also has the right to file a complaint about how his/her data have been handled to the Belgian supervising authorities responsible for the legal aspects regarding the protection of personal data. This service can be contacted at:

Data protection authority

Rue de la Presse 35
1000 Brussels
Belgium T. : + 32 (0)2 274 48 00
F. : +32 (0)2 274 48 35
contact@apd-gba.be

Additional information

Additional information about this study can be obtained from the scientific One Health EJP coordinator via email (ohjep@sciensano.be) or telephone (+32 477 911 050).

Please confirm that you agree with the protection of data by signing the following form:

I hereby confirm that I have read, understood and approved the information form regarding the protection of my personal data. I have had enough time to think and I have been able to ask all the

questions that have come to mind. I understand that if I have more questions or concerns about the use of my personal data, I can contact Sciensano (details mentioned above).

I agree with the regulations concerning the protection of personal data as explained above, the fact that my personal data as expert who has participated in the evaluation of project report will be used by Sciensano and that my identity may also appear in official OneHealth EJP documents, which will be validated by the EC and eventually become public. Sciensano will not reveal the identity of the experts per project.

Name of expert:

Evaluated project(s) name(s):

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohjep@sciensano.be

Annex C. Confirmation of No Conflict of Interest

External Experts are requested to declare any actual or potential conflict of interest towards the project documents. Disqualification may be essential for a number of reasons:

- If the expert:
 - o was involved in the preparation of the final report that she/he is invited to evaluate;
 - o is a director, trustee or partner or is in any way involved in the management of the project(s) she/he is requested to evaluate;
 - o is employed or contracted by one of the beneficiaries involved in the project;
 - o has close family ties or other close personal relationship with the leadership of the project (the project leader or deputy leader of the project, WP Leaders, etc.);
 - o has (or has had during the last five years) a scientific collaboration with the project leader or deputy leader of the project;
 - o has (or has had) a relationship of scientific rivalry or professional hostility with the leadership of the project (the project leader or deputy leader of the project, WP Leaders, etc.) for a period of three years;
 - o has (or has had), a mentor/mentee relationship with the leadership of the project (the project leader or deputy leader of the project, WP Leaders, etc.);
- If the approval or rejection of the project report may in any way benefit or harm the expert personally.

Disqualification will also be inevitable if their impartiality may otherwise be endangered, or if they feel that they have a conflict of interest.

In case of a possible conflict of interest the person must notify ohelp@sciensano.be without any delay.

I hereby confirm that I do not have a conflict of interest.

Name of expert:

Evaluated project(s) name(s):

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohelp@sciensano.be

Annex D. Template for the evaluation of joint research project (JRP) and joint integrative project (JIP) reports

Project title or acronym:

.....

	0 Weak	1 Poor	2 Good	3 Very good	4 Excel- lent	5 Out- standing
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal						
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach						
Quality and efficiency of the implementation						
Integration						
Sustainability						
Impact of the project						

Total score (max 30):

Remarks (please include at least one comment per criterion)

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal:

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Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach:

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Quality and efficiency of the implementation:

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Integration:

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Sustainability:

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Impact of the project:

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Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohelp@sciensano.be